

TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY

RAYMOND AND BEVERLY SACKLER
FACULTY OF EXACT SCIENCES
SCHOOL OF PHYSICS & ASTRONOMY

אוניברסיטת תל-אביב

הפקולטה למדעים מדויקים
ע"ש ריימונד וברלי סאקלר
בית הספר לפיזיקה ואסטרונומיה

Thesis for a Degree "Doctor of Philosophy"

On Entanglement Entropy and Quantum Complexity in QFT and holography

Submitted by

Dean Carmi

The research was carried out under the supervision of

Prof. Jacob Sonnenschein

May, 2018

Acknowledgements

I would like to thank my supervisor Cobi Sonnenschein for giving me the opportunity to do research in the remarkable field of theoretical physics, and for his advise on physics. I would like to thank Tomer Volansky, Shimon Yankielowicz, Misha Smolkin, Rob Myers, Simon Caron-Huot, David Simmons-Duffin, who were my unofficial supervisors at various stages of my phd. I would like to thank all of my wonderful collaborators, and especially Omer Ben-Ami and Lorenzo Di Pietro. I would like to thank my parents and my family for all their support.

Abstract

This thesis is based on a collection of papers written during my phd studies. In this thesis I explore various aspects of entanglement entropy and complexity, in the framework of quantum field theory and the AdS-CFT duality. Quantum field theory (QFT) is the framework for the standard model- which is to date the most precise theory for describing nature. String theory is the leading candidate for a quantum theory of gravity, and for a unification of quantum gravity with the strong and electro/weak interaction. The AdS/CFT correspondence (discovered in 1997) has taught us that QFT and string theory are dual to each other in many cases. Entanglement is a very important concept in any quantum theory, and does not exist for classical (i.e unquantum) systems. Entanglement entropy (EE) is a function that quantifies the amount of entanglement of a quantum system. In the past 15 years, EE has become an important tool in the study of quantum field theories. The AdS-CFT correspondence gives a beautiful geometric prescription for calculating EE for holographic theories. In fact, entanglement entropy has become one of the main entries in the AdS-CFT dictionary. In the past 3 years, the concept of quantum complexity has been introduced in to high energy physics. Quantum complexity is a measure of the quantumness of systems, which is of different nature from entanglement. Additionally, a conjecture for computing quantum complexity in holographic theories has been put forward.

We will discuss primarily two topics in this thesis, the first of which is entanglement entropy in QFT, for both holographic and non-holographic theories. The second topic is holographic quantum complexity. The AdS-CFT correspondence gives, a similar and yet distinct, geometrical method to compute entanglement entropy and complexity. The holographic entanglement entropy has been proven in recent years. On the other hand, the holographic complexity conjecture has not been proven yet. Indeed, the concept of quantum complexity for quantum systems is in it's infancy, and is not well understood.

This thesis contains a collection of published papers listed below.

1. **“Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips”**[1]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, J. Sonnenschein, JHEP **1411**, 144 (2014)
2. **“Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres’** [2]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, M. Smolkin, JHEP **1508**, 048 (2015)
3. **“On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy ”** [3]
D. Carmi, JHEP **1403**, 045 (2014)
4. **“On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity ”**[4]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, JHEP **1611**, (2016) 129
5. **“Comments on Holographic Complexity ”** [5]
D. Carmi, R.C. Myers, P. Rath, JHEP **1703**, (2017) 118

6. “On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity ” [6]

D. Carmi, S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, R.C. Myers, S. Sugishita, JHEP **1711**, (2017) 188

The papers are preceded by an introduction which reviews the background required for reading the papers, and a summary which discusses the conclusions of each paper. ¹

In the first paper we study the holographic entanglement entropy of multiple strips. In particular we study the phase diagram, and transitions between bulk minimal surfaces. We prove that for m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, there are only two bulk minimal surfaces. For backgrounds which contain also ”disconnected” surfaces, we show that there are only 4 bulk minimal surfaces.

In the second paper, we study entanglement entropy in a QFT, and its behaviour along renormalization group flows. We derive a formula for computing the rate of change of the EE along the RG flow. We discuss applications to the F-theorem. we apply our result to a massive free field theory, and compare the universal terms to the literature.

In the third paper, we study the behavior of entanglement entropy, when one perturbatively varies the entangling surface. We derive formulas for the corrections to the EE in holographic and non-holographic theories. We show that entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry extremize the EE with respect to shape deformations that break some of the symmetry. This result applies to EE and to Renyi entropy for any QFT and in any space-time dimension.

In the fourth paper we study the volume conjecture for holographic sub-region complexity. We discuss the effect of bulk surface transitions on the holographic sub-region complexity, and compare this with holographic EE. For an AdS black hole geometry, the volume exhibits non-monotonic behavior as a function of the size of the entangling region (unlike the holographic EE in this setup, which is monotonic).

In the fifth paper, we study the divergence structure of holographic complexity. In particular we study the complexity=volume conjecture, and the complexity= action conjecture. We show that the coefficients of the UV divergences can be written as local integrals of geometric quantities in the boundary. We discover that the leading divergence in the complexity=action conjecture is logarithmically enhanced with respect to the volume.

In the sixth paper we study the time dependence of holographic complexity for the two conjectures. Using the complexity=action conjecture , we find that the complexity bound is violated at early times. However, in the complexity=volume conjecture the complexity bound is not violated. We also compute the time dependence for charged AdS black holes.

¹Papers written during my graduate studies which are not included in this thesis are [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12]

Contents

1	Introduction	6
1.1	CFT	7
1.2	AdS	9
1.3	The AdS-CFT correspondence	10
1.4	Entanglement Entropy	11
1.4.1	Example: The 2 qubit system	12
1.4.2	EE in QFT	13
1.4.3	Holographic Entanglement Entropy	15
1.5	Quantum Complexity	17
1.5.1	Holographic Quantum Complexity	19
2	Summary	22
2.1	Holographic entanglement entropy of multiple strips	23
2.2	Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres	24
2.3	On the shape dependence of Entanglement Entropy	25
2.4	On volumes of subregions in holography and complexity	27
2.5	Comments on Holographic Complexity	27
2.6	On the time dependence of holographic complexity	29
2.7	Summary and thoughts	30
3	Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips	35
4	Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres	69
5	On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy	109
6	On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity	135
7	Comments on Holographic Complexity	161
8	On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity	204

Chapter 1

Introduction

This chapter is an introduction to the topics of the thesis. The introduction contains sections on CFT, AdS, AdS-CFT, Entanglement Entropy, and Holographic quantum complexity.

1.1 CFT

Conformal field theories (CFT for short) are quantum field theories which have a conformal symmetry. The large amount of symmetry enables one to use powerful analytical and numerical techniques for solving CFTs at strong coupling. For example, the conformal bootstrap program has been recently applied to obtain numerical solutions for the 3d Ising model.

Consider the metric of R^d in Euclidean signature:

$$ds^2 = \delta_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu \quad (1.1)$$

A conformal transformation preserves the metric up to a scale factor $\Omega^2(x)$:

$$\delta_{\mu\nu} \frac{dx'^\mu}{dx^\alpha} \frac{dx'^\nu}{dx^\beta} = \Omega^2(x) \delta_{\alpha\beta} \quad (1.2)$$

Conformal transformations form the group $SO(d+1, 1)$. The generators are translations (P_μ), rotations ($M_{\mu\nu}$), dilatations D , and special conformal transformations K_μ :

$$\begin{aligned} P_\mu &= -i\partial_\mu & , & & K_\mu &= 2ix_\mu x^\nu \partial_\nu - ix^2 \partial_\mu \\ D &= -x^\mu \partial_\mu & , & & M_{\mu\nu} &= -i(x_\mu \partial_\nu - x_\nu \partial_\mu) \end{aligned} \quad (1.3)$$

They act on space-time coordinates in the following way:

- Translations: $x'_\mu = x_\mu + a_\mu$.
- Dilatations: $x'_\mu = \Lambda x_\mu$.
- Lorentz transformations: $x'_\mu = \Lambda_\mu^\nu x_\nu$.
- Special conformal transformations: $x'_\mu = \frac{x_\mu - b_\mu x^2}{1 - 2b \cdot x + b^2 x^2}$

The generators of the conformal symmetry obey the following commutation relations:

$$\begin{aligned} [D, K_\mu] &= -K_\mu & , & & [D, P_\mu] &= P_\mu & , & & [K_\mu, P_\nu] &= 2\delta_{\mu\nu} D - 2iM_{\mu\nu} \\ [D, K_\mu] &= i(\delta_{\mu\lambda} P_\nu - \delta_{\nu\lambda} P_\mu) & , & & [M_{\mu\nu}, K_\lambda] &= i(\delta_{\mu\lambda} K_\nu - \delta_{\nu\lambda} K_\mu) \\ [M_{\lambda\rho}, M_{\mu\nu}] &= i(\delta_{\lambda\mu} M_{\rho\nu} + \delta_{\rho\nu} M_{\lambda\mu} - \delta_{\rho\mu} M_{\lambda\nu} - \delta_{\lambda\nu} M_{\rho\mu}) \end{aligned} \quad (1.4)$$

Primary operators are operators which cannot be written as derivative of other operators. They obey

$$[K_\mu, O(0)] = 0 \quad , \quad [D, O(0)] = \Delta O(0) \quad , \quad [M_{\mu\nu}, O_a(0)] = [M_{\mu\nu}]_a^b O_b(0) \quad (1.5)$$

Correlators of scalar primary operators obey:

$$\langle O_1(x_1) \dots O_n(x_n) \rangle = \Omega(x'_1)^{\Delta_1} \dots \Omega(x'_n)^{\Delta_n} \langle O_1(x'_1) \dots O_n(x'_n) \rangle \quad (1.6)$$

Conformal invariance fixes the functional form of the 2 and 3-point functions of a CFT. The 2-point function is:

$$\langle O_i(x_i) O_j(x_j) \rangle = \frac{\delta_{ij}}{(x_i - x_j)^{2\Delta_i}} \quad (1.7)$$

The 3-point function:

$$\langle O_1(x_1) O_2(x_2) O_3(x_3) \rangle = \frac{C_{123}}{|x_{12}|^{\Delta_{12,3}} |x_{13}|^{\Delta_{13,2}} |x_{23}|^{\Delta_{23,1}}} \quad (1.8)$$

where $\Delta_{ij,k} \equiv \Delta_i + \Delta_j - \Delta_k$, and C_{123} are OPE coefficients.

The 4-point function of scalar primaries with equal scaling dimensions can be written as:

$$\langle O_1(x_1) O_2(x_2) O_3(x_3) O_4(x_4) \rangle = \frac{\mathcal{A}(u, v)}{(x_{13}^2 x_{24}^2)^\Delta} \quad (1.9)$$

where $\mathcal{A}(u, v)$ is a function of the two cross ratios u and v :

$$u = z\bar{z} = \frac{x_{12}^2 x_{34}^2}{x_{13}^2 x_{24}^2}, \quad v = (1-z)(1-\bar{z}) = \frac{x_{14}^2 x_{23}^2}{x_{13}^2 x_{24}^2} \quad (1.10)$$

The operator product expansion of two scalar primaries is:

$$O_i(x) O_j(0) = \sum_k C_{ijk} |x|^{-\Delta_{ij,k}} \left(O_k(0) + \beta x^\mu \partial_\mu O_k(0) + \dots \right) \quad (1.11)$$

The 4-point functions of a CFT obey the crossing equations (illustrated in Fig. 1.1):

$$\sum_k C_{12k} C_{k34} G_{\Delta_k l_k}^{(12)(34)}(x_1 \dots x_4) = \sum_p C_{12p} C_{p34} G_{\Delta_p l_p}^{(13)(24)}(x_1 \dots x_4) \quad (1.12)$$

where $G_{\Delta_k l_k}(x_1 \dots x_4)$ is a conformal block, which gives the contributions of a primary operator of dimension and spin Δ_k and l_k and all its descendants.

Figure 1.1: Illustrating the crossing equation of the conformal bootstrap program.

1.2 AdS

Euclidean AdS is the following hyperboloid embedded in $R^{d+1,1}$:

$$-(X^0)^2 + (X^1)^2 + \dots + (X^{d+1})^2 = -R^2 \quad (1.13)$$

The generators are:

$$J_{AB} = -i \left(X_A \frac{\partial}{\partial X_B} - X_B \frac{\partial}{\partial X_A} \right) \quad (1.14)$$

We define the Poincare coordinates:

$$\begin{aligned} X^0 &= R \frac{1 + x^2 + z^2}{2z} \\ X^\mu &= R \frac{x^\mu}{z} \\ X^{d+1} &= R \frac{1 - x^2 - z^2}{2z} \end{aligned} \quad (1.15)$$

The metric in Poincare coordinates:

$$ds^2 = R^2 \frac{dz^2 + dx_\mu dx^\mu}{z^2} \quad (1.16)$$

The global coordinates are defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} X^0 &= R \cosh \tau \cosh \rho \\ X^\mu &= R \Omega^\mu \sinh \rho \\ X^{d+1} &= -\sinh \tau \cosh \rho \end{aligned} \quad (1.17)$$

where Ω^μ is the unit sphere. The metric in global coordinates is:

$$ds^2 = R^2 (\cosh^2 \rho d\tau^2 + d\rho^2 + \sinh^2 \rho d\Omega_{d-1}^2) \quad (1.18)$$

1.3 The AdS-CFT correspondence

Let us briefly describe in this section the derivation of the correspondence between type IIB string theory compactified on $AdS_5 \times S^5$ and $\mathcal{N} = 4$ super Yang-Mills theory, [13, 14, 15, 16]. Consider a stack of N parallel D_3 branes in type IIB string theory in 10d Minkowski space. Let's look at this system from two separate descriptions:

1. The perturbative excitations are open and closed strings. Taking the low energy limit (energies much smaller than the string scale), the closed strings give rise to type IIB super gravity in 10 dimensions, whereas the open strings gives rise to $\mathcal{N} = 4$ $U(N)$ super Yang-Mills theory. Moreover, the interactions between the two theories vanish in the low energy limit, and they become decoupled. To summarize, in the low energy limit we have two decoupled theories: a non-interacting 10d bulk gravity theory and a 4d gauge theory.
2. Looking at the $D3$ brane system from a different view point, namely that of p -brane solutions to 10d type IIB SUGRA:

$$ds^2 = \left(1 + \frac{R^4}{r^4}\right)^{-1/2} \eta_{ij} dx^i dx^j + \left(1 + \frac{R^4}{r^4}\right)^{1/2} (dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega_5^2) \quad (1.19)$$

where $R^4 = 4\pi g_s \alpha'^2 N$.

In the low energy limit, there are two types of excitations in the geometry of Eq. 1.19. The first type is massless particles in the bulk. In the limit $r \gg R$, Eq. 1.19 becomes the flat space metric. The second type of excitations are particles approaching the near horizon region $r = 0$. The metric in this regime is:

$$ds^2 = \frac{R^2}{z^2} (dz^2 + \eta_{\mu\nu} dx^\mu dx^\nu) + R^2 d\Omega_5^2 \quad (1.20)$$

where $z = \frac{R^2}{r}$. This is $AdS_5 \times S^5$ geometry.

So we see that in both descriptions we have two decoupled theories in the low energy limit. In both cases there is a super gravity theory in flat space. So one can identify the two remaining theories. Thus the conjecture is that type IIB string theory on $AdS_5 \times S^5$ geometry is dual $N = 4$ $U(N)$ SYM theory in $d = 4$ dimensions.

A more precise statement of the duality was given in [] in terms of an equivalence of partition functions:

$$\langle e^{\int d^4x \phi(x) O(x)} \rangle_{CFT} = Z_{string}[\phi|_{boundary} = \phi(x)] \quad (1.21)$$

On the LHS $\phi(x)$ is a source for correlation functions, and on the RHS $\phi(x)$ is the boundary condition for the string partition function Z_{string} .

1.4 Entanglement Entropy

Entanglement entropy (EE) is a measure of the quantum correlations of a quantum state. EE is an extremely useful quantity in any quantum system. Applications range from condensed matter systems, to quantum field theory and quantum gravity. We will focus mainly on entanglement entropy in quantum field theory (QFT). In QFT, entanglement entropy is notoriously difficult to calculate apart for some simplified systems.

The entanglement entropy of a quantum state defined by a density matrix ρ is given by the Von-Neumann entropy:

$$S = -Tr(\rho \log \rho) \quad (1.22)$$

The density matrix of a quantum state $|\psi\rangle$ is given by:

$$\rho_{tot} = |\psi\rangle\langle\psi| \quad (1.23)$$

which has a vanishing Von-Neumann entropy (this occurs because the quantum state was a pure state). The density operator is a Hermitian operator with $Tr\rho = 1$.

We divide the system in to two subsystems A and B , and the Hilbert space is consequently given by the direct product $\mathcal{H}_{tot} = \mathcal{H}_A \times \mathcal{H}_B$. The subsystem A has a (reduced) density matrix ρ_A , given by tracing out the subsystem's B Hilbert space \mathcal{H}_B :

$$\rho_A = Tr_B \rho_{tot} \quad (1.24)$$

The entanglement entropy S_A of the subsystem A is given by the Von-Neumann entropy of the reduced density matrix ρ_A :

$$S_A = -Tr(\rho_A \log \rho_A) \quad (1.25)$$

S_A is a measure of the entanglement between the subsystem A and B . When the state is a thermal state $\rho_{therm} = e^{-\beta H}$, the EE is simply the thermal entropy:

$$S_{therm} = -Tr(\rho_{therm} \log \rho_{therm}) = \beta Tr(H e^{-\beta H}) = \beta \langle H \rangle = \beta E \quad (1.26)$$

The entanglement entropy obeys a few important properties:

1. Dividing a system into two subsystems B and C , the EE of the respective subsystems obeys a triangle inequality called "Sub-additivity"

$$S_A + S_B \geq S_{A+B} \quad (1.27)$$

2. A stronger inequality is called strong sub-additivity:

$$S_{A+B} + S_{B+C} \geq S_{A+B+C} + S_B \quad (1.28)$$

3. When the state is a pure state and B is complement of A , we have:

$$S(B) = S(A) \quad (1.29)$$

Figure 1.2: Quantum state of a single qubit can be visualised on the Bloch sphere. The sphere has unit radius for the probability to equal 1.

1.4.1 Example: The 2 qubit system

A general quantum state of a 1 qubit system is:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_1|0\rangle + \alpha_2|1\rangle \quad (1.30)$$

where $\alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 = 1$, since the probability equals one. this state is often represented in angular variables:

$$|\psi\rangle = \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|0\rangle + e^{i\varphi} \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)|1\rangle \quad (1.31)$$

where it can be visualized on the Bloch sphere of Fig. 1.2. A convenient basis of unitary operators acting on the 1 qubit states are the Pauli matrices: $\sigma_x, \sigma_y, \sigma_z$. The basis states $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ are eigenstates of the σ_z operator.

A general quantum state of a 2 qubit system is:

$$|\psi\rangle = \alpha_1|0_A0_B\rangle + \alpha_2|0_A1_B\rangle + \alpha_3|1_A0_B\rangle + \alpha_4|1_A1_B\rangle \quad (1.32)$$

where $\alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 + \alpha_3^2 + \alpha_4^2 = 1$. The 4 basis states $\{|00\rangle, |01\rangle, |10\rangle, |11\rangle\}$ are eigenstates of the $\sigma_z^{(A)} \times \sigma_z^{(B)}$ operator. These basis states are product states, and hence are un-entangled, and clearly have zero entanglement entropy:

$$S_A = -Tr\rho_A \log \rho_A = 0 \quad (1.33)$$

Figure 1.3: Setup for entanglement entropy in quantum field theory. On a constant time slice, the codimension-2 entangling surface Σ separates the entangling region A and its complement B .

A different basis of the 4-dimensional Hilbert space is the basis of Bell states:

$$\begin{aligned}
 |\phi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A 0_B\rangle + |1_A 1_B\rangle) \\
 |\phi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A 0_B\rangle - |1_A 1_B\rangle) \\
 |\psi^+\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A 1_B\rangle + |1_A 0_B\rangle) \\
 |\psi^-\rangle &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}(|0_A 1_B\rangle - |1_A 0_B\rangle)
 \end{aligned} \tag{1.34}$$

Each one of the 4 Bell states is a maximally entangled state, with maximal EE:

$$S_A = -\text{Tr} \rho_A \log \rho_A = 2 \log 2 \tag{1.35}$$

Entanglement is a resource which is the building block of the field of quantum information and quantum computation. For example, if two parties Alice and Bob share an entangled Bell state, they can transfer (via "Dense Coding") two qubits instead of one. Another important protocol falls under the name of "quantum teleportation", where Alice can transmit a quantum state to Bob, assuming they share a bell state. Bell inequalities have been used experimentally to measure entanglement, and in particular to rule out hidden variable theories.

1.4.2 EE in QFT

Entanglement entropy in a quantum field theory, is defined as in Fig. 1.3. One chooses a constant time slice, and divides it into a region A and its complement. The codimension-2 surface separating the two regions is called the entangling surface.

Figure 1.4: (a) Illustrating the reduced density matrix ρ_A , using the path integral formalism. (b) The Riemann surface \mathcal{R}^n via the replica trick.

A way to compute the EE in QFT is via the replica trick, where one first calculates $Tr_A \rho_A^n$, and then the EE S_A is given by [17, 18, 19, 20]:

$$S_A = -\rho_A \log \rho_A = \lim_{n \rightarrow 1} \frac{Tr_A \rho_A^n - 1}{1 - n} = -\frac{\partial}{\partial n} \log Tr_A \rho_A^n \Big|_{n \rightarrow 1} \quad (1.36)$$

Let's now describe the procedure for obtaining $Tr_A \rho_A^n$, illustrated in Fig. 1.4. To compute this, we first simplify to 2 dimensional CFTs, and an interval entangling region (this generalizes in an obvious way to higher d). One first computes the ground state wave functional:

$$\Psi[\phi_0(x)] = \int_{t_E = -\infty}^{\phi(t_E=0, x) = \phi_0(x)} D\phi e^{-S(\phi)} \quad (1.37)$$

where $\phi(t_E, x)$ denotes the value of the field at time t_E . the density matrix is then given by multiplying Ψ by it's complex conjugate $\bar{\Psi}$:

$$[\rho]_{\phi_0, \phi'_0} = \Psi[\phi_0(x)] \bar{\Psi}[\phi'_0(x)] \quad (1.38)$$

The reduced density matrix is obtained by integrating over the complement region B :

$$[\rho_A]_{\phi_+ \phi_-} = (Z_1)^{-1} \int_{t_E = -\infty}^{t_E = +\infty} D\phi e^{-S(\phi)} \prod_{x \in A} \delta(\phi(+0, x) - \phi_+(x)) \delta(\phi(-0, x) - \phi_-(x)) \quad (1.39)$$

where Z_1 is the partition function on R^2 . Since we need to compute $Tr_A \rho_A^n$, we multiply n copies as follows:

$$[\rho_A]_{\phi_1+\phi_1-} [\rho_A]_{\phi_2+\phi_2-} \cdots [\rho_A]_{\phi_n+\phi_n-} \quad (1.40)$$

and then taking the trace (see Fig. 1.4.):

$$Tr \rho_A^n = (Z_1)^{-n} \int_{(t_E, x) \in \mathcal{R}_n} D\phi e^{-S(\phi)} \equiv \frac{Z_n}{Z_1^n} \quad (1.41)$$

This is a path integral on an n sheeted Riemann surface \mathcal{R}_n . It is possible to show that this is equivalent to evaluating the correlator of 2 twist operators.

Applying these results for a 2d CFT and a single interval entangling region of length l , one gets the result :

$$S_A = \frac{c}{3} \log \left(\frac{l}{\delta} \right) \quad (1.42)$$

where δ is the UV cutoff. This important result illustrates how the central charge c of the CFT can appear in the entanglement entropy. It also illustrates the appearance of log divergences in the entanglement entropy.

Another result obtained by the replica trick is the EE for a massive $d = 2$ QFT of mass m :

$$S_A = -(Area) \frac{c}{6} \log(m\delta) \quad (1.43)$$

where $Area = 2$ in our case (because the entangling surface is just two points)

1.4.3 Holographic Entanglement Entropy

For theories with a holographic dual, the AdS-CFT correspondence gives a beautiful geometrical prescription for computing the EE. This prescription is the Ryu-Takayanagi formula [19, 21, 22]:

$$S = \frac{Area(\gamma_A)}{4G_N} \quad (1.44)$$

where G_N is the gravitational constant of the bulk theory. $Area(\gamma_A)$ is the area of the bulk minimal surface γ_A which is attached on the boundary to the entangling surface of the region A . The entangling surface is a codimension-2 surface in the boundary theory, and the bulk

Figure 1.5: Holographic entanglement entropy is given by the area of the bulk minimal surface, anchored on the boundary to the entangling surface.

Figure 1.6: Illustrating the strip entangling region, and its bulk minimal surface.

minimal surface is a codimension-2 surface in the bulk theory. See Fig. 1.5.

Example: Strip entangling region:

Consider a strip entangling region, illustrated in Fig. 1.6. There is a translational symmetry, which means that we have only one non-trivial coordinate x . Computing the area of a bulk surface using Poincare coordinates:

$$Area = R_{AdS}^d L^{d-1} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} dx \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{dz}{dx}}}{z^d} \quad (1.45)$$

to find the minimal bulk surface we should solve the equations of motion:

$$\frac{dz}{dx} = \frac{\sqrt{z_*^{2d} - z^{2d}}}{z^d} \quad (1.46)$$

integrating both sides of the equation of motion gives:

$$\frac{l}{2} = \int_0^{z_*} dz \frac{z^d}{\sqrt{z_*^{2d} - z^{2d}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(\frac{d+1}{2d})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2d})} z_* \quad (1.47)$$

All together we get for the holographic entanglement entropy:

$$S_A = \frac{Area}{4G_N} = \frac{1}{4G_N} \left[\frac{2R^d L^{d-1}}{d-1 \delta^{d-1}} + \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(\frac{1-d}{2d})}{d \Gamma(\frac{1}{2d})} R^d \frac{L^{d-1}}{z_*^{d-1}} \right] = \frac{1}{4G_N} \left[\frac{2R^d L^{d-1}}{d-1 \delta^{d-1}} - \frac{2^d \pi^{d/2} R^d}{d-1} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{d+1}{2d})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2d})} \right)^d \frac{L^{d-1}}{l^{d-1}} \right] \quad (1.48)$$

1.5 Quantum Complexity

Quantum complexity [23, 24, 25] is a measure of a distance between two quantum states. Consider a quantum state consisting of N qubits:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{k_1 \dots k_N} c_{k_1 \dots k_N} |k_1 \dots k_N\rangle \quad (1.49)$$

where k_i take the values 0 or 1, and the $c_{k_1 \dots k_N}$ are complex numbers. It requires 2^N complex numbers to specify this quantum state (i.e exponential in the size of the system). In order to define quantum complexity, we start from a simple reference state, say $|0 \dots 0\rangle$. This state is a product state. One then chooses a universal gate set, i.e unitary operators, which act on the quantum state. For simplicity we consider unitary operators consisting of 1 and 2-qubit

Figure 1.7: Plot illustrating how quantum complexity is expected to change with time. Complexity is expected to grow linearly for a time exponential in the system size. Then it saturated at the maximal value, and fluctuates around this value. After a doubly exponential time, there can be a fluctuation which is large enough to return the system to it's original state.

operators. Every state in the Hilbert space can be approached (arbitrary close) by applying gates from this universal gate set. The quantum complexity of a state $|\psi\rangle$ is defined as the minimal number of gates required to prepare the state $|\psi\rangle$ from the reference state $|0\dots 0\rangle$.

For a large enough quantum system (i.e N large in the example above), nearly all states of the Hilbert space have a maximal complexity, which is exponential in N :

$$C_{max} \sim 2^N \tag{1.50}$$

Compare this to the maximal entropy of the system, which is $N \log 2$, i.e linear in N . Consider now a system out of equilibrium, which undergoes thermalization until at some point it reaches thermal equilibrium. During thermalization the entropy grows, and it saturates when the system reaches thermal equilibrium. The quantum complexity of this system initially grows linearly (Fig. 1.7), but continues to grow much longer after thermal equilibrium has been reached. After an exponentially large time $t \sim e^N$, the complexity saturates at a constant value C_{max} . After that time, the complexity fluctuates around C_{max} . After a doubly exponential time e^{e^N} , there may be a large enough fluctuation restoring the system to it's initial state. It was also argued that the rate of change of complexity is proportional to the entropy and temperature of the system: $\frac{dC}{dt} \propto TS$.

Figure 1.8: Penrose diagram for the thermo-field double state. Illustrating the volume conjecture for holographic complexity in AdS black hole geometry: showing a few spatial slices.

1.5.1 Holographic Quantum Complexity

Consider a specific quantum state described the thermo-field double state:

$$|TFD(t_L, t_R)\rangle = Z^{\frac{-1}{2}} \sum_{\alpha} e^{-E_{\alpha}/(2T)} e^{-iE_{\alpha}(t_L+t_R)} |E_{\alpha}\rangle_L |E_{\alpha}\rangle_R \quad (1.51)$$

where L and R label the quantum states (and times) associated with the left and right (entangled) systems. The thermofield double state plays an important role in the AdS-CFT duality, in which the L and R systems describe two entangled CFTs living on the 2 boundaries of the bulk AdS space-time [26]. The bulk dual geometry of the thermo-field double state is an eternal double-sided AdS black hole, Fig 1.8. The 2 CFTs are then connected in the bulk through the black hole interior (wormhole). To see this, we connected the 2 boundary CFTs with a space-like slice, attached at time t_1 on the boundary. The "wormhole" is a dynamical object whose length grows with time t_1 (linear in time when t is very large). Compare this with the holographic EE, described by the area of the Ryu-Takayanagi surface, which saturates at some finite time (for a finite size entangling surface).

There have been two conjectures put forward for computing the quantum complexity for holographic theories¹. Handwavingly, both conjectures basically equate the quantum complexity with the size of the wormhole. So according to these conjectures, complexity is

¹Quantum complexity also appears in black hole physics as a measure of the difficulty to decode Hawking radiation.

Figure 1.9: Wheeler-DeWitt patch with two different regularizations. In both cases, the WDW patch terminates at the regulator surface: (a) The edge of the WDW patch is the time slice on the asymptotic boundary. The action contains a GHY surface term and two joint terms from the new boundary at $z = \delta$. (b) The edge of the WDW patch is the time slice in the regulator surface. The action contains null joint term from the edge at $z = \delta$.

related to physics inside the black hole horizon. A loose analogy is that for an outside the observer the black hole interior is hidden, and likewise the parameters describing a quantum wave function are hidden from measurements. The first conjecture is called the "complexity = volume" conjecture. It states that the complexity at time t is given by the volume of the codimension-1 extremal surface attached to the boundary at time t , Fig 1.8:

$$C_V = \frac{V}{G_N \ell} \quad (1.52)$$

where G_N is the bulk Newton constant, and ℓ is some unspecified length scale needed to make dimensional analysis work (ℓ is sometimes chosen to be the size of the black hole).

The second conjecture is called the "complexity = action" conjecture. It states that the complexity at time t is given by the action computed on the bulk Wheeler deWitt patch attached at time t on the boundary, Fig 1.9:

$$C_A = \frac{A_{WDW}}{\pi \hbar} \quad (1.53)$$

The wheeler dewitt patch is defined as the bulk domain of dependence of a spatial slice attached at time t on the boundary (in other worrds the WDW patch is the collection of all spatial slices attached at time t on the boundary.).

One significant difference between the two conjectures, is that the for the complexity=action conjecture one needs to compute boundary terms of the action. Namely, the wheeler deWitt

patch contains null and non-null codimension-1 boundaries (the edges of the diamond), and also codimension-2 corners. These boundary and corner terms complicate the computation, and also give rise to some interesting behavior of the complexity. Another difference is that the complexity=volume (CV) conjecture contains an arbitrary length scale l (as we noted above), whereas the complexity =action (CA) conjecture does not. This makes the CA conjecture more natural.

The holographic quantum complexity conjectures pass a few checks. Similarly to complexity, the volume of the black hole interior continues growing after thermal equilibrium is reached. Likewise, they both grow linearly with time (at late times). Additionally, in the action conjecture the holographic complexity for black holes saturates the complexity bound at late times. The complexity bound (also known as Lloyd's bound) states that the rate of change of a computation done by a quantum system is bounded from above by twice the energy of the system ($\frac{dC}{dt} \leq 2E$). More detailed checks of the holographic conjectures include the behaviour in shock wave geometries, which matches that of the tensor networks. For more details on holographic complexity, see [23, 24, 25] .

Chapter 2

Summary

Figure 2.1: Illustration of the two minimal surfaces S_A and S_B for 2 strips in a CFT. There is a transition between the two surfaces when $x/l = f(d)$, where $f(d)$ depends only on d .

In this section we summarize the papers contained in this thesis.

2.1 Holographic entanglement entropy of multiple strips

This paper studies holographic entanglement entropy (HEE), and its dependence on the shape of the entangling surface. More specifically, we study holographic entanglement entropy of multiple strip entangling surfaces. Recall that the HEE is proportional to the area of the bulk minimal surface which is attached to the entangling surface on the boundary. As in soap bubble analogy, there can be multiple extremal surfaces, and the Ryu-Takayanagi prescription is to choose the (global) minimal surface. Changing the entangling surface (or the parameters of the theory) can cause transitions between bulk extremal surfaces of different topologies¹.

The simplest examples of bulk transition occurs for a CFT and an entangling surface consisting of 2 strips on the boundary. Changing the ratio between the length and separation of the strips, causes a transition between a connected bulk minimal surface and a disconnected surface, Fig 2.1.

For non-CFTs, bulk phase transitions can also occur for a single strip entangling surface. For example in a confining geometry, there is a bulk length scale, and the transition occurs when changing the ratio between this length scale and the strip width.

The main results of the paper include:

- We show that for an entangling surface of m strips of equal length and separation, there are only 2 bulk minimal surfaces.
- For geometries in which there are disconnected surfaces for the 1 strip case, the m strip case has only 4 bulk minimal surfaces.
- We study the transitions between the bulk minimal surfaces, and plot the corresponding "phase diagrams".

¹These geometric transition are reminiscent of first order phase transitions.

Figure 2.2: Illustrating the setup of a QFT living on an S^d sphere. The entangling surface (at $t = 0$ and $\theta = \pi/2$) divides the equator into two equal cap regions (shown in blue and red).

- For confining geometries with m strips we find new classes of disconnected bulk minimal surfaces, and display their rich phase diagram.
- We also consider thermal CFTs on a compact space, which exhibit an "entanglement plateaux" transition. In particular we study the BTZ black hole in global AdS with 2 a strips entangling surface.
- We further perform a perturbative analysis of the m strip system by perturbing the CFT and the length/separation between the strips.

2.2 Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres

In this paper [2] we study the RG flow of entanglement entropy on a cap-like region of De Sitter space, see Fig. 2.2. We are motivated by the c, a, and F-theorems and their relation to entanglement entropy. We derive a novel relation between the change of EE along the RG

Figure 2.3: Illustration of a perturbed circle $r(\phi) = 1 + \epsilon \sum_n a_n \cos(n\phi)$. **Left:** A Perturbation without a zero mode $a_0 = 0$. **Right:** A Perturbation with a zero mode $a_0 = 0.3$.

flow (i.e $\frac{dS}{dR}$, where R is the curvature radius of De Sitter space), and the VEV of the trace of the energy momentum tensor.

$$R \frac{dS}{dR} = \frac{\Omega_d R^{d+1}}{d} \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{C}{R^d} \right) \quad (2.1)$$

where $\langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle = -\frac{1}{d} \frac{C}{R^d} g_{\mu\nu}(x)$, and C is a dimensionless function of the couplings. At the fixed points, the RHS becomes proportional to the a anomaly.

The relation Eq. 2.1 holds for a general quantum field theory, and we discuss it's application to the $d = 3$ F-theorem. We also show that the entanglement entropy in this setup is equal to the thermal entropy of the De Sitter space. We apply our results to the case of a massive free field theory, and successfully compare to known results for the universal terms of entanglement entropy. For example a minimally coupled scalar field of mass m has universal terms of the form:

$$m^2 \frac{\partial S}{\partial m^2} = c_d A_\Sigma m^{d-2} \log(m\delta) \quad (2.2)$$

where A_Σ is the area of the entangling surface, and δ is the UV cutoff.

Additionally, we provide computational evidence that the universal "area law" for a conformally coupled scalar field is different from the known result in the literature, and this difference survives in the flat space limit.

2.3 On the shape dependence of Entanglement Entropy

In this work [3] we study the dependence of the entanglement entropy on the shape of the entangling surface. The divergence structure of entanglement entropy in a CFT of d dimensions

is:

$$S = c_{d-2} \frac{R^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} + c_{d-4} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \dots + \left\{ \begin{array}{l} c_1 \frac{R}{\delta} + (-1)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} S^{(univ)} \quad , \quad d = \text{odd} \\ c_2 \frac{R^2}{\delta^2} + (-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} S^{(univ)} \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) \quad , \quad d = \text{even} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.3)$$

where R is the scale of the entangling surface, and δ is the UV cutoff. In this work we will be interested in the universal terms $S^{(univ)}$.

We parametrize the entangling surface as follows:

$$r(y_i) = r_0(y_i) + \epsilon f(y_i) \quad (2.4)$$

where ϵ is a small deformation parameter. See Fig. 2.3. Then the entanglement entropy can be written as an expansion in ϵ :

$$S = S_0 + S_1 \epsilon + S_2 \epsilon^2 + \dots \quad (2.5)$$

This procedure can be carried out for a perturbed sphere in a d dimensional CFT:

$$r(\Omega_{d-2}) = R \left[1 + \epsilon \sum_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}} a_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}} Y_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}}(\Omega_{d-2}) \right] \quad (2.6)$$

We find the following results for the entanglement entropy:

$$S_1^{(univ)} = 0 \quad (2.7)$$

and

$$S_2^{(univ)} = C_T \frac{\pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}} (d-1)}{2^{d-2} \Gamma(d+2) \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \sum_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-1}} a_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-1}}^2 \prod_{k=1}^d (l+k-2) \times \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\pi}{2} \quad , \quad d = \text{odd} \\ 1 \quad , \quad d = \text{even} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.8)$$

see also [27] who obtained the above result.

Since the first order correction is zero and the second order correction is positive, this means that the sphere is a local minimum of the EE.

In fact, we show that Eq. 2.7 holds more generally: entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry locally extremize the EE with respect to shape deformations which break some of the symmetry.

Figure 2.4: Plot of $\Delta V \equiv V - V_{CFT}$ as a function of l (we change l and leave T fixed) for AdS_5 . At $l = 0$ we have $\Delta V = 0$.

2.4 On volumes of subregions in holography and complexity

The complexity of a quantum state is a measure of the distance between a quantum state and some simple reference state. There are 2 conjectures for the holographic bulk dual of complexity: The volume inside the codimension-1 minimal bulk (Ryu-Takayanagi) surface, and the bulk action on the Wheeler-deWitt patch. Likewise, there are analogous conjectures for subregion complexity (i.e the complexity of the state obtained by tracing out the complement of the subregion). In this paper we study the volume conjecture for subregion complexity.

For a bulk geometry consisting of an AdS black hole, we find that the volume has non-monotonic behavior when changing the size of the subregion Fig 2.4. This behavior is very different from holographic entanglement entropy, which is monotonic. We study the behavior of the volume as a function of the temperature.

For geometries in which the bulk minimal surface (whose area computes the holographic entanglement entropy) exhibits transitions, the volume has discontinuous jumps at the transition point, and we compute these discontinuities.

2.5 Comments on Holographic Complexity

There are two conjectures for the holographic bulk dual of complexity: the complexity=action conjecture, and the complexity=volume conjecture [23, 28, 29, 24, 30]:

$$C_V = \frac{V}{G_N \ell} \quad , \quad C_A = \frac{A_{WDW}}{\pi \hbar} \quad (2.9)$$

See Figs. 2.5 and 1.9.

Figure 2.5: Showing the extremal volume construction for the CV conjecture for AdS_3 . We regulate the volume by introducing a cutoff surface at $z = \delta$, where δ is the short-distance cutoff in the boundary theory.

Figure 2.6: For a ball-shaped boundary region B , the bulk region $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$ is the intersection of the entanglement wedge (b) Showing a cross-section of $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$ at $r = 0$. (See the main text for the notation.)

We study [5] the ultraviolet divergence structure of the holographic complexity in the 2 conjectures. Similarly to holographic entanglement entropy, in the holographic complexity divergent terms can be written in terms of integrals of curvatures on the boundary. For the volume, we have:

$$C_V = \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{f_1(\text{curvatures})}{\delta^{d-1}} + \frac{f_2(\text{curvatures})}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \quad (2.10)$$

For the bulk action we find that, in addition to divergences of the form of Eq. 2.10, we have divergences of the form:

$$C_A = \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N} \log\left(\frac{L}{\delta}\right) \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{f_1(\text{curvatures})}{\delta^{d-1}} + \frac{f_2(\text{curvatures})}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \quad (2.11)$$

The leading divergence arises from a corner term on the boundary of AdS. This family of divergences is enhanced with a log term, and does not arise in the volume conjecture or in holographic entanglement entropy.

We also consider a generalization of the holographic complexity conjectures to subregions on the boundary (i.e. to mixed states), and argue in favor of a prescription which also works for time-dependent states. For the volume case, the prescription is the following. For a subregion A on the boundary one constructs the extremal bulk HRT surface. The subregion complexity is then conjectured to be proportional to the volume of the maximal codimension-1 surface bounded by the HRT surface and the boundary subregion A .

The action subregion complexity conjecture is as follows. The subregion complexity is conjectured to be equal to the intersection of the WDW patch and the entanglement wedge of a subregion A on the boundary, see Fig 2.6.

2.6 On the time dependence of holographic complexity

Figure 2.7: **Left:** Plot of the rate of change of volume as a function of time for neutral planar AdS black holes in dimensions $d = 4$ (blue), $d = 3$ (red), $d = 2$ (green). **Right:** Plot of the rate of change of action as a function of time for neutral planar AdS black holes in $d = 4$ dimensions. The different curves are different values of the horizon radius $d = 4$ (blue), $d = 3$ (red), $d = 2$ (green).

We study the time dependence of holographic complexity for AdS black hole geometries. Previously the time dependence of holographic complexity was computed for very late times. We extend these calculations to all times t . In the case of the volume conjecture, the volume

grows monotonically with time and saturates at the Lloyd bound at very late times, see Fig 2.7-Left. In the case of the action conjecture, the time dependence has some interesting new behavior: the action is constant at very small times, then it starts growing at some critical time t_0 and grows until it overshoots the complexity (Lloyd) bound and reaches a maximum, then it decreases until it approaches the complexity bound from above at $t \rightarrow \infty$ see Fig 2.7-Right. This is the first example of a violation of the complexity bound in the action conjecture. We also study charged black holes and their time dependence, as well as complexity of formation.

2.7 Summary and thoughts

- One of the main motivations for our paper [2] was to obtain a better understanding of c-theorems² via entanglement entropy. c-theorem implies the existence of a c-function which is monotonic along RG flows, $\frac{dc}{d\mu} \leq 0$. c-theorems have been proved in $2d$ by considering stress tensor 2-point correlators [31], and in $4d$ by considering the dilaton effective action [32]. There are also entanglement type proofs of c-theorems that are based on the strong sub-additivity property of entanglement entropy. There is such an entanglement based proof of the $2d$ c-theorem [33], and recently there has been a proof in $4d$ [34]. The relation between the entanglement based and non-entanglement based proofs of c-theorems is an interesting open problem. In $3d$ there is an entanglement (strong sub-additivity) based proof of the F-theorem [35]. Whether there exists a proof of the F-theorem which does not employ strong subadditivity is an interesting open question. Other interesting open questions are whether there are higher dimensional c and F theorems.
- In [3] we studied the leading corrections to the entanglement entropy arising from small perturbations of the entanglement surface. Similar type shape perturbations play an important role in the quantum null energy condition (QNEC) [36], which was recently proved in [37].
- In [6] we showed for the first time that there is a violation of the complexity bound in the complexity=action conjecture for eternal double sided black holes. The origin of this violation stems from logarithmic terms coming from the bulk corner term of the Wheeler-deWitt patch, where the null sheets intersect. The rate of change of complexity

²In even space-time dimensions the c-function at the fixed point equals the a-anomaly. The a-anomaly is also the coefficient in front of the universal log piece of the sphere partition function. In odd space-time dimensions the universal piece of the sphere partition function is it's finite piece. This finite piece is called the F-function, and similarly to the c-function, it is conjectured to obey monotonicity along RG flow (i.e an F-theorem).

is given by the simple expression (See Eq. 2.35 of [6].):

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{2M}{\pi} + F(r_m) \log \frac{|f(r_m)|}{\alpha^2} \quad (2.12)$$

Where M is the mass of the black hole and r_m is the bulk position of the corner of the WDW patch. At late times $t \rightarrow \infty$ the function $F(r_m) \rightarrow 0$ and the logarithmic term vanishes. Thus at late times $\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \rightarrow \frac{2M}{\pi}$ and the complexity bound is saturated. But at early times the logarithmic term causes a violation of the complexity bound, i.e. $\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} > \frac{2M}{\pi}$. On the other hand in the case of a collapsing black hole there is no such violation of the complexity bound [38]. It would be interesting to understand the reason behind these differences.

- The logarithmic corner term above contains the free parameter α . The parameter α also enters into the divergence structure of the WDW action, [5]. There are additional free parameters coming from the null surface terms of the WDW action. The appearance of ambiguities in the holographic complexity is rather strange. We discussed these ambiguities in [5, 6], and speculated on their physical significance. One speculation is that these ambiguities capture the ambiguities that exist in the definition of complexity on the boundary. Recall that complexity contains ambiguities related to the choice of universal quantum gates. Interestingly, logarithmic divergences have shown up in computations of complexity in free QFT [39, 40]. This fact strenghtens the case for the complexity =action conjecture.
- In [5] we gave two (volume and action) covariant definitions of subregion holographic complexity of a subregion A . We speculated on the physical interpretation of subregion complexity on the boundary, which involves allowing the universal gates to act on the degrees of freedom in A coupled to an ancillary system. Clearly subregion complexity is a quantity that deserves further study.
- In [7] we speculated that since complexity is a basis dependent quantity (one has to choose a reference state), it might be interesting to compute basis dependent quantities such as³ $Tr(\rho\rho^*)$. Another speculation was regarding a bulk region called the “causal shadow”. Since the causal shadow is a region which goes through the black hole horizon, one can speculate that it has some relation to holographic complexity.

³Here ρ is the density matrix and ρ^* is it's complex conjugate.

Bibliography

- [1] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and J. Sonnenschein, *Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips*, *JHEP* **11** (2014) 144, [[arXiv:1409.6305](#)].
- [2] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and M. Smolkin, *Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres*, *JHEP* **08** (2015) 048, [[arXiv:1504.00913](#)].
- [3] D. Carmi, *On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy*, *JHEP* **12** (2015) 043, [[arXiv:1506.07528](#)].
- [4] O. Ben-Ami and D. Carmi, *On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity*, *JHEP* **11** (2016) 129, [[arXiv:1609.02514](#)].
- [5] D. Carmi, R. C. Myers, and P. Rath, *Comments on Holographic Complexity*, *JHEP* **03** (2017) 118, [[arXiv:1612.00433](#)].
- [6] D. Carmi, S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, R. C. Myers, and S. Sugishita, *On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity*, *JHEP* **11** (2017) 188, [[arXiv:1709.10184](#)].
- [7] D. Carmi, *More on Holographic Volumes, Entanglement, and Complexity*, [arXiv:1709.10463](#).
- [8] D. Carmi, A. Falkowski, E. Kuflik, T. Volansky, and J. Zupan, *Higgs After the Discovery: A Status Report*, *JHEP* **10** (2012) 196, [[arXiv:1207.1718](#)].
- [9] D. Carmi, A. Falkowski, E. Kuflik, and T. Volansky, *Interpreting the 125 GeV Higgs*, *Nuovo Cim.* **C035** (2012), no. 06 315–322, [[arXiv:1206.4201](#)]. [*Frascati Phys. Ser.*57,315(2013)].
- [10] D. Carmi, A. Falkowski, E. Kuflik, and T. Volansky, *Interpreting LHC Higgs Results from Natural New Physics Perspective*, *JHEP* **07** (2012) 136, [[arXiv:1202.3144](#)].
- [11] D. Carmi, *TeV Scale Strings and Scattering Amplitudes at the LHC*, Master’s thesis, Tel Aviv U., 2011.

- [12] D. Carmi, L. Di Pietro, and S. Komatsu, *A Study of Quantum Field Theories in AdS at Finite Coupling*, [arXiv:1810.04185](#).
- [13] J. M. Maldacena, *The Large N limit of superconformal field theories and supergravity*, *Int. J. Theor. Phys.* **38** (1999) 1113–1133, [[hep-th/9711200](#)]. [*Adv. Theor. Math. Phys.*2,231(1998)].
- [14] S. S. Gubser, I. R. Klebanov, and A. M. Polyakov, *Gauge theory correlators from noncritical string theory*, *Phys. Lett.* **B428** (1998) 105–114, [[hep-th/9802109](#)].
- [15] E. Witten, *Anti-de Sitter space and holography*, *Adv. Theor. Math. Phys.* **2** (1998) 253–291, [[hep-th/9802150](#)].
- [16] O. Aharony, S. S. Gubser, J. M. Maldacena, H. Ooguri, and Y. Oz, *Large N field theories, string theory and gravity*, *Phys. Rept.* **323** (2000) 183–386, [[hep-th/9905111](#)].
- [17] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, *Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory*, *J. Stat. Mech.* **0406** (2004) P06002, [[hep-th/0405152](#)].
- [18] T. Nishioka, S. Ryu, and T. Takayanagi, *Holographic Entanglement Entropy: An Overview*, *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504008, [[arXiv:0905.0932](#)].
- [19] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, *Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy*, *JHEP* **08** (2006) 045, [[hep-th/0605073](#)].
- [20] H. Casini and M. Huerta, *Entanglement entropy in free quantum field theory*, *J. Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504007, [[arXiv:0905.2562](#)].
- [21] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, *Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [[hep-th/0603001](#)].
- [22] V. E. Hubeny, M. Rangamani, and T. Takayanagi, *A Covariant holographic entanglement entropy proposal*, *JHEP* **07** (2007) 062, [[arXiv:0705.0016](#)].
- [23] L. Susskind, *Computational Complexity and Black Hole Horizons*, *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 44–48, [[arXiv:1403.5695](#)]. [*Fortsch. Phys.*64,24(2016)].
- [24] L. Susskind, *Entanglement is not enough*, *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 49–71, [[arXiv:1411.0690](#)].
- [25] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, *Complexity, action, and black holes*, *Phys. Rev.* **D93** (2016), no. 8 086006, [[arXiv:1512.04993](#)].
- [26] J. M. Maldacena, *Eternal black holes in anti-de Sitter*, *JHEP* **04** (2003) 021, [[hep-th/0106112](#)].

- [27] M. Mezei, *Entanglement entropy across a deformed sphere*, *Phys. Rev.* **D91** (2015), no. 4 045038, [arXiv:1411.7011].
- [28] D. Stanford and L. Susskind, *Complexity and Shock Wave Geometries*, *Phys. Rev.* **D90** (2014), no. 12 126007, [arXiv:1406.2678].
- [29] L. Susskind and Y. Zhao, *Switchbacks and the Bridge to Nowhere*, arXiv:1408.2823.
- [30] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, *Holographic Complexity Equals Bulk Action?*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116** (2016), no. 19 191301, [arXiv:1509.07876].
- [31] A. B. Zamolodchikov, *Irreversibility of the Flux of the Renormalization Group in a 2D Field Theory*, *JETP Lett.* **43** (1986) 730–732. [Pisma Zh. Eksp. Teor. Fiz.43,565(1986)].
- [32] Z. Komargodski and A. Schwimmer, *On Renormalization Group Flows in Four Dimensions*, *JHEP* **12** (2011) 099, [arXiv:1107.3987].
- [33] H. Casini and M. Huerta, *A Finite entanglement entropy and the c-theorem*, *Phys. Lett.* **B600** (2004) 142–150, [hep-th/0405111].
- [34] H. Casini, E. Testé, and G. Torroba, *Markov Property of the Conformal Field Theory Vacuum and the a Theorem*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **118** (2017), no. 26 261602, [arXiv:1704.01870].
- [35] H. Casini and M. Huerta, *On the RG running of the entanglement entropy of a circle*, *Phys. Rev.* **D85** (2012) 125016, [arXiv:1202.5650].
- [36] R. Bousso, Z. Fisher, J. Koeller, S. Leichenauer, and A. C. Wall, *Proof of the Quantum Null Energy Condition*, *Phys. Rev.* **D93** (2016), no. 2 024017, [arXiv:1509.02542].
- [37] S. Balakrishnan, T. Faulkner, Z. U. Khandker, and H. Wang, *A General Proof of the Quantum Null Energy Condition*, arXiv:1706.09432.
- [38] S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, and R. C. Myers, *Holographic complexity in Vaidya spacetimes. Part I*, *JHEP* **06** (2018) 046, [arXiv:1804.07410].
- [39] R. Jefferson and R. C. Myers, *Circuit complexity in quantum field theory*, *JHEP* **10** (2017) 107, [arXiv:1707.08570].
- [40] S. Chapman, M. P. Heller, H. Marrochio, and F. Pastawski, *Toward a Definition of Complexity for Quantum Field Theory States*, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **120** (2018), no. 12 121602, [arXiv:1707.08582].

Chapter 3

Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips

Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips

Omer Ben-Ami¹, Dean Carmi¹, Jacob Sonnenschein¹,

¹ *Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences
School of Physics and Astronomy
Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel*

e-mails: omerben@post.tau.ac.il, carmidea@post.tau.ac.il, cobi@post.tau.ac.il

ABSTRACT: We study holographic entanglement entropy (HEE) of m strips in various holographic theories. We prove that for m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, there are only 2 bulk minimal surfaces. For backgrounds which contain also “disconnected” surfaces, there are only 4 bulk minimal surfaces. Depending on the length of the strips and separation between them, the HEE exhibits first order “geometric” phase transitions between bulk minimal surfaces with different topologies. We study these different phases and display various phase diagrams. For confining geometries with m strips, we find new classes of “disconnected” bulk minimal surfaces, and the resulting phase diagrams have a rich structure. We also study the “entanglement plateau” transition, where we consider the BTZ black hole in global coordinates with 2 strips. It is found that there are 4 bulk minimal surfaces, and the resulting phase diagram is displayed. We perform a general perturbative analysis of the m -strip system: including perturbing the CFT and perturbing the length or separation of the strips.

Contents

1. Introduction	2
2. Phases of HEE in CFTs with multiple strips	4
2.1 CFT with two strips of equal length l	5
2.2 CFT with m strips	6
2.3 CFT with 2 strips of unequal length	7
2.4 CFT with 3 equal length strips and unequal separations	8
3. Phases of HEE in confining backgrounds with multiple strips	9
3.1 Confining background and 1 strip	9
3.2 Confining background with 2 strips of equal length l	11
3.3 Confining background and m strips	13
4. “Entanglement plateau-like” transitions and multiple strips	14
5. Phases of HEE in other examples	16
5.1 Dp-brane background with two strips of equal length l	16
5.2 CFT at finite T with m strips	17
5.3 Wilson loops with m strips	17
6. A general perturbative analysis for m strips	17
6.1 Perturbing the CFT	17
6.2 Perturbing the separations and lengths of the strips	19
6.2.1 Changing the separations between the strips	20
6.2.2 Changing the length of the strips	21
7. Excluding classes of bulk minimal surfaces	21
8. Discussion	24
A. Holographic Wilson lines and HEE	26
A.1 Holographic Wilson lines in Confining backgrounds	26
A.2 A correspondence between HEE and holographic Wilson loops	27
A.3 An example	28

1. Introduction

Entanglement entropy (EE) is an important tool in studying quantum systems. It has applications in areas such as condensed matter and quantum gravity. Entanglement entropy is difficult to calculate in a QFT [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7], but for CFTs with holographic duals there is a simple geometric formula proposed by [8, 9] and later derived in [10, 11].

In this paper we study the holographic entanglement entropy (HEE) of multiple strips. In situations where there is more than one locally minimal Ryu-Takayanagi surface, the prescription is to choose the absolute minimal surface amongst them. There exist phase transitions between the topologically distinct bulk minimal Ryu-Takayanagi surfaces. As a first example, recall the “geometric” phase transitions studied by Headrick [12]. He discussed HEE and mutual information for 2 strip regions in a CFT. A “geometric phase transition” occurs between two topologically distinct bulk surfaces, when one changes the separation or length of the strips, see Fig. 2. The mutual information of two entangling regions a and b is defined as:

$$I(a, b) = S(a) + S(b) - S(a \cup b) \quad (1.1)$$

where $S(a)$ and $S(b)$ are the EE of the regions a and b respectively. $I(a, b)$ is zero (non-zero) for the bulk surfaces in Fig. 2 left (right), and there is a first order phase transition.

For m strips, the mutual information can be defined in several ways. Two definitions are [13]:

$$\hat{I} = \sum_{i=1}^m S(a_i) - S(a_1 \cup a_2 \cdots \cup a_m) \quad (1.2)$$

$$\tilde{I} = \sum_{i=1}^m S(a_i) - \sum_{i<j}^m S(a_i \cup a_j) + \sum_{i<j<k}^m S(a_i \cup a_j \cup a_k) + \dots + (-1)^m S(a_1 \cup a_2 \cup \dots \cup a_m) \quad (1.3)$$

For recent papers on holographic mutual information see [12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 13, 20, 21]. For works on the CFT side see [22, 23, 24, 25, 26, 27].

Holographic Entanglement entropy exhibits additional types of phase transitions. Using a generalization of the RT formula to non-conformal backgrounds, [28, 29] studied the entanglement entropy $S(l)$ for a single strip region (Fig. 1) of length l in confining backgrounds. They discovered that a first order phase transition occurs between two distinct bulk surfaces (a “connected” and a “disconnected” surface) at a critical strip length $l = l_{crit}$, Figs. 10, 11. This phase transition was conjectured to be related to the Hagedorn transition [28, 29].

A third class of HEE transitions are the “Entanglement-plateaux” transitions discussed in [30, 31]. These transitions occur in holographic CFTs at finite temperature defined on a compact space. The simplest example is the BTZ black hole in global coordinates. In this example, consider an entangling region which is a segment of angle θ on the boundary circle, Fig. 16. Enlarging θ , there is a phase transition at $\theta = \theta_c$ to a “disjoint” Ryu-Takayanagi surface containing a piece which wraps the horizon of the black hole.

In our work, we generalize the above phenomena to 2 or more strips. We plot phase diagrams which encode the different regions of the topologically distinct bulk minimal surfaces. These phase diagrams

exhibit an interplay between the “geometric phase transitions” and the other phase transitions mentioned above.

For CFTs with 2 or more strips, various phase diagrams are displayed. The effect of changing m and d will also be studied: reducing m or d causes disentanglement.

A similar analysis is done for holographic confining backgrounds with 2 or more strips. The m strip HEE is characterized by a new class of “disconnected” bulk minimal surfaces such as S_C and S_D , Fig. 14. We display phase diagrams for different values of the number of strips m . In the limit $m \rightarrow \infty$, the area of the region S_B in the phase diagram shrinks to zero. Using the definition Eq.1.2 of the mutual information, the regions S_A and S_D have $\hat{I}^{(S_A)} = \hat{I}^{(S_D)} = 0$, whereas $\hat{I}^{(S_C)}$ depends only on x (and not l). Therefore, in the limit $m \rightarrow \infty$, \hat{I} is independent of l in all of the parameter space, unlike the CFT case which we discuss below in Eq 2.7.

The “entanglement plateaux” transition is studied in the BTZ black hole geometry in global coordinates for 2-strips. The phase diagram corresponding to the 4 different bulk minimal surfaces is studied. When enlarging the radius of the black hole the phase diagram changes such that three of the regions shrink. For a very large black hole the parameter space is dominated by one of the phases.

Two additional examples of holographic backgrounds are discussed: A Dp-brane background dual to a non-CFT, and CFTs with temperature. We also discuss a “correspondence” between holographic Wilson loops at finite T and HEE for confining backgrounds, and vice versa. Using this, we argue that our results can be applied (qualitatively) to holographic Wilson loops.

We perform a more general perturbative analysis, and study how the HEE of m -strips changes when the CFT is perturbed. A “positive” perturbation of the CFT, tends to break the “joint” bulk surfaces into “disjoint” ones. Conversely, a “negative” perturbation will tend to join together bulk “disjoint” surfaces.

We study how the HEE of m -strips changes when we perturb the separations and lengths of the strips. One result, is that a configuration with equal “inner” separations is a maximum of the HEE with respect to perturbing these “inner” separations. A second result is that enlarging the length of an “inner” strip, reduces the HEE. This is opposite behavior compared to the effect of enlarging an “outer” or “disjoint” strip.

We will derive the following theorems which will be useful to us:

- For m strips of equal lengths and equal separations, the “connected”¹ minimal bulk surface is either S_A or S_B , see Fig. 14. This means that “disjoint” surfaces S_P (exemplified in Fig. 23), are not the absolute minimal surfaces for any values of x and l . This theorem greatly simplifies the problem of m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, since one has to consider only 2 bulk surfaces, instead of at least 2^{m-1} bulk surfaces.
- For m strips of equal lengths and equal separations, the only possible “disconnected” minimal bulk surfaces are S_C or S_D , see Fig. 14. This means that bulk surfaces such as S_Q and S_R of Fig. 24, are not the absolute minimal surfaces for all values of x and l .

¹“Disconnected” surfaces are bulk surfaces which have parts that terminate at the end of the bulk space. S_C and S_D are examples of “disconnected” surfaces. “Connected” surfaces are bulk surfaces which are not “disconnected”.

- Combining the two results above gives: For m strips of equal lengths and equal separations there are only 4 possible bulk minimal surfaces: S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D . See Fig. 14.

This paper is organized as follows. In section 2 we discuss the HEE for CFTs with m -strips. In section 3 we discuss the HEE for holographic confining backgrounds with m -strips. In section 4 we study the “entanglement plateaux” transition for 2-strips in the BTZ background. In section 5 we mention two additional examples of holographic backgrounds. In section 6 we perform a more general perturbative analysis of the m -strips system. In section 7 we exclude certain classes of bulk minimal surfaces. In section 8 we discuss our results and future directions. In Appendix A we discuss holographic Wilson loops and its relation to holographic entanglement entropy.

Figure 1: A strip configuration in 3 spacetime dimensions. The figure is in a constant time slice. l is the length of the strip and $\tilde{L} \gg l$. Also shown in the picture is the bulk surface which extends in the direction r and ends on the entanglement surface.

2. Phases of HEE in CFTs with multiple strips

In a holographic theory dual to a CFT, the Ryu-Takayanagi formula for a single strip region (Fig. 1) gives [8, 9, 32]:

$$S_1(l) = \frac{1}{4G_N^{d+1}} \left[\frac{2R^{d-1}}{d-2} \left(\frac{\tilde{L}}{\epsilon} \right)^{d-2} - \frac{2^{d-1} \pi^{\frac{d-1}{2}} R^{d-1}}{d-2} \left(\frac{\Gamma(\frac{d}{2d-2})}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2d-2})} \right)^{d-1} \left(\frac{\tilde{L}}{l} \right)^{d-2} \right] \quad (2.1)$$

where d is the number of spacetime dimensions, ϵ is the UV cutoff, R is the AdS radius, l is the length of the strip, and $\tilde{L} \gg l$. We use the notation S_1 to indicate the entanglement entropy of one strip. The first term is the “Area law” and the second term is a finite term.

For our purposes the divergent term will not play a role (we will always ask questions about differences of entanglement entropies), and neither will the factor multiplying the finite term (which will always be just an overall factor which we set to be 1). With this in mind, we simply write the finite term (or the

Figure 2: Illustration of the two minimal surfaces S_A and S_B for 2 strips in a CFT. There is a transition between the two surfaces when $x/l = f(d)$, where $f(d)$ depends only on d .

log term in $2d$) as:

$$S_1(l) = -\frac{1}{l^{d-2}} \quad d > 2 \quad (2.2)$$

$$S_1(l) = \frac{c}{3} \log(l/\epsilon) \quad d = 2 \quad (2.3)$$

Notice that for a CFT the finite term has a closed analytic form (this is not true in general).

2.1 CFT with two strips of equal length l

Now consider two strips of equal length l and separated by a distance x . As shown in Fig. 2, we have two competing minimal surfaces [12] S_A and S_B (which are “joint” and “disjoint” configurations). S_B and S_A indicate the areas of these “joint” and “disjoint” surfaces respectively.

Using the translational symmetry of the 2 strip configuration, we can calculate S_A and S_B in terms of the 1-strip result S_1 (this is obvious from Fig. 2), the finite terms are:

$$S_A(x, l) = 2S_1(l) = -\frac{2}{l^{d-2}} \quad (2.4)$$

$$S_B(x, l) = S_1(2l + x) + S_1(x) = -\frac{1}{(2l + x)^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{x^{d-2}} \quad (2.5)$$

When $S_A = S_B$ there will be a transition between the two surfaces. This happens when

$$\frac{1}{(2 + y)^{d-2}} + \frac{1}{y^{d-2}} = 2 \quad (2.6)$$

where $y \equiv x/l$. The solution to this equation is $y_c = f(d)$, where $f(d)$ depends only on d . The phase diagram in the $x - l$ plane is shown in Fig. 3. It consists of the straight transition line $x = f(d) \cdot l$ which separates the 2 phases. This is, of course, a consequence of the fact that there is no scale in a CFT, therefore x/l can only depend on constants. From Eq. 1.1, the mutual information is zero for S_A and non-zero for S_B ²:

$$\begin{aligned} I_A(x, l) &= 0 \\ I_B(x, l) &= -\frac{2}{l^{d-2}} + \frac{1}{(2l + x)^{d-2}} + \frac{1}{x^{d-2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.7)$$

²The divergent parts will always drop from the mutual information so we can simply use the finite terms

Figure 3: The phase diagram for two strips in a $d = 4$ CFT (dual to AdS_5). The corresponding minimal surfaces S_A and S_B are illustrated in Fig. 2. The transition line is the straight line $x/l = f(d)$.

Figure 4: Illustrating the surfaces S_A and S_B which are defined for arbitrary m . S_B is defined to be the completely “joint” surface, and S_A is the surface for which all strips are “disjoint”. The plot illustrates S_A and S_B for the 4 strip case.

2.2 CFT with m strips

We now consider the generalization to m strips, see also [13]. For 2 strips we had 2 bulk minimal surfaces S_A and S_B , Fig. 2. For arbitrary m , we define S_B to be the completely “joint” surface, and S_A is the surface for which all strips are “disjoint”. This is illustrated in Fig. 4 for the case $m = 4$. It is easy to write down the expression for S_A and S_B in terms of the 1-strip result S_1 :

$$S_A(l_i, x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^m S_1(l_i) \quad (2.8)$$

$$S_B(l_i, x_i) = \sum_{i=1}^{m-1} S_1(x_i) + S_1\left(\sum_{i=1}^{m-1} x_i + \sum_{i=1}^m l_i\right) \quad (2.9)$$

These equations will apply to arbitrary theories (with their corresponding finite term S_1), for arbitrary strip lengths l_i , and separations x_i .

Let us focus on the case of equal length strips and equal separations between them: $l_i = l$, and $x_i = x$. In section 7 it is shown that S_A and S_B are the only bulk minimal surfaces for any x , l , d , and m .

Now consider a CFT with: $S_1(l) = -\frac{1}{l^{d-2}}$ (see Eq. 2.2). For equal lengths and equal separations,

Figure 5: The phase diagram for a CFT and m -strips. The straight lines are the transition lines. **Left:** $d = 3$ and changing $m = 2, 3, 10, 1000$. In the large m limit the transition line has a slope of 1. **Right:** $m = 2$ and changing $d = 3, 4, 5, 10, 1000$. In the large d limit the transition line has a slope of 1.

Eqs. 2.8 - 2.9 become:

$$S_A(x, l) = mS_1(l) = -\frac{m}{l^{d-2}} \quad (2.10)$$

$$S_B(x, l) = (m-1)S_1(x) + S_1((m-1)x + ml) = -\frac{m-1}{x^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{(ml + (m-1)x)^{d-2}} \quad (2.11)$$

When $S_A = S_B$ there will be a transition between the two surfaces (See Eq. 2.6 for the $m = 2$ case). This happens when:

$$\frac{1}{(m + (m-1)y)^{d-2}} + \frac{m-1}{y^{d-2}} = m \quad (2.12)$$

where $y \equiv x/l$. The solution to this equation is $y_c = f_1(d, m)$, where $f_1(d, m)$ is a function of d and m . The phase diagram in the $x-l$ plane consists of a straight transition line $x = f_1(d, m) \cdot l$. For 3 and 4 dimensions we can solve this equation analytically:

$$y_c = \frac{\sqrt{1+m^2}-1}{m} \quad d=3 \quad (2.13)$$

$$y_c = \frac{\sqrt{m^2-m+1}-1}{m-1} \quad d=4 \quad (2.14)$$

Fig. 5 shows the phase diagram for different values of m and d . If we make m or d larger, then the slope of the transition line will become larger. In the limit $m \rightarrow \infty$ or $d \rightarrow \infty$, the slope of the transition line approaches 1. Therefore reducing d or m (with constant l and x) causes disentanglement.

2.3 CFT with 2 strips of unequal length

Now let's consider the case of 2 strips with different lengths l_1 and l_2 , and a separation x (so now there is an additional scale). Again we have just two bulk surfaces S_A and S_B as shown in Fig. 6. The areas

Figure 6: Illustration of the two bulk surfaces S_A and S_B for 2 strips of unequal lengths l_1 and l_2 .

Figure 7: The phase diagram for 2 strips with unequal length. The curves are the transition lines. The curves from top to bottom correspond to dimensions $d = 5, 4$ and 3 . The corresponding bulk surfaces are illustrated in Fig 6.

of the bulk surfaces are (see Eqs. 2.8-2.9):

$$S_A(x, l) = S_1(l_1) + S_1(l_2) = -\frac{1}{l_1^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{l_2^{d-2}} \quad (2.15)$$

$$S_B(x, l) = S_1(x) + S_1(x + l_1 + l_2) = -\frac{1}{x^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{(x + l_1 + l_2)^{d-2}} \quad (2.16)$$

The phase diagram is shown in Fig 7. The three transition lines correspond to different values of d . Note that when $l_1/l_2 \rightarrow \infty$ the phase transition will occur at $x = l_2$ (where l_2 is the length of the smaller strip). The transition of eq. 2.12 (two strips of equal length) corresponds to the point in the plot where $l_1/l_2 = 1$.

2.4 CFT with 3 equal length strips and unequal separations

Consider 3 strips of equal length l , but with unequal arbitrary separations between them x_1 and x_2 , see also [18, 19, 13, 20]. We now have 2 additional bulk minimal surfaces (denoted S_E and S_F) in which one of the strips is “disjoint” from the other two, see Fig 8. The areas of the 4 bulk surfaces are:

$$\begin{aligned} S_A(x_1, x_2, l) &= 3S_1(l) = -\frac{3}{l^{d-2}} \\ S_B(x_1, x_2, l) &= S_1(x_1) + S_1(x_2) + S_1(x_1 + x_2 + 3l) = -\frac{1}{x_1^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{x_2^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{(x_1 + x_2 + 3l)^{d-2}} \\ S_E(x_1, x_2, l) &= S_1(l) + S_1(x_1 + 2l) = -\frac{1}{l^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{x_1^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{(x_1 + 2l)^{d-2}} \\ S_F(x_1, x_2, l) &= S_1(l) + S_1(x_2 + 2l) = -\frac{1}{l^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{x_2^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{(x_2 + 2l)^{d-2}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.17)$$

Figure 8: Bulk surfaces for 3 strips of equal lengths l and unequal separations x_1 and x_2 . S_E and S_F can only be minimal when $x_1 \neq x_2$, as proved in section 7.

Figure 9: 3 strips of equal lengths l and unequal separations x_1 and x_2 in $d = 4$. The regions correspond to the bulk surfaces of Fig 8. Notice that the plot is symmetrical as it should be.

The phase diagram with its 4 phases is shown in Fig 9. To explain the diagram we can start by looking at two small separation lengths (x_1 and x_2) which is the region near the origin of the diagram. Obviously the minimal surface is the “joint” one S_B . Moving to the right (enlarging x_1), one of the strips will disconnect and there will be a transition to S_F . Then moving up in the diagram there will be a transition to S_A . There is also a direct transition between S_A and S_B (as for the equal strip case). Note that the transition line between S_F and S_A is parallel to the x -axis, this is because once the transition to S_F occurred the transition to S_A does not depend on x_1 . The phase diagram is symmetric under $x_1 \leftrightarrow x_2$ as expected.

It is not hard to generalize this (but harder to draw) for m strips of equal length and unequal separation. For separations very small compared to l : $x_1 \dots x_{m-1} \ll l$, S_B will be the absolute minimum. For $x_1 \dots x_{m-2} \ll l$ and $x_{m-1} \gg l$, one strip will be separated from the rest, and so on.

3. Phases of HEE in confining backgrounds with multiple strips

So far we have been dealing with bulk theories which are dual to CFTs. We will now explore backgrounds dual to confining theories [33]. We first review the 1-strip case, and then we move along to m strips.

3.1 Confining background and 1 strip

In this section we review the 1-strip case, and follow [28]. For more details see Appendix A.1 and [28, 29, 34, 32, 35, 36].

Consider a bulk metric with the following general form:

$$ds^2 = \alpha_x(U) [\beta(U) dU^2 + dx^\mu dx_\mu] + \alpha_t(U) dt^2 + g^{ij} dy_i dy_j \quad (3.1)$$

Where $\alpha_x(U)$, $\alpha_t(U)$ and $\beta(U)$ are functions of the holographic direction U , x_μ are the boundary directions ($\mu = 1 \dots d$) and y_i are internal directions ($i, j = d + 2, \dots, 10$).

The entanglement entropy is obtained by minimizing the area of the co-dimension 2 bulk surface:

$$S = \frac{1}{4G_N} \int d^{d-1}x e^{-2\phi} \sqrt{\det g_{\mu\nu}^{(ind.)}} \quad . \quad (3.2)$$

Where ϕ is the dilaton, and $g_{\mu\nu}^{(ind.)}$ is the induced metric in the string frame.

Considering a strip of length l , we plug the metric Eq. 3.1 into Eq. 3.2 and get:

$$S = \frac{\tilde{L}^{d-2}}{4G_N} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} dx \sqrt{H(U)} \sqrt{1 + \beta(\partial_x U)^2} \quad . \quad (3.3)$$

where we defined:

$$H(U) \equiv e^{-4\phi} V_{int}^2 \alpha_x^{d-1}(U) \quad . \quad (3.4)$$

Confining backgrounds are characterized by a value $U = U_0$ at which the bulk space ends. In the cases that we consider, there will be a circle that shrinks to zero at U_0 . There will be 2 competing bulk minimal surfaces, denoted as the “connected” and “disconnected” surfaces, see Fig. 10. The HEE will correspond to the area of the absolute minimal surface. The “disconnected” surface is the surface that goes straight down to the tip of the cigar at U_0 . We can obtain the equations of motion from Eq. 3.3, and then plug them back into Eq. 3.3. We get the area of the “connected” and “disconnected” surfaces:

$$S^{(conn)} = \frac{\tilde{L}^{d-2}}{2G_N} \int_{U^*}^{U_\infty} \frac{dU \sqrt{\beta(U)H(U)}}{\sqrt{H(U) - H(U^*)}} \quad (3.5)$$

$$S^{(disconn)} = \frac{\tilde{L}^{d-2}}{2G_N} \int_{U_0}^{U_\infty} dU \sqrt{\beta(U)H(U)} \quad (3.6)$$

$$l(U^*) = 2\sqrt{H(U^*)} \int_{U^*}^{\infty} \frac{dU \sqrt{\beta(U)}}{\sqrt{H(U) - H(U^*)}} \quad (3.7)$$

$U = U^*$ is where the surface ends, and U_0 is the minimal point where the contractible cycle shrinks. Importantly, the area of the disconnected surface is independent of l , which enables us to set this constant to 0 (we care only about the differences between the “connected” and “disconnected” surfaces).

To illustrate the phase transition, consider the background of $AdS_5 \times S^5$ (D3-branes) compactified on a circle. The metric is:

$$ds_{10}^2 = \left(\frac{U}{R}\right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{R}{U}\right)^4 \frac{dU^2}{f(U)} + dx^\mu dx_\mu \right] + R^2 d\Omega_5^2 + \left(\frac{U}{R}\right)^2 f(U) (dx^3)^2 \quad (3.8)$$

Where $f(U) = 1 - \left(\frac{U_0}{U}\right)^4$, $R^4 = 4\pi\lambda$, $U_0^2 = \frac{\pi\lambda}{R_3^2}$, and $\phi = \text{constant}$. This metric is in the form of Eq. 3.1, with:

$$\alpha_x = \alpha_t = \left(\frac{U}{R}\right)^2, \quad \beta = \left(\frac{R}{U}\right)^4 \frac{1}{f(U)}, \quad V_{int} = 2\pi^4 R_3 R^4 U \sqrt{f(U)}, \quad H(U) = (2\pi^4 R_3)^2 R^4 U^6 f(U)$$

Figure 10: Illustration of the two minimal surfaces in a confining theory for 1 strip. A phase transition between a “connected” and “disconnected” bulk surface. The transition occurs at $l = l_{crit}$.

Figure 11: Showing $S(l)$ for 1 strip in a confining background: AdS_5 compactified on a circle. The blue curve is $S^{(conn)}$ and the red curve is $S^{(disconn)}$. The phase transition occurs at $l = l_{crit} \approx 0.61$. An illustration of the bulk surfaces is given in Fig 10

We can now plug these functions into Eqs. 3.5-3.7. The result is shown in Fig. 11 in which we plot $S(l)$ for this background. Recall the prescription that the HEE corresponds to the absolute minimum solution. There are two “connected” branches (the blue curves), but the top one is never the minimum solution and therefore not physical. The red curve is the constant area of the “disconnected” surface. There is a transition between the “connected” and “disconnected” solutions at the value $l = l_{crit} \approx 0.61$. The value of l_{crit} depends on the metric of the confining background, and is proportional to the confinement scale. This transition of the HEE was conjectured to be a consequence of the Hagedorn transition of the dual QFT. [28, 29]

3.2 Confining background with 2 strips of equal length l

We will now consider a confining background and 2 strips of equal length l and having a distance x between them. We expect an interplay between the Hagedorn transition mentioned above, and the “geometric” transitions of section 2. There will be several extremal surfaces, and as usual one has to choose the absolute minimum amongst them for each value of x and l . It can be seen in Fig 12 that there are 4 different possible minimal surfaces. S_C and S_D are bulk surfaces³ which contain “disconnected” pieces as shown Fig 12.

The area of these 4 minimal surfaces can easily be written down:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S_A(x, l) &= 2S_1(l) & S_C(x, l) &= S_1(x) + S_{dis} \\
 S_B(x, l) &= S_1(x) + S_1(x + 2l) & S_D(x, l) &= 2S_{dis}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{3.9}$$

Where $S_1(l)$ is the area of the “connected” surface for 1 strip in the confining background obtained from Eq. 3.5, and S_{dis} is area of the “disconnected” surface obtained from Eq. 3.6.

We did the explicit numerical calculation of these functions for the AdS_5 (D3 branes) on a circle background, and we show the phase diagram in Fig. 13. One can intuitively understand the different

³In CFTs these surfaces are never the absolute minimal surfaces.

Figure 12: Illustration of the 4 different minimal surfaces for 2 strips of equal lengths l and equal separation x in a confining background. **Top left:** S_B : Minimal surface for small x and small l . **Top right:** S_A : Minimal surface for large x and small l . **Bottom left:** S_C : Minimal surface for small x and large l . **Bottom right:** S_D : Minimal surface for large x and large l .

Figure 13: The phase diagram for the background of AdS_5 on a circle, and 2 strips of equal lengths l and equal separation x . The different phases correspond to the bulk surfaces of Fig 12.

regions in the plot as follows. The region near the origin (where all lengths are small $x, l \ll l_{crit}$) is the CFT-like region which is similar to that of Fig. 3. It is also clear that in the region $x, l > l_{crit}$, S_D is the minimal surface. Additionally, for small x and $l < l_{crit}$, there is a large region in which S_C is the minimal surface.

Figure 14: Showing the bulk minimal surfaces for m strips of equal lengths l which have equal separations x . Showing 4 different types of minimal surfaces. The plot illustrates the bulk surfaces for $m = 3$.

Figure 15: Phase diagram for AdS_5 compactified on a circle. Comparing different number of strips m . We have $m = 2$ (red), $m = 3$ (blue), and $m = 10$ (green). Illustration of the bulk minimal surfaces is given in Fig 14.

3.3 Confining background and m strips

Consider the case of m equal length strips with equal spacings between them. In the previous section we saw that for $m = 2$ there are 4 bulk minimal surfaces, Fig. 12. For $m > 2$, the analogues of these 4 surfaces are shown in Fig. 14 for the $m = 3$ example. In section 7 it is proved that for m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D are the only bulk minimal surfaces. Therefore, the problem of m equally spaced identical strips in a confining background is not more complicated than the 2-strips case.

The area of these 4 minimal surfaces is, Fig. 14:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_A(x, l) &= mS_1(l) \\
S_C(x, l) &= (m-1)S_1(x) + S_{dis} \\
S_B(x, l) &= (m-1)S_1(x) + S_1((m-1)x + ml) \\
S_D(x, l) &= mS_{dis}
\end{aligned}
\tag{3.10}$$

We show in Fig. 15 the phase diagrams for AdS_5 compactified on a circle and various values of m . There is a new feature in this phase diagram. Notice that as we add more strips, the region S_B gets smaller and eventually will disappear for $m \rightarrow \infty$. Relating this to the mutual information, we see that we are left with two “disjoint” configurations S_A and S_D with zero mutual information, and one “joint” configuration S_C with mutual information that depends only on x , and not on l . This is very different from the CFT case where the mutual information is either 0 or depends both on x and l (see Eq. 2.7).

The shrinking of the region S_B can easily be seen from Eq. 3.10: The transition between S_B and S_C occurs when $(m-1)x + ml > l_{crit}$. For $m \rightarrow \infty$ the transition occurs at $x, l \rightarrow 0$. Therefore the region S_B shrinks to zero.

4. “Entanglement plateau-like” transitions and multiple strips

Figure 16: The “entanglement plateau” transition. An interval of length θ on the boundary of the global BTZ black hole. The interval is the blue arc, and the minimal surface is the red curve. When $\theta > \theta_c$, the minimal surface contains 2 parts, (one of them wraps the horizon).

Figure 17: 2 equal strips in global BTZ black hole geometry. Illustrating the 4 minimal surfaces S_A , S_B , S_G , S_H . θ is the angle of the strips, and α is the angle separating them. Note that because there are two strips, θ is smaller than π .

Figure 18: The phase diagram in the $\theta - \alpha$ plane, for the global BTZ black hole and 2 strips. In this plot we used the minimal value $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = \frac{1}{2}$. The four regions correspond to the bulk surfaces illustrated in Fig. 17. The gray region is not part of the phase diagram since it is not in the domain $2\theta + \alpha \leq 2\pi$.

Figure 19: Same as in Fig. 18, but for different sizes of the black hole. It can be seen that enlarging the black hole, the regions S_G , S_H and S_B shrink to zero size. **Left:** $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = 2$. **Right:** $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = 8$.

Consider the geometry of a global AdS black hole. For simplicity we will discuss the BTZ black hole in global coordinates:

$$ds^2 = \frac{r^2 - r_+^2}{R_0^2} dt^2 + \frac{L_{AdS}^2 dr^2}{r^2 - r_+^2} + r^2 d\phi^2 \quad (4.1)$$

where L_{AdS} is the AdS radius and R_0 is the radius of the boundary circle. The inverse temperature is $\beta = 2\pi L_{AdS} R_0 / r_+$, and the central charge is $c = 12\pi L_{AdS} / l_P$. The dual theory is a 2d CFT with temperature compactified on a circle. There is a Hawking-Page transition: for $T < 1/(2\pi R_0)$ the dominant solution

is thermal AdS_3 , and for $T > 1/(2\pi R_0)$ the dominant solution is the BTZ black hole Eq. 4.1.

Consider an interval region of angle θ on the boundary circle, Fig. 16. At a critical value $\theta = \theta_c$ the HEE exhibits a phase transition between two bulk surfaces with different topologies [30, 31, 37, 38]. For $\theta > \theta_c$ the minimal surface contains 2 “disjoint” pieces, one of which wraps the horizon of the black hole. The areas of the two minimal surfaces are:

$$S_1(\theta) = \frac{c}{3} \log \left[\frac{\beta}{\pi\epsilon} \sinh \left(\frac{\pi R_0 \theta}{\beta} \right) \right] \quad , \quad \text{for } \theta < \theta_c$$

$$\tilde{S}_1(\theta) = S_1(2\pi - \theta) + S_{\text{Horizon}} = \frac{c}{3} \log \left[\frac{\beta}{\pi\epsilon} \sinh \left(\frac{\pi R_0 (2\pi - \theta)}{\beta} \right) \right] + \frac{c}{3} \frac{2\pi^2 R_0}{\beta} \quad , \quad \text{for } \theta > \theta_c \quad (4.2)$$

This transition between $S_1(\theta)$ and $\tilde{S}_1(\theta)$ was called “Entanglement plateau” in [30], and it has some similarity to the transition occurring in confining backgrounds, section 3. We note that unlike the case of higher dimensional black holes, the two configurations $S_1(\theta)$ and $\tilde{S}_1(\theta)$ are solutions to the equations of motion for all θ , see [30].

Now consider 2 strips on the boundary circle, of equal opening angles θ and a separation α . There will be 4 competing bulk surfaces as illustrated in Fig 17. The areas of these surfaces are:

$$S_A(\theta, \alpha) = 2S_1(\theta)$$

$$S_B(\theta, \alpha) = S_1(\alpha) + S_1(2\theta + \alpha)$$

$$S_C(\theta, \alpha) = S_1(\alpha) + S_1(2\pi - \alpha - 2\theta) + S_{\text{Horizon}}$$

$$S_H(\theta, \alpha) = S_1(2\pi - \alpha) + S_1(2\pi - \alpha - 2\theta) \quad (4.3)$$

The phase diagram in the $\alpha - \theta$ plane is shown in Fig. 18, for the minimal value $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = \frac{1}{2}$. In Fig. 19 we show the same phase diagram for the different values $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = 2, 8$. We see that the effect of enlarging $\frac{R_0}{\beta}$ (i.e enlarging the black hole radius) is the shrinking of the regions S_C , S_H , and S_B . Already for $\frac{\pi R_0}{\beta} = 2$, the area of these regions is very small compared to S_A .

5. Phases of HEE in other examples

In this section we shortly discuss phases in additional interesting backgrounds.

5.1 Dp-brane background with two strips of equal length l

The first case we consider is the Dp-brane background [39], which is qualitatively similar to the CFT case. One has to distinguish between the two classes of $p < 5$ and $p \geq 5$. Here we discuss just the former class, for the latter see [40] [34].

For a single strip in a Dp-brane background [35, 36, 41, 42], the finite term is:

$$S_1(l) = -\frac{1}{l^{\frac{4}{5-p}}} \quad (5.1)$$

Like the CFT case Eq. 2.2, this is a power law but the exponent now is non-integer.

Now consider m -strips. The analysis is similar to the CFT case, and again we have two competing minimal surfaces S_A and S_B as shown in Fig. 2 for the case $m = 2$. When $S_A = S_B$ there will be a transition between the two surfaces. This happens when:

$$\frac{1}{(m + (m - 1)y)^{\frac{4}{5-p}}} + \frac{m - 1}{y^{\frac{4}{5-p}}} = m \quad (5.2)$$

The solution to this equation is $y \equiv x/l = \tilde{f}(p, m)$, where $\tilde{f}(p, m)$ is a function of the p and m only. The phase diagram in the $x - l$ plane will consist of the straight line $x = \tilde{f}(p, m) \cdot l$, qualitatively similar to the CFT case Fig. 3.

5.2 CFT at finite T with m strips

Consider adding temperature to a CFT, [15, 17, 13]. The mutual information for these theories was computed in [15], where phase diagrams were also determined, hence we will be very concise here. At a given temperature, the phase diagram still consists of a straight line as in Fig. 3. Enlarging the temperature reduces the slope of the line. For a very large temperature, the slope of the line goes to zero. To see this, note that for large temperature the finite part of the 1-strip EE is given by the thermal entropy[8]:

$$S_1(l) \propto T^{d-1}l \quad \text{for} \quad Tl \gg 1 \quad (5.3)$$

Therefore for m strips we have:

$$\begin{aligned} S_A(x, l) &\propto mT^{d-1}l \\ S_B(x, l) &\propto (m - 1)T^{d-1}x + T^{d-1}(ml + (m - 1)x) \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

Now equating $S_A = S_B$, we get that the transition line is at $x = 0$. Thus for a very large temperature, the slope of the transition line goes to zero. Therefore for effectively all values of x and l , S_A is the dominant configuration, and there are no correlations between the strips.

5.3 Wilson loops with m strips

In Appendix A.2, we discuss the similarity between holographic entanglement entropy and holographic Wilson loops in. More precisely, the quark-antiquark potential $V(l)$ at finite temperature has qualitatively similar l dependence as $S_1(l)$ in a confining background.

We thus expect that $V(l)$ for a finite T background with m strips will have a phase diagram qualitatively similar to that of the EE in a confining background, namely Fig. 13. So once more we expect 4 different minimal surfaces.

6. A general perturbative analysis for m strips

6.1 Perturbing the CFT

In this section we start with an m -strip configuration in a CFT, and ask what happens when we perturb the CFT. We closely follow [31], see also [43]. For CFTs with a temperature turned on see [15, 17, 13].

Consider a bulk metric in Fefferman-Graham coordinates:

$$ds^2 = \frac{R_{AdS}^2}{z^2} \left(dz^2 + (\eta_{\mu\nu} + \delta g_{\mu\nu}) dx^\mu dx^\nu \right) \quad (6.1)$$

where R_{AdS} is the radius of AdS , and the perturbation of the metric is:

$$\delta g_{\mu\nu} = \frac{2l_P^{d-1}}{dR_{AdS}^{d-1}} z^d \sum_{n=0} z^{2n} T_{\mu\nu}^{(n)} \quad (6.2)$$

For simplicity assume a uniform stress tensor, i.e $T_{\mu\nu}^{(n)} = 0$ for $n \geq 1$.

We can calculate the resulting change (at linear order in the perturbation) in the HEE for 1-strip of length l :

$$\delta S_1(l) = \frac{1}{2} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{g_0} g_0^{ab} \delta g_{ab} \propto \left(\frac{d+1}{d-1} T_{00} - T_{xx} \right) l^2 \equiv \varepsilon l^2 \quad (6.3)$$

where g_0^{ab} is the zeroth order induced metric on the bulk surface, and δg_{ab} is its perturbation. It is important for the following analysis that $\delta S_1(l)$ is quadratic in l and can be positive or negative depending on the sign of ε .

Let us now consider m equal length strips equally separated. The change in S_A and S_B is:

$$\begin{aligned} \delta S_A(x, l) &= m \delta S_1(l) \propto m \varepsilon l^2 \\ \delta S_B(x, l) &= (m-1) \delta S_1(x) + \delta S_1((m-1)x + ml) \propto (m-1) \varepsilon x^2 + \varepsilon [(m-1)x + ml]^2 \end{aligned} \quad (6.4)$$

The corresponding change in the mutual information is either zero or:

$$\delta I = \delta S_A - \delta S_B = -\varepsilon m(m-1)(x+l)^2 \quad (6.5)$$

So we see that for a positive/negative ε the change in mutual information δI is always negative/positive.

We also note that for large m :

$$\frac{\delta S_B}{\delta S_A} \sim m \left(1 + \frac{x}{l} \right)^2 \gg 1 \quad (6.6)$$

So depending on whether ε is positive/negative, δS_B gets a large positive/negative contribution, much larger (in absolute value) than δS_A .

Imagine that we start in a CFT with many strips and the bulk minimal surface is S_B . Now we perturb the CFT with a “positive perturbation” $\varepsilon > 0$ (such as for a small strip in a background with temperature). Then δS_B gets a large positive contribution $\delta S_B \sim \varepsilon m^2 (x+l)^2$, which can render S_A the new minimal bulk surface. Thus a “positive perturbation” $\varepsilon > 0$ tends to break the “joint” surfaces such as S_B into “disjoint” surfaces such as S_A . This is what happened before in section 5.2 in a background with finite temperature, where the parameter space for S_B became smaller and smaller as we increased the temperature.

Figure 20: A generic bulk surface illustrating our conventions. A strip such as l_5 will be called a “disjoint” strip. A strip such as l_1 will be called an “outer” strip. A strip such as l_2 will be called an “inner” strip. L is the total length of the “joint” part of the surface.

On the other hand, if the perturbation is negative $\varepsilon < 0$, then δS_B gets a large negative contribution $\delta S_B \sim \varepsilon m^2(x+l)^2$. Such a negative perturbation tends to join together the “disjoint” surfaces such as S_A .

We can also consider other types of perturbations other than the stress energy tensor. We will now mention the cases of a scalar operator and a vector operator.

Perturbing with a scalar operator (a scalar field in the bulk), we get (see [31]):

$$\delta S_1 \propto \mathcal{O}^2(AT_{00} - BT_{xx})l^{2\Delta-d+2} \equiv \varepsilon l^{2\Delta-d+2} \quad (6.7)$$

Above the unitarity bound $\Delta > d/2 - 1$, the exponent of l is positive as in Eq. 6.3.

On the other hand, perturbing with a vector operator we get:

$$\delta S_1 \propto (CJ_0^2 + DJ_x^2 + EJ^2)l^d \equiv \varepsilon l^d \quad (6.8)$$

where A , B , C , D , and E are constants. The exponent of l is again positive.

6.2 Perturbing the separations and lengths of the strips

In the previous section we saw the effect of perturbing the CFT on the HEE of m strips. In this section we study the effect of slightly changing the length or separation of one of the strips. We assume that these perturbations are small enough as to not cause a phase transition to a different bulk surface.

Consider an arbitrary theory and a generic bulk surface⁴, as illustrated in Fig. 20. The area S of this surface is:

$$S(x_j, l_j) = S_1(x_1) + S_1(x_2) + S_1(x_3) + S_1(L) + S_1(l_5) \quad (6.9)$$

We can take derivatives to see how S changes:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial x_4} = 0 \quad , \quad \frac{\partial S}{\partial l_5} = \frac{\partial S_1(l_5)}{\partial l_5} \quad , \quad \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_1} = \frac{\partial S_1(x_1)}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial S_1(L)}{\partial L} \quad (6.10)$$

⁴We assume here that the bulk surface does not have “disconnected” parts. However, one can easily redo the analysis of this section for bulk surfaces containing “disconnected” parts.

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial l_1} = \frac{\partial S_1(L)}{\partial L} \quad , \quad \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x_1 \partial l_1} = \frac{\partial^2 S_1(L)}{\partial L^2} \quad , \quad \frac{\partial^2 S}{\partial x_1 \partial x_2} = \frac{\partial^2 S_1(L)}{\partial L^2} \quad (6.11)$$

6.2.1 Changing the separations between the strips

Now lets see the effect of changing the separations between strips. In the following, we will allow one of the strips to slightly move to the left or to the right (without changing its length).

- **A “disjoint” strip:**

Slightly moving a “disjoint” strip (see Fig. 20) a distance Δx_4 , we get from Eq. 6.10:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_4} \Delta x_4 = 0 \quad (6.12)$$

- **An “outer” strip:**

Slightly moving an “outer” strip (see Fig. 20) a distance Δx_1 , we get from Eq. 6.10:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\partial S}{\partial x_1} \Delta x_1 = \left(\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial L} \right) \Delta x_1 \quad (6.13)$$

If S_1 is monotonically growing then $\left(\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_1} + \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial L} \right) > 0$, hence the sign of ΔS is the same as that of Δx_1 . Therefore enlarging x_1 , makes S larger.

- **An “inner” strip:**

Slightly moving an “inner” strip (see Fig. 20) a distance Δx_1 , we get (at linear order):

$$\Delta S^{(1)} = \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_1} \Delta x_1 + \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_2} \Delta x_2 = \left(\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_1} - \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial x_2} \right) \Delta x_1 \quad (6.14)$$

where we used $\Delta x_1 = -\Delta x_2$ (we keep the total length L fixed).

When $x_1 = x_2$, we have $\Delta S^{(1)} = 0$, and S has a maximum at this point. To see this, consider the 2nd order variation:

$$\Delta S^{(2)} = \left[\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 S_1}{\partial x_1^2} + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2 S_1}{\partial x_2^2} \right] (\Delta x_1)^2 \quad (6.15)$$

If S_1 is concave then $\frac{\partial^2 S_1}{\partial x_1^2}, \frac{\partial^2 S_1}{\partial x_2^2} < 0$, hence

$$\Delta S^{(2)} < 0 \quad (6.16)$$

Therefore, interestingly, S has a maximum when $x_1 = x_2$ with respect to slightly moving “inner” strips.

6.2.2 Changing the length of the strips

- **A “disjoint” strip:**

Slightly changing the length of a “disjoint” strip (see Fig. 20) an amount Δl_5 , we get from Eq. 6.10:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\partial S}{\partial l_5} \Delta l_5 = \frac{\partial S_1(l_5)}{\partial l_5} \Delta l_5 \quad (6.17)$$

If S_1 is monotonically growing $\frac{\partial S_1(l_5)}{\partial l_5} > 0$, and we enlarge the strip $\Delta l_5 > 0$, then $\Delta S > 0$.

- **An “outer” strip:**

Slightly changing the length of an “outer” strip (see Fig. 20) an amount Δl_1 , we get from Eq. 6.11:

$$\Delta S = \frac{\partial S}{\partial l_1} \Delta l_1 = \frac{\partial S_1}{\partial L} \Delta l_1 \quad (6.18)$$

If S_1 is monotonically growing $\frac{\partial S_1}{\partial L} > 0$, and we enlarge the strip $\Delta l_1 > 0$, then $\Delta S > 0$.

- **An “inner” strip:**

Slightly changing the length of an “inner” strip (see Fig. 20) an amount Δl_2 , we get from the fact that $\Delta l_2 = -\Delta x_2$ (we keep the total length L fixed):

$$\Delta S = \frac{\partial S}{\partial l_2} \Delta l_2 = -\frac{\partial S_1(x_2)}{\partial x_2} \Delta l_2 \quad (6.19)$$

If S_1 is monotonically growing $\frac{\partial S_1(x_2)}{\partial x_2} > 0$, and if we enlarge the strip $\Delta l_2 > 0$, then $\Delta S < 0$. Interestingly, this is opposite behavior compared to a “disjoint” strip or an “external” strip, see Eqs. 6.17 and 6.18.

7. Excluding classes of bulk minimal surfaces

In this section we will exclude certain classes of bulk minimal surfaces. For m -strips, consider the “connected” bulk surfaces⁵. There are $(2m-1)!!$ locally minimal surfaces obtained by all the different pairings of the $2m$ entangling surfaces of the strips. In the following proofs we refer to the plots of the bulk minimal surfaces, but the proofs only use the strong subadditivity property of the EE and do not use the fact that the entangling regions are strips. Therefore the proofs should work for m identical entangling regions equally separated on a line.

- The class of bulk surfaces (denoted S_X) which have intersections Fig. 21, are never the (absolute) minimal surfaces. Proving this is straightforward: For each such intersecting bulk surface it is simple to find a non-intersecting bulk surface with a smaller area. This result has been noted by several authors.

- Consider the class of bulk surfaces (denoted S_Y) which have parts that “engulf” other parts of the bulk surface. An example of such a surface for the case of 6 strips is shown in Fig. 22-Top. For m strips

⁵“Disconnected” surfaces are bulk surfaces which have parts that terminate at the end of the bulk space. S_C and S_D are examples of “disconnected” surfaces. “Connected” surfaces are bulk surfaces which are not “disconnected”.

Figure 21: The class of “intersecting” bulk minimal surfaces denoted by S_X . It is easy to see that these are never the absolute minimal surfaces.

Figure 22: Top: The class of “engulfed” bulk minimal surfaces denoted by S_Y where A_2 is the “engulfed” region. **Bottom:** Permuting the regions A_2 and A_3 . The bulk surface is denoted by $S_Y^{(2)}$. We prove that the “engulfed” bulk minimal surfaces S_Y are not the minimal surfaces.

with equal lengths l and equal separations x , such surfaces are never the absolute minimal bulk surfaces⁶.

Proof:

We will now show that surfaces of the class of S_Y (Fig. 22-Top) are not the minimal surfaces. We have:

$$S_Y = S_{A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3} = S_{A_1 \cup A_3} + S_{A_2} \tag{7.1}$$

Now consider permuting the regions A_2 and A_3 as in Fig.22-Bottom. It is clear that $S_Y = S_{A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3} = S_{A_1 \cup A_3 \cup A_2}^{(2)}$, where the superscript (2) denotes the system after the permutation. From the monotonicity of the EE we have $S_{A_1 \cup A_3} > S_{A_1 \cup A_3}^{(2)}$, and this inequality is not saturated. Therefore Eq. 7.1 gives:

$$S_Y = S_{A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3} = S_{A_1 \cup A_3} + S_{A_2} > S_{A_1 \cup A_3}^{(2)} + S_{A_2} \geq S_{A_1 \cup A_3 \cup A_2}^{(2)} = S_Y \tag{7.2}$$

⁶Note that after excluding the classes S_X and S_Y , there remain 2^{m-1} bulk minimal surfaces. Two of these remaining surfaces are S_A and S_B , and the rest are denoted S_P (an example of of such a bulk surface is shown in Fig. 23).

Figure 23: A class of “disjoint” minimal surfaces denoted by S_P . S_P is composed of two “disjoint” parts: one of the type S_B with k_1 strips, and the other of the type S_B with k_2 strips. The plot illustrates this for the case $k_1 = 2$ and $k_2 = 5$. The partition to different regions A_1 , A_2 and A_3 is also shown. A_3 is chosen such that it contains the same number of strips as A_1 .

where in the second inequality we used subadditivity. We have thus reached a contradiction in Eq. 7.2, and therefore S_Y cannot be the bulk minimal surface.

We conjecture (without a proof) that “engulfed” bulk surfaces are never the (absolute) minimal surfaces even for arbitrary strip lengths l_i and arbitrary separations x_i . It will be interesting to try and prove this conjecture or to find a counterexample.

- For m strips of equal lengths and equal separations, the “connected” minimal bulk surface is either S_A or S_B , see Fig. 14. In other words, the “disjoint” surfaces S_P (exemplified in Fig. 23), are not the absolute minimal surfaces for all values of x and l .

Proof:

Consider $m = k_1 + k_2$ equal length and equally separated strips. Consider also a “disjoint” bulk surface (with area S_P) which is composed of 2 groups of “joint” surfaces with k_1 and k_2 strips respectively as shown in Fig. 23. We label A_1 , A_2 and A_3 as in Fig. 23, such that A_3 contains k_1 strips, as does A_1 . We know from subadditivity that:

$$S_{A_2} + S_{A_3} - S_{A_2 \cup A_3} \geq 0 \tag{7.3}$$

Importantly, this inequality is not saturated by the surface S_P of Fig. 23 (since if it was saturated then A_2 and A_3 would be disjoint from each other). Since the number of strips in A_3 and A_1 is the same, and since the strips are of equal lengths and equal separations, we get:

$$\begin{aligned} S_{A_1} &= S_{A_3} \\ S_{A_2 \cup A_3} &= S_{A_2 \cup A_1} \end{aligned} \tag{7.4}$$

Plugging Eq. 7.4 into Eq. 7.3, and recalling that the inequality is not saturated, we get:

$$S_{A_2} + S_{A_1} - S_{A_2 \cup A_1} > 0 \tag{7.5}$$

For the bulk surface S_P in Fig. 23 we have:

$$S_{A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3} = S_{A_2 \cup A_3} + S_{A_1} \tag{7.6}$$

Figure 24: Two classes of “disjoint” surfaces with a mixture of “connected” and “disconnected” parts. The special case of $k_1 = 2$ and $k_2 = 3$ is shown. **Left:** A class of surfaces denoted by S_Q . These are comprised of two “disjoint” parts: an S_C part with k_1 strips, and an S_B part with k_2 strips. **Right:** A class of surfaces denoted by S_R . These are comprised of two “disjoint” parts: an S_C part with k_1 strips, and an S_C part with k_2 strips.

Strong subadditivity (SSA) [38, 44] and Eq. 7.6 give:

$$S_{A_1 \cup A_2 \cup A_3} - S_{A_1 \cup A_2} - S_{A_2 \cup A_3} + S_{A_2} = S_{A_2} + S_{A_1} - S_{A_2 \cup A_1} \leq 0 \quad (7.7)$$

We have reached a contradiction between Eqs. 7.5 and 7.7. Therefore we exclude the class S_P (consisting of 2 groups of surfaces) of bulk minimal surfaces.

Excluding bulk surfaces with 3 or more groups is now a simple task. Consider a “disjoint” bulk surface which is composed of 3 groups of “joint” surfaces with k_1 , k_2 and k_3 strips respectively. We can apply the 2-group proof to the two groups k_1 and k_2 . As a result we see that there exists a bulk surface with smaller area than the original one, proving what we wanted to show.

This theorem greatly simplifies the problem of m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, since one has to consider only 2 bulk minimal surfaces (instead of at least 2^{m-1} bulk surfaces).

The above proof also works for surfaces with “disconnected” parts. Therefore, for equal length strips with equal separations, the bulk minimal surfaces of the classes S_Q or S_R (Fig. 24) are excluded. This brings us to the following result:

- For m strips of equal lengths and equal separations the only possible bulk minimal surfaces are S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D . See Fig.14.

As mentioned above, the proof should work for m identical non-strip entangling regions equally separated on a line. Assuming that the topology of the bulk minimal surfaces for this system is similar to that of m strips, there will be 4 possible minimal surfaces \tilde{S}_A , \tilde{S}_B , \tilde{S}_C , \tilde{S}_D with topology similar to S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D .

Additionally, the proof is not limited to holographic entanglement entropy but in principle can be applied to Wilson loops (as long as the latter obey strong subadditivity).

8. Discussion

The main goal of this paper was to study HEE of m strips, and transitions between topologically distinct minimal bulk surfaces. We began by analyzing CFTs, and studied the resulting phase diagrams. For confining backgrounds, the m strip HEE is calculated by new types of “disconnected” bulk minimal surfaces such as S_C and S_D , and the resulting phase diagrams are rich.

Note that there exist other backgrounds (non-confining) for which the 1-strip HEE has a transition between a “connected” and a “disconnected” bulk minimal surface. An example is the D3-brane shell model [43, 45]. For such backgrounds with m strips, we expect phase diagrams similar to the confining case, Fig. 13.

The BTZ black hole in global coordinates exhibits the “entanglement plateau”-like transition in the case of 1 strip. For 2 strips there are 4 possible minimal surfaces. It would be interesting to study the m -strip case and also to generalize to higher dimensional black holes.

There is a “correspondence” between holographic Wilson loops at finite T and HEE for confining backgrounds, and vice versa. Using this, it was shown how our results can be applied (qualitatively) to holographic Wilson loops.

Section 6.1, contains a perturbative analysis for m strips. A “positive” perturbation of the CFT, tends to break the “joint” bulk surfaces into “disjoint” ones. Conversely, a “negative” perturbation will tend to join together bulk “disjoint” surfaces.

Section 6.2 contains a perturbative analysis for m strips where the QFT is not perturbed, but the length or separation of the strips are. One result, is that the configuration with equal “inner” separations is a maximum of the HEE with respect to perturbing these “inner” separations. A second result, is that enlarging the length of an “inner” strip, reduces the HEE. This is opposite behavior compared to the effect of enlarging an “outer” or “disjoint” strip.

Section 7 contains a few results which exclude certain classes of bulk minimal surfaces. In particular, for m strips of equal lengths and equal separations there are only 4 possible bulk minimal surfaces: S_A , S_B , S_C , and S_D . This theorem greatly simplifies the problem of m strips with equal lengths and equal separations, since one has to consider only 4 bulk surfaces. Interestingly, it seems that this result is valid also for non-strip regions.

There are several additional questions that follow the analysis performed in this paper.

- This paper considered strip regions because the translational symmetry effectively reduces the problem of m strips to that of 1 strip. It is reasonable to conjecture that for entangling regions which are not strips (for example spheres), the topology of the bulk minimal surfaces will be as for the strip case⁷, Fig. 14. Therefore it is also reasonable to conjecture that the phase diagram in the confining case will qualitatively have the form of Fig. 13. It might also be interesting to study phase diagrams for concentric spheres.
- The dimension of the phase space of most of the systems discussed in this paper is two since we have taken the simplified case of equal strip lengths and equal separation distances. In general for the case of m strips the phase space is of dimension $2m - 1$. Analyzing the structure of this multi-dimensional phase space should follow similar procedures as those used in the current simplified case. It is quite probable that determining the general phase space will shed additional light on the considered systems.

⁷For example [35] considers sphere entangling regions for confining backgrounds. They find that there is a “connected” and a “disconnected” surface, and a phase transition between the two at a critical value of the radius of the sphere. This is analogous to the strip case of section 3.

- The procedure of [5] is based on using conformal transformations. One interesting question is if one can generalize this procedure also for computations of the EE of non-conformal and in particular confining backgrounds.
- In section 7 it is conjectured that the class of “engulfed” bulk surfaces denoted S_Y are never the (absolute) minimal surfaces for arbitrary strip lengths and arbitrary separations. It will be interesting to try to prove this conjecture or to find a counterexample.

Acknowledgments

We thank Matthew Headrick, Carlos Hoyos, Uri Kol, David Kutasov, Michael Smolkin, Tadashi Takayanagi, Erik Tonni, and Shimon Yankielowicz for useful discussions. We also thank Avner Gicelter for help with the figures. This work is partially supported by the Israel Science Foundation (grant 1989/14), the US-Israel bi-national fund (BSF) grant 2012383 and the German Israel bi-national fund GIF grant number I-244-303.7-2013.

A. Holographic Wilson lines and HEE

A.1 Holographic Wilson lines in Confining backgrounds

In this section we shortly review holographic Wilson lines in confining backgrounds, see [46], [47]. An important property of confining theories is the area law behavior of the Wilson line. This is equivalent to a linear potential between the quark and anti-quark.

Consider a bulk metric with the following general form:

$$ds^2 = \alpha_x(U)[\beta(U)dU^2 + dx^\mu dx_\mu] + \alpha_t(U)dt^2 + g^{ij}dy_i dy_j \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Where $\alpha_x(U)$, $\alpha_t(U)$ and $\beta(U)$ are functions of the holographic coordinate U , x_μ are the boundary directions ($\mu = 1 \dots d$) and y_i are internal directions ($i = d + 2, \dots, 10$).

Following [46] and [47], the distance between the quark and anti-quark is:

$$l(U^*) = 2 \int_{U^*}^{\infty} \frac{dU \sqrt{\beta}}{\sqrt{\frac{F^2(U)}{F^2(U^*)} - 1}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Where U^* is the lowest point of the string, U_∞ is the UV cutoff, and we defined $F(U) \equiv \sqrt{\alpha_x(U)\alpha_t(U)}$.

The potential energy between the quark and anti-quark is:

$$V(U^*) = 2 \int_{U^*}^{U_\infty} \frac{dU \sqrt{\beta} F^2(U)}{\sqrt{F^2(U) - F^2(U^*)}} - 2m_q \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The first term in Eq. A.3 is the bare energy, and the second term is the mass of the quark and anti-quark, which is subtracted in order to renormalize the energy. The mass of the quarks is obtained from the energy of the two straight strings stretched from U_∞ to U_0 :

$$m_q = \int_{U_0}^{U_\infty} dU \sqrt{\beta} F(U) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where U_0 is where the space ends.

Linear confinement means that at large l we have:

$$V(l) = F(U_0) \cdot l + \mathcal{O}(1/l) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

[47] showed that a background exhibits linear confinement if one of the two conditions below are satisfied:

- The function $F(U)$ has a minimum.
 - The function $\sqrt{\beta}F(U)$ diverges.
- (A.6)

and also that the tension of the string is non-zero $F(\tilde{U}) \neq 0$, where \tilde{U} is the value at which F is a minimum or the value at which $\sqrt{\beta}F$ diverges.

[47] proved that the $l(U^*)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of U^* in confining backgrounds. This corresponds to $V(l)$ being a monotonically increasing function of l . Fig. 25 illustrates the properties of Wilson loops mentioned above.

Figure 25: Left: $l(U^*)$ is a monotonically decreasing function of U^* . Right: $V(l)$. Linear confinement can be seen at large l .

A confining background is thus defined to be a background for which the holographic rectangular Wilson loop admits such an area law behavior. The model of a $D4$ brane compactified on a circle [33] is a prototypical confining background. The non-critical version of this model was studied in [48].

A.2 A correspondence between HEE and holographic Wilson loops

The calculation of a holographic Wilson loop (HWL) is very similar to that of holographic entanglement entropy (HEE), as both are given by the area of a bulk minimal surface. Let us now obtain the map between the two for the case of a strip. We consider a metric as in Eq. A.1.

Considering a strip of length l , we saw in Eq. 3.3 that the HEE is obtained by minimizing the following function:

$$S = \frac{\tilde{L}^{d-2}}{4G_N} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} dx \sqrt{H(U)} \sqrt{1 + \beta(\partial_x U)^2} \quad . \quad (\text{A.7})$$

where we defined:

$$H(U) \equiv e^{-4\phi} V_{int}^2 \alpha_x^{d-1}(U) \quad . \quad (\text{A.8})$$

On the other hand, for holographic Wilson loops we need to minimize the Nambu-Goto action:

$$S^{(NG)} = \frac{1}{2\pi\alpha'} \int d\sigma d\tau = \frac{T}{2\pi\alpha'} \int_{-l/2}^{l/2} dx \sqrt{\alpha_x \alpha_t} \sqrt{1 + \beta(\partial_x U)^2}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

Where we chose $\tau = t$ and $\sigma = x$, and $T = \int d\tau$.

So we see that Eq. A.7 and Eq. A.9 are equal when:

$$H(U) \longrightarrow \alpha_x \alpha_t \quad (\text{A.10})$$

So at least formally, we can map a holographic Wilson loop in one geometry to holographic EE in another geometry. This can be used in order to find non-trivial properties of entanglement entropy or Wilson loops on the field theory side (see also [49]).

A.3 An example

An example of this “correspondence” between HEE and HWL is the following. There is a similarity between holographic entanglement entropy in confining backgrounds [28, 29] and Wilson loops in black hole backgrounds [50], and vice versa.

Schematically:

$$\begin{aligned} S^{(conf.)}(l) &\sim V^{(BH.)}(l) \\ V^{(conf.)}(l) &\sim S^{(BH.)}(l) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where $S(l)$ is the EE and $V(l)$ is the quark-antiquark potential. By “ \sim ”, we mean that the two functions qualitatively have a similar shape, as we now show.

To exemplify this “correspondence” (See Fig. 26), consider the following two backgrounds:

AdS_5 compactified on a circle:

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{U}{R}\right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{R}{U}\right)^4 \frac{dU^2}{f(U)} + f(U) dx_3^2 + dt^2 + dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 \right] \quad (\text{A.12})$$

AdS_5 black hole:

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{U}{R}\right)^2 \left[\left(\frac{R}{U}\right)^4 \frac{dU^2}{f(U)} + f(U) dt^2 + dx_1^2 + dx_2^2 + dx_3^2 \right] \quad (\text{A.13})$$

The two backgrounds are related by $t \leftrightarrow x_3$.

We calculated the HEE and HWL in these two backgrounds, and the result is shown in Fig. 26. The black arrows show the “correspondence”. The WL for the AdS_5 BH is qualitatively similar to the EE for

Figure 26: Showing a “correspondence” between HEE and HWL. The black arrows show the correspondence. The top-left plot is qualitatively similar to the bottom-right plot. Likewise, the top-right plot is qualitatively similar to the bottom-left plot.

AdS_5 compactified on a circle. Likewise, the HEE for the AdS_5 BH is qualitatively similar to the HWL for AdS_5 compactified on a circle.

This qualitative “correspondence” is true for other confining backgrounds and other AdS black holes. It can be explicitly seen by looking at the integral expressions for the Wilson loops and entanglement entropy. The “correspondence” is related to the vanishing of the function $f(U)$ at the horizon of a black hole (for the finite T case) and at the tip of the cigar (for the confining case).

More specifically, the reason it happens is:

1. The Wilson loop picks up the coefficient of time dt^2 in the metric, but does not pick up the coefficient of the compact direction dx_3^2 .
2. The entanglement entropy does not pick up the coefficient of time dt^2 in the metric (it is defined at a constant time slice), but does pick up the coefficient of the compact direction dx_3^2 .
3. The confining metric and the metric of the black hole are related by exchanging the time direction and the spatial circle: $dt^2 \leftrightarrow dx_3^2$:

In section 5.3 we use this correspondence to note that the phase diagrams for Wilson loops of multiple strips, will be qualitatively similar to those of HEE.

References

- [1] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, “A Quantum Source of Entropy for Black Holes,” *Phys.Rev.* **D34** (1986) 373–383.
- [2] M. Srednicki, “Entropy and area,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **71** (1993) 666–669, [arXiv:hep-th/9303048 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [3] C. Holzhey, F. Larsen, and F. Wilczek, “Geometric and renormalized entropy in conformal field theory,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B424** (1994) 443–467, [arXiv:hep-th/9403108 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [4] J. Callan, Curtis G. and F. Wilczek, “On geometric entropy,” *Phys.Lett.* **B333** (1994) 55–61, [arXiv:hep-th/9401072 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [5] P. Calabrese and J. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and conformal field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504005, [arXiv:0905.4013 \[cond-mat.stat-mech\]](#).
- [6] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “Entanglement entropy in free quantum field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504007, [arXiv:0905.2562 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [7] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy of black holes,” *Living Rev.Rel.* **14** (2011) 8, [arXiv:1104.3712 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [8] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [arXiv:hep-th/0603001 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [9] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **0608** (2006) 045, [arXiv:hep-th/0605073 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [10] H. Casini, M. Huerta, and R. C. Myers, “Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1105** (2011) 036, [arXiv:1102.0440 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [11] A. Lewkowycz and J. Maldacena, “Generalized gravitational entropy,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 090, [arXiv:1304.4926 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [12] M. Headrick, “Entanglement Renyi entropies in holographic theories,” *Phys.Rev.* **D82** (2010) 126010, [arXiv:1006.0047 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [13] M. Alishahiha, M. R. M. Mozaffar, and M. R. Tanhayi, “Evolution of Holographic n-partite Information,” [arXiv:1406.7677 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [14] B. Swingle, “Mutual information and the structure of entanglement in quantum field theory,” [arXiv:1010.4038 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [15] W. Fischler, A. Kundu, and S. Kundu, “Holographic Mutual Information at Finite Temperature,” *Phys.Rev.* **D87** no. 12, (2013) 126012, [arXiv:1212.4764 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [16] D. Mukherjee and K. Narayan, “AdS plane waves, entanglement and mutual information,” *Phys.Rev.* **D90** (2014) 026003, [arXiv:1405.3553 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [17] E. Tonni, “Holographic entanglement entropy: near horizon geometry and disconnected regions,” *JHEP* **1105** (2011) 004, [arXiv:1011.0166 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [18] A. Allais and E. Tonni, “Holographic evolution of the mutual information,” *JHEP* **1201** (2012) 102, [arXiv:1110.1607 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [19] V. Balasubramanian, A. Bernamonti, N. Copland, B. Craps, and F. Galli, “Thermalization of mutual and tripartite information in strongly coupled two dimensional conformal field theories,” *Phys.Rev.* **D84** (2011) 105017, [arXiv:1110.0488 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [20] P. Hayden, M. Headrick, and A. Maloney, “Holographic Mutual Information is Monogamous,” *Phys.Rev.* **D87** no. 4, (2013) 046003, [arXiv:1107.2940 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [21] C. T. Asplund and A. Bernamonti, “Mutual information after a local quench in conformal field theory,” *Phys.Rev.* **D89** (2014) 066015, [arXiv:1311.4173 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [22] P. Calabrese, J. Cardy, and E. Tonni, “Entanglement entropy of two disjoint intervals in conformal field theory,” *J.Stat.Mech.* **0911** (2009) P11001, [arXiv:0905.2069 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [23] P. Calabrese, J. Cardy, and E. Tonni, “Entanglement entropy of two disjoint intervals in conformal field theory II,” *J.Stat.Mech.* **1101** (2011) P01021, [arXiv:1011.5482 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [24] J. Cardy, “Some results on the mutual information of disjoint regions in higher dimensions,” *J.Phys.* **A46** (2013) 285402, [arXiv:1304.7985 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [25] T. Hartman, “Entanglement Entropy at Large Central Charge,” [arXiv:1303.6955 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [26] T. Faulkner, “The Entanglement Renyi Entropies of Disjoint Intervals in AdS/CFT,” [arXiv:1303.7221 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [27] H. J. Schnitzer, “Mutual Rényi information for two disjoint compound systems,” [arXiv:1406.1161 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [28] I. R. Klebanov, D. Kutasov, and A. Murugan, “Entanglement as a probe of confinement,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B796** (2008) 274–293, [arXiv:0709.2140 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [29] T. Nishioka and T. Takayanagi, “AdS Bubbles, Entropy and Closed String Tachyons,” *JHEP* **0701** (2007) 090, [arXiv:hep-th/0611035 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [30] V. E. Hubeny, H. Maxfield, M. Rangamani, and E. Tonni, “Holographic entanglement plateaux,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 092, [arXiv:1306.4004](#).
- [31] D. D. Blanco, H. Casini, L.-Y. Hung, and R. C. Myers, “Relative Entropy and Holography,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 060, [arXiv:1305.3182 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [32] T. Nishioka, S. Ryu, and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy: An Overview,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504008, [arXiv:0905.0932 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [33] E. Witten, “Anti-de Sitter space, thermal phase transition, and confinement in gauge theories,” *Adv.Theor.Math.Phys.* **2** (1998) 505–532, [arXiv:hep-th/9803131 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [34] U. Kol, C. Nunez, D. Schofield, J. Sonnenschein, and M. Warschawski, “Confinement, Phase Transitions and non-Locality in the Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1406** (2014) 005, [arXiv:1403.2721 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [35] A. Pakman and A. Parnachev, “Topological Entanglement Entropy and Holography,” *JHEP* **0807** (2008) 097, [arXiv:0805.1891 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [36] I. Bah, A. Faraggi, L. A. Pando Zayas, and C. A. Terrero-Escalante, “Holographic entanglement entropy and phase transitions at finite temperature,” *Int.J.Mod.Phys.* **A24** (2009) 2703–2728, [arXiv:0710.5483 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [37] C. V. Johnson, “Large N Phase Transitions, Finite Volume, and Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1403** (2014) 047, [arXiv:1306.4955 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [38] M. Headrick and T. Takayanagi, “A Holographic proof of the strong subadditivity of entanglement entropy,” *Phys.Rev.* **D76** (2007) 106013, [arXiv:0704.3719 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [39] N. Itzhaki, J. M. Maldacena, J. Sonnenschein, and S. Yankielowicz, “Supergravity and the large N limit of theories with sixteen supercharges,” *Phys.Rev.* **D58** (1998) 046004, [arXiv:hep-th/9802042 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [40] J. L. Barbon and C. A. Fuertes, “Holographic entanglement entropy probes (non)locality,” *JHEP* **0804** (2008) 096, [arXiv:0803.1928 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [41] A. van Niekerk, “Entanglement Entropy in NonConformal Holographic Theories,” [arXiv:1108.2294 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [42] D.-W. Pang, “Entanglement thermodynamics for nonconformal D-branes,” *Phys.Rev.* **D88** no. 12, (2013) 126001, [arXiv:1310.3676 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [43] J. Bhattacharya, M. Nozaki, T. Takayanagi, and T. Ugajin, “Thermodynamical Property of Entanglement Entropy for Excited States,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **110** no. 9, (2013) 091602, [arXiv:1212.1164](#).
- [44] T. Hirata and T. Takayanagi, “AdS/CFT and strong subadditivity of entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **0702** (2007) 042, [arXiv:hep-th/0608213 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [45] P. Kraus, F. Larsen, and S. P. Trivedi, “The Coulomb branch of gauge theory from rotating branes,” *JHEP* **9903** (1999) 003, [arXiv:hep-th/9811120 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [46] J. M. Maldacena, “Wilson loops in large N field theories,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **80** (1998) 4859–4862, [arXiv:hep-th/9803002 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [47] Y. Kinar, E. Schreiber, and J. Sonnenschein, “Q anti-Q potential from strings in curved space-time: Classical results,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B566** (2000) 103–125, [arXiv:hep-th/9811192 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [48] S. Kuperstein and J. Sonnenschein, “Non-critical, near extremal AdS(6) background as a holographic laboratory of four dimensional YM theory,” *JHEP* **0411** (2004) 026, [arXiv:hep-th/0411009 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [49] T. Hirata, “New inequality for Wilson loops from AdS/CFT,” *JHEP* **0803** (2008) 018, [arXiv:0801.2863 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [50] A. Brandhuber, N. Itzhaki, J. Sonnenschein, and S. Yankielowicz, “Wilson loops in the large N limit at finite temperature,” *Phys.Lett.* **B434** (1998) 36–40, [arXiv:hep-th/9803137 \[hep-th\]](#).

Chapter 4

Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres

Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres

Omer Ben-Ami,^a Dean Carmi^a and Michael Smolkin^b

^a*Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences School of Physics and Astronomy Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel*

^b*Center for Theoretical Physics and Department of Physics, University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720, U.S.A.*

E-mail: omerben@post.tau.ac.il, carmidea@post.tau.ac.il, smolkinm@berkeley.edu

ABSTRACT: We explore entanglement entropy of a cap-like region for a generic quantum field theory residing in the Bunch-Davies vacuum on de Sitter space. Entanglement entropy in our setup is identical with the thermal entropy in the static patch of de Sitter, and we derive a simple relation between the vacuum expectation value of the energy-momentum tensor trace and the RG flow of entanglement entropy. In particular, renormalization of the bare couplings and logarithmic divergence of the entanglement entropy are interrelated in our setup. We confirm our findings by recovering known universal contributions for a free field theory deformed by a mass operator as well as obtain correct universal behaviour at the fixed points. Simple examples of entanglement entropy flows are elaborated in $d = 2, 3, 4$. In three dimensions we find that while the renormalized entanglement entropy is stationary at the fixed points, it is not monotonic. We provide a computational evidence that the universal ‘area law’ for a conformally coupled scalar is different from the known result in the literature, and argue that this difference survives in the limit of flat space. Finally, we carry out the spectral decomposition of entanglement entropy flow and discuss its application to the F-theorem.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	Setup	4
3	Ward identities	7
3.1	Thermal interpretation	9
3.2	RG equation for entanglement entropy	10
3.3	Conformal fixed point	10
4	Free fields on sphere	12
4.1	Conformally coupled scalar	12
4.1.1	Renormalization of EE in even d	16
4.2	Dirac fermion	20
5	Spectral decomposition	21
5.1	Example: conformally coupled scalar on S^3	24
6	Discussion	27
A	Universal area law	29
B	Free fields on a deformed waveguide	30
C	Addition theorem for spherical harmonics on S^3	32

1 Introduction

Entanglement entropy is an important tool in condensed matter physics [1–4], quantum field theory [5–9] and quantum gravity [10–21]. Nowadays this technique is in the spot light of nonperturbative studies of the structure of quantum field theories (QFT). In particular, constraints imposed by c -theorems, which describe the irreversible nature of renormalization group (RG) flows between the fixed points, is one of the examples where entanglement entropy methods are applied [22–33].¹ These theorems spring directly from Zamolodchikov’s proof [42] of irreversibility of RG flows in two dimensions. In general dimension, however, the mechanism of irreversibility is still unclear, but Cardy’s conjecture [43] suggests that this feature is inherent to any QFT for any even dimensional space-time. Recently, a striking proof was found in four dimensions [44], see also [45, 46], but its generalization to six and higher dimensions is not straightforward [47].

¹See also [34–41] for recent progress in applying entanglement entropy techniques in a QFT context.

A natural extension of Cardy’s conjecture for quantum field theories in an odd dimensional space-time was proposed in [23, 24]. Based on the holographic studies of entanglement entropy in general dimension, they suggested that the universal coefficient of entanglement entropy for a spherical region is decreasing along the RG trajectory. At the fixed points of RG flows in even dimensions this coefficient is proportional to the central charge used by Cardy to formulate his conjecture [6, 48–50], while for odd dimensions it was shown in [50], see also [51], that this coefficient is directly related to the F -theorem [52, 53]. These observations indicate that entanglement entropy provides a useful framework to study c -theorems in general odd and even dimensions.

Important progress in understanding c -theorems in three dimensions was made in [54] where Casini and Huerta used strong subadditivity of entanglement entropy [55] to prove the three-dimensional F -theorem for any unitary and Lorentz invariant QFT. There is not yet an alternative derivation. However, it is certainly important to understand the key insights of the proof in terms of conventional field theoretic methods, and one of our goals in this paper is to make a step in this direction.

Motivated by [56], we think of entanglement entropy as a scalar functional of the field theory couplings and geometry of the setup. Imposing various symmetries inherent to the underlying QFT yields a set of Ward identities and RG flow equations satisfied by the entanglement entropy functional [57]. The resulting identities depend on various correlators involving insertions of the modular Hamiltonian, and therefore from computational perspective they are not really tractable since the modular Hamiltonian is not known and not local in general. However, for a special class of co-dimension two entangling surfaces which exhibit rotational symmetry in the transverse space, the modular Hamiltonian can be identified with the angular evolution operator around a given entangling surface [58–60] while the corresponding Ward identities and RG flow equations can be written in terms of the standard correlation functions.

Flat entangling plane in Minkowski space-time is probably the simplest realization of such a symmetric setup. It has been shown in [60] that entanglement entropy in this case equals thermal entropy of the Rindler wedge. Perturbative studies of this setup are useful for understanding the structure of both the universal entanglement entropy [56, 61, 62], see also [63–65], and the modular Hamiltonian [66]. There is also a way to use it in order to set a precise relation between the entanglement entropy and renormalization of the Newton’s constant [33]. However, this setup has no built-in scale, and its topology is trivial, which makes it hard to believe that one can learn much about the non-perturbative aspects of c -theorems in higher dimensions based on this example.²

Our proposal in section 2 is to use a rotationally symmetric entangling surface for a field theory residing in the Bunch-Davies vacuum on de Sitter space.³ Rotational symmetry ensures simple structure for the modular Hamiltonian while the curvature of maximally symmetric geometry effectively sets the renormalization group scale.⁴ Such a setup is

²However, see [33] for an alternative derivation of Zamolodchikov’s theorem using this setup.

³For a CFT this construction was studied in [24] and holographically in [23, 24], see also [67] and [68] for various aspects of the entanglement entropy in de Sitter space.

⁴In the system we study, the scale of entangling surface is also defined by the radius of de Sitter space,

scalable in the sense defined by [26], and RG flow equation for entanglement entropy can be expressed in terms of two-point function of the energy-momentum tensor. A further simplification takes place after we notice in section 3 that the RG flow of entanglement entropy has simple interrelation with the vacuum expectation value (vev) of the energy-momentum tensor trace. This leads us to a quite interesting conclusion that the logarithmic divergences associated with renormalization of the bare operators and bare parameters in the energy-momentum tensor on de Sitter space are simply related to the universal entanglement entropy. We illustrate this peculiarity in section 4 using the example of massive free field theories, where renormalization of the cosmological constant must be done even in the absence of interactions.

Our construction has much in common with the Rindler space and with the observations made by [60]. For example, entanglement entropy equals thermal entropy for any QFT in our setup. However, there are several distinctions which make it more interesting. Firstly, the Euclidean continuation of the causal domain of entangling region in de Sitter space has non trivial topology in comparison to its counterpart in Minkowski space (sphere versus flat plane). Secondly, the curvature of de Sitter space sets up a characteristic temperature which manifests itself through the finite terms in entanglement entropy. Finally, one can explore an RG flow of entanglement entropy between the fixed points by varying the radius of de Sitter space. Given that de Sitter space is more realistic than Minkowski background, such RG flows are worth investigation.

In section 4 we build on the advantages of our setup to study simple RG flows. In particular, we find that renormalized entanglement entropy defined in [26, 54] is not monotonic on a three dimensional de Sitter space. Of course, this observation does not contradict [54] since there is no reason to expect that RG flows on de Sitter and Minkowski space-times share the same merits. Furthermore, in contrast to the flat space results in [69], our findings in section 4 indicate that the renormalized entanglement entropy is stationary at the fixed points on a sphere. This qualitative difference between the backgrounds can be attributed to the absence of infrared (IR) divergences in our setup, since sphere can be thought of as a finite box. It should be noted, however, that this result is in certain tension with [69], see also [70], where non-stationarity was found not only for a scalar field theory living in flat space, but also for a conformally coupled scalar on a sphere. This disagreement is closely related to another observation made in section 4 where we argue that the universal ‘area law’ for a massive conformally coupled scalar field on a sphere is different from its counterpart in flat space [71–73]. This discrepancy is not sensitive to the size of de Sitter radius which points in favour of controversial [15, 33, 36, 74–78] difference between the universal entanglement entropies for minimally and conformally coupled scalar fields in *flat* space. Possible explanation of this phenomenon is given in [79], see also [56, 62, 80].

Finally, in section 5 we use [81] to elaborate the spectral decomposition of entanglement entropy flow in general dimension. This decomposition is determined by an integral over a positive weight function which represents the spin-0 part of the spectral representation for two point function of the energy-momentum tensor. In particular, the rate of change of

therefore there is only one global geometric scale.

entanglement entropy with respect to RG scale has definite sign, provided that the integral over the weight function converges. In three dimensions it suggests that the finite part of entanglement entropy may play a role of the c -function. However, this conclusion is too naïve. Indeed, possible logarithmic divergences of the entanglement entropy for a QFT in three dimensions [56, 82] is a clear sign of potential problems with convergence of the spectral integral. Moreover, finite part of entanglement entropy at the IR fixed point is contaminated by various mass scales which are remnants of RG running into the fixed point [33]. In the deep infrared these finite terms are part of UV physics, and therefore they should be subtracted to distill the genuine universal piece of entanglement entropy at the IR fixed point.

2 Setup

Let us consider a generic QFT living on a d -dimensional background de Sitter space of radius R - a submanifold of $(d+1)$ -dimensional Minkowski space described by the hyperboloid of one sheet,

$$x_1^2 + x_2^2 + \dots + x_d^2 - x_0^2 = R^2 . \quad (2.1)$$

We will assume that the field theory resides in a unique Bunch-Davies vacuum state, also known as the Euclidean vacuum, which is invariant under all the isometries. In global coordinates,

$$\begin{aligned} x_0 &= R \sinh\left(\frac{t}{R}\right) , \\ x_i &= R \cosh\left(\frac{t}{R}\right) \Omega_i , \quad i = 1, \dots, d , \end{aligned} \quad (2.2)$$

with $\sum_i \Omega_i^2 = 1$, the metric on de Sitter space takes the form

$$ds^2 = -dt^2 + R^2 \cosh^2\left(\frac{t}{R}\right) d\Omega_{d-1}^2 . \quad (2.3)$$

In what follows we aim to consider entanglement entropy of two equal cap-like regions A and B which are located on a $x_0 = 0$ ($t = 0$) time slice of dS^d . This slice is invariant under $t \rightarrow -t$ which makes it possible to analytically continue the metric to the Euclidean signature, *i.e.*, $x_0 \rightarrow ix_{d+1}$ or equivalently $t \rightarrow i\tau$. In particular, the problem of finding entanglement entropy boils down to studies of a QFT living on a d -dimensional sphere of radius R , see Fig.1.

By construction, the entangling surface, Σ , divides the equator of S^d into two equivalent cap-like regions. In particular, it exhibits rotational symmetry in the transverse space which has topology of a 2-sphere. Hence, we find it convenient to foliate S^d such that this symmetry becomes manifest,

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= R \sin \theta \Omega_i \quad \text{for } 1 \leq i \leq d-1 \quad , \quad 0 \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2} \quad , \quad \sum_{i=1}^{d-2} \Omega_i^2 = 1 \quad , \\ x_d &= R \cos \theta \cos \tau \quad , \\ x_{d+1} &= R \cos \theta \sin \tau \quad , \end{aligned} \quad (2.4)$$

Figure 1. Illustrating the setup of a QFT living on an S^d sphere. The entangling surface (at $t = 0$ and $\theta = \pi/2$) divides the equator into two equal cap regions (shown in blue and red).

where (τ, θ) parametrize a two-dimensional transverse space to the entangling surface at $\theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$.⁵ The infinitesimal line element on S^d takes the form

$$ds^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{d+1} dx_j^2 = R^2 \left(\cos^2 \theta d\tau^2 + d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\Omega_{d-2}^2 \right). \quad (2.5)$$

It worth noting that the above foliation of S^d corresponds to analytic continuation of the static patch of de Sitter to Euclidean signature, and it has been shown in [50] that if the field theory is conformal, then entanglement entropy for a sphere of radius R in Minkowski space is equivalent to the thermodynamic entropy of the thermal state in the static patch of de Sitter geometry. Of course, in the absence of conformal symmetry there is no simple relation between these entropies. However, by construction it is still true that the entanglement entropy of two equal cap-like regions for a theory residing in the Bunch-Davies vacuum equals to the thermal entropy associated with a thermal state in the static patch of de Sitter. A quantitative manifestation of this (exact) relation is provided in section 4.

Now let us assume that the field theory on S^d is some CFT deformed by a set of relevant operators \mathcal{O}_i of scaling dimension Δ_i and associated couplings λ^i . Since entangling surface

⁵In two dimensions $-\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \theta \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$, and entangling surface consists of two disjoint points at $\theta = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$.

exhibits rotational symmetry in the transverse space, the modular Hamiltonian is given by

$$K = -2\pi \int_A T_{\mu\nu} \xi^\mu n^\nu + c' , \quad T_{\mu\nu}(x) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{g}} \frac{\delta I}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} . \quad (2.6)$$

where I is the Euclidean action of the field theory, the integral runs over the region A of the equator, $n^\nu = (R \cos \theta)^{-1} \partial_\tau$ is normal to this region, $\xi^\mu = \partial_\tau$ is the Killing vector associated with rotational symmetry around Σ and c' is an additive constant to ensure proper normalization of the reduced density matrix, *i.e.*, $\text{Tr} e^{-K} = 1$.

Now recall the general flow equations that describe changes in the entanglement entropy under flow of the relevant couplings and deformation of the geometry [57],

$$\frac{\partial S_{\text{EE}}}{\partial \lambda^i} = - \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \langle O_i(x) K \rangle_\lambda , \quad \mathcal{O}(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{g(x)}} \frac{\delta I}{\delta \lambda^i(x)} , \quad (2.7)$$

$$\frac{\delta S_{\text{EE}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} = - \frac{\sqrt{g(x)}}{2} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) K \rangle_\lambda , \quad (2.8)$$

where λ collectively denotes all the couplings. These flows are directly related to the first law of entanglement [83–86]⁶. Of course, for a general deformation K will not be given by (2.6) since rotational symmetry will be destroyed. However, if we restrict our consideration to a particular one parameter family of constant rescaling of the background, then rotational symmetry is preserved and (2.8) takes the following form

$$\int d^d x g^{\mu\nu} \frac{\delta S_{\text{EE}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} = - \frac{1}{2} \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \langle T(x) K \rangle_\lambda , \quad (2.9)$$

where $T(x) = g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu}(x)$ is the trace of the energy-momentum tensor, and integrals run over S^d .

The left hand side simplifies if we notice that for our choice of the foliation constant Weyl rescaling of the background metric is tantamount to a constant rescaling of the radius of S^d , and we obtain

$$R \frac{d S_{\text{EE}}}{d R} = \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \langle T(x) K \rangle_\lambda . \quad (2.10)$$

Eq. (2.10) can be also derived using the standard replica trick approach just because the rotational symmetry around the entangling surface makes it possible to introduce a well-defined conical defect, such that

$$S_{\text{EE}} = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon} + 1 \right) \log Z_{1-\epsilon} , \quad (2.11)$$

where $Z_{1-\epsilon}$ is the partition function on the n -fold cover of a sphere and $\epsilon = 1 - n$. Hence [13, 24],

$$\begin{aligned} R \frac{d S_{\text{EE}}}{d R} &= -2 \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon} + 1 \right) \int d^d x g^{\mu\nu}(x) \frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} \log Z_{1-\epsilon} \\ &= \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \epsilon} + 1 \right) \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \langle T(x) \rangle_{1-\epsilon} \\ &= \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \langle T(x) K \rangle , \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

⁶See also [87] for a discussion of certain parallelism between the entanglement and the laws of thermodynamics.

where the last equality rests on [37, 88].

Unfortunately, (2.10) is ambiguous when supports of the energy-momentum tensor and the modular Hamiltonian collide. Hence, we resort to the Ward identities which help to circumvent this ambiguity.

3 Ward identities

In this section we use the Ward and trace identities to constrain correlation functions involving the modular Hamiltonian and the energy-momentum tensor. They will help us to fix certain ambiguities involving situations when the energy-momentum tensor collides with the support of modular Hamiltonian.

Let us consider the vacuum entanglement entropy of a generic surface Σ for a quantum field theory defined on an arbitrary curved space. Assuming that regularization preserves invariance under the diffeomorphisms $g_{\mu\nu} \rightarrow g_{\mu\nu} + \nabla_{(\mu} v_{\nu)}$, where ∇_{μ} and v_{μ} stand for a covariant derivative and arbitrary vector field respectively, and taking into account that entanglement entropy is a scalar functional, implies⁷

$$0 = - \int d^d x (\nabla^{\mu} v^{\nu} + \nabla^{\nu} v^{\mu}) \frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} S_{\text{EE}} = - \int d^d x \sqrt{g} v^{\nu} \nabla^{\mu} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) K \rangle , \quad (3.3)$$

where in the second equality we substituted the definition $S_{\text{EE}} = -\text{Tr} \hat{\rho} \log \hat{\rho} = \langle K \rangle$ and used normalization of the density matrix to drop $\langle \delta K / \delta g^{\mu\nu} \rangle = 0$, see [56]. Hence, we conclude

$$\nabla^{\mu} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) K \rangle = 0 . \quad (3.4)$$

Let us contrast this formula with the standard Ward identity for the two point function of the energy-momentum tensor. Starting from the counterpart of (3.4),

$$\nabla^{\mu} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle = 0 , \quad (3.5)$$

which one obtains from the condition that the effective action, $W \equiv \log Z$ with Z being a partition function, is a scalar functional under diffeomorphisms, and differentiating it with respect to the metric, yields [81]

$$\nabla^{\mu} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle = \nabla_{\nu} \left(\delta_{\alpha}^{\sigma} \delta_{\beta}^{\rho} \delta^d(x, y) \right) \langle T_{\sigma\rho}(x) \rangle + 2 \nabla_{\sigma} \left(\delta_{(\alpha}^{\sigma} \delta_{\beta)}^{\rho} \delta^d(x, y) \langle T_{\rho\nu}(x) \rangle \right) , \quad (3.6)$$

where $\delta^d(x, y) = \delta^d(x - y) / \sqrt{g(x)}$, whereas the 2-point function is defined by

$$\sqrt{g(x)} \sqrt{g(y)} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle \equiv 4 \frac{\delta^2 W}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x) \delta g^{\alpha\beta}(y)} . \quad (3.7)$$

⁷The most general Ward identity of this type, which also accounts for the possibility of local sources $\lambda^i(x)$, takes the form

$$\int d^d x \left(-(\nabla^{\mu} v^{\nu} + \nabla^{\nu} v^{\mu}) \frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} + v^{\mu} \partial_{\mu} \lambda^i \frac{\delta}{\delta \lambda^i} \right) S_{\text{EE}} = 0 , \quad (3.1)$$

or equivalently

$$\nabla^{\mu} \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) K \rangle = \partial_{\mu} \lambda^i \langle O_i(x) K \rangle . \quad (3.2)$$

Ultimately, we will be interested in $\lambda^i(x) = \lambda^i$ the physical coupling constants, and therefore we drop terms involving $\partial_{\mu} \lambda^i$.

The right hand side of (3.6) vanishes up to contact terms involving δ -functions, while the right hand side of (3.4) vanishes identically. In particular, in the special case when the modular Hamiltonian is local and is given by (2.6), it would be naïve to use (3.7) to evaluate the right hand side of (2.10). One needs to modify this correlator in the limit of coincident points such that (3.4) holds identically. A necessary modification in a slightly different context was carried out in [81], and we review it here.

One starts from noting that the vacuum expectation value of any local scalar operator on a sphere is just a constant and also

$$\langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle = -\frac{1}{d} \frac{C}{R^d} g_{\mu\nu}(x) , \quad (3.8)$$

where C is some dimensionless function of the couplings. Eq. (3.5) is trivially satisfied, whereas (3.6) becomes

$$\nabla^\mu \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle = -\frac{1}{d} \frac{C}{R^d} \left(\nabla_\nu \delta^d(x, y) g_{\alpha\beta}(y) + 2 \nabla_\sigma (\delta_{(\alpha}^\sigma \delta_{\beta)}^\rho \delta^d(x, y) g_{\rho\nu}(x)) \right) \quad (3.9)$$

Next define,

$$\langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle_{\text{con}} = \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle + \frac{1}{d} \frac{C}{R^d} (g_{\mu\alpha} g_{\nu\beta} + g_{\mu\beta} g_{\nu\alpha} + g_{\mu\nu} g_{\alpha\beta}) \delta^d(x, y) . \quad (3.10)$$

where $\langle \rangle_{\text{con}}$ means “conserved”, as in [81]. This 2-point correlator satisfies a desired conservation equation [81],

$$\nabla^\mu \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle_{\text{con}} = 0 , \quad (3.11)$$

and therefore it should be used in (2.10) to ensure that the Ward identity (3.4) is satisfied.

Now recall that for our setup homogeneous Weyl rescaling obeys

$$2 \int d^d x g^{\mu\nu}(x) \frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} = -R \frac{d}{dR} . \quad (3.12)$$

In particular, applying this operator to the both sides of (3.8) leads to

$$- \int d^d y \sqrt{g(y)} \langle T(y) T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle + d \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle = \frac{1}{d} R \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{C}{R^d} \right) g_{\mu\nu}(x) - \frac{2}{d} \frac{C}{R^d} g_{\mu\nu}(x) . \quad (3.13)$$

Or equivalently, using (3.10)

$$- \int d^d y \sqrt{g(y)} \langle T(y) T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle_{\text{con}} = \frac{g_{\mu\nu}(x)}{d} R \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{C}{R^d} \right) . \quad (3.14)$$

Substituting this formula into (2.10) and using (2.6), we obtain one of our main results⁸

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} = \frac{2\pi}{d} R \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{C}{R^d} \right) \int_A \xi \cdot n = \frac{\Omega_d R^{d+1}}{d} \frac{d}{dR} \left(\frac{C}{R^d} \right) , \quad (3.15)$$

⁸We stress that unlike the one point function $\langle K \rangle$, the (divergent) constant c' drops out of connected correlators.

where Ω_d is the surface area of a unit d -dimensional sphere,

$$\Omega_d = \frac{2\pi^{\frac{d+1}{2}}}{\Gamma\left(\frac{d+1}{2}\right)}. \quad (3.16)$$

It worth mentioning that (3.15) relates finite quantities on both sides of the equation since C is finite by definition. In particular, this formula eliminates the power law divergent terms of EE such as the well known ‘area law’. Of course, there is nothing bad about absence of these terms since they are scheme dependent and therefore vanish under appropriate choice of the regularization scheme (*e.g.*, dimensional regularization). However, the logarithmic divergence of EE is always retained, and its coefficient is scheme independent. This observation may cast doubts on possible applications of (3.15) for a QFT in even dimensions, where the universal EE is associated with a logarithmic divergence. In section 4 we elaborate on simple examples which clarify this subtlety. We show that the universal EE in our setup is directly related to the logarithmic divergences of the bare parameters defining the theory, and the standard renormalization results in a finite EE with the universal data being encoded in the coefficient of the (finite) logarithmic running. Throughout the paper we apply dimensional regularization scheme, and therefore non-universal divergences of EE will be absent from our calculations.

3.1 Thermal interpretation

As pointed out in section 2, entanglement entropy equals thermal entropy in the system under study, $S_{EE} = S_{Th}$. Therefore (3.15) should have a simple interpretation in terms of standard thermodynamics. We provide such an argument below, see also [50] for thermal analysis of $S_{EE} = S_{Th}$ at the fixed point.

Let us start from the following thermodynamic relation,

$$S_{Th} = \beta(U - F), \quad (3.17)$$

where U and F are thermal and free energies respectively, and $\beta = 2\pi R$ is the inverse temperature. As usual, U is given by the expectation value of the operator which generates translations around the thermal circle parametrized by τ in (2.5). Hence, based on (3.8)

$$\beta U = \frac{\Omega_d}{d} C. \quad (3.18)$$

Now we can operate with $R \frac{d}{dR}$ on both sides of (3.17). Using (3.12), our convention (2.6) for the energy-momentum tensor, and recalling that $\beta F = -W$, yields

$$R \frac{d}{dR}(\beta F) = \Omega_d C \quad \Rightarrow \quad R \frac{d}{dR} S_{Th} = \frac{\Omega_d}{d} \left(R \frac{dC}{dR} - dC \right). \quad (3.19)$$

This is exactly (3.15), thus we showed that $S'_{EE} = S'_{Th}$. Since at the fixed point we have $S_{EE} = S_{Th}$, we conclude that this is true also outside the fixed point.

3.2 RG equation for entanglement entropy

The renormalization group running of entanglement entropy in our setup can be readily evaluated. Based on (3.8), we have

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial \lambda^i} = -R^d \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda^i} \langle T(x) \rangle = R^d \int d^d y \sqrt{g(y)} \langle O_i(y) T(x) \rangle + dR^d \langle O_i(x) \rangle = R \frac{d}{dR} \left(R^d \langle O_i(x) \rangle \right), \quad (3.20)$$

where in the last equality we used homogeneity of the sphere to replace integral over y with integral over x and then applied the correspondence (3.12). Next we combine this result with the trace Ward identity⁹ [81, 89]

$$\langle T \rangle + (d - \Delta - \beta) \lambda \langle O \rangle = \mathcal{A} \quad \Rightarrow \quad C = R^d \left((d - \Delta - \beta) \lambda \langle O \rangle - \mathcal{A} \right), \quad (3.21)$$

where β is the beta function, and \mathcal{A} is the trace anomaly formed from the Riemann tensor and its derivatives, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{A} = 0$ for any odd dimensional space-time while for even dimensional sphere $\mathcal{A} \propto R^{-d}$. As a result, we obtain [81]

$$\left(R \frac{d}{dR} - (d - \Delta - \beta) \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \right) C = -R \frac{d}{dR} \left(R^d \mathcal{A} \right) = 0. \quad (3.22)$$

This equation combined with (2.7), (3.8), (3.15) and the definition of the modular Hamiltonian (2.6) leads to $\lambda \frac{\partial S}{\partial \lambda} = -\frac{1}{d} \Omega_d \lambda \frac{\partial C}{\partial \lambda} + \Omega_d R^d \langle O(x) \rangle$,¹⁰ substituting this we get:

$$\left(R \frac{d}{dR} - (d - \Delta - \beta) \lambda \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} \right) S_{\text{EE}} = \Omega_d R^d \mathcal{A}. \quad (3.23)$$

Given that \mathcal{A} is constant on a sphere, we deduce that the right hand side is just the integrated trace anomaly. This equation is a particular realization of the general idea presented in [57]. Here, however, we keep the finite anomalous term on the right hand side of (3.23) since we are interested to evaluate finite logarithms which combine with the universal divergence of entanglement entropy to form a dimensionless term.

3.3 Conformal fixed point

Let us consider a rotationally symmetric entangling surface for a CFT residing in a vacuum state on some curved manifold.¹¹ In this case, the right hand side of (2.9) is completely fixed by the trace anomaly

$$\langle T(x) \rangle = \mathcal{A} = \sum_n b_n I_n(x) - 2(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}} a E_d(x) + B^I \nabla_\mu J^\mu(x), \quad (3.24)$$

which defines the central charges for a CFT in an even number of dimensions. Each term on the right-hand side is constructed from the background geometry. I_n are Weyl invariant combinations of the Weyl tensor, the Cotton tensor and the Bach tensor as well as their

⁹For brevity we suppress index i of the relevant couplings. Sum over this index is implicitly assumed.

¹⁰When deriving this relation it should be noted that the difference between $\lambda \frac{\partial C}{\partial \lambda}$ and $\lambda \frac{\partial S}{\partial \lambda}$ stems from the fact that $\left\langle \frac{\partial T_{\mu\nu}}{\partial \lambda} \right\rangle \sim g_{\mu\nu} \langle O \rangle$ but $\left\langle \frac{\partial K}{\partial \lambda} \right\rangle = 0$, as can be seen from the requirement $\text{Tr } e^{-K} = 1$

¹¹It should not necessarily be our setup, *e.g.*, waveguide geometry [71, 73] works equally well.

covariant derivatives. These basis tensors all vanish on any conformally flat background. The last term in eq. (3.24) is a scheme-dependent total derivative which can be eliminated by adding a covariant counter-term to the effective action. Finally, E_d is the Euler density in d dimensions,

$$E_{2p}(\mathcal{R}) \equiv \frac{1}{(8\pi)^p \Gamma(p+1)} \delta_{\mu_1 \mu_2 \dots \mu_{2p-1} \mu_{2p}}^{\nu_1 \nu_2 \dots \nu_{2p-1} \nu_{2p}} \mathcal{R}^{\mu_1 \mu_2 \nu_1 \nu_2} \dots \mathcal{R}^{\mu_{2p-1} \mu_{2p} \nu_{2p-1} \nu_{2p}}, \quad (3.25)$$

where $\delta_{\mu_1 \mu_2 \dots \mu_{2p-1} \mu_{2p}}^{\nu_1 \nu_2 \dots \nu_{2p-1} \nu_{2p}}$ denotes a totally antisymmetric product of $2p$ Kronecker delta symbols and the normalization ensures that $\int_{S^d} d^d x \sqrt{g} E_d = 2$.

Varying (3.24) with respect to $g^{\mu\nu}(y)$ and using the definition (3.7), yields

$$\langle T(x) T_{\mu\nu}(y) \rangle - \delta^d(x, y) g_{\mu\nu}(x) \langle T(x) \rangle - 2\delta^d(x, y) \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) \rangle = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{g(y)}} \frac{\delta \mathcal{A}(x)}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(y)}. \quad (3.26)$$

In our setup the vev of the energy-momentum tensor takes a simple form (3.8), and therefore according to the definition of conserved 2-point function (3.10), we may identify the left hand side with $\langle T(x) T_{\mu\nu}(y) \rangle_{\text{con}}$. We will assume that similar redefinition exists for any system with rotationally invariant entangling surface.¹² Hence, (2.9) at the fixed point reads

$$\int d^d x g^{\mu\nu} \frac{\delta S_{\text{EE}}}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} = -2\pi \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \int d^{d-1} y \sqrt{h(y)} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{g(y)}} \frac{\delta \mathcal{A}(x)}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(y)} \right) \xi^\mu n^\nu, \quad (3.27)$$

where $h_{\mu\nu}$ denotes the induced metric on a region A enclosed by the entangling surface.

The right hand side can be readily evaluated in our case. Indeed, I_n terms in the trace anomaly (3.24) play no role since they are at least quadratic in the building blocks which vanish for a conformally flat background. Total derivatives can be ignored,¹³ whereas the contribution of the Euler density is easy to evaluate since its integral is a topological term, *i.e.*,

$$0 = \frac{\delta}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(y)} \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} E_d(x) = \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \left(\frac{\delta E_d(x)}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(y)} - \frac{1}{2} g_{\mu\nu}(x) E_d(x) \delta(x-y) \right). \quad (3.29)$$

Hence,

$$\int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} \frac{\delta E_d(x)}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(y)} = \frac{\sqrt{g(y)}}{2} g_{\mu\nu}(y) E_d(y). \quad (3.30)$$

¹²It would be interesting to work out the details of this redefinition based on the requirement that Ward identity (3.4) holds. Our assumption here rests on the observation that in the replica trick approach there are no δ -functions away from the entangling surface.

¹³Variation of the total derivative is given by

$$\delta(\nabla_\mu J^\mu) = (\delta \nabla_\mu) J^\mu + \nabla_\mu (\delta J^\mu). \quad (3.28)$$

First term on the right hand side vanishes since $J^\mu = 0$ on a sphere, whereas the integral of the last term vanishes since sphere has no boundaries. Therefore we conclude that the net contribution of the total derivatives to entanglement entropy flow is zero.

Now E_d is obviously constant on a sphere, therefore we can use our choice of normalization condition to get

$$E_d|_{S^d} = \frac{2}{\Omega_d} R^{-d} . \quad (3.31)$$

Combining, yields

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} = \frac{8\pi(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}-1} a}{\Omega_d R^d} \int d^{d-1} y \sqrt{h(y)} \xi \cdot n = 4(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}-1} a . \quad (3.32)$$

In accord with [23, 24], see also [50].

4 Free fields on sphere

In this section we use free massive fields to elaborate on various properties of the formalism that we have developed in the previous section.

4.1 Conformally coupled scalar

Let us consider a free massive scalar field on a d -dimensional sphere of radius R

$$I = \int_{S^d} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\partial\phi)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m^2 \phi^2 + \frac{1}{2} \xi_c \mathcal{R} \phi^2 \right) , \quad (4.1)$$

where $\xi_c = \frac{d-2}{4(d-1)}$ is the conformal coupling, $\mathcal{R} = \frac{d(d-1)}{R^2}$ is the Ricci scalar of a sphere and m^2 is the mass of the field. The energy-momentum tensor is given by

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \nabla_\mu \phi \nabla_\nu \phi - g_{\mu\nu} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\partial\phi)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m^2 \phi^2 + \frac{1}{2} \xi_c \mathcal{R} \phi^2 \right) + \xi_c \mathcal{R}_{\mu\nu} \phi^2 + \xi_c (g_{\mu\nu} \nabla^2 - \nabla_\mu \nabla_\nu) \phi^2 . \quad (4.2)$$

Hence,

$$T = g^{\mu\nu} T_{\mu\nu} = -m^2 \phi^2 - \frac{d-2}{2} \phi (-\nabla^2 + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + m^2) \phi . \quad (4.3)$$

Discarding equation of motion operator leads to

$$C_\phi = m^2 R^d \langle \phi^2 \rangle . \quad (4.4)$$

The vev of ϕ^2 is given by the coincident point limit of the Green's function which solves the Green's equation on S^d

$$\left[-\frac{1}{R^2 \sin^{d-1} \chi} \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \left(\sin^{d-1} \chi \frac{\partial}{\partial \chi} \right) + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + m^2 \right] G_m(\chi) = \delta^d(R\chi) , \quad (4.5)$$

where χ is the polar angle on a sphere, and we used rotational symmetry to bring one of the points to the north pole.

To solve the above equation, one needs to impose regularity at $\chi = \pi$, and

$$G_m(\chi) \sim \frac{(R\chi)^{2-d}}{(d-2)\Omega_{d-1}} \quad \text{for } \chi \ll 1 . \quad (4.6)$$

which corresponds to a scalar potential created by a unit charge placed at $\chi = 0$. The general solution which satisfies these conditions is

$$G_m(\chi) = \frac{R^{2-d}}{(4\pi)^{d/2}} \frac{\Gamma(\lambda)\Gamma(-\lambda+d-1)}{\Gamma(d/2)} {}_2F_1\left(\lambda, d-1-\lambda; \frac{d}{2}; \cos^2 \frac{\chi}{2}\right), \quad (4.7)$$

$$\lambda = \frac{d-1}{2} + i\sqrt{(mR)^2 - \frac{1}{4}}. \quad (4.8)$$

Taking the limit $\chi \rightarrow 0$ and dropping a mass independent (divergent) constant¹⁴, we have

$$\langle \phi^2 \rangle = \frac{\Gamma(1-d/2)\Gamma(\lambda)\Gamma(d-1-\lambda)}{\pi(4\pi)^{d/2}R^{d-2}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(d-2\lambda)\right). \quad (4.9)$$

In particular, $\langle \phi^2 \rangle$ is finite for odd d , whereas for even d it exhibits a simple pole which corresponds to the logarithmic divergence. We treat these cases separately.

Odd d

For odd d , we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_\phi &= \frac{\pi(mR)^2 \coth(\pi\sqrt{m^2R^2 - 1/4})}{\sqrt{m^2R^2 - 1/4}} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{(4\pi)^{d/2}\Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \prod_{j=1}^{\frac{d-1}{2}} \left((d/2 - 1/2 - j)^2 - 1/4 + m^2R^2 \right) \\ &= \frac{\pi(mR)^2 \coth(\pi\sqrt{m^2R^2 - 1/4})}{\sqrt{m^2R^2 - 1/4}} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{(4\pi)^{d/2}\Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \\ &\quad \times \left((mR)^{d-1} + \frac{(d-1)(d^2 - 5d + 3)}{24} (mR)^{d-3} + \dots + \frac{\pi}{2\Gamma\left(\frac{2-d}{2}\right)\Gamma\left(\frac{4-d}{2}\right)} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.10)$$

Appearance of the hyperbolic function in both the C_ϕ and the entanglement entropy after using (3.15) is not surprising. Indeed, such functions are the direct associates of any thermal computation, whereas the state in de Sitter space has thermal interpretation. To get rid of the thermal effects, let us consider the behaviour of entanglement entropy in the IR limit, $mR \gg 1$. In this regime curvature corrections are negligibly small, while thermal effects are exponentially suppressed, and we get

$$C_\phi \underset{mR \gg 1}{=} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} \pi}{(4\pi)^{d/2}\Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \left((mR)^d + \frac{d(d-2)(d-4)}{24} (mR)^{d-2} + \dots \right) \quad (4.11)$$

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}}}{dR} \underset{mR \gg 1}{=} \frac{(d-2)(d-4)}{24(d-1)} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d+1}{2}} \pi}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}\Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} A_\Sigma m^{d-2} + \dots \quad (4.12)$$

where ellipsis encapsulate curvature corrections to the leading order term also known as universal ‘area law’. As shown in Appendix A, this term is identical to the universal ‘area law’ of entanglement entropy of a half space for a conformally coupled scalar field residing in the Minkowski vacuum. This result is a consequence of the fact that any surface and any background are locally flat.

¹⁴The mass independent term behaves as χ^{2-d} , and therefore it diverges as power law in $d > 2$. Such divergences are scheme dependent, and therefore one can choose a particular scheme where it vanishes, *e.g.*, in dimensional regularization one gets $\chi^{2-d} \rightarrow 0$ for $d < 2$, and therefore analytic continuation to higher d also vanishes.

Renormalized Entanglement Entropy in 3D

For a vacuum state in 3-dimensional flat space QFT, the general pattern for EE of a disk is

$$S_{\text{EE}} = c_1 \frac{R}{\delta} - c_0 , \quad (4.13)$$

where R is the radius of the disk and δ is a UV cut off. At the fixed point, c_0 and c_1 are some constants,¹⁵ whereas outside the fixed point c_0 is a function of R and various scales characterizing a given QFT. Obviously, c_1 is scheme dependent while c_0 is universal, therefore the authors of [26, 28, 54] defined the so-called renormalized entanglement entropy (REE) to isolate the universal contribution,¹⁶

$$\mathcal{S}_3 \equiv R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} - S_{\text{EE}} \equiv RS'_{\text{EE}} - S_{\text{EE}} . \quad (4.14)$$

Using strong sub-additivity of EE [55], Casini and Huerta proved that $S''_{\text{EE}} \leq 0$ for a disk in flat space. Hence, $\mathcal{S}'_3 = RS''_{\text{EE}} \leq 0$, which clearly indicates that REE has a monotonic RG flow in flat space, and [54]

$$\Delta c_0 = c_0^{\text{UV}} - c_0^{\text{IR}} = - \int_0^\infty dR R S''_{\text{EE}} \geq 0 . \quad (4.15)$$

Of course, the RG flow itself is ambiguous but the fixed points satisfy an F-theorem [52, 53]. Furthermore, conformal symmetry relates the REE at the fixed points in flat space to the universal EE in our setup [50], hence it is worthwhile to explore REE on a sphere outside the fixed points.

For a conformally coupled scalar field, S''_{EE} can be readily evaluated based on (3.15), (4.4) and (4.9). Fig. 2 shows the corresponding plot, and it can be seen that S''_{EE} changes sign. A similar issue is discussed in [53] for the free energy on a sphere, where the authors argue that additional subtractions are necessary because of emergence of the cosmological constant term in the IR limit. Although REE is not monotonic, other choices of subtraction scheme might result in a monotonic flow as was suggested for the free energy in [53].

Moreover, REE in our setup exhibits stationarity at the fixed points, *i.e.*, $S''_{\text{EE}} \rightarrow 0$ as $mR \rightarrow 0, \infty$. This result should be contrasted with numerical studies in [69], where it has been shown that REE for a disk in flat space is not stationary in the massless limit. Similar considerations for the free energy showed that although the IR divergent free energy obeys stationarity, the existence of a subtraction scheme that maintains stationarity, monotonicity and analyticity is not obvious [53].

We have calculated $\Delta c_0 \sim 0.0638$ which agrees with the expected result from the free energy calculation of a conformally coupled massless scalar in the UV and an empty theory in the IR, in spite of thermal effects mentioned above.

¹⁵At the IR fixed point there could be additional terms, which are remnants of the RG flow [33], *e.g.*, the universal ‘area law’ $\sim mR$ for massive QFTs [71–73]. However, the characteristic (relevant) scale of such terms is very large in the deep IR, and therefore in this regime they are not really distinguishable from the R/δ term. Hence, we do not write them out.

¹⁶See [26, 28] for definition of REE in general dimension.

Figure 2. $\frac{d^2 S_{EE}}{d(mR)^2}$ for a massive conformally coupled scalar field on a 3-sphere. Unlike its counterpart in Minkowski space, $\frac{d^2 S_{EE}}{d(mR)^2}$ changes sign around $mR \sim 1.6$.

Even d

For even d_0 the pole structure of C_ϕ is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
C_\phi &= (-)^{d_0/2} m^2 R^2 \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{(d_0-2)/2} ((d_0/2 - 1/2 - j)^2 + m^2 R^2 - 1/4)}{(4\pi)^{d_0/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)} \frac{2}{d - d_0} + \dots \\
&= \frac{(-)^{d_0/2}}{(4\pi)^{d_0/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)} \left((mR)^{d_0} + \frac{d_0(d_0-2)(d_0-4)}{24} (mR)^{d_0-2} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{d_0(d_0-2)(d_0-4)(d_0-6)(5d_0^2 - 18d_0 + 4)}{5760} (mR)^{d_0-4} + \dots + 2 \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)}{d_0-2} (mR)^4 \right) \frac{2}{d - d_0} + \dots
\end{aligned} \tag{4.16}$$

The universal divergence of the entanglement entropy is obtained by substituting this expression into¹⁷ (3.15)

$$\begin{aligned}
R \frac{dS_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}}}{dR} &= \frac{(d_0-2)(d_0-4)}{12(d-1)} \frac{(-)^{d_0/2+1} A_\Sigma}{(4\pi)^{(d_0-2)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)} \\
&\times \left(m^{d_0-2} + \frac{(d_0-6)(5d_0^2 - 18d_0 + 4)}{120} \frac{m^{d_0-4}}{R^2} + \dots + 24 \frac{\Gamma^2\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)}{d_0(d_0-2)^2} \frac{m^4}{R^{d_0-6}} \right) \log(m\delta).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.17}$$

The leading order term in the limit $mR \gg 1$ represents the universal ‘area law’. In this limit curvature effects can be disregarded, and the system can be approximated by a free scalar field theory living in the Rindler wedge [90], therefore it should be possible to recover the same result by considering the entanglement entropy of a half space for

¹⁷As usual, simple poles in the dimensional regularization scheme correspond to logarithmic divergences, and we use the following dictionary $\log(m\delta) = \frac{1}{d-d_0}$, see Appendix A.

a massive scalar field residing in the Minkowski vacuum state [60]. We carry out this computation in Appendix A and find full agreement. However, the resulting expression for the universal ‘area law’ is not the same as in, *e.g.*, [71–73]. Possible interpretation of this discrepancy is given in [79], see also [56, 62, 80]. In Appendix B we present an independent computation of the curvature correction to the universal ‘area law’ and find full agreement with (4.17). Note also that unlike odd d , the universal entanglement entropy in even dimensions is not affected by de Sitter temperature. Absence of thermal corrections is due to the fact that UV divergences of EE are state independent, see *e.g.*, [82].

So far we discussed how the logarithmic divergences of EE are encoded in (3.15). In particular, we used a naïve bare expression (4.4) for C_ϕ to uncover the universal entanglement entropy. Counter terms which are unavoidable even in the absence of interactions will contribute to (4.4) and result in a finite C_ϕ . This makes us believe that the universal entanglement entropy for a QFT in the setup under study is directly related to the logarithmic divergences associated with renormalization of the bare operators and bare parameters in the energy-momentum tensor trace, whereas renormalization of the theory generates a finite EE through the use of (3.15). Of course, the finite part of EE depends on the choice of subtraction scheme, and therefore it is ambiguous, but the coefficients of the logarithmic running are universal. In what follows we elaborate the details of RG flow of the (finite) EE for a free massive scalar field in $d = 2, 4$. These results generalize easily to higher dimensions.

4.1.1 Renormalization of EE in even d

Eq. (4.17) reveals how the universal EE is encoded in (3.15) (recall that dimensional regularization eliminates non-universal power law divergences). However, as we stressed in the previous section, this calculation is incomplete without accounting for the counter terms which are necessary to render the partition function of the theory finite. Taking these terms into account results in a finite vev of the energy-momentum tensor and thus finite EE through the use of (3.15). Of course, the universal divergence of EE is not lost. It transmutes into a finite term which represents the logarithmic running of EE. In this section we calculate all necessary counter terms needed to renormalize the partition function and obtain a renormalized expression for the EE.

$$d = 2$$

In $d = 2$, the total action which includes all possible counter terms that are necessary to render the partition function of the theory finite is¹⁸

$$S_{\text{tot}}^{d=2} = \int_{S^d} \left(\frac{1}{2}(\partial\phi)^2 + \frac{1}{2}m^2\phi^2 + \frac{1}{2}\xi_c\mathcal{R}\phi^2 + \Lambda_0 + \kappa_0\mathcal{R} \right), \quad (4.18)$$

where Λ_0 describes a bare cosmological constant and κ_0 is the usual bare coupling of the Einstein action. In 2D this term is responsible for the trace anomaly. The conformal coupling ξ_c vanishes in two dimensions, however, we are going to use the method of dimensional renormalization, and therefore we keep it in the action.

¹⁸For a free field theory the mass and the non-minimal coupling are not corrected by the divergences of higher-order loops, therefore we do not distinguish between the bare and renormalized m^2 and ξ_c .

The bare and renormalized parameters in the minimal subtraction scheme are related as

$$\begin{aligned}\Lambda_0 &= \mu^{d-2} \left(\Lambda + \frac{\Lambda_p}{d-2} m^2 \right), \\ \kappa_0 &= \mu^{d-2} \left(\kappa + \frac{\kappa_p}{d-2} \right),\end{aligned}\tag{4.19}$$

where Λ, κ are renormalized parameters, μ is an arbitrary mass scale and Λ_p, κ_p are residues of simple poles. These counter terms are necessary to ensure a finite partition function. For an interacting QFT the above expression contains higher order poles and much more complicated residues.

The constant Λ_p is determined from the requirement that

$$-m^2 \frac{\partial Z}{\partial m^2} = \int_{S^d} \left(\frac{m^2}{2} \langle \phi^2 \rangle + \mu^{d-2} m^2 \frac{\Lambda_p}{d-2} \right)\tag{4.20}$$

must be finite. Expanding (4.9) around $d = 2$ gives

$$\langle \phi^2 \rangle = -\frac{1}{2\pi(d-2)} + \frac{1}{4\pi} (\log(4\pi R^2) - \psi(1-\lambda) - \psi(\lambda) - \gamma) + \mathcal{O}(d-2).\tag{4.21}$$

Hence,

$$\Lambda_p = \frac{1}{4\pi}.\tag{4.22}$$

Similarly, the free parameter κ_p is determined by the divergence of a 1-loop diagram with external gravitons. However, we resort to a different method. Let us consider the vacuum expectation value of the energy-momentum tensor trace

$$\langle T(x) \rangle = -\frac{2}{\sqrt{g}} g^{\mu\nu} \frac{\delta \log Z}{\delta g^{\mu\nu}(x)} = -\frac{d-2}{2} \langle \phi(-\nabla^2 + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + m^2) \phi \rangle - m^2 \langle \phi^2 \rangle - d\Lambda_0 - (d-2)\kappa_0 \mathcal{R}.\tag{4.23}$$

The first term on the right hand side vanishes since it corresponds to the equation of motion operator's vev. The rest can be expanded around $d = 2$ using (4.19), (4.21), (4.22)

$$\langle T(x) \rangle = -\frac{m^2}{4\pi} (\log(4\pi R^2 \mu^2) - \psi(1-\lambda) - \psi(\lambda) - \gamma + 1) - 2\Lambda - \kappa_p \mathcal{R}.\tag{4.24}$$

As expected, the vev of the energy-momentum tensor trace is finite after the bare operators and bare parameters are replaced with renormalized parameters. The unspecified μ, Λ and κ_p can be determined by imposing the decoupling condition $\langle T \rangle \rightarrow 0$ as $mR \rightarrow \infty$ [91]

$$\mu^2 = m^2, \quad \Lambda = m^2 \frac{(\gamma - \log(4\pi) - 1)}{8\pi}, \quad \kappa_p = \frac{-1}{24\pi}.\tag{4.25}$$

Substituting into $\langle T \rangle$, we obtain

$$\langle T(x) \rangle = -\frac{m^2}{4\pi} (2\log(mR) - \psi(1-\lambda) - \psi(\lambda)) + \frac{\mathcal{R}}{24\pi}.\tag{4.26}$$

Note that the last term cannot be modified by adding to the action a finite counter term, hence it represents the trace anomaly in two dimensions.

Next we evaluate the EE flow using (3.8) and (3.15)

$$\begin{aligned} C_\phi &= \frac{(mR)^2}{4\pi} (2\log(mR) - \psi(1-\lambda) - \psi(\lambda)) - \frac{1}{12\pi} , \\ R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} &= (mR)^2 + \frac{i(mR)^4 (\psi'(1-\lambda) - \psi'(\lambda))}{2\sqrt{(mR)^2 - 1/4}} + \frac{1}{3} . \end{aligned} \quad (4.27)$$

It can be readily verified that RS'_{EE} vanishes as $mR \rightarrow \infty$. In this limit the RG running takes us to an empty fixed point. In the opposite limit, $mR \rightarrow 0$, we recover a pathological massless scalar field on S^2 ($\xi_c = 0$ in 2D)¹⁹. Therefore the above equations describe RG running of a massive theory into an empty fixed point.

$$d = 4$$

This case is similar to $d = 2$ except that the total action admits more counter terms, see *e.g.*, [92],

$$\begin{aligned} S_{\text{tot}}^{d=4} &= \int_{S^d} \left(\frac{1}{2} (\partial\phi)^2 + \frac{1}{2} m^2 \phi^2 + \frac{1}{2} \xi_c \mathcal{R} \phi^2 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \Lambda_0 + \kappa_0 \mathcal{R} + \frac{b_0}{16\pi^2} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} + 2a_0 E_4 + c_0 \mathcal{R}^2 \right) , \end{aligned} \quad (4.28)$$

where $C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma}$ is the Weyl tensor. The relation between bare and renormalized parameters is

$$\Lambda_0 = \mu^{d-4} \left(\Lambda + \frac{\Lambda_p}{d-4} m^4 \right) , \quad \kappa_0 = \mu^{d-4} \left(\kappa + \frac{\kappa_p}{d-4} m^2 \right) , \quad (4.29)$$

$$a_0 = \mu^{d-4} \left(a + \frac{a_p}{d-4} \right) , \quad b_0 = \mu^{d-4} \left(b + \frac{b_p}{d-4} \right) , \quad c_0 = \mu^{d-4} \left(c + \frac{c_p}{d-4} \right) .$$

As before, the constant Λ_p is obtained by requiring that

$$-m^2 \frac{\partial Z}{\partial m^2} = \int_{S^d} \left(\frac{m^2}{2} \langle \phi^2 \rangle + \mu^{d-4} m^2 \mathcal{R} \frac{\kappa_p}{d-4} + 2\mu^{d-4} m^4 \frac{\Lambda_p}{d-4} \right) \quad (4.30)$$

is finite. Expanding (4.9) around $d = 4$ gives

$$\langle \phi^2 \rangle = \frac{m^2}{8\pi^2(d-4)} - \frac{m^2}{16\pi^2} (\log(4\pi R^2) - \psi(\lambda) - \psi(3-\lambda) + 1 - \gamma) + \mathcal{O}(d-4) . \quad (4.31)$$

Hence,

$$\Lambda_p = \frac{-1}{32\pi^2} , \quad \kappa_p = 0 . \quad (4.32)$$

¹⁹We call this theory ‘pathological’ since Laplace operator on a sphere is not invertible. It has a normalizable zero mode which corresponds to a constant field configuration. Thus a minimally coupled massless scalar field on a sphere does not have a well-defined two point function without excluding zero mode from consideration.

To determine other counter terms, let us consider vev of the energy-momentum trace,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T(x) \rangle &= -\frac{d-2}{2} \langle \phi(-\nabla^2 + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + m^2)\phi \rangle - m^2 \langle \phi^2 \rangle - d\Lambda_0 - (d-2)\kappa_0 \mathcal{R} \\ &\quad - (d-4) \left(\frac{b_0}{16\pi^2} C^{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} C_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} + 2a_0 E_4 + c_0 \mathcal{R}^2 \right) + 4(d-1)c_0 \nabla^2 \mathcal{R} . \end{aligned} \quad (4.33)$$

The first term is proportional to the equation of motion operator's vev, thus it vanishes. Furthermore, \mathcal{R} is constant on a sphere, whereas Weyl tensor vanishes. Thus,

$$\begin{aligned} \langle T(x) \rangle &= -m^2 \langle \phi^2 \rangle - d\Lambda_0 - (d-2)\kappa_0 \mathcal{R} - (d-4) (-2a_0 E_4 + c_0 \mathcal{R}^2) \\ &= \frac{m^4}{16\pi^2} \left(\log(4\pi R^2 \mu^2) - \psi(\lambda) - \psi(3-\lambda) + \frac{3}{2} - \gamma \right) - 4\Lambda - 2\kappa \mathcal{R} - 2a_p E_4 - c_p \mathcal{R}^2 , \end{aligned} \quad (4.34)$$

where we used (4.29), (4.31) and (4.32). The last two terms correspond to the trace anomaly. Obviously, these terms cannot be modified by adding a finite counter term to the action.

Next we impose the decoupling condition, $\langle T \rangle \rightarrow 0$ as $mR \rightarrow \infty$, to determine $a_p, c_p, \mu, \kappa, \Lambda$ [91]

$$\mu^2 = m^2, \quad \Lambda = m^4 \frac{3 - 2\gamma + 2 \log(4\pi)}{128\pi^2}, \quad \kappa = \frac{-m^2}{(24\pi)^2}, \quad \frac{3}{2\pi^2} a_p + 144 c_p = \frac{1}{240\pi^2}. \quad (4.35)$$

Although for our needs it is not necessary to calculate a_p and c_p separately, it is still worth mentioning that $c_p = 0$ for a free massive scalar field. Indeed, c_p is mass independent, and it vanishes for a massless conformally coupled scalar field (CFT). One can also verify that $c_p = 0$ by a direct calculation [92, 93]. Substituting the above parameters into $\langle T \rangle$, we obtain

$$\langle T(x) \rangle = \frac{m^4}{16\pi^2} \left(2 \log(mR) - \psi(\lambda) - \psi(3-\lambda) + \frac{2}{3(mR)^2} \right) - \frac{1}{240\pi^2 R^4}. \quad (4.36)$$

Finally, using (3.8) and (3.15), results in

$$\begin{aligned} C_\phi &= -\frac{(mR)^4}{16\pi^2} \left(2 \log(mR) - \psi(\lambda) - \psi(3-\lambda) + \frac{2}{3(mR)^2} \right) + \frac{1}{240\pi^2}, \\ R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} &= \frac{(mR)^2}{18} - \frac{(mR)^4}{12} - \frac{i(mR)^6 (\psi'(3-\lambda) - \psi'(\lambda))}{24\sqrt{(mR)^2 - 1/4}} - \frac{1}{90}. \end{aligned} \quad (4.37)$$

In the deep IR limit, $mR \rightarrow \infty$, the theory flows into an empty fixed point and RS'_{EE} vanishes. In the UV limit, $mR \rightarrow 0$, we recover a conformally coupled massless scalar field, and $RS'_{\text{EE}} = -1/90$ in accordance with (3.32).²⁰ Therefore RG running happens between two fixed points which correspond to the conformally coupled scalar field and an empty theory.

²⁰ $a = a_p = \frac{1}{360}$.

4.2 Dirac fermion

Let us consider a free Dirac field of mass m . The Euclidean action is given by

$$I = \int d^d x \bar{\psi} (\not{\nabla} + m) \psi , \quad (4.38)$$

and the corresponding energy-momentum tensor reads

$$T_{\mu\nu} = \frac{1}{2} \bar{\psi} \gamma_{(\alpha} \overleftrightarrow{\nabla}_{\beta)} \psi - \delta_{\alpha\beta} (\bar{\psi} \not{\nabla} \psi + m \bar{\psi} \psi) , \quad (4.39)$$

where γ_μ are the gamma matrices satisfying the anticommutation relations

$$\{\gamma_\mu, \gamma_\nu\} = 2g_{\mu\nu} . \quad (4.40)$$

Taking the trace of the energy-momentum tensor and using the Dirac equation of motion we obtain,

$$T = -m \bar{\psi} \psi . \quad (4.41)$$

Hence

$$C_\psi = m R^d \langle \bar{\psi} \psi \rangle . \quad (4.42)$$

To evaluate C_ψ we use propagator of the Dirac field on S^d [94]

$$\begin{aligned} \langle \psi(y) \bar{\psi}(x) \rangle &= \frac{\Gamma(\frac{d}{2} + imR) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2} - imR)}{2^d \pi^{d/2} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2} + 1) R^{d-1}} \\ &\times \left(mR U(y, x) \cos \frac{\chi}{2} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{d}{2} + imR, \frac{d}{2} - imR; \frac{d}{2} + 1; \cos^2 \frac{\chi}{2}\right) \right. \\ &\left. + \frac{d}{2} n^\mu \gamma_\mu U(y, x) \sin \frac{\theta}{2} {}_2F_1\left(\frac{d}{2} + imR, \frac{d}{2} - imR; \frac{d}{2}; \cos^2 \frac{\chi}{2}\right) \right) , \end{aligned} \quad (4.43)$$

where n^μ is the unit tangent vector to the geodesic connecting x to y , $U(y, x)$ is a matrix in the spinor indices which parallel propagates a spinor between the two points, and χ is the polar angle between x and y . In particular,

$$\langle \bar{\psi} \psi \rangle = -2^{\lfloor \frac{d}{2} \rfloor} \frac{\Gamma(\frac{d}{2} + imR) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2} - imR) \sinh(\pi m)}{R^{d-1} (4\pi)^{d/2} \sin(\frac{d\pi}{2}) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} . \quad (4.44)$$

This vev is finite for odd d , whereas for even d it has simple poles which correspond to the logarithmic divergences. Let us consider these cases separately

Odd d

For odd d , we have

$$\begin{aligned} C_\psi &= (-)^{\frac{d+1}{2}} \frac{(\pi m R) \tanh(\pi m R)}{\sqrt{2} (2\pi)^{d/2} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \prod_{j=1}^{\frac{d-1}{2}} ((d/2 - j)^2 + m^2 R^2) \\ &= (-)^{\frac{d+1}{2}} \frac{(\pi m R) \tanh(\pi m R)}{\sqrt{2} (2\pi)^{d/2} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \left((mR)^{d-1} + \frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{24} (mR)^{d-3} + \dots + \frac{\Gamma^2(\frac{d}{2})}{\pi} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.45)$$

The hyperbolic function is associated with the thermal corrections, and in principle it should be stripped off to isolate the impact of entanglement. We achieve this goal by taking the limit $mR \gg 1$, in which case the thermal effect is exponentially suppressed. To leading order we recover a known result [71], see also Appendix A

$$C_\psi \underset{mR \gg 1}{=} \frac{\pi(-)^{\frac{d+1}{2}}}{\sqrt{2}(2\pi)^{d/2}\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \left((mR)^d + \frac{d(d-1)(d-2)}{24}(mR)^{d-2} + \dots + \frac{\Gamma^2(\frac{d}{2})}{\pi} mR \right) \quad (4.46)$$

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}}}{dR} \underset{mR \gg 1}{=} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} \pi(d-2)}{12\sqrt{2}(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} A_\Sigma m^{d-2} + \dots, \quad (4.47)$$

where ellipsis encapsulate curvature corrections.

Even d

The pole structure of C_ψ for even d_0 is given by

$$\begin{aligned} C_\psi &= (-)^{d_0/2-1} \frac{\prod_{j=1}^{d_0/2} ((d_0/2-j)^2 + m^2 R^2)}{(2\pi)^{d_0/2} \Gamma(\frac{d_0}{2})} \frac{2}{d-d_0} + \dots \\ &= \frac{(-)^{d_0/2-1}}{(2\pi)^{d_0/2} \Gamma(\frac{d_0}{2})} \left((mR)^{d_0} + \frac{d_0(d_0-1)(d_0-2)}{24}(mR)^{d_0-2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{d_0(d_0-1)(d_0-2)(d_0-3)(d_0-4)(5d_0+2)}{5760}(mR)^{d_0-4} + \dots + \Gamma^2(\frac{d_0}{2})(mR)^2 \right) \frac{2}{d-d_0} + \dots \end{aligned} \quad (4.48)$$

The universal entanglement entropy is obtained by substituting it into (3.15)

$$\begin{aligned} R \frac{dS_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}}}{dR} &= \frac{(-)^{d_0/2}(d_0-2)A_\Sigma}{6(2\pi)^{(d_0-2)/2}\Gamma(\frac{d_0}{2})} \left(m^{d_0-2} + \frac{(d_0-3)(d_0-4)(5d_0+2)}{120} \frac{m^{d_0-4}}{R^2} \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \dots + 12 \frac{\Gamma^2(\frac{d_0}{2})}{d_0(d_0-1)} \frac{m^2}{R^{d-4}} \right) \log \delta \end{aligned} \quad (4.49)$$

The leading order term matches a well-known universal ‘area law’ [71], see also Appendix A. Subleading terms represent corrections to the entanglement entropy induced by curvatures. In Appendix B we present independent computation of the curvature corrections and find full agreement with (4.49). Although we do not present it here, similar analysis to section 4.1.1 for the massive scalar can be applied to the massive fermion, giving a renormalized expression for the EE, and the UV limit agrees with (3.32).

5 Spectral decomposition

In this section we derive an expression for the right hand side of (2.10) in terms of specific spectral function. We start from the spectral decomposition of the conserved two point function (3.10). In general, it can be expressed as [81]

$$\Omega_{d-1}^2 \langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle_{\text{con}} = \Gamma_{0\mu\nu,\alpha\beta}(x, y) + \Gamma_{2\mu\nu,\alpha\beta}(x, y), \quad (5.1)$$

where the spin-2 piece, $\Gamma_{2\mu\nu,\alpha\beta}$, is traceless, and therefore it does not contribute to (2.10).²¹ The spin-0 piece is given by

$$\begin{aligned}\Gamma_{0\mu\nu,\alpha\beta}(x,y) &= S_{\mu\nu}(x)F_0(\sigma)\overleftarrow{S}_{\alpha\beta}(y), \\ S_{\alpha\beta} &\equiv \nabla_\alpha\nabla_\beta - g_{\alpha\beta}\nabla^2 - \frac{(d-1)}{R^2}g_{\alpha\beta},\end{aligned}\quad (5.2)$$

where $\sigma(x,y)$ is the geodesic interval in units of R between x and y , covariant derivatives on the left of $F_0(\sigma)$ act on x , whereas covariant derivatives on the right of $F_0(\sigma)$ act on y , as indicated by the arrow sign above $S_{\alpha\beta}(y)$, and

$$F_0(\sigma) = \Omega_{d-1} \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu \rho_0(\mu) G_\mu(\sigma), \quad (5.3)$$

where as before $G_\mu(\sigma)$ is the Green's function satisfying

$$(-\nabla^2 + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2)G_\mu(x,y) = \delta^d(x,y), \quad (5.4)$$

with μ being the mass of the field. Thus, the two point function which is necessary to evaluate the right hand side of (2.10) is completely determined by $\rho_0(\mu)$,

$$\Omega_{d-1}^2 \langle T(x)T_{\alpha\beta}(y) \rangle_{\text{con}} = g^{\mu\nu} S_{\mu\nu}(x)F_0(\sigma)\overleftarrow{S}_{\alpha\beta}(y). \quad (5.5)$$

Before substituting (5.5) into (2.10), it is worth mentioning that for our choice of foliation (2.4), we have $\xi^\mu = \delta_\tau^\mu$ and $n_\mu = R \cos \theta \delta_\mu^\tau$. Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla^2 &= g^{\tau\tau}\nabla_\tau\nabla_\tau + \frac{1}{R^2 \sin^{d-2}\theta} \partial_\theta(\sin^{d-2}\theta\partial_\theta) + \frac{1}{R^2 \sin^2\theta} \nabla_{S^{d-2}}^2 \\ \xi^\alpha n^\beta S_{\alpha\beta} &= -R \cos \theta \left(\frac{1}{R^2 \sin^{d-2}\theta} \partial_\theta(\sin^{d-2}\theta\partial_\theta) + \frac{1}{R^2 \sin^2\theta} \nabla_{S^{d-2}}^2 + \frac{(d-1)}{R^2} \right),\end{aligned}\quad (5.6)$$

with $\nabla_{S^{d-2}}^2$ being the intrinsic Laplacian on S^{d-2} .

Next, we find it useful to define

$$G_\mu^{(2)}(\tau - \tau', \theta, \theta') \equiv \int d\Omega' G_\mu(\tau, \theta, \Omega; \tau', \theta', \Omega') \quad (5.7)$$

where (τ, θ, Ω) and $(\tau', \theta', \Omega')$ are coordinates (2.5) of x and y respectively, and the integral runs over a $(d-2)$ -dimensional sphere parametrized by Ω' . The first thing to note about $G_\mu^{(2)}$ is that it depends on the difference $\tau - \tau'$ due to the symmetry of (2.5) under translations in τ , and it is independent of Ω since (2.5) is symmetric under rotations of S^{d-2} .

Combining (2.6) and (5.5), leads to

$$\begin{aligned}\langle T(x)K \rangle_{\text{con}} &= -\frac{2\pi(d-1)}{\Omega_{d-1}} \int_V \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu (\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \frac{d}{R^2} + \mu^2) \rho_0(\mu) G_\mu(x,y) \overleftarrow{S}_{\alpha\beta}(y) \xi^\alpha n^\beta \\ &= \frac{2\pi(d-1)}{\Omega_{d-1}} \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu (\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \frac{d}{R^2} + \mu^2) \rho_0(\mu) \\ &\quad \times \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\theta' \cos \theta' \left(\partial_{\theta'}(\sin^{d-2}\theta'\partial_{\theta'}) + (d-1)\sin^{d-2}\theta' \right) G_\mu^{(2)}(\tau, \theta, \theta'),\end{aligned}\quad (5.8)$$

²¹Explicit expression for $\Gamma_{2\mu\nu,\alpha\beta}$ is derived in [81].

where based on (5.4) we substituted $\nabla^2 G_\mu(\sigma) = (\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2) G_\mu(\sigma)$ in the first equality,²² whereas in the second equality we used (5.6) and the definition (5.7).²³ We also assumed that $d > 2$.²⁴ Finally, integrating the right hand side of (5.8) by parts twice, yields

$$\langle T(x)K \rangle_{\text{con}} = \frac{2\pi(d-1)}{\Omega_{d-1}} \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu (\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \frac{d}{R^2} + \mu^2) \rho_0(\mu) G_\mu^{(2)}(\tau, \theta, \theta' = \frac{\pi}{2}), \quad (5.9)$$

where $G_\mu^{(2)}(\tau, \theta, \theta' = \frac{\pi}{2})$ is independent of τ since $\theta' = \frac{\pi}{2}$, and the system exhibits rotational symmetry in the transverse space. As expected, $\langle T(x)K \rangle$ is just a function of θ which parametrizes the geodesic distance from the entangling surface in the transverse space.

Another useful result follows directly from (5.4)

$$\int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} G_\mu(x, y) = \frac{1}{\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2}. \quad (5.10)$$

Indeed, the integral on the left hand side is convergent since the Green's function is everywhere regular on a sphere except at $x = y$, where it diverges as σ^{2-d} . However, this divergence is balanced by the integration measure which behaves as σ^{d-1} . Furthermore, S^d is a maximally symmetric space, and therefore the result of integration is given by some constant independent of y . In particular, (5.10) follows from the following identities

$$(\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2) \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} G_\mu(x, y) = (-\nabla^2 + \xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2) \int d^d x \sqrt{g(x)} G_\mu(x, y) = 1, \quad (5.11)$$

where the last equality rests on (5.4).

Substituting now (5.9) into (2.10), and using (5.7), (5.10) to integrate $G_\mu^{(2)}$ over x , yields

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} = -\frac{(d-1)\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}{\pi^{\frac{d-2}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu \left(1 + \frac{d}{R^2(\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2)} \right) \rho_0(\mu), \quad (5.12)$$

where \mathcal{A}_Σ is the area of the entangling surface.

The integral on the right hand side of (5.12) is convergent at the lower bound since sphere introduces a natural IR cut off, but it does not necessarily converges at the upper bound. Indeed, in the UV limit curvature corrections are irrelevant, and convergence of the integral is essentially the same as in Minkowski space. Note also that in the limit $\mu^2 \mathcal{R} \gg 1$ we recover the result of [33].

Furthermore, if the integral on the right hand side converges, then positivity of the spectral function guarantees $RS'_{\text{EE}} \leq 0$ along the RG flow. However, it certainly does not

²²We ignored the delta function on the right hand side of (5.4). There is nothing bad about it if x is disjoint from V . If, however, x hits the support of K , then one may question whether it is justified to suppress the delta function in (5.4). In general, if supports of the operators overlap, it is a must to include contact terms. However, inclusion of such contact terms will break the $O(2)$ invariance inherent to the setup under study, and therefore we disregard them. From computational point of view, we simply assume that $x \notin V$.

²³Note that by assumption x is disjoint from V , therefore $G_\mu(x, y) \overleftarrow{\nabla}_{S^{d-2}}^2$ is everywhere regular on V and its integral over S^{d-2} vanishes just because this manifold has no boundaries.

²⁴The special case $d = 2$ can be treated similarly. In this case the entangling surface consists of two disjoint points $\theta' = \pm \frac{\pi}{2}$, and the integral over θ' in (5.8) should be extended from $-\frac{\pi}{2}$ to $\frac{\pi}{2}$ in order to cover all of S^2 , see (2.4).

ensure (4.15) since finite EE at the IR fixed point, $S_{\text{EE}}^{\text{IR}}$, includes terms which are part of the UV physics. These terms should be subtracted to isolate the universal contribution, c_0^{IR} . We elaborate details of this point in the discussion section.

5.1 Example: conformally coupled scalar on S^3

In this section we carry out spectral decomposition for a massive conformally coupled scalar field described by the Euclidean action (4.1). In this case, based on (4.3), we have

$$\langle T(x)T(y) \rangle = m^4 \langle \phi^2(x)\phi^2(y) \rangle = 2m^4 G_m^2(x, y), \quad (5.13)$$

where by assumption x and y are two disjoint points, and therefore the equation of motion operator in (4.3) does not contribute. In particular, it follows that the spin-0 piece of (5.1) is straightforwardly related to the spectral representation of

$$\langle \phi^2(x)\phi^2(y) \rangle = \int_{\mu_\phi}^{\infty} d\mu \rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) G_\mu(x, y) = \int_{\mu_\phi^2}^{\infty} d\mu^2 \tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2}(\mu) G_\mu(x, y), \quad (5.14)$$

where $\rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) = 2\mu\tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2}(\mu)$. In the meantime we keep the lower bound μ_ϕ unspecified. We find it convenient to use μ^2 as the integration measure in the spectral representation since μ_ϕ may admit imaginary values to account for the possibility of negative μ_ϕ^2 on a sphere.

A useful relation can be established between $\partial_{m^2}\langle\phi^2\rangle$ and $\tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2}$

$$-2\frac{\partial}{\partial m^2}\langle\phi^2\rangle = \int d^d y \sqrt{g(y)} \langle \phi^2(y)\phi^2(x) \rangle = \int_{\mu_\phi^2}^{\infty} d\mu^2 \frac{\tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2}(\mu)}{\xi_c \mathcal{R} + \mu^2}, \quad (5.15)$$

where in the last equality we used (5.10). Shifting the integration measure, $z = (R\mu)^2 - (R\mu_\phi)^2$ and using (4.9), yields

$$\frac{\psi(\lambda) - \psi(d-1-\lambda) - \pi \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{2}(d-2\lambda)\right)}{\mathcal{N}} \langle \phi^2 \rangle = iR^{2-d} \int_0^\infty dz \frac{\tilde{\rho}(z)}{(d-1)^2/4 + \mathcal{N}_\phi^2 + z}. \quad (5.16)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_\phi^2 = (R\mu_\phi)^2 - \frac{1}{4}$ and $\tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2} = R^{4-d}\tilde{\rho}$. We will use this result to check our computations in what follows.

For the rest of this section we continue to explore the spectral decomposition in $d=3$. In this case solution (4.7) to the Green's equation can be expressed in terms of elementary functions

$$G_m(\chi) = -\frac{\sinh[\mathcal{N}(\chi - \pi)]}{4\pi R \sinh(\pi\mathcal{N}) \sin \chi}, \quad \mathcal{N} \equiv \sqrt{(mR)^2 - \frac{1}{4}}, \quad (5.17)$$

We choose to work in the basis of scalar spherical harmonics on S^3 of radius R . They are given by [95]

$$Y_{l_3, l_2, l_1}(\chi, \theta, \phi) = \frac{1}{R^{3/2}\sqrt{2\pi}} e^{il_1\phi} {}_2c_{l_2}^{l_1} P_{l_2}^{-l_1}(\cos\theta) {}_3c_{l_3}^{l_2} (\sin\chi)^{-1/2} P_{l_3+\frac{1}{2}}^{-(l_2+\frac{1}{2})}(\cos\chi), \quad (5.18)$$

where $l_3 \geq l_2 \geq |l_1|$ and

$$P_\nu^{-\mu}(x) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1+\mu)} \left(\frac{1-x}{1+x}\right)^{\mu/2} {}_2F_1\left(-\nu, \nu+1; 1+\mu; \frac{1-x}{2}\right),$$

$${}_n c_L^l = \left[\frac{2L+n-1}{2} \frac{(L+l+n-2)!}{(L-l)!}\right]^{1/2}. \quad (5.19)$$

Note, that by definition spherical harmonics satisfy

$$Y_{l_3, l_2, l_1}^*(\chi, \theta, \phi) = (-1)^{l_1} Y_{l_3, l_2, -l_1}(\chi, \theta, \phi) . \quad (5.20)$$

In particular, the only nontrivial coefficients in the expansion of $G_m(\chi)$, are given by

$$G_{l_3}(m^2) = \int_{S^3} Y_{l_3 0 0}(\chi) G_m(\chi) = \frac{R^{1/2}}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{l_3 + 1}{(l_3 + 1)^2 + \mathcal{N}^2} , \quad (5.21)$$

where according to (5.18)

$$Y_{l_3 0 0}(\chi) = \frac{1}{R^{3/2} \sqrt{2\pi}} \frac{\sin[(l_3 + 1)\chi]}{\sin \chi} . \quad (5.22)$$

Similarly, one can find the expansion of $G_m^2(\chi)$.

According to (5.17),

$$G_m^2(\chi) = \frac{\sinh^2[\mathcal{N}(\chi - \pi)]}{16\pi^2 R^2 \sinh^2(\pi\mathcal{N}) \sin^2 \chi} . \quad (5.23)$$

Hence, its expansion in terms of spherical harmonics (5.18), is given by

$$G_{l_3}^{(2)}(m^2) = \int_{S^3} Y_{l_3 0 0}(\chi) G_m^2(\chi) = \frac{1}{2^{5/2} \pi^2 R^{1/2} \sinh^2(\pi\mathcal{N})} \times \begin{cases} 2\mathcal{N} \sinh(2\pi\mathcal{N}) \left(\frac{1}{1+4\mathcal{N}^2} + \frac{1}{9+4\mathcal{N}^2} + \dots + \frac{1}{l_3^2+4\mathcal{N}^2} \right) & ; l_3 \text{ odd} \\ -\frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\sinh(2\pi\mathcal{N})}{4} \left(\frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} + \frac{2\mathcal{N}}{1+\mathcal{N}^2} + \frac{2\mathcal{N}}{4+\mathcal{N}^2} + \dots + \frac{2\mathcal{N}}{(l_3/2)^2+\mathcal{N}^2} \right) & ; l_3 \text{ even} \end{cases} \quad (5.24)$$

Using the digamma function, $\psi(x)$, it can be succinctly written as

$$G_{l_3}^{(2)}(m^2) = \frac{1}{2^{7/2} R^{1/2} \pi} \left[1 - i \frac{\coth(\pi\mathcal{N})}{\pi} \left[\psi\left(1 + \frac{l_3}{2} - i\mathcal{N}\right) - \psi\left(1 + \frac{l_3}{2} + i\mathcal{N}\right) \right] \right] . \quad (5.25)$$

The spectral representation (5.14) is equivalent to the spectral representation in the angular momentum space

$$G_{l_3}^{(2)}(m^2) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\mu_\phi^2}^{\infty} d\mu^2 \tilde{\rho}_{\phi^2}(\mu) G_{l_3}(\mu^2) . \quad (5.26)$$

Substituting (5.21) and (5.25), and shifting the integration variable $z = (R\mu)^2 - (R\mu_\phi)^2$, yields

$$\frac{1}{4(l_3 + 1)} \left[1 - i \frac{\coth(\pi\mathcal{N})}{\pi} \left[\psi\left(1 + \frac{l_3}{2} - i\mathcal{N}\right) - \psi\left(1 + \frac{l_3}{2} + i\mathcal{N}\right) \right] \right] = \int_0^{\infty} dz \frac{\tilde{\rho}(z)}{(l_3 + 1)^2 + \mathcal{N}_\phi^2 + z} . \quad (5.27)$$

As expected, the special case of this formula, $l_3 = 0$, matches (5.16).

Before we proceed, let us discuss possible values of μ_ϕ^2 . If $\mu_\phi^2 = 0$ it means that the spectrum of particles starts from a conformally coupled scalar field ($z = 0$ in this case) and

continues all the way up to infinite massive modes ($z = \infty$). However, there is nothing bad about negative μ_ϕ^2 since conformal coupling in the Euclidean action (4.1) may compensate its negativity such that the overall ϕ^2 term is positive. The lowest possible negative value of μ_ϕ^2 is given by $(R\mu_\phi)^2 = -\frac{3}{4}$. It can be read off either from the Euclidean action (4.1), or by setting $z = l_3 = 0$ in the integrand of (5.27) and demanding positivity.

We need to invert (5.27) to get the spectral density $\tilde{\rho}(z)$. For brevity, we define

$$\begin{aligned} z_0 &\equiv (l_3 + 1)^2 + \mathcal{N}_\phi^2 \quad \Rightarrow \quad l_3 = -1 + \sqrt{z_0 - \mathcal{N}_\phi^2}, \\ f(z_0) &\equiv \int_0^\infty dz \frac{\tilde{\rho}(z)}{z_0 + z}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.28)$$

To express $\tilde{\rho}(z)$ in terms of $f(z)$, we first note that by definition

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(-z_0 - i\epsilon) - f(-z_0 + i\epsilon)}{2i} = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_0^\infty dz \tilde{\rho}(z) \frac{\epsilon}{(z - z_0)^2 + \epsilon^2} \quad (5.29)$$

Combining this result with

$$\delta(z - z_0) = \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\epsilon}{(z - z_0)^2 + \epsilon^2}, \quad (5.30)$$

yields,

$$\tilde{\rho}(z) = \frac{1}{\pi} \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{f(-z - i\epsilon) - f(-z + i\epsilon)}{2i}. \quad (5.31)$$

Using now (5.27), (5.28) and the definition of $\tilde{\rho}$, we get,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) &= \frac{\mu R}{2\pi \mathcal{N}_\mu} \left(1 - i \frac{\coth(\pi \mathcal{N})}{2\pi} \left[\psi\left(\frac{1}{2}(1 - i\mathcal{N}_\mu) - i\mathcal{N}\right) - \psi\left(\frac{1}{2}(1 - i\mathcal{N}_\mu) + i\mathcal{N}\right) \right. \right. \\ &\quad \left. \left. + \psi\left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + i\mathcal{N}_\mu) - i\mathcal{N}\right) - \psi\left(\frac{1}{2}(1 + i\mathcal{N}_\mu) + i\mathcal{N}\right) \right] \right) \Theta((\mu R)^2 - 1/4) \end{aligned} \quad (5.32)$$

where $\mathcal{N}_\mu = \sqrt{(\mu R)^2 - 1/4}$. There are certain limits when (5.32) can be checked.

- In the limit of conformally coupled scalar which is also a UV limit, $mR \rightarrow 0$, and we have $\mathcal{N} = \frac{i}{2}$. Hence, in this limit

$$\rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) \xrightarrow{mR \rightarrow 0} \frac{\mu R}{2\pi \sqrt{(\mu R)^2 - 1/4}} \Theta((\mu R)^2 - 1/4). \quad (5.33)$$

and it can be checked by a direct computation that (5.27) holds.

- Flat space limit is recovered if we fix m and μ while $R \rightarrow \infty$, *i.e.*, $R \gg m^{-1}, \mu^{-1}$

$$\rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) \xrightarrow{R \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2\pi} \Theta(\mu - 2m), \quad (5.34)$$

where we used $\psi(x) \sim \log(x)$ for $x \gg 1$. In particular, in accord with [96], we obtain

$$\rho_0(\mu) \xrightarrow{R \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{m}{\mu} \right)^4 \Theta(\mu - 2m). \quad (5.35)$$

Substituting into (5.12) gives $RS'_{\text{EE}} \sim mR \gg 1$. On the other hand, according to (2.10) one expects $RS'_{\text{EE}} = 0$ since $mR \rightarrow \infty$ limit represents deep IR in our setup, which corresponds to an empty theory in this case. This contradiction is, however, apparent. Indeed, R represents the characteristic RG scale and therefore one should only consider $\mu \sim 1/R \ll m$. In this region theta-function and hence ρ_0 vanish. On the other hand, the spectral integral (5.12) accounts for all possible scales including $\mu \gg m$, and therefore RS'_{EE} is contaminated by various terms which are not part of the IR physics.

- It worth noting that in the limit of $\mu R \gg 1$ with m and R fixed, we expect that the spectral function on a sphere asymptotically approaches its counterpart in flat space. Indeed,

$$\rho_{\phi^2}(\mu) \xrightarrow{\mu R \gg 1} \frac{1}{2\pi} . \quad (5.36)$$

6 Discussion

In this paper we study the renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy in an analytically tractable setup - a cap-like entangling region in de Sitter space. Our system has much in common with the indispensable Rindler wedge, *e.g.*, the entangling surface exhibits $O(2)$ symmetry in the transverse space, and the corresponding entanglement entropy equals thermal entropy for *any* QFT. However, in contrast to the Rindler space, where the geometry is flat and there is no characteristic temperature, in our setup the background curvature does not vanish, and it sets a characteristic length scale, R , for both the curvature of the entangling surface and temperature of the environment.

Since there is only one global geometric scale, it also effectively determines the mass scale of RG running to be of order $1/R$. In particular, studies of RG flow boil down to a constant Weyl rescaling of the background geometry. From this perspective, our setup is scalable [26], and we argue that EE satisfies the following RG equation

$$R \frac{dS_{\text{EE}}}{dR} = -\frac{V_{S^d}}{d} R \frac{d}{dR} \langle T^\mu_\mu \rangle , \quad (6.1)$$

with V_{S^d} being the volume of a d -dimensional sphere.

The above simple relation between the entanglement entropy flow and trace of the energy-momentum tensor allows to analytically explore various properties of the entanglement entropy running when the system flows between the UV and IR fixed points.

In section 4 we scrutinize the RG flows of EE in $d = 2, 3, 4$ for a conformally coupled scalar field deformed by a mass operator. In $d = 3$ our findings indicate that the renormalized entanglement entropy defined in [26, 28, 54] exhibits stationarity at the fixed points on a sphere, but it is not monotonic along the RG trajectory. This result is completely opposite to the behaviour of REE in Minkowski space, where it has been shown that REE is monotonic [54], but not stationary [69].

Lack of monotonicity may result from various causes. For instance, REE in de Sitter space receives thermal corrections which are absent in Minkowski space. Furthermore, absence of IR divergences in a QFT living on a sphere might be another plausible explanation for a qualitative difference in the behaviour of REE on de Sitter and on Minkowski space. That being said these arguments are unlikely to explain the discrepancies in the behaviour of REE in the vicinity of UV fixed point, since in the deep UV both the curvature and temperature of de Sitter space are irrelevant.

Moreover, our calculations reveal another interesting and closely related result. We find that the universal ‘area law’ for a conformally coupled scalar field is different from the known expression in Minkowski space [71–73]. This discrepancy cannot be attributed to a curved geometry since the universal ‘area law’ depends solely on the area of entangling surface. This observation raises a controversial [15, 33, 36, 74–78] question whether there exists any difference between the universal entanglement entropies for minimally and conformally coupled scalar fields in *flat* space. Possible explanation and interpretation of this phenomenon can be found in [79] and [56, 62, 80], see also [33] for interpretation based on calculations of the mutual information in Minkowski space. Our findings here point out in favour of the difference between the minimally and conformally coupled scalar fields in the limit of flat space.

In section 5 we derive the spectral representation of entanglement entropy flow. The final expression (5.12) depends on a specific spectral function which determines the spin-0 part of a two-point function of the energy-momentum tensor [81]. Reflection positivity ensures that the spectral function is positive, and therefore (5.12) suggests that the rate of change of entanglement entropy along the RG trajectory is negative provided that the integral on the right hand side converges. In particular, it implies $S_{EE}^{UV} \geq S_{EE}^{IR}$ for a finite part of EE in $d = 3$.

Obviously, this inequality is not the same as (4.15), and therefore it does not prove the F -theorem [52, 53] in three dimensions. To understand the difference between the two inequalities, it is enough to consider the universal ‘area law’ for a massive free field, see Appendix A. In $d = 3$ it represents a finite contribution to EE which grows linearly in the IR limit. Since massive degrees of freedom decouple in the deep IR, the universal ‘area law’ becomes part of the UV physics, and therefore it should be subtracted to isolate a ‘true’ universal entanglement entropy in this limit.

Of course, IR entanglement entropy may contain all kind of finite terms associated with the fingerprints of UV physics. Such remnants of the RG trajectory should be subtracted to extract the universal piece. REE is a particular subtraction scheme which proved to be effective in building a c -function in Minkowski space [54]. However, we have shown that it is not as good on a sphere. Unfortunately, we were not able to identify a reasonable candidate for a c -function on a sphere. Thermodynamic inequalities might be a good source to look for plausible candidates, *e.g.*, the generalized second law is one such example [97]. We will explore this avenue elsewhere.

Acknowledgments

We thank Igor Klebanov, Robert C. Myers and Vladimir Rosenhaus for helpful discussions. The work of MS is supported in part by NSF Grant PHY-1214644 and the Berkeley Center for Theoretical Physics. The work of OB and DC is partially supported by the Israel Science Foundation (grant 1989/14), the US-Israel bi-national fund (BSF) grant 2012383 and the German Israel bi-national fund GIF grant number I-244-303.7-2013.

A Universal area law

It has been shown in [33, 62] that variation of the entanglement entropy with respect to the relevant coupling can be expressed in terms of a particular structure in the spectral decomposition of the energy-momentum tensor

$$\lambda \frac{\partial S_{EE}}{\partial \lambda} = \frac{-4\pi \Omega_{d-1} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma}{2^d (d - \Delta - \beta_\lambda) (d-1) (d+1) \Gamma(d)} \int_0^\infty d\mu c^{(0)}(\mu), \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where $c^{(0)}(\mu)$ is the spectral function which corresponds to spin $s = 0$ states in Minkowski space [96]. For free conformally coupled scalar and Dirac fermion, we have [96]

$$\begin{aligned} c_F^{(0)}(\mu) &= 2^{[d/2]} \frac{2(d+1)(d-1)}{\Omega_{d-1}^2} m^2 \mu^{d-5} \left(1 - \frac{4m^2}{\mu^2}\right)^{(d-1)/2} \Theta(\mu - 2m), \\ c_S^{(0)}(\mu) &= \frac{8(d+1)(d-1)}{\Omega_{d-1}^2} m^4 \mu^{d-7} \left(1 - \frac{4m^2}{\mu^2}\right)^{(d-3)/2} \Theta(\mu - 2m). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Substituting into (A.1), and using dimensional regularization, yields

$$m \frac{\partial S_{EE}^{\text{Dirac}}}{\partial m} = -\frac{2^{[d/2]} \Gamma\left(\frac{4-d}{2}\right)}{12 (4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$m^2 \frac{\partial S_{EE}^{\text{scalar}}}{\partial m^2} = \frac{(d-4)}{24(d-1)} \frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{4-d}{2}\right)}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

Hence, we get

$$m \frac{\partial S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}}}{\partial m} = \begin{cases} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d}{2}} (d-2)}{6(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} \log(m\delta) & \text{for even } d, \\ \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} \pi (d-2)}{12\sqrt{2}(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} & \text{for odd } d, \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

where simple pole in the gamma function is identified with $\log(m\delta)$ ²⁵.

Similarly for the conformally coupled scalar,

$$m^2 \frac{\partial S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}}}{\partial m^2} = \begin{cases} \frac{(d-2)(d-4)}{24(d-1)} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d}{2}+1}}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} \log(m\delta) & \text{for even } d, \\ \frac{(d-2)(d-4)}{48(d-1)} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d+1}{2}} \pi}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \mathcal{A}_\Sigma m^{d-2} & \text{for odd } d. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

²⁵To establish this dictionary, it is enough to introduce a sharp cut off $\mu_{\text{max}} = 1/\delta$ in (A.1).

Note that this result is different from the universal ‘area law’ for minimally coupled scalar field [71–73],

$$m^2 \frac{\partial S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}}}{\partial m^2} = \begin{cases} \frac{(d-2)}{12} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d}{2}}}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} A_{\Sigma} m^{d-2} \log(m\delta) & \text{for even } d, \\ \frac{(d-2)}{24} \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} \pi}{(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} A_{\Sigma} m^{d-2} & \text{for odd } d. \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

B Free fields on a deformed waveguide

In this Appendix we perform an independent computation of the leading curvature correction displayed in (4.17) and (4.49). To this end one can resort to the replica trick [7, 11, 98, 99] combined with the heat kernel technique, see *e.g.*, [100]. Indeed, rotational symmetry around the entangling surface makes it possible to introduce a well-defined conical defect [51, 70, 78]. However, we choose to follow a different approach [61], where a special role played by the neighbourhood of the entangling surface is made manifest.

Recall that divergences of the entanglement entropy are local and dominated by the region near the entangling surface. In particular, to recover (4.17) and (4.49) it is enough to explore our metric (2.5) in the vicinity of the entangling surface at $\theta = \pi/2$

$$ds^2 = (1 - \frac{r^2}{3R^2} + \dots)r^2 d\tau^2 + R^2 d\theta^2 + (1 - \frac{r^2}{R^2} + \dots)R^2 d\Omega_{d-2}^2, \quad (\text{B.1})$$

where $r \equiv R(\theta - \pi/2)$. To leading order in the radial distance r , the geometry can be approximated by a waveguide with spherical cross-section $R^2 \times S^{d-2}$, whereas subleading terms can be treated as perturbations.

In Cartesian coordinates $x^1 = r \cos \theta$, $x^2 = r \sin \theta$, the expansion of the metric takes the form

$$ds^2 = (1 - \frac{1}{3}\mathcal{R}_{abcd}x^b x^d + \dots)dx^a dx^c + (\gamma_{ij} + \mathcal{R}_{iacj}x^a x^c + \dots)dy^i dy^j, \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where ellipsis encode higher derivative terms which are irrelevant for our needs, $\{y^i\}_{i=1}^{d-2}$ and γ_{ij} are coordinates and induced metric on S^{d-2} respectively, and $\mathcal{R}_{\mu\nu\sigma\rho}$ is the Riemann curvature tensor on S^d

$$\mathcal{R}_{\mu\nu\rho\sigma} = \frac{1}{R^2}(g_{\mu\rho}g_{\nu\sigma} - g_{\mu\sigma}g_{\nu\rho}). \quad (\text{B.3})$$

Of course, for a generic entangling surface (B.2) contains terms with extrinsic curvatures [16, 61, 101–104],²⁶ however in our setup they vanish due to rotational symmetry around Σ .

Next we observe that the curvature terms in (B.2) are small close to the entangling surface ($x^a = 0$) where the divergences are localized, and therefore we treat them as perturbations, $h_{\mu\nu}$, of the waveguide geometry, see [61] for details. In particular, it follows from (2.8) that linear correction to the entanglement entropy takes the form

$$\delta S_{\text{EE}} = \frac{1}{2} \int d^2 x \int d^{d-2} y \sqrt{\gamma} \langle T^{\mu\nu}(x, y) K \rangle h_{\mu\nu}(x, y) + \mathcal{O}(h^2). \quad (\text{B.4})$$

²⁶See also critique of [103, 104] in [105].

Only universal divergences of the above expression can be taken at face value, otherwise there is no reason to expect that higher order terms in $h_{\mu\nu}$ do not contribute.

Now the first term within parenthesis in (4.17), (4.49) represents the universal ‘area law’ [71–73], see also [33, 62] and Appendix A. This term is entirely encoded in the leading order entanglement entropy, whereas δS_{EE} contributes to the second term in (4.17), (4.49) which is proportional to the Riemann tensor. Given that $h_{\mu\nu}$ is also proportional to the Riemann tensor, we can replace $\langle T^{\mu\nu} K \rangle$ by its flat space counterpart without losing contributions to (4.17), (4.49), then according to [62]

$$\begin{aligned} \delta S_{\text{EE}} &= \frac{\pi \Omega_{d-1}}{2^{d-2}(d-1)^2(d+1)\Gamma(d)} \int_{\Sigma} \left(\delta^{ac} \delta^{ij} \mathcal{R}_{iajc} + \frac{1}{2} \delta^{ac} \delta^{bd} \mathcal{R}_{abcd} \right) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{d\mu}{\mu^2} c^{(0)}(\mu) \quad (\text{B.5}) \\ &+ \frac{\pi \Omega_{d-1}}{2^{d-2}(d-1)(d+1)\Gamma(d)} \int_{\Sigma} \left(\frac{d-2}{2} \delta^{ac} \delta^{bd} \mathcal{R}_{abcd} - \delta^{ac} \delta^{ij} \mathcal{R}_{iajc} \right) \int_0^{\infty} \frac{d\mu}{\mu^2} c^{(2)}(\mu), \end{aligned}$$

where $c^{(0)}(\mu)$ and $c^{(2)}(\mu)$ are two spectral functions which define a two point function of the energy-momentum tensor for a generic QFT in Minkowski space [96]. For free fields $c^{(0)}(\mu)$ is given by (A.2), whereas $c^{(2)}(\mu)$ reads [96]

$$\begin{aligned} c_F^{(2)}(\mu) &= 2^{[d/2]} \frac{(d-1)}{2\Omega_{d-1}^2} \mu^{d-3} \left(1 - \frac{4m^2}{\mu^2} \right)^{(d-1)/2} \left(1 + \frac{2}{d-1} \frac{4m^2}{\mu^2} \right) \Theta(\mu - 2m), \\ c_S^{(2)}(\mu) &= \frac{\mu^{d-3}}{\Omega_{d-1}^2} \left(1 - \frac{4m^2}{\mu^2} \right)^{(d+1)/2} \Theta(\mu - 2m). \quad (\text{B.6}) \end{aligned}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \delta S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}} &= \frac{(-)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} (d-2)(-76 + 84d - 25d^2 + 2d^3)}{240(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} (d-1)^2 \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \frac{A_{\Sigma} m^{d-4}}{R^2} \log(m\delta), \\ \delta S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}} &= \frac{(-)^{\frac{d}{2}} (d-2)(d-3)}{60(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \frac{A_{\Sigma} m^{d-4}}{R^2} \log(m\delta), \quad (\text{B.7}) \end{aligned}$$

where we introduced a UV cut off $\mu_{\text{max}} \sim 1/\delta$. This contribution should be combined with the leading order entanglement entropy. To leading order the geometry is identical to a waveguide with spherical cross-section, and therefore for Dirac fermion we can use the results of [73]

$$S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}} \Big|_{R^2 \times S^{d-2}} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}} A_{\Sigma}}{6(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \left(m^{d-2} + \frac{(d-2)^2(d-3)}{24} \frac{m^{d-4}}{R^2} + \dots \right) \log(m\delta), \quad (\text{B.8})$$

while for conformally coupled scalar, the result reads²⁷

$$S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}} \Big|_{R^2 \times S^{d-2}} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}} (1 - 6\xi_c) A_{\Sigma}}{6(4\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \left(m^{d-2} - \frac{(d-2)^2(d-3)(1 - 6\xi_c)}{12} \frac{m^{d-4}}{R^2} + \dots \right) \log(m\delta), \quad (\text{B.11})$$

²⁷Entanglement entropy of a scalar field on a waveguide geometry was studied in [73] using the heat kernel methods. In particular, the authors apply the same heat kernel, K_{C_n} , on a two-dimensional cone, C_n , with an angular excess $2\pi(n-1)$ to evaluate entanglement entropy for both minimally and non-minimally

Combining altogether, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}} &= S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}} \Big|_{R^2 \times S^{d-2}} + \delta S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{scalar}} = \frac{(d_0 - 4)}{12(d-1)} \frac{(-)^{d_0/2+1} A_\Sigma}{(4\pi)^{(d_0-2)/2} \Gamma\left(\frac{d_0}{2}\right)} \\
&\quad \times \left(m^{d_0-2} + \frac{(d_0-2)(d_0-6)(5d_0^2-18d_0+4)}{120(d-4)} \frac{m^{d_0-4}}{R^2} \right) \log(m\delta) , \\
S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}} &= S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}} \Big|_{R^2 \times S^{d-2}} + \delta S_{\text{univ}}^{\text{Dirac}} \tag{B.12} \\
&= \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}} A_\Sigma}{6(2\pi)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2}\right)} \left(m^{d-2} + \frac{(d-2)(d-3)(5d+2)}{120} \frac{m^{d-4}}{R^2} + \dots \right) \log(m\delta) ,
\end{aligned}$$

in full agreement with (4.17), (4.49).

C Addition theorem for spherical harmonics on S^3

In this appendix we review the proof of the following useful mathematical result

$$Y_{l_3 0 0}(\gamma) = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{l_3 + 1} \sum_{l_2=0}^{l_3} \sum_{l_1=-l_2}^{l_2} Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}^*(y) Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(x) \quad , \tag{C.1}$$

where x, y are two arbitrary points on S^3 and γ is an angle between them. This identity is called the addition theorem for spherical harmonics.

Any function $f(x)$ on S^3 can be expanded as follows

$$f(x) = \sum_{l_3=0}^{\infty} \sum_{l_2=0}^{l_3} \sum_{l_1=-l_2}^{l_2} A_{l_3 l_2 l_1} Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(x) \quad , \quad A_{l_3 l_2 l_1} = \int_x Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}^*(x) f(x) \quad . \tag{C.2}$$

If we set $\chi = 0$ then according to (5.18), (5.19) only terms with $l_2 = 0 \Rightarrow l_1 = 0$ contribute

$$f(x)|_{\chi=0} = \sum_{l_3=0}^{\infty} A_{l_3 0 0} \frac{l_3 + 1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \quad , \quad A_{l_3 0 0} = \int_x Y_{l_3 0 0}(x) f(x) \quad . \tag{C.3}$$

On the other hand, expanding $Y_{l_3 0 0}(\gamma)$ in spherical harmonics and taking into account that it is a spherical harmonic of order l_3 , yields

$$Y_{l_3 0 0}(\gamma) = \sum_{l_2=0}^{l_3} \sum_{l_1=-l_2}^{l_2} A_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(y) Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(x) \quad , \quad A_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(y) = \int_x Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}^*(x) Y_{l_3 0 0}(\gamma) \quad . \tag{C.4}$$

coupled scalar fields. However, to get (B.11) we make use of the following expression

$$\text{Tr} K_{\mathcal{C}_n}(t) = \frac{(1-n)}{6} (1-6\xi) + n \text{Tr} K_{R^2}(t) + \mathcal{O}(1-n)^2 \quad , \tag{B.9}$$

where ξ represents a non-minimal coupling to the background curvature. To derive it, there is no need to find or use the exact solution [106–108] to the heat kernel equation on a cone. Instead, one can use the general form of the heat kernel expansion in the vicinity of $t = 0$ [100], and substitute curvature scalar on \mathcal{C}_n

$$\mathcal{R} = 4\pi(1-n)\delta_\Sigma + \mathcal{O}(1-n)^2 \quad , \tag{B.10}$$

where δ_Σ is a two-dimensional δ -function supported on Σ .

$A_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(y)$ can be viewed as $A_{l_3 00}$ coefficient in an expansion of $Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}^*(x)$ in a series of $Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(\gamma)$ referred to the axis y . From (C.3) it is then found that, since only one l_3 is present this coefficient is given by

$$A_{l_3 l_2 l_1}(y) = \frac{\sqrt{2\pi}}{l_3 + 1} Y_{l_3 l_2 l_1}^*(y) \quad , \quad (\text{C.5})$$

from which (C.1) follows.

References

- [1] A. Kitaev and J. Preskill, “Topological entanglement entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **96** (2006) 110404, [arXiv:hep-th/0510092](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [2] M. Levin and X.-G. Wen, “Detecting topological order in a ground state wave function,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96** (Mar, 2006) 110405. <http://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.96.110405>.
- [3] B. Hsu, M. Mulligan, E. Fradkin, and E.-A. Kim, “Universal entanglement entropy in two-dimensional conformal quantum critical points,” *Phys. Rev. B* **79** (Mar, 2009) 115421. <http://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevB.79.115421>.
- [4] T. Grover, A. M. Turner, and A. Vishwanath, “Entanglement Entropy of Gapped Phases and Topological Order in Three dimensions,” *Phys.Rev.* **B84** (2011) 195120, [arXiv:1108.4038](#) [[cond-mat.str-el](#)].
- [5] M. Srednicki, “Entropy and area,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **71** (1993) 666–669, [arXiv:hep-th/9303048](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [6] C. Holzhey, F. Larsen, and F. Wilczek, “Geometric and renormalized entropy in conformal field theory,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B424** (1994) 443–467, [arXiv:hep-th/9403108](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [7] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory,” *J.Stat.Mech.* **0406** (2004) P06002, [arXiv:hep-th/0405152](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [8] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “Entanglement entropy in free quantum field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504007, [arXiv:0905.2562](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [9] P. Calabrese and J. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and conformal field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504005, [arXiv:0905.4013](#) [[cond-mat.stat-mech](#)].
- [10] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, “A Quantum Source of Entropy for Black Holes,” *Phys.Rev.* **D34** (1986) 373–383.
- [11] J. Callan, Curtis G. and F. Wilczek, “On geometric entropy,” *Phys.Lett.* **B333** (1994) 55–61, [arXiv:hep-th/9401072](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [12] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [arXiv:hep-th/0603001](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [13] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **0608** (2006) 045, [arXiv:hep-th/0605073](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [14] V. E. Hubeny, M. Rangamani, and T. Takayanagi, “A Covariant holographic entanglement entropy proposal,” *JHEP* **0707** (2007) 062, [arXiv:0705.0016](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [15] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy of black holes,” *Living Rev.Rel.* **14** (2011) 8, [arXiv:1104.3712](#) [[hep-th](#)].

- [16] A. Lewkowycz and J. Maldacena, “Generalized gravitational entropy,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 090, [arXiv:1304.4926 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [17] T. Faulkner, A. Lewkowycz, and J. Maldacena, “Quantum corrections to holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1311** (2013) 074, [arXiv:1307.2892](#).
- [18] T. Faulkner, M. Guica, T. Hartman, R. C. Myers, and M. Van Raamsdonk, “Gravitation from Entanglement in Holographic CFTs,” *JHEP* **1403** (2014) 051, [arXiv:1312.7856 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [19] R. Bousso, H. Casini, Z. Fisher, and J. Maldacena, “Proof of a Quantum Bousso Bound,” *Phys.Rev.* **D90** no. 4, (2014) 044002, [arXiv:1404.5635 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [20] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and J. Sonnenschein, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips,” *JHEP* **1411** (2014) 144, [arXiv:1409.6305 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [21] N. Engelhardt and A. C. Wall, “Quantum Extremal Surfaces: Holographic Entanglement Entropy beyond the Classical Regime,” *JHEP* **1501** (2015) 073, [arXiv:1408.3203 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [22] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “A Finite entanglement entropy and the c-theorem,” *Phys.Lett.* **B600** (2004) 142–150, [arXiv:hep-th/0405111 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [23] R. C. Myers and A. Sinha, “Seeing a c-theorem with holography,” *Phys.Rev.* **D82** (2010) 046006, [arXiv:1006.1263 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [24] R. C. Myers and A. Sinha, “Holographic c-theorems in arbitrary dimensions,” *JHEP* **1101** (2011) 125, [arXiv:1011.5819 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [25] R. C. Myers and A. Singh, “Comments on Holographic Entanglement Entropy and RG Flows,” *JHEP* **1204** (2012) 122, [arXiv:1202.2068 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [26] H. Liu and M. Mezei, “A Refinement of entanglement entropy and the number of degrees of freedom,” *JHEP* **1304** (2013) 162, [arXiv:1202.2070 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [27] S. N. Solodukhin, “The a-theorem and entanglement entropy,” [arXiv:1304.4411 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [28] H. Liu and M. Mezei, “Probing renormalization group flows using entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1401** (2014) 098, [arXiv:1309.6935 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [29] S. Banerjee, A. Bhattacharyya, A. Kaviraj, K. Sen, and A. Sinha, “Constraining gravity using entanglement in AdS/CFT,” *JHEP* **1405** (2014) 029, [arXiv:1401.5089 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [30] S. N. Solodukhin, “Conformal a-charge, correlation functions and conical defects,” *Phys.Lett.* **B736** (2014) 283–287, [arXiv:1406.5368 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [31] T. Kawano, Y. Nakaguchi, and T. Nishioka, “Holographic Interpolation between a and F ,” *JHEP* **1412** (2014) 161, [arXiv:1410.5973 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [32] V. Balasubramanian, J. J. Heckman, and A. Maloney, “Relative Entropy and Proximity of Quantum Field Theories,” [arXiv:1410.6809 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [33] H. Casini, F. Mazzitelli, and E. T. Lino, “Area terms in entanglement entropy,” [arXiv:1412.6522 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [34] M. Nozaki, T. Numasawa, and T. Takayanagi, “Quantum Entanglement of Local Operators in Conformal Field Theories,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **112** (2014) 111602, [arXiv:1401.0539 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [35] J. Cardy and C. P. Herzog, “Universal Thermal Corrections to Single Interval Entanglement Entropy for Two Dimensional Conformal Field Theories,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **112** no. 17, (2014) 171603, [arXiv:1403.0578 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [36] C. P. Herzog, “Universal Thermal Corrections to Entanglement Entropy for Conformal Field Theories on Spheres,” *JHEP* **1410** (2014) 28, [arXiv:1407.1358 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [37] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Twist operators in higher dimensions,” *JHEP* **1410** (2014) 178, [arXiv:1407.6429 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [38] T. Faulkner, “Bulk Emergence and the RG Flow of Entanglement Entropy,” [arXiv:1412.5648 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [39] M. Goykhman, “On entanglement entropy in ’t Hooft model,” [arXiv:1501.07590 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [40] X. Huang, L.-Y. Hung, and F.-L. Lin, “OPE of the stress tensors and surface operators,” [arXiv:1502.02487 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [41] R.-X. Miao, “Universal Terms of Entanglement Entropy for 6d CFTs,” [arXiv:1503.05538 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [42] A. Zamolodchikov, “Irreversibility of the Flux of the Renormalization Group in a 2D Field Theory,” *JETP Lett.* **43** (1986) 730–732.
- [43] J. L. Cardy, “Is There a c Theorem in Four-Dimensions?,” *Phys.Lett.* **B215** (1988) 749–752.
- [44] Z. Komargodski and A. Schwimmer, “On Renormalization Group Flows in Four Dimensions,” *JHEP* **1112** (2011) 099, [arXiv:1107.3987 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [45] Z. Komargodski, “The Constraints of Conformal Symmetry on RG Flows,” *JHEP* **1207** (2012) 069, [arXiv:1112.4538 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [46] M. A. Luty, J. Polchinski, and R. Rattazzi, “The a -theorem and the Asymptotics of 4D Quantum Field Theory,” *JHEP* **1301** (2013) 152, [arXiv:1204.5221 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [47] H. Elvang, D. Z. Freedman, L.-Y. Hung, M. Kiermaier, R. C. Myers, *et al.*, “On renormalization group flows and the a -theorem in 6d,” *JHEP* **1210** (2012) 011, [arXiv:1205.3994 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [48] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy, conformal invariance and extrinsic geometry,” *Phys.Lett.* **B665** (2008) 305–309, [arXiv:0802.3117 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [49] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “Entanglement entropy for a Maxwell field: Numerical calculation on a two dimensional lattice,” [arXiv:1406.2991 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [50] H. Casini, M. Huerta, and R. C. Myers, “Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1105** (2011) 036, [arXiv:1102.0440 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [51] J. Dowker, “Entanglement entropy for odd spheres,” [arXiv:1012.1548 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [52] D. L. Jafferis, I. R. Klebanov, S. S. Pufu, and B. R. Safdi, “Towards the F-Theorem: $N=2$ Field Theories on the Three-Sphere,” *JHEP* **1106** (2011) 102, [arXiv:1103.1181 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [53] I. R. Klebanov, S. S. Pufu, and B. R. Safdi, “F-Theorem without Supersymmetry,” *JHEP* **1110** (2011) 038, [arXiv:1105.4598 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [54] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “On the RG running of the entanglement entropy of a circle,” *Phys.Rev.* **D85** (2012) 125016, [arXiv:1202.5650 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [55] E. Lieb and M. Ruskai, “Proof of the strong subadditivity of quantum-mechanical entropy,” *J.Math.Phys.* **14** (1973) 1938–1941.
- [56] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy for Relevant and Geometric Perturbations,” *JHEP* **1502** (2015) 015, [arXiv:1410.6530 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [57] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy Flow and the Ward Identity,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **113** no. 26, (2014) 261602, [arXiv:1406.2716 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [58] J. J. Bisognano and E. H. Wichmann, “On the duality condition for a Hermitian scalar field,” *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **16** no. 4, (1975) .
- [59] J. J. Bisognano and E. H. Wichmann, “On the duality condition for quantum fields,” *Journal of Mathematical Physics* **17** no. 3, (1976) .
- [60] D. N. Kabat and M. Strassler, “A Comment on entropy and area,” *Phys.Lett.* **B329** (1994) 46–52, [arXiv:hep-th/9401125 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [61] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy: A Perturbative Calculation,” *JHEP* **1412** (2014) 179, [arXiv:1403.3733 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [62] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement entropy, planar surfaces, and spectral functions,” *JHEP* **1409** (2014) 119, [arXiv:1407.2891 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [63] S. Banerjee, “Wess-Zumino Consistency Condition for Entanglement Entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **109** (2012) 010402, [arXiv:1109.5672 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [64] A. Allais and M. Mezei, “Some results on the shape dependence of entanglement and Rényi entropies,” [arXiv:1407.7249 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [65] M. Mezei, “Entanglement entropy across a deformed sphere,” [arXiv:1411.7011 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [66] A. Lewkowycz and E. Perlmutter, “Universality in the geometric dependence of Rényi entropy,” [arXiv:1407.8171 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [67] J. Maldacena and G. L. Pimentel, “Entanglement entropy in de Sitter space,” *JHEP* **1302** (2013) 038, [arXiv:1210.7244 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [68] W. Fischler, S. Kundu, and J. F. Pedraza, “Entanglement and out-of-equilibrium dynamics in holographic models of de Sitter QFTs,” *JHEP* **1407** (2014) 021, [arXiv:1311.5519 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [69] I. R. Klebanov, T. Nishioka, S. S. Pufu, and B. R. Safdi, “Is Renormalized Entanglement Entropy Stationary at RG Fixed Points?,” *JHEP* **1210** (2012) 058, [arXiv:1207.3360 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [70] J. Dowker, “Sphere Rényi entropies,” *J.Phys.* **A46** (2013) 225401, [arXiv:1212.2098 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [71] M. P. Hertzberg and F. Wilczek, “Some Calculable Contributions to Entanglement Entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **106** (2011) 050404, [arXiv:1007.0993 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [72] M. Huerta, “Numerical Determination of the Entanglement Entropy for Free Fields in the Cylinder,” *Phys.Lett.* **B710** (2012) 691–696, [arXiv:1112.1277 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [73] A. Lewkowycz, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Observations on entanglement entropy in massive QFT’s,” *JHEP* **1304** (2013) 017, [arXiv:1210.6858 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [74] S. N. Solodukhin, “Nonminimal coupling and quantum entropy of black hole,” *Phys.Rev.* **D56** (1997) 4968–4974, [arXiv:hep-th/9612061 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [75] M. Hotta, T. Kato, and K. Nagata, “A Comment on geometric entropy and conical space,” *Class.Quant.Grav.* **14** (1997) 1917–1925, [arXiv:gr-qc/9611058 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [76] T. Nishioka, “Relevant Perturbation of Entanglement Entropy and Stationarity,” *Phys.Rev.* **D90** (2014) 045006, [arXiv:1405.3650 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [77] J. Lee, A. Lewkowycz, E. Perlmutter, and B. R. Safdi, “Renyi entropy, stationarity, and entanglement of the conformal scalar,” [arXiv:1407.7816 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [78] J. Dowker, “Expansion of Rényi entropy for free scalar fields,” [arXiv:1408.4055 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [79] R. C. Myers, V. Rosenhaus, and M. Smolkin. in progress.
- [80] F. Larsen and F. Wilczek, “Renormalization of black hole entropy and of the gravitational coupling constant,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B458** (1996) 249–266, [arXiv:hep-th/9506066 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [81] H. Osborn and G. Shore, “Correlation functions of the energy momentum tensor on spaces of constant curvature,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B571** (2000) 287–357, [arXiv:hep-th/9909043 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [82] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Some Calculable Contributions to Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1108** (2011) 039, [arXiv:1105.6055 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [83] D. Marolf, D. Minic, and S. F. Ross, “Notes on space-time thermodynamics and the observer dependence of entropy,” *Phys.Rev.* **D69** (2004) 064006, [arXiv:hep-th/0310022 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [84] J. Bhattacharya, M. Nozaki, T. Takayanagi, and T. Ugajin, “Thermodynamical Property of Entanglement Entropy for Excited States,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **110** no. 9, (2013) 091602, [arXiv:1212.1164](#).
- [85] D. D. Blanco, H. Casini, L.-Y. Hung, and R. C. Myers, “Relative Entropy and Holography,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 060, [arXiv:1305.3182 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [86] G. Wong, I. Klich, L. A. Pando Zayas, and D. Vaman, “Entanglement Temperature and Entanglement Entropy of Excited States,” *JHEP* **1312** (2013) 020, [arXiv:1305.3291 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [87] D. Allahbakhshi, M. Alishahiha, and A. Naseh, “Entanglement Thermodynamics,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 102, [arXiv:1305.2728 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [88] M. Smolkin and S. N. Solodukhin, “Correlation functions on conical defects,” *Phys.Rev.* **D91** no. 4, (2015) 044008, [arXiv:1406.2512 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [89] H. Osborn and A. Petkou, “Implications of conformal invariance in field theories for general dimensions,” *Annals Phys.* **231** (1994) 311–362, [arXiv:hep-th/9307010 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [90] E. Bianchi and R. C. Myers, “On the Architecture of Spacetime Geometry,” *Class.Quant.Grav.* **31** no. 21, (2014) 214002, [arXiv:1212.5183 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [91] S. Forte and J. I. Latorre, “A Proof of the irreversibility of renormalization group flows in four-dimensions,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B535** (1998) 709–728, [arXiv:hep-th/9805015 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [92] L. S. Brown and J. C. Collins, “Dimensional Renormalization of Scalar Field Theory in Curved Space-time,” *Annals Phys.* **130** (1980) 215.
- [93] L. S. Brown, “Stress Tensor Trace Anomaly in a Gravitational Metric: Scalar Fields,” *Phys.Rev.* **D15** (1977) 1469.

- [94] R. Camporesi, “The Spinor heat kernel in maximally symmetric spaces,” *Commun.Math.Phys.* **148** (1992) 283–308.
- [95] A. Higuchi, “Symmetric Tensor Spherical Harmonics on the N Sphere and Their Application to the De Sitter Group $SO(N,1)$,” *J.Math.Phys.* **28** (1987) 1553.
- [96] A. Cappelli, D. Friedan, and J. I. Latorre, “C theorem and spectral representation,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B352** (1991) 616–670.
- [97] A. C. Wall, “Ten Proofs of the Generalized Second Law,” *JHEP* **0906** (2009) 021, [arXiv:0901.3865 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [98] D. V. Fursaev and S. N. Solodukhin, “On the description of the Riemannian geometry in the presence of conical defects,” *Phys.Rev.* **D52** (1995) 2133–2143, [arXiv:hep-th/9501127 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [99] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory: A Non-technical introduction,” *Int.J.Quant.Inf.* **4** (2006) 429, [arXiv:quant-ph/0505193 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [100] D. Vassilevich, “Heat kernel expansion: User’s manual,” *Phys.Rept.* **388** (2003) 279–360, [arXiv:hep-th/0306138 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [101] D. V. Fursaev, A. Patrushev, and S. N. Solodukhin, “Distributional Geometry of Squashed Cones,” *Phys.Rev.* **D88** no. 4, (2013) 044054, [arXiv:1306.4000 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [102] A. Bhattacharyya, M. Sharma, and A. Sinha, “On generalized gravitational entropy, squashed cones and holography,” *JHEP* **1401** (2014) 021, [arXiv:1308.5748 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [103] X. Dong, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy for General Higher Derivative Gravity,” *JHEP* **1401** (2014) 044, [arXiv:1310.5713 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [104] J. Camps, “Generalized entropy and higher derivative Gravity,” *JHEP* **1403** (2014) 070, [arXiv:1310.6659 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [105] A. Bhattacharyya and M. Sharma, “On entanglement entropy functionals in higher derivative gravity theories,” *JHEP* **1410** (2014) 130, [arXiv:1405.3511 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [106] J. Dowker, “Quantum Field Theory on a Cone,” *J.Phys.* **A10** (1977) 115–124.
- [107] J. Dowker, “Vacuum Averages for Arbitrary Spin Around a Cosmic String,” *Phys.Rev.* **D36** (1987) 3742.
- [108] S. Deser and R. Jackiw, “Classical and Quantum Scattering on a Cone,” *Commun.Math.Phys.* **118** (1988) 495.

Chapter 5

On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy

On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy

Dean Carmi

Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences School of Physics and Astronomy Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel

E-mail: deancarmi1@gmail.com

ABSTRACT: We study the shape dependence of entanglement entropy (EE) by deforming symmetric entangling surfaces. We show that entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry extremize (locally) the EE with respect to shape deformations that break some of the symmetry (i.e. the 1st order correction vanishes). This result applies to EE and Renyi entropy for any QFT in any dimension. Using Solodukhin's formula in $4d$ and holography in any d , we calculate the 2nd order correction to the universal EE for CFTs and simple symmetric entangling surfaces. In all cases we find that the 2nd order correction is positive, and thus the corresponding symmetric entangling surface is a local minimum. Some of the results are extended to free massive fields and to $4d$ Renyi entropy.

Contents

1	Introduction	1
2	The First Order Correction: Stationarity	4
3	The Second Order Correction in Holography	5
3.1	Cylinder Entangling Surface	6
3.2	Plane Entangling Surface	8
4	The Second Order Correction in Field theory	9
4.1	4d CFT: Solodukhin's Formula	9
4.2	Renyi Entropy	13
4.3	Free Massive Fields	13
5	Discussion	14
A	Equations of Motion for the Minimal Bulk Surface	16
A.1	Strip Entangling Surface	16
A.2	Plane Entangling Surface	17
A.3	Cylinder Entangling Surface	18

1 Introduction

Entanglement entropy is a measure of the quantum correlations of a system. It has a very wide range of applications from condensed matter physics to quantum field theory [1–33] and AdS/CFT [35–62]. The EE in QFT is generally hard to calculate, and most computations have been done in simple setups, such as: free fields, CFTs, and symmetric entangling surfaces (e.g. spheres and planes). Thus there is a need to obtain analytical results for interacting theories, non-CFTs, and less symmetrical entangling surfaces. This work aims to make a step in this direction by studying the shape dependence of EE. Previous works on the shape dependence of EE include [63–81].

The divergent structure of entanglement entropy for a CFT in d -dimensions is:

$$S = c_{d-2} \frac{R^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} + c_{d-4} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \dots + \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} c_1 \frac{R}{\delta} + (-1)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} S^{(univ)} & , \quad d = \text{odd} \\ c_2 \frac{R^2}{\delta^2} + (-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} S^{(univ)} \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) & , \quad d = \text{even} \end{array} \right\} \quad (1.1)$$

where R is the scale of the entangling region, and δ is the UV cutoff. The leading divergence is the area law, and all of the power law divergences are non-universal. We will be interested in the universal term $S^{(univ)}$, which in $d = \text{even}$ is the coefficient of the log divergence and in $d = \text{odd}$ it is the finite term.

Figure 1. Illustration of a perturbed circle $r(\phi) = 1 + \epsilon \sum_n a_n \cos(n\phi)$. **Left:** A Perturbation without a zero mode $a_0 = 0$. **Right:** A Perturbation with a zero mode $a_0 = 0.3$.

Consider a QFT parametrized by coordinates (t, y_i, r) , where $i = 1 \dots, d - 2$. For instance take r to be the radial coordinate in spherical coordinates, and y_i to be angles parameterizing the entangling surface. We will always work in a constant time slice $t = 0$. Consider a codimension-2 entangling surface defined by:

$$r(y_i) = r_0(y_i) \tag{1.2}$$

where $r_0(y_i)$ is some given function of y_i . Thus we choose r to be the dependent coordinate, and y_i as the independent coordinates. We denote the entanglement entropy corresponding to the entangling surface $r_0(y_i)$ as S_0 . Now we slightly perturb the entangling surface:

$$r(y_i) = r_0(y_i) + \epsilon f(y_i) \tag{1.3}$$

where ϵ is a small parameter, and $f(y_i)$ is some arbitrary perturbation function¹.

The entanglement entropy will change as a result of the perturbation of the entangling surface, and it can generally be written as an expansion in ϵ :

$$S = S_0 + S_1\epsilon + S_2\epsilon^2 + \dots \tag{1.4}$$

The above procedure was carried out in [63, 64] for the case of a perturbed sphere for a CFT in d dimensions. They start with a sphere entangling surface in a flat space-time background, and perturb the sphere as follows:

$$r(\Omega_{d-2}) = R \left[1 + \epsilon \sum_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}} a_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}} Y_{l, m_1, \dots, m_{d-3}}(\Omega_{d-2}) \right] \tag{1.5}$$

where R is the sphere radius, the a 's are constants, and the Y 's are (real) hyper-spherical harmonics. Then they calculate the resulting change in the universal term of the EE. They find that the the change in the universal EE vanishes at 1st order, namely

¹As an example, a perturbed circle in $d = 3$ is shown in Fig. 1. In this case, (1.3) is given by: $r(\phi) = R[1 + \epsilon \sum_n a_n \cos(n\phi)]$, where we Fourier expanded the perturbation f . R is the radius of the circle, ϕ is the angle in polar coordinates, and a_n are the Fourier coefficients.

$$S_1^{(univ)} = 0 \quad (1.6)$$

Thus, for a CFT the sphere is a local² extremum with respect to perturbations of the entangling surface. Additionally, for holographic CFTs [64] uses the Ryu-Takayanagi formula [35, 36] (more specifically, its generalization to higher derivative gravity [83–86]) to calculate the 2^{nd} order correction $S_2^{(univ)}$:

$$S_2^{(univ)} = C_T \frac{\pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}}(d-1)}{2^{d-2}\Gamma(d+2)\Gamma(\frac{d}{2})} \sum_{l,m_1\dots m_{d-1}} a_{l,m_1\dots m_{d-1}}^2 \prod_{k=1}^d (l+k-2) \times \begin{cases} \frac{\pi}{2} & , \quad d = \text{odd} \\ 1 & , \quad d = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (1.7)$$

where C_T is the (positive) central charge appearing in the 2-point function: $\langle TT \rangle \sim \frac{C_T}{x^{2d}}$. A priori, $S_2^{(univ)}$ could have depended on the three parameters C_t, t_2 , and t_4 of the 3-point function $\langle TTT \rangle$, but it turns out that it depends just on C_T .

$S_2^{(univ)}$ is clearly positive, implying that the sphere is a local minimum for holographic CFTs. (1.7) was compared to $S_2^{(univ)}$ obtained from Solodukhin’s formula in 4d CFTs, and precise agreement was found.

In this work we will generalize the above results of [64] to less symmetric entangling surfaces, and (in some cases) to non-CFTs. We will show that entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry in some direction (see Fig. 2), extremize the universal EE with respect to shape deformations that break some of the symmetry³, i.e:

$$S_1^{(univ)} = 0 \quad (1.8)$$

The proof of this result will be purely geometrical, and hence will apply to any QFT (and also to Renyi entropy). A simple corollary is that for $d = \text{even}$, (1.8) is true also for multiply connected entangling surfaces⁴.

Additionally, we will calculate the 2^{nd} order correction $S_2^{(univ)}$ (whose sign determines if the local extremum is a minimum or a maximum) for some simple entangling surfaces. We perform this calculation using holography (the Ryu-Takayanagi formula), and also by using Solodukhin’s formula (for 4d CFTs). In all of the the examples of symmetric entangling surfaces that we have checked, the 2^{nd} order correction is positive, and this corresponds to a local minimum. We conjecture this to hold more generally to symmetric entangling surfaces. We also comment on results for free massive fields, and 4d Renyi entropy.

²If the topology of the entangling surface is allowed to change, then the EE can become unbounded from below, as shown in 4d in [82].

³It should be emphasized that the family of shape perturbations that extremize the EE, are only those which break some of the symmetry of the original entangling surface. For example, for a 3d circle the perturbation in Fig. 1-Left is allowed, whereas the perturbation in Fig. 1-Right is not allowed because it has a component in the radial direction (a zero mode of the Fourier expansion). Such perturbations cannot deform a sphere into a larger/smaller sphere. More generally, such perturbations cannot deform a surface of revolution into a different surface of revolution (containing the same number of symmetries).

⁴For $d = \text{even}$ the universal term of the EE is a log divergence which is determined locally by the shape of the entangling surface. Thus for a multiply connected entangling surface the log term is a superposition of the contribution from each separate piece of the entangling surface.

Figure 2. Left: An example of a $d = 4$ surface of revolution entangling surface with rotational symmetry. **Right:** A $d = 4$ waveguide entangling surface with translational symmetry. Such symmetric entangling surfaces can obviously be generalized to higher dimensions.

2 The First Order Correction: Stationarity

Consider a QFT parametrized by coordinates (ϕ, y_i, r) , where $i = 1 \dots, d - 3$. Assume ϕ to be a symmetry direction of the entangling surface. Now perturb the entangling surface (see (1.3)) with a single Fourier mode⁵ :

$$r(\phi, y_i) = r_0(y_i) + \epsilon A_n a_n(y_i) \cos(n\phi) \quad , \quad n \neq 0 \quad (2.4)$$

where $r_0(y_i)$ doesn't depend on the symmetry direction ϕ , the $a_n(y_i)$ are functions of y_i , and A_n are constants. The resulting EE can be expanded as:

$$S = S_0 + \epsilon S_1 + \epsilon^2 S_2 + \dots \quad (2.5)$$

Now lets consider the same perturbation but with negative sign, i.e. $\epsilon \rightarrow -\epsilon$:

$$\tilde{r}(\phi, y_i) = r_0(y_i) - \epsilon A_n a_n(y_i) \cos(n\phi) \quad , \quad n \neq 0 \quad (2.6)$$

⁵A general perturbation (without a zero mode) can be written as:

$$r(\phi, y_i) = r_0(y_i) + \epsilon \sum_{n \neq 0} \left(A_n a_n(y_i) \cos(n\phi) + B_n b_n(y_i) \sin(n\phi) \right) \quad (2.1)$$

Then the EE can be expanded:

$$S = S_0 + \epsilon S_1 + \epsilon^2 S_2 + \dots \quad (2.2)$$

At linear order in ϵ the modes don't mix, and their contributions to S_1 add up linearly:

$$S_1 = \sum_{n \neq 0} \left(A_n U_1(n) + B_n U_2(n) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

where $U_1(n)$ and $U_2(n)$ are some functions of n . Because the modes don't mix at linear order, we can compute the contribution of a single mode and then sum over all modes.

The resulting EE will be (just flipping the sign of ϵ in (2.5):

$$\tilde{S} = S_0 - \epsilon S_1 + \epsilon^2 S_2 + \dots \quad (2.7)$$

But the two perturbations (2.6) and (2.4) describe precisely the same entangling surface, only rotated. This can be seen by performing $\phi \rightarrow \phi + \frac{\pi}{n}$ on (2.6), which gives (2.4). Since the two entangling surfaces are the same, they have same EE and therefore from (2.5) and (2.7) we have:

$$\tilde{S} = S \quad \longrightarrow \quad S_1 = 0 \quad (2.8)$$

and we proved what we wanted.

An important point to make is that the proof above used only the rotation symmetry, and did not use any specific property of entanglement entropy or of the QFT. Therefore stationarity will hold for any quantity which is a function of the surface (e.g. Renyi entropy), and for any QFT.

3 The Second Order Correction in Holography

Consider a boundary QFT parametrized by coordinates (t, y_i, r) , $i = 1 \dots, d-2$. z is the holographic coordinate, and we set $t = 0$. The holographic EE according to the Ryu-Takayanagi formula is:

$$S = \int d^{d-2} y_i dz \mathcal{L}(z, r, y_i) \quad (3.1)$$

where $\mathcal{L} \equiv \frac{\sqrt{\det g}}{4G_N}$. The corresponding equation of motion for the bulk surface is:

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial r} - \frac{d}{dz} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_z r)} - \frac{d}{dy_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_{y_i} r)} = 0 \quad (3.2)$$

where there is a summation convention on y_i .

Consider an entangling surface defined by:

$$r(y_i) = r_0(y_i) \quad (3.3)$$

Now perturb the entangling surface:

$$r(y_i) = r_0(y_i) + \epsilon f(y_i) \quad (3.4)$$

where ϵ is a small parameter. Then the bulk surface will also get perturbed⁶:

$$r(z, y_i) = r_0(z, y_i) + \epsilon r_1(z, y_i) + \epsilon^2 r_2(z, y_i) + \dots \quad (3.5)$$

⁶We use the same letter r for the entangling surface and the bulk surface. They can simply be distinguished by the fact that for the bulk surface there is a z dependence.

For the rest of this section we assume $d = \text{even}$ dimensions, and we will want to compute the universal log term. We can then write the resulting perturbed \mathcal{L} and S as:

$$S = S_0 + S_1\epsilon + S_2\epsilon^2 + \dots = \int d^{d-2}y_i dz \mathcal{L} = \int d^{d-2}y_i dz \left[\mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_1\epsilon + \mathcal{L}_2\epsilon^2 + \dots \right] \quad (3.6)$$

We can derive a formula for the 2^{nd} order correction S_2 . Assuming that the entangling surface has a symmetry in all directions (e.g. the cylinder surface in the next section), terms containing r_2 will fall and we get:

$$S_2 = \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \int d^{d-2}y_i dz \left[r_1 \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \frac{d}{dy_i} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_{y_i} r)} + \partial_{y_i} r_1 \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_{y_i} r)} \right]_{\epsilon=0} + \int_{\partial \mathcal{M}} d^{d-2}y_i r_1 \frac{d}{d\epsilon} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_z r)} \Big|_{\epsilon=0} \Big|_{z=\delta}^{z_{max}} \right\} \quad (3.7)$$

3.1 Cylinder Entangling Surface

Now let us assume that the entangling surface is a cylinder $S^p \times \mathbb{R}^{d-2-p}$ in flat space-time. We denote y_j as cartesian directions along \mathbb{R}^{d-2-p} (where $-L \leq y_j \leq L$) and Ω_p as directions along the sphere S^p (of radius R). The holographic EE written in these cylindrical coordinates is (see also (A.20)):

$$S = \int dz d^{d-2-p} y_j d\Omega_p \mathcal{L}(z, r, y_j, \Omega_p) \quad (3.8)$$

where:

$$\mathcal{L}(z, r, y_i, \Omega_p) = \frac{r^p F_1(z)}{z^{d-1}} \sqrt{1 + F_2(z)(\partial_z r)^2 + F_3(z) \left[(\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2 \right]} \quad (3.9)$$

We are not committing yet to a particular metric in the bulk, therefore $F_1(z)$, $F_2(z)$, $F_3(z)$ are arbitrary functions of z . For an AdS metric we have: $F_2(z) = F_3(z) = 1$, and $F_1 = \frac{R_{AdS}^{d-1}}{4G_N}$.

We Fourier expand the perturbation f in (3.4):

$$f(y_j, \Omega_p) = \sum_{\{n_j, l_p\}} \left[a_{\{n_j, l_p\}} Y_{l_p}(\Omega_p) \prod_{i=1}^{d-2-p} \cos(n_i y_i) \right] \quad (3.10)$$

where $Y_{l_p}(\Omega_p)$ are (real) hyperspherical harmonics, the n_j are integers, the $a_{\{n_j, l_p\}}$ are the coefficients of the Fourier expansion, and for conciseness we defined $\{n_j\} \equiv n_1, \dots, n_{d-2-p}$ and $\{l_p\} \equiv l, m_1, \dots, m_{p-1}$.

The bulk surface perturbation r_1 of (3.5) can also be Fourier expanded (see (A.25)):

$$r_1(z, y_j, \Omega_p) = \sum_{\{n_j, l_p\}} \left[a_{\{n_j, l_p\}} r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z) Y_{l_p}(\Omega_p) \prod_{i=1}^{d-2-p} \cos(n_i y_i) \right] \quad (3.11)$$

where $r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z)$ are functions of z , which must obey the boundary condition: $r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z=0) = 1$.

Now we can derive an expression for the boundary term (the last term on the RHS of (3.7)):

$$S_2^{\text{bound.}} = \frac{L^{d-2-p} F_1(z) F_2(z) r_0^{p-1}}{2z^{d-1} [1 + F_2(\partial_z r_0)^2]^{1/2}} \sum_{\{n_j, l_p\}} a_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^2 \left[\frac{r_0 r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)} \partial_z r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}}{1 + F_2(\partial_z r_0)^2} + p \partial_z r_0 (r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)})^2 \right] \Big|_{z=\delta} \quad (3.12)$$

where L is the length of the \mathbb{R}^{d-2-p} directions, and we take the limit $L \rightarrow \infty$. This formula is a boundary term which is evaluated at the boundary $z = \delta$. We will want to extract the universal log divergence from this formula in $d = \text{even}$ dimensions.

In principle, $r_0(z)$ and $r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z)$ can be obtained by solving the EOM's for the bulk minimal surface (A.23) and (A.26). These solutions will generally have Fefferman-Graham type expansions of the form ([19, 43, 87, 88]):

$$r_0(z) = q_0 + q_2 z^2 + \dots + q_d z^d + \tilde{q}_d z^d \log(z) + \dots \quad (3.13)$$

$$r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z) = u_0 + u_2 z^2 + \dots + u_d z^d + \tilde{u}_d z^d \log(z) + \dots \quad (3.14)$$

The terms in (3.12) can then be written as:

$$\frac{r_0 r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)} \partial_z r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}}{[1 + F_2(\partial_z r_0)^2] z^{d-1}} \Big|_{\log} = dq_0 u_0 \tilde{u}_d \log z \quad , \quad \frac{p \partial_z r_0 (r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)})^2}{z^{d-1}} \Big|_{\log} = dp u_0^2 \tilde{q}_d \log z \quad (3.15)$$

where we extracted the log terms. Using (3.12), and also the fact that the background is asymptotically AdS: $F_1(0) = \frac{R_{\text{AdS}}^{d-1}}{4G_N} = \frac{2\pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}} (d-1) \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}{\Gamma(d+2)} C_T$ and $F_2(0) = 1$, we get⁷

$$S_2^{\text{bound.}} \Big|_{\log} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}{(d+1) \Gamma(d-1)} C_T L^{d-2-p} R^{p-1} \sum_{\{n_j, l_p\}} a_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^2 (R \tilde{u}_d + p \tilde{q}_d) \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) \quad (3.16)$$

where we used $u_0 = 1$ and $q_0 = R$, and multiplied by $(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}$, see (1.1).

It can be shown that for the two special cases $p = 0, 1$, the boundary term above is the only contribution to $S_2^{(\text{univ})}$. Thus the $p = 1$ case gives:

$$S_2^{(\text{univ})} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}{(d+1) \Gamma(d-1)} C_T L^{d-3} \sum_{\{n_j, l\}} a_{\{n_j, l\}}^2 (R \tilde{u}_d + \tilde{q}_d) \quad (3.17)$$

⁷Note that for a CFT, dimensional analysis (and (A.23), (A.26)) dictate the functional dependence of \tilde{q}_d and \tilde{u}_d such that: $\tilde{q}_d = f_1(d) R^{-d+1}$ and $\tilde{u}_d = f_2(l, \tilde{n}, R, d)$, where f_1, f_2 are some functions and $\tilde{n}^2 \equiv \sum_i n_i^2$. Note that there is no dependence on m_1, \dots, m_{p-1} , since the bulk EOM's (A.23), (A.26) do not depend on them. Likewise it can be seen that the sphere result (1.7) doesn't depend on the m 's.

We see from (3.17) that the sign of $S_2^{(univ)}$ depends solely on the coefficients \tilde{u}_d and \tilde{q}_d of the log term in the FG expansions. These coefficients can be obtained by solving the bulk EOMs (A.23) and (A.26). It might be interesting to understand if generally these coefficients are constrained to have a definite sign. The $p = 0$ case (the plane) is examined in the following subsection.

3.2 Plane Entangling Surface

The plane entangling surface \mathbb{R}^{d-2} is a special case of the cylinder with $p = 0$. Therefore (3.16) becomes⁸:

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{d}{2})}{(d+1)\Gamma(d-1)} C_T L^{d-2} \sum_{\{n_j\}} a_{\{n_j\}}^2 \tilde{u}_d \quad (3.18)$$

So the sign of $S_2^{(univ)}$ depends solely on the coefficient \tilde{u}_d , which we shall now determine. For a plane entangling surface and Einstein gravity in the bulk, we will find an explicit solution⁹ (A.19):

$$x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)}(z) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} z^{\frac{d}{2}} K_{\frac{d}{2}}(\tilde{n}z) \quad (3.19)$$

where \mathcal{N} is a normalization constant, and $\tilde{n}^2 \equiv \sum_i n_i^2$. The small z expansion of this function gives (see (A.16)) $\tilde{u}_d = \frac{(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \tilde{n}^d}{2^{d-2} d (\frac{d}{2}-1)!}$. Therefore we have:

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{\pi^{\frac{d-2}{2}} (d-1)}{2^{d-2} \Gamma(d+2) (\frac{d}{2}-1)!} C_T L^{d-2} \sum_{\{n_j\}} \tilde{n}^d a_{\{n_j\}}^2 \quad (3.20)$$

Since the above expression is positive, we have proved that a plane is a local minimum for Einstein gravity in the bulk. It is now natural to conjecture that (3.20) holds for any CFT. (3.20) was derived for $d = \text{even}$, but it would be simple task to obtain the analogous $d = \text{odd}$ result. The $d = \text{odd}$ result will differ from (3.20) only by its d dependence, and for $d = 3$ it was obtained in [77].

For the case $d = 4$, (3.20) gives:

$$S_2^{(univ)} = C_T \frac{\pi^3 L^2}{160} \sum_{n_2=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n_3=1}^{\infty} (n_2^2 + n_3^2)^2 a_{n_2, n_3}^2 \quad (3.21)$$

This precisely matches (4.13) which we will obtain in the next section for 4d CFTs via Solodukhin's formula.

⁸Note that (3.16), (3.17), and (3.18) apply to any asymptotically AdS background.

⁹This result was also derived in [52] in the context of "entanglement density".

4 The Second Order Correction in Field theory

4.1 4d CFT: Solodukhin's Formula

For a $d = \text{even}$ CFT there is a universal log term (1.1):

$$S|_{\log} = (-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} S^{(univ)} \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) \quad (4.1)$$

and as in (1.4), we can expand in small ϵ :

$$S^{(univ)} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} S_k^{(univ)} \epsilon^k \quad (4.2)$$

Solodukhin's formula [65] (which applies to a CFT in 4d) is¹⁰:

$$S^{(univ)} = \frac{a_4}{180} \int_{\Sigma} d^2\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} E_2 + \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} d^2\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} I_2 \quad (4.3)$$

where E_2 is the Euler density, and the integrals are over the entangling surface Σ , and

$$I_2 \equiv \text{Tr}(k^2) - \frac{1}{2} k^a k^a = (k_{\mu\nu}^a - \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{\mu\nu} k^a)^2 \geq 0 \quad (4.4)$$

The second fundamental form and extrinsic curvature are defined as:

$$k_{\mu\nu}^a = \gamma_{\mu}^{\alpha} \gamma_{\nu}^{\beta} \nabla_{\alpha} \hat{n}_{\beta}^a \quad , \quad k^a = \text{Tr}(k_{\mu\nu}^a) = \gamma^{\mu\nu} k_{\mu\nu}^a \quad , \quad \text{Tr}(k^2) = \gamma^{\mu\nu} \gamma^{\rho\sigma} k_{\nu\rho}^a k_{\sigma\mu}^a \quad (4.5)$$

where $\gamma_{\mu\nu}$ is the induced metric on the entangling surface.

We consider shape perturbations that leave the topology of the entangling surface fixed, therefore the change in the Euler term above is zero, and $S_2^{(univ)}$ of (4.2) will be given by the integral of I_2 :

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} d^2\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} I_2 \Big|_{\epsilon^2} \quad (4.6)$$

In (4.4) I_2 is always positive [78, 82] and is zero for the sphere. Therefore the sphere locally minimizes I_2 and $S^{(univ)}$. This argument also works for flat entangling surfaces (plane, strips) since these have $I_2 = 0$.

In the following, we calculate $S_2^{(univ)}$ for several examples. See also [63, 64].

- **Example 1: Plane Entangling Surface**

The metric in cartesian coordinates is:

$$ds^2 = dx^2 + dy_2^2 + dy_3^2 \quad (4.7)$$

¹⁰ a_4 and c_4 are the a and c anomalies in 4d. Both are normalized such that for a real scalar field their value is 1. We will sometimes use $C_T = \frac{c_4}{3\pi^4}$ instead of c_4 .

Consider a plane at $x = 0$, where y_2, y_3 are coordinates along the surface. Now perturb it as follows:

$$x = 0 + \epsilon f(y_2, y_3) \quad (4.8)$$

The vector normal to the surface is:

$$\hat{n}_\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \epsilon^2(f_{y_2}^2 + f_{y_3}^2)}}(1, -\epsilon f_{y_2}, -\epsilon f_{y_3}) \quad , \quad \text{where} \quad f_{y_i} \equiv \partial_{y_i} f \quad (4.9)$$

The second fundamental form at order $O(\epsilon^2)$ is:

$$k_{\mu\nu}^a = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -\epsilon^2(f_{y_3}f_{y_2y_3} + f_{y_2}f_{y_2y_2}) & -\epsilon^2(f_{y_3}f_{y_3y_3} + f_{y_2}f_{y_2y_3}) \\ -\epsilon^2(f_{y_3}f_{y_2y_3} + f_{y_2}f_{y_2y_2}) & -\epsilon f_{y_2y_2} & -\epsilon f_{y_2y_3} \\ -\epsilon^2(f_{y_3}f_{y_3y_3} + f_{y_2}f_{y_2y_3}) & -\epsilon f_{y_2y_3} & -\epsilon f_{y_3y_3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4.10)$$

$k_{\mu\nu}^a$ starts at order ϵ since the unperturbed plane is flat. Plugging this in (4.4) gives:

$$\sqrt{\gamma}I_2 = I_2 + O(\epsilon^3) = \frac{\epsilon^2}{2} \left[(f_{y_2y_2} - f_{y_3y_3})^2 + 4f_{y_2y_3}^2 \right] (f_{y_2}^2 + f_{y_3}^2) + O(\epsilon^3) \quad (4.11)$$

Note that I_2 starts at order ϵ^2 , therefore the order ϵ correction vanishes even before integration over the surface. Now Fourier expand the perturbation:

$$f(y_2, y_3) = \sum_{n_2, n_3=1}^{\infty} a_{n_2 n_3} \cos(n_2 y_2) \cos(n_3 y_3) \quad (4.12)$$

and plug (4.11), (4.12) in (4.6):

$$S_2^{(univ)} = C_T \frac{\pi^3 L^2}{160} \sum_{n_2=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n_3=1}^{\infty} (n_2^2 + n_3^2)^2 a_{n_2 n_3}^2 \quad (4.13)$$

where we used $c_4 = 3\pi^4 C_T$, and the integral $\int_{-L}^L dy \cos^2(ny) = L$, where the width of the plane is very large $L \rightarrow \infty$. So we got a positive result, and therefore the universal term of a plane in 4d is a local minimum. We see that (4.13) precisely matches the result (3.21) obtained in holography.

We can compute higher orders of ϵ in (4.2), and we note that for the plane all odd terms vanish: $S_{2k+1}^{(univ)} = 0$. At 4th order we get:

$$S_4^{(univ)} = -C_T \frac{\pi^3 L^2}{11520} \sum_{n_2=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n_3=1}^{\infty} a_{n_2 n_3}^4 \left(15n_2^6 + 15n_3^6 + 13n_2^4 n_3^2 + 13n_3^4 n_2^2 \right) \quad (4.14)$$

- **Example 2: Sphere Entangling Surface**

This case was calculated in [63, 64], and we write their result.

The perturbed sphere entangling surface is:

$$r(\theta, \phi) = R[1 + \epsilon f(\theta, \phi)] = R\left[1 + \epsilon \sum_{l,m} a_{lm} Y_{lm}(\theta, \phi)\right] \quad (4.15)$$

where R is the radius of the sphere. Plugging in (4.6) gives:

$$S_2^{(univ)} = C_T \frac{\pi^3}{160} \sum_{l,m} a_{lm}^2 (l-1)l(l+1)(l+2) \quad (4.16)$$

This matches the holographic result (1.7) [64].

• **Example 3: Cylinder Entangling Surface**

The metric in cylindrical coordinates is:

$$ds^2 = dr^2 + dy^2 + r^2 d\phi^2 \quad (4.17)$$

Consider a perturbed cylinder entangling surface with radius R :

$$r(y, \phi) = R + \epsilon f(y, \phi) \quad (4.18)$$

We get:

$$\sqrt{\gamma} I_2|_{\epsilon^2} = \frac{1}{4R^3} [2f^2 + 3f_\phi^2 + 2f_{\phi\phi}^2 + 8ff_{\phi\phi} - R^2 f_y^2 + 8R^2 f_{y\phi}^2 - 4R^2 f_{yy} f_{\phi\phi} + 2R^4 f_{yy}^2] \epsilon^2 \quad (4.19)$$

Plugging $f(y, \phi) = \sum_{n,m} a_{n,m} \cos(m\phi) \cos(ny)$,

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} dy d\phi \sqrt{\gamma} I_2|_{\epsilon^2} = C_T \frac{\pi^4 L}{320R^3} \sum_{n,m} a_{nm}^2 \left[2 - 5m^2 + 2m^4 + (nR)^2 (4m^2 - 1) + 2(nR)^4 \right] \quad (4.20)$$

Thus $S_2^{(univ)} \geq 0$ for $m \geq 2$ and for all n , and the cylinder is a local minimum.

• **Example 4: 4d Surface of Revolution**

Consider a surface of revolution entangling surface (e.g. Fig. 2-Left) given by:

$$r(\theta, \phi) = r_0(\theta) \quad (4.21)$$

where we use spherical coordinates (r, θ, ϕ) . This surface has rotational symmetry in the ϕ direction. Now perturb the surface as follows:

$$r(\theta, \phi) = r_0(\theta) [1 + \epsilon f_2(\theta) \cdot f_3(\phi)] \quad (4.22)$$

with $f_3(\phi) = \sum_{m \neq 0} a_m \cos(m\phi)$. (4.3) and (4.4) give at most 4 derivatives of ϕ , thus the result can be written as a polynomial in m (after integrating over ϕ):

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} d\theta d\phi \sqrt{\gamma} I_2 \Big|_{\epsilon^2} = \frac{\pi^3 C_T}{80} \int d\theta \sum_{m \neq 0} a_m^2 \left[G_1(r_0, f_2, \theta) m^4 + G_2(r_0, f_2, \theta) m^2 + G_3(r_0, f_2, \theta) \right] \quad (4.23)$$

where the $G_i(r_0, f_2, \theta)$ are some functions of r_0, f_2 and their derivatives. Explicit calculation gives the m^4 coefficient:

$$G_1(r_0, f_2, \theta) = \frac{\pi f_2^2 \left(4 + 4 \csc^2(\theta) r_0^2 r_0'^8 + 16 \csc^2(\theta) r_0^4 r_0'^6 + 24 \csc^2(\theta) r_0^6 r_0'^4 + 16 r_0^8 r_0'^2 \right)}{8 r_0^3 \sin \theta (r_0^2 + r_0'^2)^{\frac{9}{2}}} \quad (4.24)$$

Since $r_0 \geq 0$, we see that $G_1(r_0, f_2, \theta) \geq 0$. Therefore for perturbations with large enough m (short wave-length perturbations) (4.23) is positive, and thus all 4d surfaces of revolution are local minima. We are not able to show that the functions $G_2(r_0, f_2, \theta), G_3(r_0, f_2, \theta)$ are positive (though the final integrated result $S_2^{(univ)}$ may still turn out to be positive).

- **Example 5: 4d Waveguide Surface**

Consider a general waveguide entangling surface (e.g. Fig. 2-Right) given by:

$$r(y, \phi) = r_0(\phi) \quad (4.25)$$

where we use cylindrical coordinates (r, y, ϕ) . This surface has translational symmetry in the y direction. Now we perturb the surface as follows:

$$r = r_0(\phi) [1 + \epsilon f_2(\phi) f_3(y)] \quad (4.26)$$

with $f_3(y) = \sum_{m \neq 0} a_m \cos(my)$. The result can be written as a polynomial in m (after integrating over y):

$$S_2^{(univ)} = \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} d\phi dy \sqrt{\gamma} I_2 \Big|_{\epsilon^2} = \frac{\pi^3 C_T}{80} \int d\phi \sum_{m \neq 0} a_m^2 \left[G_1(r_0, f_2) m^4 + G_2(r_0, f_2) m^2 + G_3(r_0, f_2) \right] \quad (4.27)$$

where the $G_i(r_0, f_2)$ are some functions of r_0, f_2 and their derivatives. Explicit calculation gives the m^4 coefficient:

$$G_1(r_0, f_2) = \frac{\pi f_2^2 \left(2r_0^{10} + 6r_0^8 r_0'^2 + 6r_0^6 r_0'^4 + 2r_0^4 r_0'^6 \right)}{4(r_0^2 + r_0'^2)^{\frac{7}{2}}} \geq 0 \quad (4.28)$$

Therefore for perturbations with large enough m (short wave-length perturbations) (4.27) is positive, and thus all 4d waveguide surfaces are local minima. We are not able to show that the functions $G_2(r_0, f_2)$, $G_3(r_0, f_2)$ are positive (though the final integrated result $S_2^{(univ)}$ may still turn out to be positive).

4.2 Renyi Entropy

There is a generalization of (4.3) to Renyi entropy in a 4d a CFT [79],[70]:

$$\mathcal{S}_q^{(univ)} = Q_1(q) \frac{a_4}{180} \int_{\Sigma} d^2\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} E_2 + Q_2(q) \frac{c_4}{240\pi} \int_{\Sigma} d^2\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} I_2 \quad (4.29)$$

where $\mathcal{S}_q^{(univ)}$ is the universal log term for the q -th Renyi entropy. $Q_{1,2}(q)$ are functions of q such that $Q_1(1) = Q_2(1) = 1$, so it matches (4.3) in the EE limit $q \rightarrow 1$. Up to these functions, (4.29) and (4.3) are the same, hence the results in the previous sections can be used. In particular, if $Q_2(q)$ is positive then for any entangling surface the Renyi entropy will have the same sign as the EE. Note that $Q_2(q)$ is positive for free fields, and there is strong evidence that it is positive for holographic CFTs [70, 82, 89]. If this turns out to be correct, then the Renyi entropy will be a local minimum whenever the EE is.

4.3 Free Massive Fields

Certain universal EE terms for free massive field theories have been found [16–19]. The so called "universal area law" for free scalars or fermions with mass m has the following form:

$$S = \begin{cases} (-1)^{\#} \gamma_d A_{\Sigma} m^{d-2} & , \quad d = \text{odd} \\ (-1)^{\#} \tilde{\gamma}_d A_{\Sigma} m^{d-2} \log(m\delta) & , \quad d = \text{even} \end{cases} \quad (4.30)$$

where γ_d is a positive constant that depends only on the dimension d . All of the shape dependence is contained in A_{Σ} , the area of the entangling surface. Table 1 lists the sign factors $(-1)^{\#}$ in (4.30) for a Dirac fermion, a conformally coupled scalar, and a minimally coupled scalar.

	Dirac Fermion	Conformal scalar	Minimal scalar
$d = \text{odd}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d+1}{2}}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}$
$d = \text{even}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}}$	$(-1)^{\frac{d}{2}}$

Table 1. The sign factor in the "universal area law" (4.30).

As an example, let us now compute the "universal area law" term for a deformed sphere entangling surface:

$$r(\Omega_{d-2}) = R \left[1 + \epsilon \sum_{\{lm\}} a_{\{lm\}} Y_{\{lm\}}(\Omega_{d-2}) \right] \quad (4.31)$$

The area of the deformed sphere is:

$$A_{\Sigma} = \int d\Omega_{d-2} r^{d-2} = \frac{(d-1)\pi^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{\Gamma(\frac{d+1}{2})} R^{d-2} + \epsilon^2 \frac{(d-2)(d-3)}{2} R^{d-2} \sum_{\{lm\}} a_{\{lm\}}^2 + O(\epsilon^3) \quad (4.32)$$

where we plugged (4.31) and performed the integrals.

The first term on the RHS is the area of the undeformed sphere, the $O(\epsilon)$ correction vanishes as expected, and the $O(\epsilon^2)$ correction is positive. Therefore the $O(\epsilon^2)$ correction in S has the same sign as the zeroth order, which can be read from Table 1. Generalizing to non-spheres, it is easy to see that the area of a perturbed surface of revolution is larger than that of the unperturbed surface of revolution. It would be interesting to perform a similar analysis to higher curvature terms for free massive fields (i.e to curvature corrections to the "universal area law").

A similar analysis applies to "universal area law" terms in interacting theories [19, 21, 69], with a shape dependence that comes only from the area A_Σ . The EE for a CFT perturbed by a relevant operator of dimension $\Delta = \frac{d+2}{2}$, contains the following term:

$$S = N\lambda^2 \frac{d-2}{4(d-1)} \frac{\pi^{\frac{d+2}{2}}}{\Gamma(\frac{d+2}{2})} A_\Sigma \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) \quad (4.33)$$

where λ is the coupling constant. Such log terms occur both in odd and even dimensions.

5 Discussion

In this work we studied the shape dependence of entanglement entropy by deforming symmetric entangling surfaces. We showed that entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry locally extremize the EE with respect to shape deformations that break some of the symmetry. This result applies to EE and Renyi entropy for any QFT in any dimension. Using Solodukhin's formula and holography, we calculated the 2nd order correction to the EE for CFTs and simple symmetric entangling surfaces. In all cases we found that the 2nd order correction is positive, and thus the corresponding symmetric entangling surface is a local minimum. Perhaps this result holds more generally for any symmetric entangling surface.

Let us mention some possible future directions.

- The calculation in section 3 considered only Einstein gravity in the bulk, and it would be interesting to consider also higher derivative gravity. For spheres, [64] found that $S_2^{(univ)}$ depends just on C_T and not on t_2 or t_4 (these are the three parameters in the 3-point function of stress tensors). It would be nice to check if this continues to hold for other entangling surfaces.
- Computing the FG coefficients \tilde{u}_d and \tilde{q}_d in (3.16) by solving the bulk EOMs for the cylinder (A.23) and (A.26). Maybe it is also possible to show, using a more general principle, that \tilde{q}_d and \tilde{u}_d in (3.17) must have a definite sign. It would also be interesting to consider (in holography) more general entangling surfaces with a symmetry.
- The work of [69] attempted to compute S_2^{univ} for a plane entangling surface in a $d = 4$ CFT using the perturbative formalism of EE [66]. They were not able to obtain the I_2 term of Solodukhin's formula (4.3), and the current situation is somewhat puzzling. Our result (3.20) as well as (1.7) (obtained in [64]) might help in resolving this puzzle.

- It would be interesting to repeat the analysis of section 4.1 for 6d CFTs using the results of [80, 81].
- Other possible extensions are to compute higher orders $S_j^{(univ)}$ for $j > 2$, and also to perform computations in a curved space-time background.

Acknowledgments

I thank Carlos Hoyos, Eric Perlmutter, Misha Smolkin, and especially Omer Ben-Ami for helpful discussions. I am very grateful to Zohar Komargodski, Mark Mezei, and Shimon Yankielowicz for valuable discussions and collaboration during some stages of this work. Our work is partially supported by the Israel Science Foundation (grant 1989/14), the US-Israel bi-national fund (BSF) grant 2012383 and the German Israel bi-national fund GIF grant number I-244-303.7-2013.

A Equations of Motion for the Minimal Bulk Surface

In this section, we obtain EOMs for the bulk minimal surfaces of cylinder, strip, and plane. We solve the 1st EOM for the plane, and obtain \tilde{u}_d in (3.18).

A.1 Strip Entangling Surface

Consider a strip entangling surface and a bulk metric in Poincare coordinates:

$$ds^2 = \frac{R_{AdS}^2}{z^2} \left[\frac{1}{\beta(z)} dz^2 - dt^2 + dx^2 + dy_i^2 \right] \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Where $\beta(z)$ is some function of the holographic coordinate z , which for AdS: $\beta(z) = 1$. x is the direction perpendicular to the strip entangling surface, y_i are directions along the strip entangling surface, and $i = 1, \dots, d-2$. The holographic EE is (see (3.1), (3.2)):

$$S = \frac{R_{AdS}^{d-1}}{4G_N} \int d^{d-2} y_i \int_{\delta}^{z_{max}} dz \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} \left[1 + (\partial_{y_i} x)^2 \right] + (\partial_z x)^2} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

In the ansatz of (3.9) this corresponds to $p = 0$, $F_1 = \frac{R_{AdS}^{d-1}}{4G_N \sqrt{\beta(z)}}$, $F_2 = \beta(z)$, and $F_3 = 1$. The corresponding EOM is:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\partial_z x}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} \left[1 + (\partial_{y_i} x)^2 \right] + (\partial_z x)^2}} \right) + \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{d}{dy_i} \left(\frac{\partial_{y_i} x}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} \left[1 + (\partial_{y_i} x)^2 \right] + (\partial_z x)^2}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The bulk surface can be expanded in ϵ :

$$x(z, y_i) = x_0(z) + \epsilon x_1(z, y_i) + \epsilon^2 x_2(z, y_i) + \dots \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where because of the translational symmetry of the strip, $x_0(z)$ does not depend on y_i . The EOM (A.3) at 0th order in ϵ is:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{\partial_z x_0}{z^{d-1} \sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} + (\partial_z x_0)^2}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The solution to this is:

$$(\partial_z x_0)^2 = \frac{z^{2d-2}}{\beta(z)(z_{max}^{2d-2} - z^{2d-2})} \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where z_{max} is the turning point of the bulk surface. The EOM at 1st order in ϵ is:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} \partial_z x_1}{\left(\frac{1}{\beta(z)} + (\partial_z x_0)^2 \right)^{3/2}} \right) + \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\partial_{y_i}^2 x_1}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\beta(z)} + (\partial_z x_0)^2}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

Plugging (A.6) in (A.7):

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{z^{d-1}} \frac{(z_{max}^{2d-2} - z^{2d-2})^{3/2} \partial_z x_1}{z_{max}^{2d-2}} \right) + \frac{\beta^{\frac{1}{2}}}{z^{d-1}} (z_{max}^{2d-2} - z^{2d-2})^{1/2} \partial_{y_i}^2 x_1 = 0 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Simplifying, we get:

$$\partial_z^2 x_1 + \left[\frac{\beta'(z)}{2\beta(z)} - \frac{(d-1)}{z} \cdot \frac{1 + 2\left(\frac{z}{z_{max}}\right)^{2d-2}}{1 - \left(\frac{z}{z_{max}}\right)^{2d-2}} \right] \partial_z x_1 + \frac{\partial_{y_i}^2 x_1}{1 - \left(\frac{z}{z_{max}}\right)^{2d-2}} = 0 \quad (\text{A.9})$$

This equation seems hard to solve analytically. In the next section we consider the simpler case of a plane entangling surface.

A.2 Plane Entangling Surface

For a plane entangling surface situated at $x = 0$, the bulk minimal surface goes straight down in the bulk: $x_0(z) = 0$. We have (see (A.4)):

$$x(z, y_i) = \epsilon x_1(z, y_i) + \epsilon^2 x_2(z, y_i) + \dots \quad (\text{A.10})$$

The turning point of the bulk surface is at $z_{max} \rightarrow \infty$, therefore (A.9) becomes:

$$\partial_z^2 x_1 + \left[\frac{\beta'(z)}{2\beta(z)} - \frac{(d-1)}{z} \right] \partial_z x_1 + \partial_{y_i}^2 x_1 = 0 \quad (\text{A.11})$$

We Fourier expand x_1 :

$$x_1(z, y) = \sum_{\{n_i\}} a_{\{n_i\}} x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)}(z) \prod_{i=1}^{d-2} \cos(n_i y_i) \quad (\text{A.12})$$

where the n_i are integers, and we defined the shorthand notation: $\{n_i\} \equiv n_1, \dots, n_{d-2}$. Plugging this in (A.11) gives:

$$\partial_z^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} + \left[\frac{\beta'(z)}{2\beta(z)} - \frac{(d-1)}{z} \right] \partial_z x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} - \tilde{n}^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} = 0 \quad (\text{A.13})$$

where we defined $\tilde{n}^2 = \sum_i n_i^2$. Now we consider the ansatz $\beta(z) = 1 + \alpha z^k$ for the bulk metric, then:

$$\partial_z^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} + \left[\frac{\alpha k z^{k-1}}{2(1 + \alpha z^k)} - \frac{d-1}{z} \right] \partial_z x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} - \tilde{n}^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} = 0 \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The CFT case $\beta(z) = 1$ can be recovered by plugging $\alpha = 0$:

$$\partial_z^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} - \frac{d-1}{z} \partial_z x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} - \tilde{n}^2 x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)} = 0 \quad (\text{A.15})$$

This equation is solved by modified Bessel functions¹¹:

$$x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)}(z) = C_1 z^{\frac{d}{2}} K_{\frac{d}{2}}(\tilde{n}z) + C_2 z^{\frac{d}{2}} I_{\frac{d}{2}}(\tilde{n}z) \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Choosing a boundary condition such that $x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)}(z)$ does not explode at $z \rightarrow \infty$, leaves only $K_{\frac{d}{2}}$. Therefore the final solution is:

$$x_{\{n_i\}}^{(1)}(z) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} z^{\frac{d}{2}} K_{\frac{d}{2}}(\tilde{n}z) \quad (\text{A.19})$$

where the normalization constant is $\mathcal{N} = 2^{\frac{d}{2}-1} (\frac{d}{2} - 1)! \tilde{n}^{-\frac{d}{2}}$. We will use the above solution in (3.19). This result was also derived in [52] in the context of "entanglement density".

A.3 Cylinder Entangling Surface

Consider a cylinder entangling surface $S^p \times \mathbb{R}^{d-2-p}$ in flat space-time \mathbb{R}^d . The holographic EE in cylindrical coordinates is (see (3.8),(3.9)):

$$S = \frac{R_{AdS}^{d-1}}{4G_N} \int dz d^{d-2-p} y d\Omega_p \frac{r^p}{z^{d-1}} \sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r)^2 + (\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

where we assumed the AdS_{d+1} metric. The corresponding EOM is:

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{r^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\partial_z r}{\sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r)^2 + (\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2}} \right) + \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{d}{dy_i} \left(\frac{r^p \partial_{y_i} r}{\sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r)^2 + (\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2}} \right) \\ & \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{d}{d\Omega_p} \left(\frac{r^{p-2} \partial_{\Omega_p} r}{\sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r)^2 + (\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2}} \right) - \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} \frac{d}{dr} \left(r^p \sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r)^2 + (\partial_{y_j} r)^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} (\partial_{\Omega_p} r)^2} \right) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.21})$$

The bulk surface expanded around the 0^{th} order cylinder is:

$$r = r_0(z) + \epsilon r_1(z, y_j, \Omega_p) + \epsilon^2 r_2(z, y_j, \Omega_p) + \dots \quad (\text{A.22})$$

¹¹ The modified Bessel function:

$$\begin{aligned} K_\nu(z) = & \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^{-\nu} \sum_{j=0}^{\nu-1} (-1)^j \frac{(\nu-j-1)!}{4^j j!} z^{2j} + (-1)^{\nu+1} \log(z/2) I_\nu(z) \\ & + (-1)^\nu \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^\nu \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\psi(j+1) + \psi(n+j+1)}{4^j j! (\nu+j)!} z^{2j} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where ψ is the digamma function, and

$$I_\nu(z) = \left(\frac{z}{2}\right)^\nu \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^j j! \Gamma(\nu+j+1)} z^{2j} \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The 0th order EOM is:

$$\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{r_0^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\partial_z r_0}{\sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2}} \right) - \frac{1}{z^{d-1}} p r_0^{p-1} \sqrt{1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2} = 0 \quad (\text{A.23})$$

The 1st order EOM is:

$$\partial_z^2 r_1 + \left[\frac{\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{r_0^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{1}{(1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2)^{3/2}} \right)}{\left(\frac{r_0^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{1}{(1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2)^{3/2}} \right)} \right] \partial_z r_1 + [1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2] \left(\frac{p}{r_0^2} r_1 + \frac{1}{r_0^2} \partial_{\Omega_p}^2 r_1 + \partial_{y_j}^2 r_1 \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A.24})$$

We Fourier expand r_1 (see (3.11)):

$$r_1(z, y_j, \Omega_p) = \sum_{\{n_j, l_p\}} \left[a_{\{n_j, l_p\}} r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}(z) Y_{l_p}(\Omega_p) \prod_{i=1}^{d-2-p} \cos(n_i y_i) \right] \quad (\text{A.25})$$

where the n_j are integers, and we defined the shorthand notation: $\{n_j\} \equiv n_1, \dots, n_{d-2-p}$ and $\{l_p\} \equiv l, m_1, \dots, m_{p-1}$. We plug (A.25) in (A.24):

$$\partial_z^2 r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)} + \left[\frac{\frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{r_0^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{1}{(1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2)^{3/2}} \right)}{\left(\frac{r_0^p}{z^{d-1}} \frac{1}{(1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2)^{3/2}} \right)} \right] \partial_z r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)} + [1 + (\partial_z r_0)^2] \left(\frac{p - l(l + p - 1)}{r_0^2} - \tilde{n}^2 \right) r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)} = 0 \quad (\text{A.26})$$

where we defined $\tilde{n}^2 \equiv \sum_j n_j^2$, and used $\partial_{\Omega_p}^2 Y_{l_p} = -l(l + p - 1) Y_{l_p}$ [64]. Since the parameters m_1, \dots, m_{p-1} do not appear in (A.26), the solution $r_{\{n_j, l_p\}}^{(1)}$ will not depend on them (and neither will $S_2^{\text{bound.}}|_{\log}$ in (3.16)).

For a plane entangling surface we have $p = 0$ and $r \equiv x$, and $\partial_z x_0 = 0$, and in this case (A.26) reduces to (A.15). On the other hand, for a sphere entangling surface we have $p = d - 2$ and $r_0^2 = R^2 - z^2$. Thus for a sphere the EOM is:

$$\partial_z^2 r_l^{(1)} - \frac{1}{z} \frac{(d-1)R^2 + 2z^2}{R^2 - z^2} \partial_z r_l^{(1)} + \frac{R^2[d-2-l(l+d-3)]}{(R^2 - z^2)^2} r_l^{(1)} = 0 \quad (\text{A.27})$$

We find a solution to this equation in terms of hypergeometric functions. For $d = 3$ the solution is:

$$r_l^{(1)}(z) = \frac{1}{\mathcal{N}} \left(\frac{z-R}{z+R} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{R+lz}{\sqrt{z^2 - R^2}} \right) \quad (\text{A.28})$$

which agrees with Eq. 43 of [63].

References

- [1] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “Entanglement entropy in free quantum field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504007, [arXiv:0905.2562 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [2] P. Calabrese and J. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and conformal field theory,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504005, [arXiv:0905.4013 \[cond-mat.stat-mech\]](#).
- [3] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory,” *J.Stat.Mech.* **0406** (2004) P06002, [arXiv:hep-th/0405152 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [4] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory: A Non-technical introduction,” *Int.J.Quant.Inf.* **4** (2006) 429, [arXiv:quant-ph/0505193 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [5] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy of black holes,” *Living Rev.Rel.* **14** (2011) 8, [arXiv:1104.3712 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [6] H. Casini, M. Huerta, and R. C. Myers, “Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1105** (2011) 036, [arXiv:1102.0440 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [7] C. Holzhey, F. Larsen, and F. Wilczek, “Geometric and renormalized entropy in conformal field theory,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B424** (1994) 443–467, [arXiv:hep-th/9403108 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [8] F. Larsen and F. Wilczek, “Renormalization of black hole entropy and of the gravitational coupling constant,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B458** (1996) 249–266, [arXiv:hep-th/9506066 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [9] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, “A Quantum Source of Entropy for Black Holes,” *Phys.Rev.* **D34** (1986) 373–383.
- [10] J. Callan, Curtis G. and F. Wilczek, “On geometric entropy,” *Phys.Lett.* **B333** (1994) 55–61, [arXiv:hep-th/9401072 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [11] M. Srednicki, “Entropy and area,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **71** (1993) 666–669, [arXiv:hep-th/9303048 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [12] M. Levin and X.-G. Wen, “Detecting topological order in a ground state wave function,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96** (Mar, 2006) 110405. <http://link.aps.org/doi/10.1103/PhysRevLett.96.110405>.
- [13] A. Kitaev and J. Preskill, “Topological entanglement entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **96** (2006) 110404, [arXiv:hep-th/0510092 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [14] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “On the RG running of the entanglement entropy of a circle,” *Phys.Rev.* **D85** (2012) 125016, [arXiv:1202.5650 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [15] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “A Finite entanglement entropy and the c-theorem,” *Phys.Lett.* **B600** (2004) 142–150, [arXiv:hep-th/0405111 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [16] M. P. Hertzberg and F. Wilczek, “Some Calculable Contributions to Entanglement Entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **106** (2011) 050404, [arXiv:1007.0993 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [17] A. Lewkowycz, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Observations on entanglement entropy in massive QFT’s,” *JHEP* **1304** (2013) 017, [arXiv:1210.6858 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [18] M. Huerta, “Numerical Determination of the Entanglement Entropy for Free Fields in the Cylinder,” *Phys.Lett.* **B710** (2012) 691–696, [arXiv:1112.1277 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [19] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Some Calculable Contributions to Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1108** (2011) 039, [arXiv:1105.6055 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [20] D. V. Fursaev, A. Patrushev, and S. N. Solodukhin, “Distributional Geometry of Squashed Cones,” *Phys.Rev.* **D88** no. 4, (2013) 044054, [arXiv:1306.4000 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [21] C. Park, “Logarithmic Corrections in the Entanglement Entropy,” [arXiv:1505.03951 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [22] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and M. Smolkin, “Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres,” [arXiv:1504.00913 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [23] H. Casini, F. Mazzitelli, and E. Test, “Area terms in entanglement entropy,” *Phys.Rev.* **D91** no. 10, (2015) 104035, [arXiv:1412.6522 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [24] H. Liu and M. Mezei, “A Refinement of entanglement entropy and the number of degrees of freedom,” *JHEP* **1304** (2013) 162, [arXiv:1202.2070 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [25] H. Liu and M. Mezei, “Probing renormalization group flows using entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **1401** (2014) 098, [arXiv:1309.6935 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [26] M. Nozaki, “Notes on Quantum Entanglement of Local Operators,” *JHEP* **1410** (2014) 147, [arXiv:1405.5875 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [27] C. P. Herzog, “Universal Thermal Corrections to Entanglement Entropy for Conformal Field Theories on Spheres,” *JHEP* **1410** (2014) 28, [arXiv:1407.1358 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [28] M. Goykhman, “On entanglement entropy in ’t Hooft model,” [arXiv:1501.07590 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [29] H. Casini, M. Huerta, R. C. Myers, and A. Yale, “Mutual information and the F-theorem,” [arXiv:1506.06195 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [30] H. Elvang and M. Hadjiantonis, “Exact results for corner contributions to the entanglement entropy and Renyi entropies of free bosons and fermions in 3d,” [arXiv:1506.06729 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [31] W. Donnelly and A. C. Wall, “Geometric entropy and edge modes of the electromagnetic field,” [arXiv:1506.05792 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [32] Y. Zhou, “Universal Features of Four-Dimensional Superconformal Field Theory on Conic Space,” [arXiv:1506.06512 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [33] C. P. Herzog and M. Spillane, “Thermal Corrections to Rényi entropies for Free Fermions,” [arXiv:1506.06757 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [34] D. Carmi, “TeV Scale Strings and Scattering Amplitudes at the LHC,” Master’s thesis, Tel Aviv U., 2011. <http://inspirehep.net/record/928308/files/arXiv:1109.5161.pdf>.
- [35] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **0608** (2006) 045, [arXiv:hep-th/0605073 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [36] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [arXiv:hep-th/0603001 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [37] T. Nishioka, S. Ryu, and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy: An Overview,” *J.Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504008, [arXiv:0905.0932 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [38] A. Lewkowycz and J. Maldacena, “Generalized gravitational entropy,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 090, [arXiv:1304.4926 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [39] R. C. Myers and A. Sinha, “Holographic c-theorems in arbitrary dimensions,” *JHEP* **1101** (2011) 125, [arXiv:1011.5819 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [40] R. C. Myers and A. Sinha, “Seeing a c-theorem with holography,” *Phys.Rev.* **D82** (2010) 046006, [arXiv:1006.1263 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [41] T. Faulkner, “The Entanglement Renyi Entropies of Disjoint Intervals in AdS/CFT,” [arXiv:1303.7221 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [42] T. Hartman, “Entanglement Entropy at Large Central Charge,” [arXiv:1303.6955 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [43] A. Schwimmer and S. Theisen, “Entanglement Entropy, Trace Anomalies and Holography,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B801** (2008) 1–24, [arXiv:0802.1017 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [44] T. Faulkner, M. Guica, T. Hartman, R. C. Myers, and M. Van Raamsdonk, “Gravitation from Entanglement in Holographic CFTs,” *JHEP* **1403** (2014) 051, [arXiv:1312.7856 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [45] D. D. Blanco, H. Casini, L.-Y. Hung, and R. C. Myers, “Relative Entropy and Holography,” *JHEP* **1308** (2013) 060, [arXiv:1305.3182 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [46] M. Headrick and T. Takayanagi, “A Holographic proof of the strong subadditivity of entanglement entropy,” *Phys.Rev.* **D76** (2007) 106013, [arXiv:0704.3719 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [47] U. Kol, C. Nunez, D. Schofield, J. Sonnenschein, and M. Warschawski, “Confinement, Phase Transitions and non-Locality in the Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1406** (2014) 005, [arXiv:1403.2721 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [48] C. A. Agon and H. J. Schnitzer, “Holographic Mutual Information at small separations,” [arXiv:1501.03775 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [49] K. Ghoroku and M. Ishihara, “Entanglement temperature for the excitation of SYM theory in (De)confinement phase,” [arXiv:1506.06474 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [50] J. Bhattacharya, V. E. Hubeny, M. Rangamani, and T. Takayanagi, “Entanglement density and gravitational thermodynamics,” *Phys. Rev.* **D91** no. 10, (2015) 106009, [arXiv:1412.5472 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [51] M. Nozaki, T. Numasawa, and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic Local Quenches and Entanglement Density,” *JHEP* **05** (2013) 080, [arXiv:1302.5703 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [52] M. Nozaki, T. Numasawa, A. Prudenziati, and T. Takayanagi, “Dynamics of Entanglement Entropy from Einstein Equation,” *Phys. Rev.* **D88** no. 2, (2013) 026012, [arXiv:1304.7100 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [53] G. Georgiou and D. Zoakos, “Entanglement entropy of the Klebanov-Strassler model with dynamical flavors,” *JHEP* **07** (2015) 003, [arXiv:1505.01453 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [54] S. He, J.-R. Sun, and H.-Q. Zhang, “On Holographic Entanglement Entropy with Second Order Excitations,” [arXiv:1411.6213 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [55] S. Chakraborty, P. Dey, S. Karar, and S. Roy, “Entanglement thermodynamics for an excited state of Lifshitz system,” *JHEP* **1504** (2015) 133, [arXiv:1412.1276 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [56] T. Faulkner, “Bulk Emergence and the RG Flow of Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1505** (2015) 033, [arXiv:1412.5648 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [57] A. Parnachev and N. Poovuttikul, “Topological Entanglement Entropy, Ground State Degeneracy and Holography,” [arXiv:1504.08244 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [58] B. Czech, L. Lamprou, S. McCandlish, and J. Sully, “Integral Geometry and Holography,” [arXiv:1505.05515 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [59] D. Momeni, R. Myrzakulov, and M. Raza, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy for noncommutative Anti-de Sitter space,” [arXiv:1504.00106 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [60] D. Momeni, M. Raza, H. Gholizade, and R. Myrzakulov, “Realization of Holographic Entanglement Temperature for a Nearly-AdS Boundary,” [arXiv:1505.00215 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [61] P. Bueno, R. C. Myers, and W. Witzczak-Krempa, “Universality of corner entanglement in conformal field theories,” [arXiv:1505.04804 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [62] P. Bueno and R. C. Myers, “Corner contributions to holographic entanglement entropy,” [arXiv:1505.07842 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [63] A. Allais and M. Mezei, “Some results on the shape dependence of entanglement and Rényi entropies,” [arXiv:1407.7249 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [64] M. Mezei, “Entanglement entropy across a deformed sphere,” [arXiv:1411.7011 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [65] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy, conformal invariance and extrinsic geometry,” *Phys.Lett.* **B665** (2008) 305–309, [arXiv:0802.3117 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [66] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy: A Perturbative Calculation,” *JHEP* **1412** (2014) 179, [arXiv:1403.3733 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [67] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy Flow and the Ward Identity,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **113** no. 26, (2014) 261602, [arXiv:1406.2716 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [68] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement entropy, planar surfaces, and spectral functions,” *JHEP* **1409** (2014) 119, [arXiv:1407.2891 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [69] V. Rosenhaus and M. Smolkin, “Entanglement Entropy for Relevant and Geometric Perturbations,” *JHEP* **1502** (2015) 015, [arXiv:1410.6530 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [70] A. Lewkowycz and E. Perlmutter, “Universality in the geometric dependence of Renyi entropy,” [arXiv:1407.8171 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [71] I. R. Klebanov, T. Nishioka, S. S. Pufu, and B. R. Safdi, “On Shape Dependence and RG Flow of Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **1207** (2012) 001, [arXiv:1204.4160 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [72] S. Banerjee, “Wess-Zumino Consistency Condition for Entanglement Entropy,” *Phys.Rev.Lett.* **109** (2012) 010402, [arXiv:1109.5672 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [73] R. C. Myers, R. Pourhasan, and M. Smolkin, “On Spacetime Entanglement,” *JHEP* **1306** (2013) 013, [arXiv:1304.2030 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [74] P. Fonda, L. Gioni, A. Salvio, and E. Tonni, “On shape dependence of holographic mutual information in AdS₄,” *JHEP* **1502** (2015) 005, [arXiv:1411.3608 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [75] Y. Nakaguchi and T. Nishioka, “Entanglement Entropy of Annulus in Three Dimensions,” *JHEP* **1504** (2015) 072, [arXiv:1501.01293 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [76] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and J. Sonnenschein, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips,” *JHEP* **1411** (2014) 144, [arXiv:1409.6305 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [77] X. Huang, L.-Y. Hung, and F.-L. Lin, “OPE of the stress tensors and surface operators,” [arXiv:1502.02487 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [78] A. F. Astaneh, G. Gibbons, and S. N. Solodukhin, “What surface maximizes entanglement entropy?,” *Phys.Rev.* **D90** no. 8, (2014) 085021, [arXiv:1407.4719 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [79] D. Fursaev, “Entanglement Renyi Entropies in Conformal Field Theories and Holography,” *JHEP* **1205** (2012) 080, [arXiv:1201.1702 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [80] B. R. Safdi, “Exact and Numerical Results on Entanglement Entropy in (5+1)-Dimensional CFT,” *JHEP* **1212** (2012) 005, [arXiv:1206.5025 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [81] R.-X. Miao, “Universal Terms of Entanglement Entropy for 6d CFTs,” [arXiv:1503.05538 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [82] E. Perlmutter, M. Rangamani, and M. Rota, “Positivity, negativity, and entanglement,” [arXiv:1506.01679 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [83] X. Dong, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy for General Higher Derivative Gravity,” *JHEP* **1401** (2014) 044, [arXiv:1310.5713 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [84] J. Camps, “Generalized entropy and higher derivative Gravity,” *JHEP* **1403** (2014) 070, [arXiv:1310.6659 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [85] A. Bhattacharyya, A. Kaviraj, and A. Sinha, “Entanglement entropy in higher derivative holography,” *JHEP* **08** (2013) 012, [arXiv:1305.6694 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [86] A. Bhattacharyya, M. Sharma, and A. Sinha, “On generalized gravitational entropy, squashed cones and holography,” *JHEP* **01** (2014) 021, [arXiv:1308.5748 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [87] C. Fefferman and C. R. Graham, “The ambient metric,” [arXiv:0710.0919 \[math.DG\]](#).
- [88] C. R. Graham and E. Witten, “Conformal anomaly of submanifold observables in AdS / CFT correspondence,” *Nucl.Phys.* **B546** (1999) 52–64, [arXiv:hep-th/9901021 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [89] J. Lee, L. McGough, and B. R. Safdi, “Rnyi entropy and geometry,” *Phys.Rev.* **D89** no. 12, (2014) 125016, [arXiv:1403.1580 \[hep-th\]](#).

Chapter 6

On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity

On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity

Omer Ben-Ami¹, Dean Carmi^{1,2}

¹ *Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences
School of Physics and Astronomy, Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel*

² *Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics
31 Caroline Street North, ON N2L 2Y5, Canada*

ABSTRACT: The volume of the region inside the bulk Ryu-Takayanagi surface is a codimension-one object, and a natural generalization of holographic complexity to the case of subregions in the boundary QFT. We focus on time-independent geometries, and study the properties of this volume in various circumstances. We derive a formula for computing the volume for a strip entangling surface and a general asymptotically AdS bulk geometry. For an AdS black hole geometry, the volume exhibits non-monotonic behaviour as a function of the size of the entangling region (unlike the behaviour of the entanglement entropy in this setup, which is monotonic). For setups in which the holographic entanglement entropy exhibits transitions in the bulk, such as global AdS black hole, geometries dual to confining theories and disjoint entangling surfaces, the corresponding volume exhibits a discontinuous finite jump at the transition point (and so do the volumes of the corresponding entanglement wedges). We compute this volume discontinuity in several examples. Lastly, we compute the codim-zero volume and the bulk action of the entanglement wedge for the case of a sphere entangling surface and pure AdS geometry.

Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Bulk Subregion Volumes	4
2.1 Strip Entangling surface	5
2.1.1 Pure AdS	7
2.1.2 D_p -branes	7
2.1.3 The leading temperature correction to the volume	8
2.1.4 The volume at finite temperature	9
2.1.5 m -strips in an AdS black hole geometry with large temperature	10
3. Volume Transitions and Discontinuities	11
3.1 Two strips in AdS_{d+1}	11
3.2 Two strips in Global AdS_3	13
3.3 Strip in a Confining theory dual to $\text{AdS}_5 \times S^5$ compactified on a circle	14
3.4 Global AdS black holes	15
3.4.1 Example: BTZ Black hole	15
3.4.2 Example: Global AdS_5 Black hole	17
4. Discussion	17
A. Leading temperature Correction for a Sphere	18
B. The Volume and Action of the Entanglement wedge	19
B.1 The volume of the entanglement wedge for a sphere and pure AdS	19
B.2 The action in the entanglement wedge	20

1. Introduction

Quantum physics differs from classical physics in two important aspects: entanglement and complexity. The entanglement entropy (EE) (e.g [1–18]) is a measure of the quantum correlations of a quantum state, and is extremely useful in many quantum systems, ranging from condensed matter physics to black hole physics. The AdS/CFT correspondence [19–22] gives a simple geometrical way to compute entanglement entropy in holographic QFTs, using the Ryu-Takayanagi (RT) formula [9, 10] (and its covariant HRT generalization [23]):

$$S = \frac{\text{Area}(\gamma_A)}{4G_N} \tag{1.1}$$

where γ_A is the bulk extremal surface, and G_N is Newton's constant.

However the entanglement (Renyi) entropies are not the whole story, and a quantum state contains a large amount of information which is not contained in them. Quantum complexity is a quantum information quantity which has to do with the difficulty converting one quantum state to another quantum state. In the following we briefly review the concept of quantum complexity, and its proposed holographic conjectures as given in [24–31].

Consider K qubits in an arbitrary quantum state:

$$|\psi\rangle = \sum_{j_1, \dots, j_K} c_{j_1, \dots, j_K} |j_1, \dots, j_K\rangle \quad (1.2)$$

where the c_{j_1, \dots, j_K} are complex numbers, and each j_i is either 0 or 1. It takes a huge amount of information, namely 2^K complex numbers, to specify the state of K qubits. To define quantum complexity, one starts by considering some simple reference state $|0 \dots 0\rangle$, which is a product state. One then chooses a universal gate set of 2-qubit unitary operations. Every state in the Hilbert can be approached (arbitrarily close) by applying a sequence of these 2-qubit operations. The quantum complexity of a state $|\psi\rangle$ is then defined as the minimal number of 2-qubit gates required to prepare the state $|\psi\rangle$ from the reference state $|0 \dots 0\rangle$. When K is large, nearly all states $|\psi\rangle$ have a maximal complexity which is exponential in K :

$$\mathcal{C}_{max} \sim e^K \quad (1.3)$$

On the other hand, the maximal entropy is $K \log 2$ and thus the maximal complexity is exponentially larger than the maximal entropy. For a system which undergoes thermalization, the quantum complexity grows linearly in t for a very long time which is much larger than the thermalization time. After an exponentially large time $t \sim e^K$, the complexity saturates at a constant value \mathcal{C}_{max} . There can be fluctuations around the mean value \mathcal{C}_{max} , and the time at which the system can fluctuate back to the reference state is doubly exponential: $t_{rec} \sim e^{e^K}$. It was also argued that the rate of change of complexity is proportional to the entropy and the temperature of the system: $\frac{d\mathcal{C}}{dt} = TS$.

Consider now the double sided AdS black hole geometry [32] which is dual to a specific entangled state, namely the thermo-field double state, see Fig 1. The left and right CFTs can be viewed as being connected through the black hole interior by a wormhole (e.g by drawing a space-like slice between the two sides)¹. The wormhole is a dynamical object which grows linearly in time at late times. In this classical bulk geometry the wormhole continues to grow forever. On the other hand, thermal equilibrium is achieved much quicker, and the entanglement entropies saturate [34–37].

In [24–31] there were two important conjectures made about how to compute complexity in holography². The proposals relate quantum complexity to the size of the wormhole. The linear growth of complexity in a thermalizing system is then holographically dual to the linear growth of the wormhole in an AdS black hole geometry. More precisely, the first conjecture states that the complexity is given by

¹The relation between the entanglement (EPR) of causally disconnected systems and the wormhole (Einstein-Rosen bridge) in the dual bulk theory was conjectured by [33] to hold more generally and is now known as ER=EPR.

²For additional recent work on complexity, see [38–44].

Figure 1: Left: Illustration of the double sided AdS black hole Penrose diagram dual to the thermofield double state. The left and right boundaries are where CFT_L and CFT_R live. The singularity is shown in dashed red. A few maximal codim-one surfaces are shown, including the one at $t \rightarrow \infty$ in green (which does not reach the singularity.). **Right:** Illustration of embedding diagram of a wormhole.

the volume³ of the codim-one maximal bulk surface that ends on the boundary at a time t :

$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{V}{G\ell} \quad (1.4)$$

where ℓ is some length scale (typically the AdS radius or the BH radius) which needs to be chosen for each case at hand. This is somewhat unsatisfactory, and led [25, 26] to suggest a refined version where the dual of complexity equals the action evaluated in a specific bulk region, as we review below.

For AdS black holes the collection of all maximal slices foliate the entire space-time outside of the horizon, but not the entire interior of the black hole. At $t \rightarrow \infty$ the final slice is achieved, and it does not reach the singularity. However, the volume grows linearly in t (for late times) as expected from quantum complexity. Additionally, the volume passes a few tests such as having the correct behavior in shock wave geometries.

The second conjecture [25, 26] states that the complexity is given by the bulk action evaluated on the Wheeler-deWitt patch attached at some boundary time t^4 :

$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{\mathcal{A}}{\pi\hbar} \quad (1.5)$$

The action proposal is more satisfactory than the volume proposal in the sense that one does not need to choose by hand a length scale ℓ . The calculation of the action on the WDW patch has a few challenging features: surface terms arising from the null boundaries of the WDW patch, corner terms where the null boundaries meet, and a surface term from the singularity of the black hole⁵, see [25, 26, 43, 44].

In [25, 26] it was shown that for AdS black holes the rate of change of the WDW action at late times is:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{A}}{dt} = 2M \quad (1.6)$$

³The volumes of the interior of black holes in flat space were studied in [45, 46].

⁴The WDW patch is the union of all spatial curves anchored at a time t on the boundary.

⁵Some of these issues can be ignored when calculating the time derivative of the WDW action.

This result led to the very interesting conjecture [25,26,47] that black holes saturate the inequality:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}}{dt} \leq \frac{2E}{\pi\hbar} \quad (1.7)$$

and as a result, black holes are the fastest computers in nature.

The recent progress in holographic complexity, and especially the complexity equals volume conjecture, serves us as motivation to study bulk codim-one surfaces and their volumes. Volumes of codim-one surfaces can be defined also for subregions on the boundary, and can be seen as a natural subregion generalization of holographic complexity. In [48] the codim-one volume contained inside the codim-two Ryu-Takayanagi surface was considered as the dual of complexity for subregions⁶. In our work we further study codim-one volumes for subregions, and uncover some interesting properties which they possess. We will also be agnostic about the length scale ℓ and assume that one can be chosen appropriately. The volume is also closely related to the volume of the entanglement wedge of the subregion, which is believed to be the region in the bulk corresponding to the reduced density matrix of the subregion [55]. The entanglement wedge is the domain of dependence of the “subregion volume”.

The contents of this paper are as follows. In section 2 we consider the codim-one volume inside the Ryu-Takayanagi surface as a natural dual to “sub-region complexity”. We proceed to compute this volume for time-independent geometries, and we write a general formula for the case of a strip entangling surface. We compute the volume in a few examples, and plot the temperature dependence of the volume for an AdS black hole geometry which exhibits non-monotonic behavior. In section 3 we show that the volume has a discontinuous jump in geometries in which there is a transition between 2 bulk minimal surfaces. We compute this jump in several examples. In section 4 we summarize our results, and discuss future directions. In Appendix A we present the computation of the leading temperature correction for an AdS black hole geometry and sphere entangling surface. In Appendix B we calculate the volume and action of the entanglement wedge for the case of a sphere entangling surface and pure AdS.

2. Bulk Subregion Volumes

Consider a holographic QFT in d space-time dimensions and an entangling surface of typical length R . Now consider the codim-one volume contained inside the corresponding Ryu-Takayanagi surface. The divergence structure of this volume was shown to be⁷ (see [44, 48]):

$$V = c_{d-1} \frac{R^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} + c_{d-3} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots + \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} c_1 \frac{R}{\delta} + (-1)^{\frac{d-1}{2}} c_0 & , \quad d = \text{even} \\ c_2 \frac{R^2}{\delta^2} + (-1)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \tilde{c}_0 \log\left(\frac{R}{\delta}\right) & , \quad d = \text{odd} \end{array} \right\} \quad (2.1)$$

where δ is the UV cutoff. The leading divergence scales like the volume of the entangling region, and there are subleading divergences. The expansion above contains universal terms, meaning in odd d there is a universal logarithmic divergence, and in even d there is universal finite term (i.e opposite to the EE case).

In [44] we define a covariant generalization of the volume inside a Ryu-Takayanagi surface, which is applicable also to time-dependent geometries. The prescription is the following:

⁶For additional related work, see [49–54]

⁷We set $L_{\text{AdS}} = G_N = \ell = 1$ such that V is dimensionless.

- For a given time t on the boundary and an entangling region A , find the codim-two HRT surface [23]. Then find the codim-one maximal volume attached to the HRT surface and the entangling region A . This gives a covariant construction of the volume associated with a subregion on the boundary.

Similar to the case of entanglement entropy [13, 14], in [44] this divergence structure is written in terms of the curvatures of the boundary CFT.

2.1 Strip Entangling surface

Figure 2: A strip entangling region with width l and length $L \rightarrow \infty$ on the boundary, and its corresponding minimal surface in the bulk. The boundary is at $z \rightarrow 0$.

In this section we study the volume prescription written above for the case of a strip entangling surface of length l and width $L \rightarrow \infty$, in a time-independent background geometry⁸, see Fig. 2. Namely we compute the volume inside the Ryu-Takayanagi surface. The case of a sphere in pure AdS was studied in [48]. Since the strip entangling surface has zero curvature, there will only be a single divergence (“volume law”) plus a finite term:

$$V = c_{d-1} \frac{lL^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-1}} + c_{finite} \quad (2.2)$$

Now consider a general asymptotically AdS_{d+1} metric:

$$ds^2 = \frac{1}{z^2} \left[f_0(z) dt^2 + f_1(z) dx_\mu^2 + f_2(z) dz^2 \right] \quad (2.3)$$

where $f_0(z)$, $f_1(z)$, and $f_2(z)$ are some arbitrary functions of z , which at the boundary are $f_i(z=0) = 1$.

The holographic entanglement entropy (area of the minimal surface) of a strip of length l is:

$$S(z_*) = \frac{2L^{d-2}}{4G_N} \int_0^{l/2} dx \frac{f_1^{\frac{d-2}{2}}}{z^{d-1}} \sqrt{f_1(z) + f_2(z)(\partial_x z)^2} = \frac{2L^{d-2}}{4G_N} \int_\delta^{z_*} \frac{dz}{z^{d-1}} \frac{\sqrt{f_2 f_1^{d-2}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{f_1^{d-1}(z_*) z^{2d-2}}{f_1^{d-1}(z) z_*^{2d-2}}} \quad (2.4)$$

where z_* is the deepest point of the minimal surface in the bulk. In the second equation the corresponding equation of motion was used. The equation of motion is:

⁸The translational symmetry of the strip considerably simplifies this problem.

$$\partial_x z = \mp \sqrt{\frac{f_1}{f_2} \sqrt{\frac{f_1^{d-1}(z) z_*^{2d-2}}{f_1^{d-1}(z_*) z_*^{2d-2}} - 1}} \quad \Rightarrow \quad x_1(z) = \int_z^{z_*} dZ \frac{\sqrt{\frac{f_2(Z)}{f_1(Z)}}}{\sqrt{\frac{f_1^{d-1}(Z) Z_*^{2d-2}}{f_1^{d-1}(z_*) Z^{2d-2}} - 1}} \quad (2.5)$$

Note that the solution for $x_1(z)$ is computed as a one-dimensional integral.

Since the background is static, the volume inside the minimal surface is obtained simply by integrating the inside of the minimal surface. We do this integral by slicing the bulk with planes of constant z , with the result:

$$V(z_*) = \int dx \int d^{d-2} y \sqrt{\tilde{g}} = 2L^{d-2} \int_\delta^{z_*} \frac{dz \sqrt{f_1^{d-1}(z) f_2}}{z^d} \int_0^{x_1(z)} dx = 2L^{d-2} \int_\delta^{z_*} \frac{dz \sqrt{f_1^{d-1}(z) f_2}}{z^d} x_1(z) \quad (2.6)$$

where $\sqrt{\tilde{g}}$ is the volume element, and $x_1(z)$ is the profile of the minimal surface given in Eq. 2.5. Plugging Eq. 2.5 into Eq. 2.6 gives:

$$V(z_*) = 2L^{d-2} \int_\delta^{z_*} \frac{dz \sqrt{f_1^{d-1}(z) f_2(z)}}{z^d} \int_z^{z_*} dZ \frac{\sqrt{\frac{f_2(Z)}{f_1(Z)}}}{\sqrt{\frac{f_1^{d-1}(Z) Z_*^{2d-2}}{f_1^{d-1}(z_*) Z^{2d-2}} - 1}} \quad (2.7)$$

This is our formula for the volume as a function of z_* for any asymptotically AdS geometry (any $f_{1,2,3}(z)$). This formula is only slightly more complicated than the corresponding formula for the entanglement entropy of the strip Eq. 2.4, since there are two integrals that one needs to perform instead of one.

From Eq. 2.5 we have:

$$l(z_*) = 2 \int_\delta^{z_*} dz \frac{\sqrt{\frac{f_2(z)}{f_1(z)}}}{\sqrt{\frac{f_1^{d-1}(z) z_*^{2d-2}}{f_1^{d-1}(z_*) z^{2d-2}} - 1}} \quad (2.8)$$

So in Eqs. 2.7 and 2.8 we have formulas for $V(z_*)$ and $l(z_*)$, and we can plot V as a function of l for any background. In the following we will compute the volume in several examples using these formulas.

Note that there is another solution to the equation of motion for which $x_1(z) = \frac{l}{2}$, meaning a constant solution for which the surface does not cap off smoothly at some point z_* in the bulk. Although this is not the minimal surface for most cases⁹, it will be interesting to consider its behavior compared to the minimal surface. The volume of this surface is given by:

$$V_c(l) = lL^{d-2} \int_\delta^\infty \frac{dz \sqrt{f_1^{d-1}(z) f_2}}{z^d} \quad (2.9)$$

⁹As we will review below, for confining theories the constant solution can be the minimal surface.

2.1.1 Pure AdS

For a pure AdS_{d+1} background $f_i(z) = 1$, the EE is given by:

$$S(l) = \frac{1}{2(d-2)} \left(\frac{L}{\delta}\right)^{d-2} - \frac{2^{d-3}\pi^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{d-2} \left(\frac{\Gamma\left(\frac{d}{2d-2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(\frac{1}{d-2}\right)}\right)^{d-1} \left(\frac{L}{l}\right)^{d-2} \quad (2.10)$$

Similarly, the volume is:

$$V(l) = \frac{1}{d-1} \frac{L^{d-2}l}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{2^{d-2}\pi^{\frac{d-1}{2}}\Gamma^{d-3}\left(\frac{d}{2d-2}\right)L^{d-2}}{(d-1)^2\Gamma^{d-3}\left(\frac{1}{2d-2}\right)l^{d-2}} \equiv \frac{c_1}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{c_0}{l^{d-2}} \quad (2.11)$$

Note that the finite term has the same l dependence as the finite part of the entanglement entropy.

Similarly, the volume of the constant solution Eq. 2.9 is given by:

$$V_c(l) = \frac{1}{d-1} \frac{L^{d-2}l}{\delta^{d-1}} \quad (2.12)$$

we get that for this solution there is no finite, universal, term.

2.1.2 D_p -branes

Consider a D_p -brane background with metric [56]:

$$ds^2 = \alpha' \left(\frac{U^{\frac{\tau-p}{2}}}{c_p} (-dt^2 + dx_1^2 + \dots + dx_p^2) + \frac{c_p}{U^{\frac{\tau-p}{2}}} dU^2 + c_p U^{\frac{p-3}{2}} d\Omega_{8-p}^2 \right) \quad (2.13)$$

$$e^\phi = (2\pi)^{2-p} g_{\text{YM}}^2 \left(\frac{c_p^2}{U^{7-p}} \right)^{\frac{3-p}{4}}$$

where $c_p = g_{\text{YM}} N^{\frac{1}{2}} \sqrt{2^{7-2p} \pi^{\frac{9-3p}{2}} \Gamma\left(\frac{7-p}{2}\right)}$

For non-conformal theories, in which the dilaton and the volume of the internal coordinates are in general not constant, we use the natural generalization from quantum gravity for the codim-2 surface:

$$S_A = \frac{1}{4G_N^{(10)}} \int d^8\sigma e^{-2\phi} \sqrt{G_{\text{ind}}^{(8)}} \quad (2.14)$$

Similarly, since we expect the general relation between complexity and the codim-1 surface $V \sim \frac{1}{G_N^{(d+2)} \ell}$, the generalization will be:

$$V \sim \frac{1}{\ell G_N^{(10)}} \int d^9\sigma e^{-2\phi} \sqrt{G_{\text{ind}}^{(9)}} \quad (2.15)$$

Plugging in the equation for the dilaton and the metric we get that for the minimal surface¹⁰:

$$\frac{dU}{dx} = U^{\frac{\tau-p}{2}} \sqrt{\frac{U^{9-p}}{U_*^{9-p}} - 1} \quad (2.16)$$

¹⁰To avoid clutter we set $c_p = 1$.

where U_* is the turning point of the surface, and we assume that we can trust the supergravity solution at least up to this region.

Following the same procedure as for the conformal case we can extract the dependence of the finite term on the length of the strip. The corresponding volume inside the minimal surface is:

$$V_{\text{finite}} \sim -\frac{f(p, g_{\text{YM}}, N)}{l^{\frac{p+5}{2(5-p)}}} \quad (2.17)$$

where $f(p, g_{\text{YM}}, N)$ is some function which depends on the dimensions of the D_p brane, the coupling constant and the central charge. Like for AdS, the finite term is an inverse power law $-l^{\frac{-(p+5)}{2(5-p)}}$. However for the D_p brane case the power in the volume finite term is different from the power in the entanglement entropy, which has the form $S_{\text{finite}} \sim -l^{-\frac{4}{5-p}}$.

2.1.3 The leading temperature correction to the volume

In this section we calculate the 1st order temperature correction to the volume in an AdS black hole geometry. Consider again the metric:

$$ds^2 = \frac{1}{z^2} \left[f_0(z) dt^2 + f_1(z) dx_\mu^2 + f_2(z) dz^2 \right] \quad (2.18)$$

The form of the temperature perturbation is $f_2(z) = \frac{1}{f_0(z)} = \frac{1}{1-k_0 T^d z^d} \approx 1 + k_0 T^d z^d$, where k_0 is a constant, and T is the temperature. The finite term of the volume will have an expansion of the form¹¹:

$$V_{\text{finite}} = \left(\frac{L}{l} \right)^{d-2} \left[a_1 + a_2 (Tl)^d + a_3 (Tl)^{2d} + \dots \right] \quad (2.19)$$

and we want to find the first correction a_2 . We use Eqs. 2.7 and 2.8, and after a few manipulations we get an integral expression for the volume:

$$\Delta V \equiv V - V_{\text{CFT}} = c_0 T^d l^2 (2g_0)^{-3} \left[-g_1 g_0 + \int_1^\infty dU U^{d-1} \left(-dg_1 g_0 + (d-1)g_1 g_0(U) + g_0 U^{-d-1} g_0(U) + g_0 g_1(U) \right) \right] \quad (2.20)$$

where we subtracted the volume in the vacuum state: $V_{\text{CFT}} = V(T=0)$. We also defined the integrals:

$$g_0(U) \equiv \int_1^U \frac{dt}{t^2 \sqrt{t^{2d}-1}} \quad , \quad g_1(U) \equiv \int_1^U \frac{dt t^{-d-3}}{\sqrt{t^{2d}-1}} \quad (2.21)$$

and

$$g_0 \equiv g_0(U \rightarrow \infty) \quad , \quad g_1 \equiv g_1(U \rightarrow \infty) \quad (2.22)$$

¹¹For temperature expansions for the holographic entanglement entropy see [57].

We plot the leading correction ΔV from Eq. 2.20 as a function of the dimension d in Fig. 3-Left. We see from the plot that the 1st order correction is negative for any d . This is different from the case of sphere (see appendix A and [48]), where the 1st order correction vanishes but the 2nd order is positive [48]. For $d = 2$ the correction vanishes as expected since the interval is like a one dimensional sphere.

Now consider a more general perturbation of the form $f_2(z) = 1 + Mz^q$. We again go through a similar calculation, and we show the results in Fig. 3-Right for several values of q . We see that the first order ΔV is negative for all d and q . We also see that for $d = 2$ the leading correction is non zero when $q \neq 2$. This implies that the vanishing leading correction for the sphere (obtained in [48] and shown in section A) applies only to temperature perturbations, and for a general perturbation the 1st order correction will not vanish.

Figure 3: **Left:** Plot of $\Delta V \equiv V - V_{CFT}$ as a function of d for a temperature perturbation. **Right:** Plot of $V - V_{CFT}$ as a function of d for perturbations of the form $f_2(z) = 1 + mz^q$. Curves from top to bottom correspond to: $q = d$, $q = d + 1$, $q = d + 2$, and $q = d + 3$.

2.1.4 The volume at finite temperature

In the previous section we computed the 1st order temperature correction to the volume in various dimensions. In the high temperature regime we expect an expansion of the form¹²:

$$V_{finite} = a_0 L^{d-2} l T^{d-1} [1 + O(1/(Tl))] \quad (2.23)$$

which is linear in l at very high T . We now focus on the AdS_4 and AdS_5 planar black hole geometries and a strip entangling surface. We compute numerically the dependence of the volume on the strip's length at a finite constant temperature. Fig. 4 shows the result of $\Delta V \equiv V - V_{CFT}$ as a function of the dimensionless parameter l when T is held fixed.

The plot starts at the origin at $l = 0$ and $\Delta V = 0$, and we see the expected linear growth behavior at large l . Curiously the plot is non-monotonic and has a minimum. Compare this plot to the monotonic behavior of the entanglement entropy, shown in Fig. 5 for the AdS_5 black hole and a strip entangling surface. It would be interesting to understand the meaning of the minimum in the volume. It would also be interesting to understand if for general shaped entangling surfaces the volume likewise has a minimum.

¹²For a general shaped entangling surface the high temperature expansion will go like $V \sim a_0 v T^{d-1}$, where v is the volume of the entangling region. This is similar to the EE at high temperature.

It is also easy to see that for the constant solution Eq. 2.9, we have:

$$\Delta V_c \sim a_0 L^{d-2} l T^{d-1} \quad (2.24)$$

which is monotonic and linear in l .

Figure 4: Plots of $\Delta V \equiv V - V_{CFT}$ as a function of l (we change l and leave T fixed). At $l = 0$ we have $\Delta V = 0$. **Left:** The AdS_5 black hole. **Right:** The AdS_4 black hole.

Figure 5: The entanglement entropy $\Delta S = S - S_{CFT}$ as a function of l (we change l and leave T fixed) for an AdS_5 black hole and a strip entangling surface. ΔS starts at the origin, and has linear behavior at large lT .

2.1.5 m -strips in an AdS black hole geometry with large temperature

For an AdS black hole geometry at very large temperature and a strip entangling surface, the volume is linear in l , as we saw in the previous subsection. Now consider m strips in an AdS planar black hole background, e.g [58]. The length of the strips is denoted by l , and the distance between them x . Now take the separation between the strips to be very large: $xT \gg 1$. The bulk minimal surface will correspond to m disconnected bulk surfaces. Nevertheless, in this section we compute the volume inside the connected surface. Although it is not the minimal surface it has an interesting property. The volume of this surface is easily computed:

$$V_{connected} = C_0(ml + (m - 1)x) - C_0(m - 1)x = C_0ml \quad (2.25)$$

where C_0 is a constant. We see that if we take the length of the strips l to be constant and we separate the strips a large distance x apart, then the volume inside the connected bulk minimal surface goes to a constant $C_0 ml$. If we take the “mutual volume” by subtracting $mV_{1-strip}$, we simply get zero.

Compare this with the area (entanglement entropy) of such a connected surface:

$$S_{connected} \sim 2C_1((m-1)x + ml) \quad , \quad xT \gg 1 \quad (2.26)$$

and this quantity grows linearly with x . So the volume of the connected surface goes to a constant independent of x , even though its area depends linearly on x .

3. Volume Transitions and Discontinuities

There are various cases in which the holographic entanglement entropy exhibits “phase transitions”, as one changes some parameter of the system. This occurs when two bulk minimal surfaces exchange dominance, and is reminiscent of 1st order phase transitions. The entanglement entropy is continuous across the transition, but there is a jump in the derivative of EE. Such transitions occur for example in disjoint entangling surfaces, global AdS black hole geometries, and confining geometries.

In this section we compute the behavior of the volume inside the minimal surface, when there are bulk transitions. In all of the examples that we consider, the volume has a discontinuous jump at the transition point. Note that these transitions imply that the volume of the entanglement wedge jumps discontinuously. In the following we will compute a few examples where such transitions occur.

3.1 Two strips in AdS_{d+1}

Figure 6: Changing the separation x between the two strips while keeping the length l fixed (or vice versa), there is a transition between minimal surfaces marked in red. We also marked in gray the volume inside the minimal surfaces.

When calculating the entanglement entropy of a subregion composed of two disjoint regions, there is a transition between a connected and a disconnected surface. More precisely, as the distance between the subregions is varied, a transition occurs when the areas of the bulk minimal surfaces exchange dominance, see Fig 6.

The EE of two parallel strips can now be easily calculated. The disconnected surface is simply the addition of two strips of length l , and the connected surface is composed of two strips of length x and $2l + x$, see Fig 6.

Figure 7: 2 strips of constant length l for an AdS_5 geometry. **Left:** $\Delta S = S_{\text{con}} - S_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of the separation distance x (in units of l) for a fixed strip length l . The red constant line is the disconnected surface area. When $\Delta S = 0$, the EE has a transition, and this occurs at $\frac{x}{l} \approx 0.71$. **Right:** Plot of $\Delta V = V_{\text{con}} - V_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of the separation distance x (in units of l) for a fixed strip length l . From the right plot it is clear that at the transition (marked by the red line) $\Delta V > 0$, hence there will be a jump in the volume. After the transition to the disconnected surface, the area and volume do not depend on x .

When calculating the difference of the volume between two types of surfaces in Fig 6, the divergent terms cancel. So for clarity we write just the finite terms. The volume of the connected surface is obtained by subtracting the volume of a strip of length x from the volume for a strip of length $(2l + x)$:

$$V_{\text{con}} = -\frac{c_0}{(x + 2l)^{d-1}} + \frac{c_0}{x^{d-1}} \quad (3.1)$$

where c_0 can be read from Eq. 2.11. The volume of the disconnected surface is simply the volume of two strips with length l :

$$V_{\text{discon}} = -\frac{2c_0}{l^{d-1}} \quad (3.2)$$

Subtracting the two volumes, we get:

$$\Delta V = V_{\text{con}} - V_{\text{discon}} = c_0 \left[-\frac{1}{(2l + x)^{d-2}} + \frac{1}{x^{d-2}} + \frac{2}{l^{d-2}} \right] > 0 \quad (3.3)$$

Note that this is always positive. Positivity can also be seen from the fact that the disconnected surface is contained inside the connected surface. In Fig. 7 we plot ΔS and ΔV as a function of $\frac{x}{l}$, with fixed l for AdS_5 geometry. The right plot shows the finite jump of the volume at the transition.

At the transition point the connected and disconnected surfaces have equal area:

$$S_{\text{con}} - S_{\text{discon}} \Big|_{\text{transition}} \propto -\frac{1}{(2l + x)^{d-2}} - \frac{1}{x^{d-2}} + \frac{2}{l^{d-2}} = 0 \quad (3.4)$$

Plugging this in eq. 3.3 gives:

$$\Delta V \Big|_{\text{transition}} = V_{\text{con}} - V_{\text{discon}} \Big|_{\text{transition}} = \frac{2c_0}{x^{d-2}} > 0 \quad (3.5)$$

Therefore at the transition point there is a finite jump in the volume.
Repeating the analysis for m strips gives:

$$\Delta V \Big|_{\text{transition}} = (m-1) \frac{2c_0}{x^{d-2}} \quad (3.6)$$

We can also do the same analysis for a D_p -brane geometry with m -strips (instead of AdS). This gives (see Eq. 2.17):

$$\Delta V \Big|_{\text{transition}} = (m-1) \frac{2c_0}{x^{\frac{p+5}{2(5-p)}}} \quad (3.7)$$

3.2 Two strips in Global AdS₃

Figure 8: Two strips in global AdS₃ at the transition point. The boundary entangling region A is marked in green, the minimal surface in blue and the volume inside the bulk surface in gray. The Left and Right plots show the connected and disconnected minimal surfaces respectively. The difference in volumes between the right and left plots is: $V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}} = 2\pi$. Note that the disconnected surface is contained inside the connected surface.

As another example, consider global AdS₃ ($d = 2$) and a strip entangling region with an opening angle at the boundary θ_∞ . The metric is given by:

$$ds^2 = -f(r)dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2d\theta^2, \quad f(r) = \frac{r^2}{L_{AdS}^2} + 1 \quad (3.8)$$

Setting $L_{AdS} = 1$ and solving the EOM the geodesic is given by:

$$r_0(\theta) = \left(\frac{\sin^2(\theta_\infty) - \sin^2(\theta)}{\cos^2(\theta_\infty)} \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3.9)$$

The volume is:

$$V(\theta_\infty) = 2 \int_0^{\theta_\infty} d\theta \int_{r_0(\theta)}^{r_\infty} dr \frac{r}{(1+r^2)^{\frac{1}{2}}} = 2\theta_\infty r_\infty - \pi \quad (3.10)$$

where $r_\infty = r(\theta_\infty)$ is the UV cutoff. The finite term is a constant equal to $-\pi$.

Now consider 2 strips of opening angle θ_∞ each. The “disconnected” and a “connected” minimal surfaces are shown in Fig. 8 at their transition point. Their volumes are:

$$V_{\text{disconn}}(\theta_\infty) = 4\theta_\infty r_\infty - 2\pi \quad , \quad V_{\text{conn}}(\theta_\infty) = 4\theta_\infty r_\infty \quad (3.11)$$

Therefore the difference of the volumes is a constant:

$$\Delta V = V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}} = 2\pi \quad (3.12)$$

and the jump in the volume at the transition point is thus:

$$\Delta V \Big|_{\text{transition}} = 2\pi \quad (3.13)$$

3.3 Strip in a Confining theory dual to $\text{AdS}_5 \times S^5$ compactified on a circle

Figure 9: The transition between connected and disconnected minimal surface for a confining background. In red we mark the codim-two minimal surface, in blue the boundary subregion A , and in gray the volume inside the minimal surface.

Figure 10: AdS_5 compactified on a circle. **Left:** $\Delta S_{EE} = S_{\text{conn}} - S_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of l (we plot here only the physical branch). The blue and red curves are the areas of the “connected” and “disconnected” surfaces respectively. The transition occurs at the point where the curves meet. **Right:** Plot of $\Delta V = V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of l . The transition point can be read from the left plot. The transition point is marked by the dashed red line, and it can be seen that there is a jump with $\Delta V < 0$ at the transition point.

Another well known example of a holographic entanglement entropy transition occurs for bulk geometries which are dual to confining theories [59]. These transitions were first studied in [17, 18] (see

also [58, 60]), and were interpreted as a probe of the confinement-deconfinement transition. The bulk minimal surface jumps from a “connected” to a “disconnected” surface as the size of the region A is changed, see Fig. 9. The entanglement entropy is continuous at the transition, but its derivative is not, as is seen in Fig. 10-Left.

The volume inside the minimal surface has a discontinuous jump at the transition point, as we will now show. We study the case of AdS_5 compactified on a spatial circle, with a strip entangling surface. However, we expect a discontinuity to occur generically in any holographic confining theory and any shaped entangling region. Similar to the case of entanglement entropy transitions, we believe that this first order phase transition of the volume is a large N effect, which will be smoothed out after computing $\frac{1}{N}$ corrections [61].

Consider the metric of AdS_5 compactified on a circle in Poincaré coordinates:

$$ds^2 = \left(\frac{L_{AdS}}{z}\right)^2 \left[\frac{dz^2}{1 - \left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right)^4} + dx^\mu dx_\mu \right] + \left(\frac{L_{AdS}}{z}\right)^2 \left(1 - \left(\frac{z}{z_0}\right)^4\right) (dx^3)^2 \quad (3.14)$$

where L_{AdS} is the radius of AdS, and z_0 is the point where the contractible cycle shrinks to zero. In this geometry we consider a strip of length l . In Fig. 10 we plot the area difference ΔS_{EE} and volume difference ΔV . From the left plot we see that the transition occurs at $l \approx 0.62$, and from the right plot it can be seen that there is a jump in the volume with $\Delta V < 0$ at the transition point. Note that the volume will keep changing (growing linearly with the size l of the region A) after the transition to the disconnected surface, unlike the area.

3.4 Global AdS black holes

In this section we consider the global AdS black hole, and a cap entangling surface. We follow the notation of [62], which considered these “Entanglement plateaux” transitions for the entanglement entropy. The minimal surface is constrained to satisfy the homology constraint. Additionally, there is a bulk region in which the minimal surface never enters, see Fig. 11. As a result there will be a discontinuous volume jump at the transition point, which we now will compute.

Consider the metric for a black hole in global AdS:

$$ds^2 = -f(r)dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 (d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\Omega_{d-2}^2) \quad , \quad f(r) = r^2 + 1 - \frac{r_+^{d-2} (r_+^2 + 1)}{r^{d-2}} \quad (3.15)$$

where r_+ is the size of the black hole horizon, and we set $L_{AdS} = 1$. The relation between the temperature and the size of the horizon is given by $r_+ = \frac{2\pi}{d} [RT + \sqrt{(RT)^2 - \frac{d(d-2)}{4\pi^2}}]$ where R is the radius of the boundary sphere.

3.4.1 Example: BTZ Black hole

For the BTZ black hole ($d = 2$) we have an analytic solution for the geodesic (see [62]):

$$r(\theta) = r_+ \left(1 - \frac{\cosh^2(r_+ \theta)}{\cosh^2(r_+ \theta_\infty)}\right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \quad (3.16)$$

where θ_∞ is the strip opening angle on the boundary. The minimal surfaces are depicted in Fig. 11 at the transition point¹³. The volume for the strip is identical to that of pure AdS, Eq. 3.10:

$$V(\theta_\infty) = 2\theta_\infty r_\infty - \pi \quad (3.17)$$

Note that this result is independent of the temperature of the black hole. Then the difference between the volumes of the connected and disconnected volumes

$$\Delta V = V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}} = -2\pi \quad (3.18)$$

Figure 11: We plot the two types of minimal surfaces for the AdS_5 black hole with horizon size $r_+ = 1$, and a cap entangling region. The surfaces are shown exactly at the transition point (when their areas are equal). In red we mark the boundary, blue is the minimal surface, green is the boundary entangling region, and gray is the volume inside the minimal surface. **Left:** The connected minimal surface. **Right:** The disconnected minimal surface. The homology constraint implies that the horizon is part of the minimal surface.

Figure 12: **Left:** Plot of $\Delta S_{EE} = S_{\text{conn}} - S_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of α for the case of an AdS_5 black hole with horizon size $r_+ = 1$. The transition occurs at $\alpha \approx 0.915$. **Right:** Plot of $\Delta V = V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of α . The transition point is marked by the red dashed line, and we see that $\Delta V|_{\text{trans.}} \approx -0.18$ in our units.

¹³In the figure the horizon size is taken as $r_+ = 1$.

3.4.2 Example: Global AdS_5 Black hole

We numerically calculate the minimal surfaces and the volume inside them (see [62] for more details on the numerical calculation). Fig. 12-Left shows the EE difference $\Delta S_{EE} = S_{\text{conn}} - S_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of α , where $\alpha \equiv \frac{\text{vol}(A)}{\text{vol}(S^{d-1})}$ (the size of the entangling surface which is a cap centered at the $\theta = 0$ with radius θ_∞). One can see a transition at $\alpha \approx 0.915$ when $\Delta S_{EE} = 0$. Fig. 12-Right shows the volume difference $\Delta V = V_{\text{conn}} - V_{\text{disconn}}$ as a function of α . One can see that the volume of the disconnected surface is always larger than the connected as expected. In particular, at the transition point ($\alpha \approx 0.915$) the volume jumps discontinuously: $\Delta V|_{\text{transition}} \approx -0.18 < 0$ in our units..

4. Discussion

In this paper we studied the codim-one volume inside the Ryu-Takayanagi surface, first considered in [48]. We performed explicit computations for various examples in time-independent geometries. We found that for an AdS black hole, the volume is a non-monotonic function of the strip's length at a fixed finite temperature, even though the EE is monotonic. We also showed that the volume exhibits a discontinuous jump in geometries for which two bulk minimal surfaces exchange dominance. It will be important to understand better the QFT quantity dual to the subregion volume, and the significance of its universal terms in order to compare to the bulk results. It will be also interesting to understand the dual interpretation of the discontinuous jump in the volume assuming that this is indeed the dual of quantum complexity of a subregion. As we mentioned before these jumps imply that the volume of the entanglement wedge exhibits a discontinuous jumps under small changes of the reduced density matrix.

It would be interesting to compute the subregion volume for time dependent backgrounds (e.g quenches). The time dependence was very important in the study of holographic complexity of Susskind et al. for the case in which the region A is the whole boundary, and the bulk geometry is a double sided black hole. In that case, the linear late time behavior matches the expectation from complexity.

It would also be interesting to understand $\frac{1}{N}$ corrections to the subregion volume. For the entanglement entropy this is given by the bulk EE, where the entangling region is precisely the volume inside the RT surface [61]. It would be interesting to understand if there is a relation to bulk relative entropy [16, 63, 64]. Another direction would be to understand the behavior of the volume for higher derivative gravity in the bulk.

The suggestion of [65] is a reformulation of the Ryu-Takayanagi formula in terms of bit threads, which loosely speaking probe the volume inside the RT surface. It would be interesting to understand our results in terms of the bit thread formulation.

In [50] it was shown that the quantum fisher information metric (the 2nd correction of the relative entropy) for a sphere and a CFT is dual to the canonical energy integrated inside the RT surface. Instead, one can alternatively integrate other bulk fields inside the volume, and try to understand the dual information theoretic quantities.

One can study further properties of the subregion volume by performing relevant perturbations or shape perturbations. From the analysis of [66], it can be immediately shown that the volume corresponding to entangling surfaces with a rotational or translational symmetry is an extremum with respect to shape perturbations of the entangling surface.

For some entangling surfaces Σ , when there are no transitions between bulk extremal surfaces, the volume inside the RT surface can be foliated with bulk extremal surfaces attached to concentric entangling surfaces with different scales. Perhaps this result can relate the subregion volume (complexity) to an integral over entanglement entropies.

Acknowledgments

We thank Rob Myers for many helpful discussions. We also thank Mohsen Alishahiha, Michal Heller, and Pratik Rath. The work of OB and DC is partially supported by the Israel Science Foundation (grant 1989/14), the US-Israel bi-national fund (BSF) grant 2012383 and the German Israel bi-national fund GIF grant number I-244-303.7-2013. DC is grateful for the support from the “visiting graduate fellows” program at the Perimeter Institute. Research at Perimeter Institute is supported by the Government of Canada through the Department of Innovation, Science and Economic Development and by the Province of Ontario through the Ministry of Research & Innovation.

A. Leading temperature Correction for a Sphere

We will show that the 1st order temperature correction to the volume vanishes for a sphere entangling surface of radius l (we thus verify the calculation of [48]). Consider again the general asymptotically AdS metric:

$$ds^2 = \frac{1}{z^2} \left[f_0(z) dt^2 + f_1(z) dx_\mu^2 + f_2(z) dz^2 \right] \quad (\text{A.1})$$

Where for a black hole geometry at small temperature, $f_1(z) = 1$ and $f_2(z) = \frac{1}{1 - k_0 T^d z^d} \approx 1 + k_0 T^d z^d$.

The area of a bulk surface is:

$$\text{Area} = \int_\delta^{z_*} dz \frac{r(z)^{d-2} \sqrt{f_2(z) + r'^2}}{z^{d-1}} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where r is a radial coordinate. The equation of motion is:

$$(d-2) \frac{r^{d-3}}{z^{d-1}} \sqrt{f_2(z) + r'^2} - \frac{d}{dz} \left(\frac{r^{d-2} r'}{z^{d-1} \sqrt{f_2(z) + r'^2}} \right) = 0 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

To 1st order in T^d , the solution is:

$$r(z) = \sqrt{z_*^2 - z^2} + k_0 T^d \frac{2z_*^{d+2} - z^d(z_*^2 + z^2)}{2(d+1)\sqrt{z_*^2 - z^2}} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

The volume inside the bulk minimal surface is:

$$V = \int_\delta^{z_*} dz \frac{\sqrt{f_2(z)} r^{d-1}(z)}{z^d} \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Plugging $r(z)$ from Eq. A.4 gives:

$$V(l) \propto \int_\delta^{l - \frac{k_0 T^d l^{d+1}}{(d+1)}} dz \frac{(l^2 - z^2)^{(d-1)/2}}{z^d} \left[1 + \frac{k_0 T^d}{2} z^d \right] \left[1 - k_0 T^d \frac{(d-1)z^d(l^2 + z^2)}{2(d+1)(l^2 - z^2)} \right] \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Expanding at linear order in T^d , and changing variables to $t = z/l$ gives:

$$V(l) - V_{T=0}(l) \propto \frac{T^d l^d}{(d+1)} \int_0^1 dt \frac{(1-t^2)^{\frac{d-3}{2}}}{t^d} [t^d - dt^{d+2}] = 0 \quad (\text{A.7})$$

and the integral is zero. Therefore we showed that the 1st order temperature correction to the volume vanishes for a sphere entangling surface.

B. The Volume and Action of the Entanglement wedge

The entanglement wedge [55] is a codim-zero bulk region defined as the bulk domain of dependence¹⁴ of the volume inside the HRT surface. Thus the HRT surface is the rim of the entanglement wedge. It was argued in [55] that the entanglement wedge is the region most suitable to be the bulk dual of the reduced density matrix.

B.1 The volume of the entanglement wedge for a sphere and pure AdS

As a simple example consider Poincaré AdS_{d+1} and a sphere entangling surface of radius l :

$$z^2 + r^2 = l^2 \quad (\text{B.1})$$

The corresponding entanglement wedge is half of a cone in the bulk in Poincaré coordinates, and is shown in Fig. 13 for the case of AdS_3 . The null boundary surface of the entanglement wedge (for $t > 0$) is given by the equation:

$$\sqrt{r^2 + z^2} = l - t \quad (\text{B.2})$$

where t is the time, $r = \sqrt{x_i^2}$ is a boundary radial coordinate, z is the bulk coordinate, and l is the radius of the entangling surface sphere. Thus, the volume of the entanglement wedge is simply given by twice (because there is an equal contribution from $t < 0$) the volume inside the surface of Eq. B.2:

$$V_{wedge} = 2 \int_0^l dt \int_{\delta}^{l-t} dz \sqrt{g(z)} \int_0^{\sqrt{(l-t)^2 - z^2}} dr r^{d-2} \Omega_{d-2} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where Ω_{d-2} is the area of a $(d-2)$ -sphere, and $\sqrt{g(z)} = z^{-(d+1)}$. We can easily expand this integral to derive the leading divergences:

$$V_{wedge} = \frac{2\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \int_0^l dt \int_{\delta}^{l-t} dz \frac{((l-t)^2 - z^2)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{z^{d+1}} = \frac{2\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \left[\frac{1}{d^2} \frac{l^d}{\delta^d} - \frac{d-1}{2(d-2)^2} \frac{l^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} + \dots \right] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

Note that the leading divergence goes like $\frac{1}{\delta^d}$, and there are subleading divergences $\frac{1}{\delta^{d-2}} + \dots$ etc. We can also easily compute the universal finite or log terms.

¹⁴The causal domain of dependence $D[A]$ of a region A is defined as the set of all points P for which all causal curves through P intersect A .

Figure 13: For AdS_3 and an interval A , showing the the entanglement wedge region (the inside of the half-cone). The region A is the blue interval, and the bulk minimal surface is the gray dashed curve.

B.2 The action in the entanglement wedge

In the previous section we calculated the volume of the entanglement wedge. In this section we consider a related quantity, the gravitational action computed inside the entanglement wedge. We stick to the simple example of a sphere entangling surface and Poincaré AdS.

The gravitational action is composed of a bulk term, a null-boundary term, and a corner term (for more details see [43, 44, 67]):

$$\mathcal{A} = \mathcal{A}_{bulk} + \mathcal{A}_{Null} + \mathcal{A}_{corner} = \frac{1}{16\pi G} \int d^{d+1}x \sqrt{-g} \left(\mathcal{R} - \frac{d(d-1)}{L_{AdS}^2} \right) \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$+ \frac{1}{8\pi G} \int d\lambda \sqrt{-\gamma} d^d x \kappa + \frac{1}{8\pi G} \int d^{d-1}x \sqrt{-\tilde{g}} a \quad (\text{B.6})$$

For pure AdS, the bulk term is proportional to the volume that we computed in a previous section:

$$\mathcal{A}_{bulk} = \left(\mathcal{R} - \frac{d(d-1)}{L_{AdS}^2} \right) V_{wedge} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where V_{wedge} was computed in Eq. B.4.

We can choose an affine parameter, and then κ is zero and the null boundary terms vanish, see [43, 44, 67]:

$$\mathcal{A}_{Null} = 0 \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The codim-two corner term of the action arises from the dashed gray curve in Fig. 13. The action contribution from this corner is (see [43, 44]) :

$$\mathcal{A}_{corner} = \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{u_3 u_4}}{L^2} \delta \right) \left[\frac{l^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} + \frac{l^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \dots \right] + \left[\frac{l^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} + \frac{l^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \dots \right] \quad (\text{B.9})$$

where $u_{3,4}$ are the normalization vectors of the null boundaries of the entanglement wedge. Above, there are only even or odd powers, but not both. Summing the bulk and corner terms, we obtain the action in the entanglement wedge.

References

- [1] P. Calabrese and J. L. Cardy, “Entanglement entropy and quantum field theory,” *J. Stat. Mech.* **0406** (2004) P06002, [arXiv:hep-th/0405152](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [2] H. Casini and M. Huerta, “Entanglement entropy in free quantum field theory,” *J. Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504007, [arXiv:0905.2562](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [3] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, “A Quantum Source of Entropy for Black Holes,” *Phys. Rev.* **D34** (1986) 373–383.
- [4] A. Lewkowycz and J. Maldacena, “Generalized gravitational entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2013) 090, [arXiv:1304.4926](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [5] M. Srednicki, “Entropy and area,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71** (1993) 666–669, [arXiv:hep-th/9303048](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [6] H. Casini, M. Huerta, and R. C. Myers, “Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **05** (2011) 036, [arXiv:1102.0440](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [7] C. Holzhey, F. Larsen, and F. Wilczek, “Geometric and renormalized entropy in conformal field theory,” *Nucl. Phys.* **B424** (1994) 443–467, [arXiv:hep-th/9403108](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [8] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy, conformal invariance and extrinsic geometry,” *Phys. Lett.* **B665** (2008) 305–309, [arXiv:0802.3117](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [9] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2006) 045, [arXiv:hep-th/0605073](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [10] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [arXiv:hep-th/0603001](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [11] T. Nishioka, S. Ryu, and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy: An Overview,” *J. Phys.* **A42** (2009) 504008, [arXiv:0905.0932](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [12] M. Headrick, “Entanglement Renyi entropies in holographic theories,” *Phys. Rev.* **D82** (2010) 126010, [arXiv:1006.0047](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [13] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “On Holographic Entanglement Entropy and Higher Curvature Gravity,” *JHEP* **04** (2011) 025, [arXiv:1101.5813](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [14] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Some Calculable Contributions to Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2011) 039, [arXiv:1105.6055](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [15] O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, and M. Smolkin, “Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres,” *JHEP* **08** (2015) 048, [arXiv:1504.00913](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [16] D. D. Blanco, H. Casini, L.-Y. Hung, and R. C. Myers, “Relative Entropy and Holography,” *JHEP* **08** (2013) 060, [arXiv:1305.3182](#) [[hep-th](#)].
- [17] T. Nishioka and T. Takayanagi, “AdS Bubbles, Entropy and Closed String Tachyons,” *JHEP* **01** (2007) 090, [arXiv:hep-th/0611035](#) [[hep-th](#)].

- [18] I. R. Klebanov, D. Kutasov, and A. Murugan, “Entanglement as a probe of confinement,” *Nucl. Phys.* **B796** (2008) 274–293, [arXiv:0709.2140 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [19] J. M. Maldacena, “The Large N limit of superconformal field theories and supergravity,” *Int. J. Theor. Phys.* **38** (1999) 1113–1133, [arXiv:hep-th/9711200 \[hep-th\]](#). [Adv. Theor. Math. Phys.2,231(1998)].
- [20] S. S. Gubser, I. R. Klebanov, and A. M. Polyakov, “Gauge theory correlators from noncritical string theory,” *Phys. Lett.* **B428** (1998) 105–114, [arXiv:hep-th/9802109 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [21] E. Witten, “Anti-de Sitter space and holography,” *Adv. Theor. Math. Phys.* **2** (1998) 253–291, [arXiv:hep-th/9802150 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [22] O. Aharony, S. S. Gubser, J. M. Maldacena, H. Ooguri, and Y. Oz, “Large N field theories, string theory and gravity,” *Phys. Rept.* **323** (2000) 183–386, [arXiv:hep-th/9905111 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [23] V. E. Hubeny, M. Rangamani, and T. Takayanagi, “A Covariant holographic entanglement entropy proposal,” *JHEP* **07** (2007) 062, [arXiv:0705.0016 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [24] L. Susskind, “Entanglement is not enough,” *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 49–71, [arXiv:1411.0690 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [25] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, “Holographic Complexity Equals Bulk Action?,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116** no.~19, (2016) 191301, [arXiv:1509.07876 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [26] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, “Complexity, action, and black holes,” *Phys. Rev.* **D93** no.~8, (2016) 086006, [arXiv:1512.04993 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [27] D. Stanford and L. Susskind, “Complexity and Shock Wave Geometries,” *Phys. Rev.* **D90** no.~12, (2014) 126007, [arXiv:1406.2678 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [28] L. Susskind and Y. Zhao, “Switchbacks and the Bridge to Nowhere,” [arXiv:1408.2823 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [29] L. Susskind, “Computational Complexity and Black Hole Horizons,” *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 24–43, [arXiv:1403.5695 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [30] L. Susskind, “Computational Complexity and Black hole horizons,” [arXiv:1402.5674](#) .
- [31] A. R. Brown, L. Susskind, and Y. Zhao, “Quantum Complexity and Negative Curvature,” [arXiv:1608.02612 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [32] J. M. Maldacena, “Eternal black holes in anti-de Sitter,” *JHEP* **04** (2003) 021, [arXiv:hep-th/0106112 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [33] J. Maldacena and L. Susskind, “Cool horizons for entangled black holes,” *Fortsch. Phys.* **61** (2013) 781–811, [arXiv:1306.0533 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [34] T. Hartman and J. Maldacena, “Time Evolution of Entanglement Entropy from Black Hole Interiors,” *JHEP* **05** (2013) 014, [arXiv:1303.1080 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [35] V. E. Hubeny and H. Maxfield, “Holographic probes of collapsing black holes,” *JHEP* **03** (2014) 097, [arXiv:1312.6887 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [36] H. Liu and S. J. Suh, “Entanglement Tsunami: Universal Scaling in Holographic Thermalization,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **112** (2014) 011601, [arXiv:1305.7244 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [37] H. Liu and S. J. Suh, “Entanglement growth during thermalization in holographic systems,” *Phys. Rev.* **D89** no.~6, (2014) 066012, [arXiv:1311.1200 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [38] R.-G. Cai, S.-M. Ruan, S.-J. Wang, R.-Q. Yang, and R.-H. Peng, “Complexity Growth for AdS Black Holes,” [arXiv:1606.08307 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [39] J. L. F. Barbon and E. Rabinovici, “Holographic complexity and spacetime singularities,” *JHEP* **01** (2016) 084, [arXiv:1509.09291 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [40] J. L. F. Barbon and J. Martin-Garcia, “Holographic Complexity Of Cold Hyperbolic Black Holes,” *JHEP* **11** (2015) 181, [arXiv:1510.00349 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [41] W. Chemissany and T. J. Osborne, “Holographic fluctuations and the principle of minimal complexity,” [arXiv:1605.07768 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [42] V. Vanchurin, “Dual Field Theories of Quantum Computation,” [arXiv:1603.07982 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [43] L. Lehner, R. C. Myers, E. Poisson, and R. D. Sorkin, “Gravitational action with null boundaries,” [arXiv:1609.00207 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [44] D. Carmi, R. C. Myers, and P. Rath, “On Holographic Complexity Conjectures,” *To appear*.
- [45] M. Christodoulou and C. Rovelli, “How big is a black hole?,” *Phys. Rev.* **D91** no.~6, (2015) 064046, [arXiv:1411.2854 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [46] M. Christodoulou and T. De Lorenzo, “On the volume inside old black holes,” [arXiv:1604.07222 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [47] S. Lloyd, “Ultimate physical limits to computation,” *Nature* **406** (2000), no. 6799 1047 -1054.
- [48] M. Alishahiha, “Holographic Complexity,” *Phys. Rev.* **D92** no.~12, (2015) 126009, [arXiv:1509.06614 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [49] M. Miyaji, T. Numasawa, N. Shiba, T. Takayanagi, and K. Watanabe, “Distance between Quantum States and Gauge-Gravity Duality,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **115** no.~26, (2015) 261602, [arXiv:1507.07555 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [50] N. Lashkari and M. Van Raamsdonk, “Canonical Energy is Quantum Fisher Information,” *JHEP* **04** (2016) 153, [arXiv:1508.00897 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [51] D. Momeni, S. A. H. Mansoori, and R. Myrzakulov, “Holographic Complexity in Gauge/String Superconductors,” *Phys. Lett.* **B756** (2016) 354–357, [arXiv:1601.03011 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [52] D. Momeni, K. Myrzakulov, and R. Myrzakulov, “Fidelity Susceptibility as Holographic PV criticality,” [arXiv:1604.06909 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [53] D. Momeni, M. Faizal, S. Bahamonde, A. Myrzakul, and R. Myrzakulov, “A Holographic Bound for D3-Brane,” [arXiv:1608.08819 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [54] N. S. Mazhari, D. Momeni, S. Bahamonde, M. Faizal, and R. Myrzakulov, “Holographic Complexity and Fidelity Susceptibility as Holographic Information Dual to Different Volumes in AdS,” [arXiv:1609.00250 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [55] M. Headrick, V. E. Hubeny, A. Lawrence, and M. Rangamani, “Causality & holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **12** (2014) 162, [arXiv:1408.6300 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [56] N. Itzhaki, J. M. Maldacena, J. Sonnenschein, and S. Yankielowicz, “Supergravity and the large N limit of theories with sixteen supercharges,” *Phys. Rev.* **D58** (1998) 046004, [arXiv:hep-th/9802042 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [57] W. Fischler and S. Kundu, “Strongly Coupled Gauge Theories: High and Low Temperature Behavior of Non-local Observables,” *JHEP* **05** (2013) 098, [arXiv:1212.2643 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [58] O. Ben-Ami, D. , and J. Sonnenschein, “Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips,” *JHEP* **11** (2014) 144, [arXiv:1409.6305 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [59] E. Witten, “Anti-de Sitter space, thermal phase transition, and confinement in gauge theories,” *Adv. Theor. Math. Phys.* **2** (1998) 505–532, [arXiv:hep-th/9803131 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [60] U. Kol, C. Nunez, D. Schofield, J. Sonnenschein, and M. Warschawski, “Confinement, Phase Transitions and non-Locality in the Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **06** (2014) 005, [arXiv:1403.2721 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [61] T. Faulkner, A. Lewkowycz, and J. Maldacena, “Quantum corrections to holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **11** (2013) 074, [arXiv:1307.2892 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [62] V. E. Hubeny, H. Maxfield, M. Rangamani, and E. Tonni, “Holographic entanglement plateaux,” *JHEP* **08** (2013) 092, [arXiv:1306.4004 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [63] D. L. Jafferis, A. Lewkowycz, J. Maldacena, and S. J. Suh, “Relative entropy equals bulk relative entropy,” [arXiv:1512.06431 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [64] D. L. Jafferis and S. J. Suh, “The Gravity Duals of Modular Hamiltonians,” [arXiv:1412.8465 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [65] M. Freedman and M. Headrick, “Bit threads and holographic entanglement,” [arXiv:1604.00354 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [66] D. Carmi, “On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **12** (2015) 043, [arXiv:1506.07528 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [67] K. Parattu, S. Chakraborty, B. R. Majhi, and T. Padmanabhan, “A Boundary Term for the Gravitational Action with Null Boundaries,” *Gen. Rel. Grav.* **48** no. 7, (2016) 94, [arXiv:1501.01053 \[gr-qc\]](#).

Chapter 7

Comments on Holographic Complexity

Comments on Holographic Complexity

Dean Carmi,^{1,2} Robert C. Myers¹ and Pratik Rath^{1,3}

¹ *Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics
31 Caroline Street North, Waterloo, ON N2L 2Y5, Canada*

² *Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences
School of Physics and Astronomy, Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel*

³ *Center for Theoretical Physics and Department of Physics
University of California, Berkeley, CA 94720, USA*

ABSTRACT: We study two recent conjectures for holographic complexity: the complexity=action conjecture and the complexity=volume conjecture. In particular, we examine the structure of the UV divergences appearing in these quantities, and show that the coefficients can be written as local integrals of geometric quantities in the boundary. We also consider extending these conjectures to evaluate the complexity of the mixed state produced by reducing the pure global state to a specific subregion of the boundary time slice. The UV divergences in this subregion complexity have a similar geometric structure, but there are also new divergences associated with the geometry of the surface enclosing the boundary region of interest. We discuss possible implications arising from the geometric nature of these UV divergences.

Contents

1. Introduction	1
2. Complexity Equals Volume Conjecture	3
3. Complexity Equals Action Conjecture	7
4. Subregion Complexity: CV Duality	13
5. Subregion Complexity: CA duality	16
6. Discussion	22
A. Action User's Manual	29
B. Example: Extremal volume for a spherical boundary	32
C. Example: Wheeler-DeWitt action for global AdS	34
D. Geometric details for CA duality calculation	37

1. Introduction

Concepts and perspectives from quantum information science are having a rapidly growing influence in investigations of quantum field theory and quantum gravity. Quantum complexity is one such concept which has recently begun to be discussed. Loosely speaking, the complexity of a particular state corresponds to the minimum number of simple (universal) gates needed to build a quantum circuit which prepares this state from a particular reference state, *e.g.*, see [1, 2, 3]. In the context of the AdS/CFT correspondence, discussions have focused on understanding the growth of the Einstein-Rosen bridge for AdS black holes in terms of quantum complexity in the dual boundary CFT [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10].

There are two independent proposals to evaluate the complexity of a holographic boundary state, which we will refer to as the complexity=volume (CV) conjecture [4, 5, 6, 7, 8] and the complexity=action (CA) conjecture [9, 10]. The first of the proposals states that the complexity of the boundary state is dual to the volume of the extremal codimension-one bulk hypersurface which meets the asymptotic boundary on the desired time slice.¹ More precisely, the CV duality states that the complexity of the state on a time slice Σ is given by:

$$\mathcal{C}_v(\Sigma) = \max_{\Sigma=\partial\mathcal{B}} \left[\frac{\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{B})}{G_N \ell} \right], \quad (1.1)$$

¹An alternative proposal related to complexity=volume was recently put forward in [11]. We also note that similar extremal volumes in the interior of asymptotically flat black holes were studied in [12, 13].

where \mathcal{B} is the corresponding bulk surface and ℓ is some length scale associated with the bulk geometry, *e.g.*, the AdS curvature scale or the horizon radius of a black hole. The ambiguity in choosing the latter scale is an unappealing feature of CV duality and provided some motivation for developing CA duality [9, 10]. This second conjecture equates the complexity with the gravitational action evaluated on a particular bulk region, now known as the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) patch:

$$\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) = \frac{I_{\text{WDW}}}{\pi \hbar}. \quad (1.2)$$

The WDW patch can be defined as the domain of dependence of any Cauchy surface in the bulk which asymptotically approaches the time slice Σ on the boundary.

The complexity evaluated with either the CV or CA duality satisfies a number of expected properties, *e.g.*, they continue to grow (linearly with time) after the boundary theory reaches thermal equilibrium. However, the second conjecture has certain advantages. In particular, as noted above, CV duality requires choosing an additional length scale, while there are no free parameters in eq. (1.2) for the CA duality. However, the latter faced the obstacle that when the conjecture was originally proposed, there was no rigorous method for evaluating the gravitational action on spacetime regions with null boundaries. This problem was recently overcome with a careful analysis of the boundary terms which must be added to the gravitational action for null boundary surfaces and for joints where such null boundaries intersect with other boundary surfaces [14].

On the gravity side, either of these dualities deals with a geometric entity which extends to the asymptotic AdS boundary and as a result, the holographic complexity is divergent. To understand these divergences, it is natural to draw upon lessons from holographic entanglement entropy [15, 16]. In particular, for both the CV duality and holographic entanglement entropy, the bulk calculations evaluate the volume of an extremal surface extending to the asymptotic boundary. Now UV divergences are found in calculating holographic entanglement entropy, *e.g.*, [17, 18], and these divergences are related to the existence of correlations down to arbitrarily short scales in the boundary CFT. The leading divergence gives rise to the famous ‘area law’ term [19, 20] and the subleading divergent terms involve integrals of curvature invariants, both extrinsic and intrinsic, over the entangling surface in the boundary. In this paper, we will examine the divergent contributions appearing in holographic complexity and show that the structure of these UV divergent terms in the holographic complexity have a similar geometric interpretation in the boundary CFT, *i.e.*, the coefficients in these divergent terms are given by local geometric integrals over the time slice of interest. One might have anticipated that the UV divergences would appear in the complexity from the necessity of establishing correlations down to the cut-off scale in the boundary CFT. As we comment in the discussion section, the geometric structure of these divergences leads to some unusual behaviour for the complexity.

We also consider the structure of divergences for the holographic complexity of subregions, *i.e.*, evaluating the complexity of the mixed state produced by reducing the global boundary state to specific subregion on the time slice. The latter idea was discussed previously for time-independent geometries in, *e.g.*, [21, 22]. We will begin by proposing a covariant extension of eqs. (1.1) and (1.2) which aims to evaluate subregion complexity. Our proposals are motivated by the suggestion that the mixed state on the boundary is encoded in the corresponding entanglement wedge in the bulk [23, 24]. We then find a

similar geometric structure for the UV divergences in this subregion complexity, but there are also new divergences associated with the entangling surface which encloses the boundary region.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 considers the CV conjecture and we investigate the structure of UV divergences appearing in $\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma)$. The coefficients of the divergences are given in terms of extrinsic and intrinsic curvatures integrated over the boundary time slice. In section 3, we study the analogous divergences arising in the CA conjecture. In particular, $\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma)$ contains an additional class of divergences involving the logarithm of the cutoff scale, which are produced where the null boundaries reach the asymptotic AdS boundary. Next we extend our studies to consider the complexity of subregions on the boundary. In section 4, we propose an extension of CV duality with a covariant definition of extremal surface whose volume defines the subregion complexity, and we study the divergence structure of this quantity. In section 5, we propose an extension of CA duality to evaluate subregion complexity and we examine the corresponding UV divergences. In section 6, we conclude with a brief discussion of our results, and we consider some directions for future research. In appendix A, we review the prescription introduced by [14] for computing the gravitational action in the presence of null boundary surfaces. In appendix B, we apply the CV duality to a simple example and compare the results to the general geometric expressions found in section 2. In appendix C, we apply the CA duality to the simple example of global AdS and compare the results to the general geometric expressions found in section 3. We also show the coefficients of the logarithmic divergences agree for two different schemes to regulate the bulk divergences. In appendix D, we provide some geometric details which are needed for our CA duality calculations in section 3.

2. Complexity Equals Volume Conjecture

In this section, we examine the structure of UV divergences appearing in holographic complexity for the complexity=volume (CV) conjecture [4, 5, 6, 7, 8]. Recall that the CV duality is captured by eq. (1.1) and the corresponding construction is illustrated in Figure 1. Of course, the asymptotic AdS metric diverges at the boundary and so this prescription would yield a divergent volume for the extremal bulk surface, and hence a divergent complexity. As usual, we regulate the calculation by introducing a cut-off surface at some large radius, which will be related to a short-distance cut-off in the boundary theory — see, *e.g.*, [25, 26, 27]. Given this framework, we want to study the structure of the UV divergences appearing in the complexity.

In the following, we are borrowing results from [17, 18] — see also [26, 27, 28]. According to the Fefferman-Graham (FG) construction [29, 30], any asymptotically AdS geometry can be described with the following metric:

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{z^2} (dz^2 + g_{ij}(x, z) dx^i dx^j) . \quad (2.1)$$

where L is the AdS radius, x^i denote the boundary directions,² and z is the radial coordinate in the

²Our notation in the following will be: Greek indices μ denote tensors in the bulk spacetime and run from 0 to d ; Latin indices i from the middle of the alphabet denote tensors in the boundary spacetime, running from 0 to $d - 1$; and Latin indices a from the beginning of the alphabet denote tensors in the boundary time slice, running from 1 to $d - 1$. We note that often the metric (2.1) is expressed in terms of the dimensionless radial coordinate $\rho = z^2/L^2$ — see [26, 27].

Figure 1: Showing the extremal volume construction for the CV conjecture for AdS_3 . We regulate the volume by introducing a cutoff surface at $z = \delta$, where δ is the short-distance cutoff in the boundary theory.

bulk. For d boundary dimensions, $g_{ij}(x, z)$ admits a Taylor series expansion in z^2 near the asymptotic boundary, *i.e.*, as $z \rightarrow 0$,

$$g_{ij}(x, \rho) = g_{ij}^{(0)}(x^i) + z^2 g_{ij}^{(1)}(x^i) + z^4 g_{ij}^{(2)}(x^i) + \cdots + z^{d(d/2)} g_{ij}^{(d/2)}(x^i) + z^d \log(z/L) f_{ij}(x^i) + \cdots \quad (2.2)$$

where $g_{ij}^{(0)}$ is the boundary metric. We note that the logarithmic term arises only for even d . We see that this Taylor series breaks down at $\mathcal{O}(z^d)$ where the logarithmic terms above start appearing for even d ($f_{ij}(x^i)$ is determined by $g_{ij}^{(0)}(x^i)$), or where odd powers, *e.g.*, z^d , start appearing for odd d . All of the expansion coefficients $g_{ij}^{(n)}$ for $n < d/2$ are determined in terms of the boundary metric $g_{ij}^{(0)}$ via the Einstein equations, *e.g.*, see [17, 26, 27]. For example,

$$g_{ij}^{(1)}(x^i) = -\frac{1}{d-2} \left(\mathcal{R}_{ij}[g^{(0)}] - \frac{g_{ij}^{(0)}}{2(d-1)} \mathcal{R}[g^{(0)}] \right) \quad (2.3)$$

where $\mathcal{R}_{ij}[g^{(0)}]$ and $\mathcal{R}[g^{(0)}]$ are the Ricci tensor and Ricci scalar, respectively, calculated using the boundary metric $g_{ij}^{(0)}$. At order $\mathcal{O}(z^d)$, an independent solution (starting from $g_{ij}^{(d/2)}(x^i)$) appears which cannot be fixed by the boundary metric alone and it contains information about the expectation value of the boundary stress tensor, *e.g.*, [26, 27].

As described earlier, we pick a time slice Σ on the boundary and then look for the extremal codimension-one bulk surface \mathcal{B} which approaches this slice at the boundary. We describe this submanifold embedded in the $d+1$ dimensional bulk using coordinates $X^\mu = X^\mu(\tau, \sigma^a)$, where $X^\mu = \{z, x^i\}$ and $\{\tau, \sigma^a\}$ are coordinates intrinsic to the submanifold \mathcal{B} . The induced metric on the bulk surface is:

$$h_{\alpha\beta} = \partial_\alpha X^\mu \partial_\beta X^\nu G_{\mu\nu}[X] \quad (2.4)$$

For simplicity, we make the gauge choice

$$\tau = z, \quad h_{a\tau} = 0. \quad (2.5)$$

Then from eq. (1.1), the complexity is:

$$\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{1}{G_N L} \int_{\mathcal{B}} d^{d-1} \sigma d\tau \sqrt{h} \quad (2.6)$$

where for simplicity, we have chosen $\ell = L$, the AdS scale.

Extremizing the volume above gives the following equation of motion:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{h}} \partial_\alpha \left(\sqrt{h} h^{\alpha\beta} \partial_\beta X^\mu \right) + h^{\alpha\beta} \Gamma_{\nu\sigma}^\mu \partial_\alpha X^\nu \partial_\beta X^\sigma = 0. \quad (2.7)$$

where $\Gamma_{\nu\sigma}^\mu$ are the Christoffel symbols associated with the bulk metric $G_{\mu\nu}$. This equation can be solved order by order near the boundary with a series solution for $X^i(\tau, \sigma^a)$ [30]:

$$X^i(\tau, \sigma^a) = X^{(0)i}(\sigma^a) + z^2 X^{(1)i}(\sigma^a) + z^4 X^{(2)i}(\sigma^a) + \dots. \quad (2.8)$$

For $n < \frac{d+1}{2}$ the term $X^{(n)i}$ is determined by $X^{(0)i}$. For example, solving for $X^{(1)i}$ yields:

$$X^{(1)i} = \frac{L^2}{2(d-1)} \left(\nabla_a \partial^a X^{(0)i} + \partial^a X^{(0)j} \partial_a X^{(0)k} \Gamma_{jk}^i \right) = \frac{L^2}{2(d-1)} K \mathbf{n}^i, \quad (2.9)$$

where \mathbf{n}^i is the (future pointing) timelike unit normal to the time slice Σ (in the boundary), and K is the trace of the corresponding extrinsic curvature.

Using eqs. (2.3) and (2.9), one can begin to write the induced metric (2.4) in a near boundary series expansion as well, *e.g.*,

$$h_{zz} = \frac{L^2}{z^2} \left(1 + z^2 h_{zz}^{(1)} + \dots \right), \quad h_{ab} = \frac{L^2}{z^2} \left(h_{ab}^{(0)} + z^2 h_{ab}^{(1)} + \dots \right) \quad (2.10)$$

where $h_{ab}^{(0)}$ represents the induced metric on the boundary time slice and $h_{\alpha\beta}^{(1)}$ are the first order corrections. In particular, we find

$$\begin{aligned} h_{zz}^{(1)} &= \frac{4X^{(1)i} X^{(1)j} g_{ij}^{(0)}}{L^2} = -\frac{1}{(d-1)^2} K^2, \\ h_{ab}^{(1)} &= \left(\partial_a X^{(1)i} \partial_b X^{(1)j} + \partial_a X^{(0)i} \partial_b X^{(1)j} \right) g_{ij}^{(0)} + \partial_a X^{(0)i} \partial_b X^{(1)j} g_{ij}^{(1)} \\ &= -\frac{1}{d-1} \left(\frac{d-1}{d-2} \mathcal{R}_{ab} - \frac{\mathcal{R}}{2(d-2)} h_{ab}^{(0)} - K K_{ab} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where \mathcal{R}_{ab} is the projection of the boundary Ricci tensor into the time slice Σ , *i.e.*, $\mathcal{R}_{ab} = e_a^i e_b^j \mathcal{R}_{ij}$ with $e_a^i = \frac{\partial X^i}{\partial \sigma^a}$. Further note that in both of these expressions, we have implicitly used $\mathbf{n}^i \mathbf{n}^j g_{ij}^{(0)} = -1$.

Given the bulk metric (2.1), we introduce a regulator surface at $\rho = \delta^2/L^2$, where δ then plays the role of a short distance cut-off in the boundary CFT. From eq. (2.6), we can now extract the leading divergences in the complexity

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_V &= \frac{1}{G_N L} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \int_{z=\delta} dz \frac{L^d}{z^d} \sqrt{h^{(0)}} \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{2} \left(h_{zz}^{(1)} + h^{ab(0)} h_{ab}^{(1)} \right) + \dots \right) \\ &= \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h^{(0)}} \left(\frac{1}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} + \frac{1}{2(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} \left(h_{\tau\tau}^{(1)} + h^{ab(0)} h_{ab}^{(1)} \right) + \dots \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2.12)$$

Substituting eq. (2.11), we find

$$\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{L^{d-1}}{(d-1)G_N} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{(d-1)}{2(d-2)(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} \left(\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{R} - \frac{(d-2)^2}{(d-1)^2} K^2 \right) + \dots \right] \quad (2.13)$$

where to simplify the notation, we denote the induced metric on the boundary time slice as simply: $h_{ab} = h_{ab}^{(0)}$. In the above, we also use $\mathcal{R}_a^a = h^{ab} \mathcal{R}_{ab}$. The power law divergent terms here are regulator dependent, but we see that their coefficients have a geometric interpretation, *e.g.*, the leading divergence scales as the volume of Σ while the sub-leading terms involve integrals of curvature invariants over this time slice. Of course, this is very similar in nature to the divergence structure found in holographic entanglement entropy. If we consider the special case of $d = 3$ dimensions, the first sub-leading divergence in eq. (2.13) is replaced by a logarithmic term

$$\mathcal{C}_V^{(\text{universal})} = \log \left(\frac{\delta}{L} \right) \frac{L^2}{8G_N} \int d^2 \sigma \sqrt{h} (4 \mathcal{R}_a^a - 2 \mathcal{R} - K^2). \quad (2.14)$$

Similar logarithmic divergences will generally appear whenever the boundary dimension is odd, *i.e.*, when the extremal surface is even dimensional. Of course, they are related to the submanifold conformal anomalies studied in [31]. The dimensionless coefficient(s) of these logarithmic divergences will be regulator-independent parameters characterizing the underlying boundary theory. As expected in eq. (2.14), this parameter is proportional to $L^2/G_N \sim L^2/\ell_{\text{Planck}}^2$. This ratio is well known to characterize the number of degrees of freedom in the boundary CFT dual to (four-dimensional) Einstein gravity. However, L^2/G_N is the only dimensionless parameter intrinsic to the bulk theory and so the same ratio appears in any physical quantity involving some count of degrees of freedom, *e.g.*, the entropy density of a thermal bath. One approach to distinguish the various parameters appearing in different physical quantities in holographic boundary theories is to consider higher curvature theories for the bulk gravity, *e.g.*, see [17, 32, 33, 34]. The challenge in the present case would be developing the extension of the CV duality (1.1) for higher curvature bulk theories.

Let us provide a few geometric comments on the above result: Using the Gauss-Codazzi relations, we could replace \mathcal{R}_a^a in eqs. (2.13) or (2.14) in favour of the intrinsic Ricci scalar on the time slice Σ , as well as a term proportional to $K^{ab} K_{ab}$. Note that in the case of entanglement entropy, the first subleading

contribution, *e.g.*, the universal contribution for $d = 4$ contains a term with the Weyl curvature C_{ijkl} of the boundary metric [35], however, we see that this tensor does not appear in eq. (2.13). The key difference is that for holographic entanglement, one is considering a codimension-two surface and hence there are two normal vectors which can be contracted with C_{ijkl} . On the other hand, in evaluating holographic complexity, one considers a codimension-one surface in the boundary and hence there is one normal vector. Then given the symmetries and traceless property of the Weyl curvature, there are not enough geometric structures to construct a scalar which is linear in C_{ijkl} . However, the Weyl tensor might appear in higher order contributions to the complexity with a scalar such as $C_{ijkl}C^{ijkl}$. In Appendix B, we study the divergence structure in a specific example of a CFT living on a sphere.

General divergence structure

While the calculations above are somewhat preliminary, our experience with analogous calculations for holographic entanglement entropy *e.g.*, [17, 18, 36], suggests the following framework: With d boundary dimensions, the general structure of divergences appearing in the CV duality is:

$$\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma) = \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \int_{\Sigma} d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} v(\mathcal{R}, K) \quad \text{where} \quad v(\mathcal{R}, K) = \sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \rfloor} \sum_i c_{i,n}(d) \delta^{2n} [\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}. \quad (2.15)$$

That is, there can be a number of power law divergences beginning with $1/\delta^{d-1}$ where the coefficient is proportional to the volume of the time slice Σ . The power of the subsequent divergences is reduced by two at each step and the coefficients of these terms are fixed purely in terms of a local integral over Σ of various curvature invariants on the boundary. The schematic expression $[\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}$ indicates invariant combinations of boundary curvatures (represented by \mathcal{R}) and the extrinsic curvature of the time slice (represented by K), with a mass dimension of $2n$, so that the combination $\delta^{2n} [\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}$ is dimensionless. Of course, for odd (even) d , there are only even (odd) power divergences. Further, in odd dimensions with the special case that $2n = d - 1$, logarithmic divergences appear which provide universal parameters characterizing the underlying CFT, as discussed below eq. (2.14).

Again in eq. (2.15) and in the preceding example (2.13), we observe that there are only even (odd) power divergences for a boundary CFT in odd (even) d . At first sight, one may have thought the first subleading divergence would be proportional to $\int_{\Sigma} d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} K / \delta^{d-2}$, which would have disrupted this pattern. However, the simple reason that this term can not appear is that it depends on the orientation of time, *i.e.*, the orientation of \mathbf{n}^i , while the bulk volume in eq. (1.1) does not. We should add that in the boundary theory, the natural notions of complexity are intrinsic to a given state, and are independent of the time evolution of the state under some Hamiltonian. That is, the invariance of $\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma)$ under reversing the time orientation can be counted as a success of the definition in eq. (1.1).

3. Complexity Equals Action Conjecture

In this section, we examine the divergence structure emerging in the CA duality [9, 10]. The procedure to evaluate the gravitational action for the Wheeler-DeWitt patch was carefully examined in [14]. In particular, the WDW patch has null boundary surfaces and ref. [14] constructed the boundary terms

which must be added to the gravitational action for these null boundaries and for the joints where such null boundaries intersect with other boundary surfaces. We review these results in appendix A.

Again, the holographic complexity \mathcal{C}_A diverges because the WDW patch extends to the asymptotic AdS boundary and the focus here is to examine the structure of the resulting UV divergences. As in the previous section, we adopt the usual approach to regulating our calculations of introducing a cut-off surface at some large radius, *e.g.*, see [25, 26, 27]. However, given this framework, we can propose two different approaches to regulating the WDW action, as illustrated in figure 2. In particular, in figure 2a, we discard the portion of the WDW patch extending beyond the regulator surface, *i.e.*, we only integrate the bulk action out to this maximum radius. In this case, the regulated WDW region has a new timelike boundary segment and two null joints where the regulator surface intersects with the null sheets defining the past and future boundaries of the WDW patch, both of which contribute to I_{WDW} . In figure 2b, we instead regulate the action by simply shifting the edge of the WDW patch inwards to the regulator surface and hence we only have a single null joint at this time slice. In Appendix C, we will show that the structure of the UV divergences in the corresponding complexity \mathcal{C}_A is the same for both regularization procedures with a simple example. For simplicity, in the following general discussion, we adopt the second regulator which is shown in figure 2b.

Figure 2: Wheeler-DeWitt patch with two different regularizations. In both cases, the WDW patch terminates at the regulator surface: (a) The edge of the WDW patch is the time slice on the asymptotic boundary. The action contains a GHY surface term and two joint terms from the new boundary at $z = \delta$. (b) The edge of the WDW patch is the time slice in the regulator surface. The action contains null joint term from the edge at $z = \delta$.

We begin again with the bulk metric in FG gauge, as in eq. (2.1). For simplicity, we restrict the boundary metric to take the following form

$$g_{ij}^{(0)}(x^i) dx^i dx^j = -dt^2 + h_{ab}(t, \sigma) d\sigma^a d\sigma^b. \quad (3.1)$$

In particular, the (ta) -components of the boundary metric are fixed to be zero and the (tt) -component is simply -1 . However, we should note that this form is not preserved in the full tensor $g_{ij}(x, z)$ in eq. (2.1). For example, the first correction (2.3) appearing in the Taylor expansion around $z = 0$, *i.e.*, at order z^2 ,

will generally introduce a nonvanishing g_{ta} and nontrivial dependence on $x^i = (t, \sigma^a)$ in g_{tt} . We made this choice for the boundary metric (3.1) as it greatly simplifies the analysis of the WDW action below, but it is still general enough that most of curvature invariants appearing in the power law divergences are still nontrivial. In the following, we will compute the leading divergences of the WDW action, working to second order in the near boundary expansion.

We begin by determining the equations defining the null boundaries of the WDW patch near the asymptotic boundary, *i.e.*, $z = 0$.³ We will also set the time slice Σ to be $t = 0$ and hence in our calculations, we will expand both for small z and for small t . For simplicity, we focus on the future null boundary for most of the discussion. Given the boundary metric (3.1), this null surface can be described as $t = z - \delta + \dots$ to leading order and the corresponding normal would be $\mathbf{k}_1 = \alpha_1(dt - dz + \dots)$, where α_1 is some (positive) normalization constant.⁴ Now we wish to extend the former equation to

$$S^+ : t = t_+(z, \sigma^a) = f_+(z, \sigma^a) - f_+(\delta, \sigma^a) \quad (3.2)$$

for $t \geq 0$.⁵ In the vicinity of the boundary, $f_+(z, \sigma^a)$ has an expansion in powers of z , which we write as

$$f_+(z, \sigma^a) = z + \frac{z^2}{2} f^{(2)}(\sigma^a) + \frac{z^3}{6} f^{(3)}(\sigma^a) + \dots, \quad (3.3)$$

where the leading term was fixed in the above discussion. The form of the second expression in eq. (3.2) was chosen to ensure that $t = 0$ at $z = \delta$ (for all σ^a) order by order in this z expansion. Now, in fact, to the order that we will be interested in here, the coefficients in eq. (3.3) can be fixed by demanding that the normal to S^+ is null. That is, we determine $f^{(2)}(\sigma^a)$ and $f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)$ by imposing that $\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_1 = 0$ with the one-form \mathbf{k}_1 given by the exterior derivative of the function determining the boundary surface (up to an overall normalization factor), *i.e.*, $\mathbf{k}_1 = \alpha_1 d[t - t_+(z, \sigma^a)]$. The result of this calculation is that $f^{(2)}(\sigma^a) = 0$ while

$$f^{(3)}(\sigma^a) = n^i n^j g_{ij}^{(1)}(\sigma^a, t=0) = -\frac{1}{d-2} \left(\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{2d-3}{2(d-1)} \mathcal{R} \right) \Big|_{t=0} \quad (3.4)$$

where $n_i = \delta_i^t$ is the unit normal to the boundary surface $t = 0$. The second expression written in terms of the boundary curvature follows from eq. (2.3), as well as making the replacement that $n^i n^j \mathcal{R}_{ij} = \mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R}$. Hence to order z^3 , we can write the null boundaries of the WDW patch as

$$\begin{aligned} S^+ : t = t_+(z, \sigma^a) &= (z - \delta) + \frac{f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)}{6} (z^3 - \delta^3) + \dots \quad \text{for } t \geq 0, \\ S^- : t = t_-(z, \sigma^a) &= -(z - \delta) - \frac{f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)}{6} (z^3 - \delta^3) + \dots \quad \text{for } t \leq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (3.5)$$

In the second line above, the result for the past null boundary S^- is found with the same analysis as that given for S^+ above.

³We would like to thank Run-Qiu Yang for pointing out an error in an earlier version of this discussion.

⁴We have adopted the convention that \mathbf{k}_1 points outward from the region of interest — see appendix A.

⁵In general, we could have a different functional dependence on (δ, σ^a) , but this works to the required order since we simply integrate using eq. (3.13)

At this point, we are ready to evaluate the WDW action with eq. (A.1), and we begin with the bulk integral of the Einstein-Hilbert term and the cosmological constant. Using the Einstein equations for the bulk, we may substitute $R = -d(d+1)/L^2$, and this contribution simplifies to evaluating the spacetime volume of the WDW patch

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{d}{8\pi G_N L^2} \mathcal{V}(\mathcal{W}). \quad (3.6)$$

Now recall $g_{at} \sim \mathcal{O}(z^2)$ and thus we find to leading order

$$\sqrt{-g(x, z)} = \sqrt{-g_{tt}(x, z)} \sqrt{\det[g_{ab}(x, z)]} + \mathcal{O}(z^4) \quad (3.7)$$

in the measure of the above bulk integral, *i.e.*, the cross terms with g_{at} only appear at order $\mathcal{O}(z^4)$. Hence it is useful to write a double expansion for $\sqrt{\gamma} \equiv \sqrt{\det[g_{ab}(x, z)]}$:

$$\sqrt{\gamma} = \sqrt{h(\sigma)} \left([1 + q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + \dots] + [q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a) + q_1^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + \dots]t + [q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a) + \dots]t^2 + \dots \right) \quad (3.8)$$

where $\sqrt{h(\sigma)} \equiv \sqrt{\det[h_{ab}(\sigma^a, t=0)]}$ using the boundary metric in eq. (3.1). Hence using these expressions, as well as eq. (3.4) to substitute for $g_{tt}^{(1)}$, we identify the leading contributions near the asymptotic boundary in eq. (3.6) as

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{bulk}} &= -\frac{d}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \int_{\delta} dz \int_{t_-(z, \sigma^a)}^{t_+(z, \sigma^a)} dt \frac{L^{d+1}}{z^{d+1}} \sqrt{-g(x, z)} \\ &= -\frac{d L^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h(\sigma)} \int_{\delta} \frac{dz}{z^{d+1}} \int_{t_-(z, \sigma^a)}^{t_+(z, \sigma^a)} dt \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a)t + q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a)t^2 + \dots \right] \\ &= -\frac{d L^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h(\sigma)} \int_{\delta} \frac{dz}{z^{d+1}} \left[\left(1 - \frac{1}{2} f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 \right) [t_+(z, \sigma^a) - t_-(z, \sigma^a)] \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a)}{2} [t_+^2(z, \sigma^a) - t_-^2(z, \sigma^a)] + \frac{q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a)}{3} [t_+^3(z, \sigma^a) - t_-^3(z, \sigma^a)] + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Now substituting $t_+(z, \sigma^a) - t_-(z, \sigma^a) = 2(z - \delta) + \dots$ into eq.(3.5), the leading divergence in the above expression becomes

$$-\frac{dL^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} \int_{\delta} \frac{dz}{z^{d+1}} (z - \delta) = -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N (d-1)} \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h}. \quad (3.10)$$

That is, the leading divergence in the bulk integral is proportional to $\mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$. We note, however, that this leading term is *negative* — see further comments below.

Next, $t_+^2(z, \sigma^a) - t_-^2(z, \sigma^a)$ vanishes to the order that we are calculating and hence the first subleading divergence in the above expression becomes

$$-\frac{dL^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} \int_{\delta} \frac{dz}{z^{d+1}} \left[(z - \delta)z^2 \left(2q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a) - f^{(3)}(\sigma^a) \right) + \frac{f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)(z^3 - \delta^3)}{3} + \frac{2q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a)(z - \delta)^3}{3} \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{dL^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \frac{1}{\delta^{d-3}} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} \left[-\frac{f^{(3)}(\sigma^a)}{d(d-2)(d-3)} + \frac{q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a)}{(d-2)(d-3)} + \frac{2q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a)}{d(d-1)(d-2)(d-3)} \right] \\
&= -\frac{L^{d-1}}{16\pi G_N} \frac{1}{\delta^{d-3}} \int \frac{d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h}}{(d-1)(d-2)(d-3)} \left[4K^2 + 4K_{ab}K^{ab} + (d-7)\mathcal{R} - 2(d-3)\mathcal{R}_a^a \right] \quad (3.11)
\end{aligned}$$

We used a number of identities to produce the geometric expression in the last line above. In particular, we substitute the result in eq. (3.3) and further, in appendix D, we derive:

$$\begin{aligned}
q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a) &= -\frac{1}{2(d-2)} \left(\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{1}{2}\mathcal{R} \right) \Big|_{t=0}, \quad (3.12) \\
q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a) &= \frac{1}{2} \left(K^2 + K_{ab}K^{ab} + \mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R} \right) \Big|_{t=0}.
\end{aligned}$$

In addition to the bulk term above, we must include the contribution from the joint where the past and future null sheets (3.5) intersect, *i.e.*, $(z, t) = (\delta, 0)$ — see figure 2b. Given eq. (3.5), we may write the null normals to order $\mathcal{O}(z^2)$ as

$$\begin{aligned}
S^+ : \quad \mathbf{k}_1 &= \alpha_1(dt - dt_+(z, \sigma^a)) \simeq \alpha_1 \left(dt - dz - \frac{z^2}{2} f^{(3)} dz + \dots \right), \quad (3.13) \\
S^- : \quad \mathbf{k}_2 &= \alpha_2(-dt + dt_-(z, \sigma^a)) \simeq \alpha_2 \left(-dt - dz - \frac{z^2}{2} f^{(3)} dz + \dots \right).
\end{aligned}$$

Hence their inner product yields

$$\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2 \simeq \alpha_1 \alpha_2 \frac{z^2}{L^2} \left(-g^{tt} + \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{2} f^{(3)} \right)^2 + \mathcal{O}(z^4) \right) = 2\alpha_1 \alpha_2 \frac{z^2}{L^2} \left(1 + z^2 f^{(3)} \right) + \mathcal{O}(z^4), \quad (3.14)$$

where we have used $g^{tt} = -1 - g_{tt}^{(1)} z^2 + \mathcal{O}(z^4)$, as well as substituting eq. (3.4) for $g_{tt}^{(1)}$. Now using the prescription in appendix A, as well as eq. (3.8), the leading contributions from the joint term are

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{\text{joint}} &= -\frac{L^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N \delta^{d-1}} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} \log \left(\frac{\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2}{2} \right) \Big|_{(z,t)=(\delta,0)} \\
&\simeq -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N \delta^{d-1}} \log \left(\frac{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta}{L} \right) \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} - \frac{L^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N \delta^{d-3}} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{\gamma} f^{(3)}(\sigma^a) \\
&\simeq \frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \log \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta} \right) \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{2\mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R}}{4(d-2)\delta^{d-3}} \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{L^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N \delta^{d-3}} \int d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} \frac{1}{d-2} \left[\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{2d-3}{2(d-1)} \mathcal{R} \right]. \quad (3.15)
\end{aligned}$$

The leading term here is proportional to $\log(L/\delta) \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$ and hence this contribution from the asymptotic joint $S^+ \cap S^-$ becomes the leading divergence in the WDW action. This joint divergence is always positive in contrast to the leading divergence in the bulk action (3.10), which guarantees the positivity of the corresponding complexity in the boundary theory.

Combining the contributions in eqs. (3.10), (3.11) and (3.15), we find the leading divergences in the holographic complexity (1.2),

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) = \frac{1}{\pi} (I_{\text{bulk}} + I_{\text{jnt}}) \simeq & -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{1}{d-1} \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \right. \\ & \left. + \frac{1}{\delta^{d-3}} \frac{1}{2(d-1)(d-2)(d-3)} \left(2K^2 + 2K_{ab}K^{ab} + (d^2 - 4d + 1) \mathcal{R} - d(d-3) \mathcal{R}_a^a \right) \right] \\ & + \frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \log \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta} \right) \int d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[\frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{1}{4(d-2)\delta^{d-3}} (2\mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R}) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

In Appendix C, we compare these results with an explicit example in global AdS, and we find that the leading divergences match, as expected. We also examine the alternate regularization in figure 2a applied to this example.

General divergence structure

From the insights coming from the above calculation, we expect the general structure of the divergences in the CA duality to be:

$$\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) = \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \int_{\Sigma} d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[v_1(\mathcal{R}, K) + \log \left(\frac{L}{\alpha \delta} \right) v_2(\mathcal{R}, K) \right] \quad (3.17)$$

$$\text{with} \quad v_k(\mathcal{R}, K) = \sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \rfloor} \sum_i c_{i,n}^{[k]}(d) \delta^{2n} [\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}, \quad (3.18)$$

for d boundary dimensions. As in eq. (2.15), the schematic expressions $[\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}$ appearing in each of the integrands indicate invariant combinations of boundary curvatures (denoted \mathcal{R}) and the extrinsic curvature of the time slice (denoted K), with a mass dimension of $2n$, so that the combination $\delta^{2n} [\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}$ is dimensionless. Hence for the CA duality, there are two sets of divergences: The first (coming from the bulk term in the action) associated with v_1 is a series of power law divergences beginning with $1/\delta^{d-1}$ and then lower powers decreasing in steps of two. The second set of divergences (coming from the joint term) identified with v_2 involve a $\log \delta$ multiplying powers $1/\delta^{d-2n-1}$. In both series, only even (odd) power divergences appear for odd (even) d . Further, when d is odd, the final term in v_1 with $2n = d - 1$ yields an extra $\log(L/\delta)$. Hence in odd d , the universal term (proportional to $\log \delta$) has contributions coming from both v_1 and v_2 , while in even d there is no $\log \delta$ term. Again all of the coefficients in the two integrands are determined by local integrals on Σ of various curvature invariants on the boundary. We note that there is some ambiguity in these expressions related the logarithmic factor in eq. (3.17), and in particular, because of the coefficient α in the argument there. We will return to discuss this point in section 6.

We should comment again on the appearance of only even (odd) power divergences for odd (even) d . As discussed at the end of section 2, this indicates that there are no contributions in $v_{1,2}$ which are proportional to an odd power of the extrinsic curvature. However, this is actually a requirement for a holographic definition of the complexity since the latter should be independent of the orientation of time on the

boundary. The gravitational action, as described in appendix A, is independent of the orientation of time⁶ and so the definition (1.2) of CA duality satisfies this requirement.

4. Subregion Complexity: CV Duality

It is also interesting to extend holographic complexity to subregions. That is, one would evaluate the complexity of the mixed state produced by reducing the boundary state to a specific subregion of the boundary time slice. Given the proposal that in holography, this mixed state is encoded in the corresponding entanglement wedge in the bulk [23, 24], it is natural that the holographic prescription for the complexity of this state should involve the entanglement wedge. These ideas were first considered for time-independent geometries by [21] in the context of CV duality — see also [22]. Below, we propose a covariant definition of the appropriate volume, which can be applied in a time-dependent bulk and reduces to [21] for static geometries. We then examine the structure of the UV divergences for this subregion complexity.

For a static bulk geometry, the CV duality for subregions [21] evaluates the volume of the extremal codimension-one surface in the bulk which is bounded by the subregion on the asymptotic boundary and the Ryu-Takayanagi (RT) surface [15, 16] for this subregion. A natural extension of this prescription to a time-dependent bulk spacetime refers to the Hubeny-Rangamani-Takayanagi (HRT) prescription for holographic entanglement entropy [37] (see also [38]) as follows:⁷

- Beginning with a subregion A on a given boundary time slice Σ , one constructs \mathcal{E}_A , the corresponding extremal HRT surface in the bulk — this defines the inner edge of the entanglement wedge [24]. Then consider the codimension-one bulk surfaces \mathcal{R}_A which are bounded by this HRT surface \mathcal{E}_A and the boundary subregion A . The subregion complexity is then conjectured to be given by maximizing the volume $\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}_A)$ over this class of surfaces:

$$\mathcal{C}_V(A) = \max_{A \cup \mathcal{E}_A = \partial \mathcal{R}_A} \left[\frac{\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{R}_A)}{G_N \ell} \right], \quad (4.1)$$

where as in eq. (1.1), ℓ is some length scale associated with the bulk geometry, *e.g.*, the AdS radius.

We note that in defining the entanglement wedge [24], reference was made to ‘homology surfaces,’ which had precisely the definition of \mathcal{R}_A above. Hence, our proposal for CV duality for subregions assigns a special role to the homology surface with maximal volume.

Divergence Structure

Now we make some general comments on the divergence structure of the complexity of a subregion A that would arise from the above proposal (4.1). If the subregion is extended to the full time slice on the

⁶We have adopted slightly different conventions in appendix A than originally presented in [14]. Our prescription is entirely equivalent to that given in [14], but the latter has the disadvantage that it explicitly refers to the time orientation. Since this is not the case in appendix A, the above statement becomes manifest with the present prescription.

⁷There is some ambiguity in producing a covariant definition of the CV duality for subregions, just as there was for holographic entanglement entropy [37]. However, we think this proposal is the most natural as it connects the complexity directly to the entanglement wedge [24].

boundary, *i.e.*, $A = \Sigma$, we will reproduce the divergence structure found in section 2. In particular, the coefficients of the various power law divergences are determined by local integrals of geometric invariants over $A = \Sigma$, as in eq. (2.15). When the subregion A is a proper subregion of Σ , we will still have the same ‘volume’ contributions $v(\mathcal{R}, K)$ now integrated only over the subregion. However, there is the additional possibility that new divergences may arise associated with the boundary of the subregion ∂A , which we will refer to as the entangling surface following the discussions of entanglement entropy. Thus, we expect that the full divergence structure of the subregion complexity has the following general form:

$$\mathcal{C}_V(A) = \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \int_A d^{d-1}\sigma \sqrt{h} v(\mathcal{R}, K) + \frac{1}{\delta^{d-2}} \int_{\partial A} d^{d-2}\tilde{\sigma} \sqrt{\tilde{h}} b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}). \quad (4.2)$$

Again, the first term would be identical to that found in eq. (2.15) except that the integration is restricted to the subregion A . In the second term, we have a local integral over the entangling surface, and \tilde{h}_{ab} is the induced metric on ∂A . Now the integrand $b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t})$ is again a dimensionless quantity constructed from the cut-off δ and various geometric curvatures including \mathcal{R} , the background curvatures of the AdS boundary, and \tilde{K}_{ab}^i , the extrinsic curvatures of the codimension-two entangling surface, *i.e.*,

$$b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) = \sum_{n=0}^{d-1} \sum_i \tilde{c}_{i,n}(d) \delta^n [\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}]_i^n. \quad (4.3)$$

However, we have also introduced an explicit dependence on a particular basis of vectors in transverse space. The entangling surface ∂A is a codimension-two surface and so the transverse space is spanned by a basis of two unit vectors. In discussions of entanglement entropy in (relativistic) theories, there is nothing to distinguish one such basis from another. However, in the present discussion, we have defined a preferred time slice A where the state resides for which we are evaluating the complexity. Hence there is a preferred basis in the space transverse to ∂A : \mathbf{s}^i , the spacelike unit vector which is in the tangent space of A , points outward from A , and is orthogonal to ∂A ; and \mathbf{t}^i , the timelike unit vector which is points to the future from A (or Σ), and is orthogonal to both \mathbf{s}^i and ∂A .⁸

We now wish to constrain the function $b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t})$ with some general considerations. First, as discussed at the end of section 2, the complexity should be invariant if the time orientation is reversed. This invariance should also apply for the subregion complexity $\mathcal{C}_V(A)$ and in fact, it follows because the bulk volume in eq. (4.1) does not depend on the orientation of time. Therefore, we must have

$$b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) = b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, -\mathbf{t}), \quad (4.4)$$

i.e., this functional only contains terms that are even in the timelike normal \mathbf{t}^i . Note that this restriction was enough to eliminate the possibility of any odd powers of δ appearing in $v(\mathcal{R}, K)$, the integrand in the integral over A in eqs. (2.15) and (4.2). However, the integrand on the entangling surface may still contain odd powers of $\mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}_{ab}^i$, which would produce odd powers of δ .

Next, let us consider a pure global state on the time slice $\Sigma = A + \bar{A}$ dual to a time-symmetric bulk geometry. Now if we choose Σ to be the time-symmetric time slice in the boundary, the extremal volume

⁸Note that \mathbf{t}^i actually coincides with the timelike normal \mathbf{n}^i to Σ when the latter is evaluated on ∂A .

surface yielding the complexity of any of these regions, *i.e.*, Σ , A or \bar{A} , will lie in the special Cauchy slice running through the moment of time symmetry in the bulk and hence from eq. (4.1), we will find

$$\text{time symmetry : } \mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma) = \mathcal{C}_V(A) + \mathcal{C}_V(\bar{A}). \quad (4.5)$$

Now as a result of the time symmetry, various extrinsic curvatures must vanish, *i.e.*, the extrinsic curvature of the time slice vanishes and on the entangling surface, $\mathbf{t}_i \tilde{K}_{ab}^i = 0$. Now combining eqs. (4.2) and (4.5), we find

$$\text{time symmetry : } b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t})|_{\partial A} + b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t})|_{\partial \bar{A}} = 0, \quad (4.6)$$

where since this cancellation is a general result, we have assumed that the integrands must cancel point by point. Now the only geometric quantity in this expression that distinguishes ∂A from $\partial \bar{A}$ is the spacelike normal \mathbf{s}^i , which points outward from the corresponding subregion, *i.e.*, $\mathbf{s}^i|_{\partial A} = -\mathbf{s}^i|_{\partial \bar{A}}$. Therefore we can write eq. (4.6) as

$$\text{time symmetry : } \left[b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) + b(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; -\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) \right]_{\partial A} = 0. \quad (4.7)$$

That is, this geometric functional on the entangling surface only contains terms with odd powers of the normal vector \mathbf{s}^i .

In particular then, eq. (4.7) rules out the possibility that b contains a constant term, *i.e.*, the coefficient $\tilde{c}_{1,0} = 0$ in eq. (4.3) and there will *not* be a contribution proportional to $\mathcal{V}(\partial A)/\delta^{d-2}$ in eq. (4.2). Hence given the constraint (4.4), there is only one possible term which can appear at the next order, namely, $b = \tilde{c}_{1,1} \delta \mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i + \mathcal{O}(\delta^2)$ where \tilde{K}^i is the trace of the extrinsic curvature on ∂A . More generally, it is not hard to show that in the time-symmetric situation, all of the terms in b will involve odd powers of δ , *i.e.*, all of the even n coefficients in eq. (4.3) vanish. Therefore the subregion complexity only contains divergences with odd (even) powers of δ in even (odd) d in this case. However, it is unclear whether this property extends to cases without time symmetry. For example, one can imagine a term of the form $\delta^2 (\mathbf{t}_i \tilde{K}^i)^2$ appearing, which would lead to a divergence of $\mathcal{O}(1/\delta^{d-4})$. It would be interesting to examine explicit examples for the appearance of such divergences.

Example: Ball-shaped Region

As an explicit example, consider a ball-shaped region B in a flat background. Hence we consider AdS space in Poincaré coordinates,

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{z^2} [dz^2 - dt^2 + dx_i^2] \quad (4.8)$$

and we take B to be the region defined by $\sum_i x_i^2 \leq R^2$ on some constant time slice. With the bulk volume computed in [21], the subregion complexity (4.1) becomes

$$\mathcal{C}_V(B) = \frac{\Omega_{d-2} L^{d-1}}{G_N (d-1)} \left(\frac{1}{d-1} \frac{R^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{2(d-3)} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \frac{(d-1)(d-3)}{8(d-5)} \frac{R^{d-5}}{\delta^{d-5}} + \dots \right). \quad (4.9)$$

Since this is a time-symmetric configuration, there are only odd or even powers of δ appearing above, as expected from the discussion above. Now we can recognize a factor of the volume of B in the first term, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{V}(B) = \Omega_{d-2} R^{d-1}/(d-1)$, and so this contribution is simply the first term in v in eq. (4.2). Now the background curvature vanishes since we are considering flat space and the extrinsic curvature of B also vanishes since it was chosen to live on a constant time slice. Hence all of the subleading terms (*i.e.*, $n \geq 1$) in v must vanish and hence the remaining contributions in eq. (4.9) must be associated with boundary divergences. Further note we are considering a time-symmetric situation and so $\mathcal{C}_V(B)$ only contains odd (even) powers of δ for even (odd) dimensions, as follows from eq. (4.7). From the same equation, we also argued that the leading term in b in must be proportional to

$$\mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i = \mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}_{ab}^i \tilde{h}^{ab} = \frac{d-2}{R}. \quad (4.10)$$

Hence comparing to eq. (4.2), we can write the above result as

$$\mathcal{C}_V(B) = \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N} \left[\frac{\mathcal{V}(B)}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{1}{2(d-2)(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} \int_{\partial A} d^{d-2} \tilde{\sigma} \sqrt{\tilde{h}} \mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i + \dots \right]. \quad (4.11)$$

The term proportional to $(R/\delta)^{d-5}$ in eq. (4.9) is also a boundary divergence and the coefficient is given by some linear combination of terms in b proportional to $(\mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i)^3$ and $\mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i (\mathbf{s}_j \tilde{K}_{ab}^j)^2$.

5. Subregion Complexity: CA duality

In this section, we consider generalizing the CA duality to subregions, and study the resulting divergence structure. We re-iterate that given the proposal that the mixed state associated with a subregion in the boundary theory is encoded in the corresponding entanglement wedge in the bulk [23, 24], it is natural that the holographic prescription for the complexity of this state should involve this bulk region. This was the motivation for the approach taken in the previous section with the CV duality and it motivates the following proposal here for the CA duality:

- Beginning with a subregion A on a given boundary time slice Σ , we construct the corresponding entanglement wedge $\mathcal{W}_{\mathcal{E}}[A]$ [24], as well as the Wheeler-DeWitt patch $\mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$. Next we define the bulk region $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$ as the intersection of these two bulk regions: $\tilde{\mathcal{W}} = \mathcal{W}_{\mathcal{E}}[A] \cap \mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$ — see figure 3. The subregion complexity is then conjectured to be given by the gravitational action evaluated on $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$:

$$\mathcal{C}_A(A) = \frac{I_{\text{WDW}}(\tilde{\mathcal{W}})}{\pi \hbar} \quad (5.1)$$

In the limit when the subregion A is the entire time slice Σ , we have $\tilde{\mathcal{W}} = \mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$ and we recover eq. (1.2) for the original CA duality.

Consistency of this new holographic definition for subregion complexity would require that the result is independent of the specific choice of the time slice Σ used to define the WDW patch. In particular, our definition only fixes the global time slice to coincide with the subregion of interest but leaves the

Figure 3: For a ball-shaped boundary region B , the bulk region $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$ is the intersection of the entanglement wedge $\mathcal{W}_E[B]$ and the WDW patch $\mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$. (a) Showing details of the null joints appearing in the boundary of $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$. (b) Showing a cross-section of $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$ at $r = 0$. (See the main text for the notation.)

extension of this boundary surface outside of this subregion unspecified. While it is obvious that the bulk region $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$ is independent of the choice of time slice for simply connected subregions, the situation is less clear when the boundary subregion consists of a number of disconnected components. Yet it is straightforward to explicitly verify that this property holds in a number of simple situations, *e.g.*, for a number of disconnected intervals on the boundary of pure AdS_3 or for a number of parallel strips on the boundary of AdS_{d+1} .

A general proof of the desired time slice independence is as follows:⁹ Denote the boundary subregion as A , which may be comprised of any number of disconnected components. Choose a Cauchy surface Σ on the boundary which contains A but is otherwise arbitrary, and denote the complement of A on this time slice as A^c . We denote the boundary causal development of these two subregions as $\mathcal{D}(A)$ and $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$, and the corresponding entanglement wedges, as $\mathcal{W}_E[A]$ and $\mathcal{W}_E[A^c]$. Recall that $\mathcal{D}(A)$ and $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$ are the asymptotic boundaries of $\mathcal{W}_E[A]$ and $\mathcal{W}_E[A^c]$ respectively, *i.e.*, these boundary regions are where the entanglement wedges meet the asymptotic AdS boundary [24]. In passing, we also note that $\mathcal{D}(A)$ and $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$ are independent of the particular choice made above for the global time slice Σ . Now the desired time slice independence follows if we can show that all points in $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$ are space-like separated from all points in $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$. But here, we simply recall the definition $\tilde{\mathcal{W}} = \mathcal{W}_E[A] \cap \mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$. Therefore $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$ is contained inside the entanglement wedge $\mathcal{W}_E[A]$. However, we know that all points in $\mathcal{W}_E[A^c]$ and hence $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$ are

⁹We thank Veronika Hubeny for a discussion on this issue.

space-like separated from all points in $\mathcal{W}_{\mathcal{E}}[A]$ [24].¹⁰ Therefore we have proven that the bulk region $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$, and hence the corresponding complexity (5.1), is independent of the choice of the Cauchy surface Σ on the boundary outside of the subregion A .

In the rest of this section, we examine the above proposal in a specific example where A is a ball-shaped region in a flat background. In particular, we focus on the structure of the divergences and this example allows us to infer general properties of the divergence structure.

Example: Ball-shaped Region

As in the previous section, let us apply the proposed CA duality to evaluate the subregion complexity for a ball-shaped region B in a flat background. Hence we consider AdS space in Poincaré coordinates

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{z^2} [dz^2 - dt^2 + dr^2 + r^2 d\Omega_{d-2}^2] \quad (5.2)$$

where we use polar coordinates in the spatial boundary directions. For simplicity, we then take B to be the region defined by: $r \leq R$ and $t = 0$. The extremal bulk surface on which we would evaluate the holographic entanglement entropy is a hemisphere [15, 16]: $R^2 = r^2 + z^2$. The entanglement wedge $\mathcal{W}_{\mathcal{E}}[B]$ is the bulk region enclosed by the two null cones:¹¹

$$\begin{aligned} C^+ & : \quad t = R - \sqrt{r^2 + z^2} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq t \leq R, \\ C^- & : \quad t = -R + \sqrt{r^2 + z^2} \quad \text{for } 0 \geq t \geq -R. \end{aligned} \quad (5.3)$$

As in section 3, we must regulate the WDW patch by introducing a regulator surface at $z = \delta$. In particular, we will use the approach illustrated in figure 2b, where the null boundaries begin at the time slice on this regulator surface, *i.e.*, they begin at $(z, t) = (\delta, 0)$. The boundary of the WDW patch $\mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[t = 0]$ is then the two null sheets:

$$\begin{aligned} S^+ & : \quad t = z - \delta \quad \text{for } t \geq 0, \\ S^- & : \quad t = -(z - \delta) \quad \text{for } t \leq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (5.4)$$

Now following eq. (5.1), we compute the gravitational action on the intersection of these two bulk regions: $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}} = \mathcal{W}_{\mathcal{E}}[A] \cap \mathcal{W}_{\text{WDW}}[\Sigma]$, as illustrated in figure 3.

Following the prescription in appendix A, there are only two kinds of nonvanishing contributions in eq. (A.1), which need to be considered here. That is, we must evaluate the Einstein-Hilbert integral and four null joint contributions,

$$I(\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}) = \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} \int_{\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}} d^{d+1}x \sqrt{-g} \left(\mathcal{R} + \frac{d(d-1)}{L^2} \right) + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\Sigma'} d^{d-1}x \sqrt{\sigma} a. \quad (5.5)$$

No other contributions need to be considered because all of the boundary surfaces for $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$ are null.

¹⁰Recall that this result holds as long as the bulk obeys the null energy condition. Further, this property was required because otherwise the reduced density matrix on A could be affected by operations in $\mathcal{D}(A^c)$.

¹¹The boundary of the entanglement wedge has no caustics in this simple example.

Let us begin with the Einstein Hilbert term. Using the Einstein equations, we may substitute $\mathcal{R} = -d(d+1)/L^2$, and this contribution simplifies to evaluating the spacetime volume of the intersection region

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{d}{8\pi G_N L^2} \mathcal{V}(\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}). \quad (5.6)$$

As shown in figure 3b, it is straightforward to evaluate this volume by first dividing it into two parts:

$$\mathcal{V}(\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}) = \mathcal{V}_1\left(z > \frac{R+\delta}{2}\right) + \mathcal{V}_2\left(z < \frac{R+\delta}{2}\right), \quad (5.7)$$

where $\mathcal{V}_1(z > (R+\delta)/2)$ is the volume of the portion of the region bounded above and below entirely by the null cones C^\pm , and $\mathcal{V}_2(z < (R+\delta)/2)$ is the volume of the portion of the region which is also bounded above and below by the null sheets S^\pm . We begin with the former

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{V}_1 &= 2L^{d+1}\Omega_{d-2} \int_0^{\frac{R-\delta}{2}} dt \int_{\frac{R+\delta}{2}}^{R-t} \frac{dz}{z^{d+1}} \int_0^{\sqrt{(R-t)^2-z^2}} dr r^{d-2} \\ &= \frac{2L^{d+1}\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \int_0^{\frac{R-\delta}{2}} dt \int_{\frac{R+\delta}{2}}^{R-t} dz \frac{((R-t)^2-z^2)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{z^{d+1}} \end{aligned} \quad (5.8)$$

This volume remains finite in the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$ since the integration does not reach the asymptotic boundary. Hence in an expansion for $\delta/R \ll 1$, \mathcal{V}_1 only contains positive powers of δ . Turning to the volume of the region with $z < (R+\delta)/2$, we find

$$\mathcal{V}_2 = \frac{2L^{d+1}\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \int_0^{\frac{R-\delta}{2}} dt \int_{t+\delta}^{\frac{R+\delta}{2}} dz \frac{((R-t)^2-z^2)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{z^{d+1}} \quad (5.9)$$

$$= \frac{2L^{d+1}\Omega_{d-2}}{d(d-1)} \left[\frac{R^{d-1}}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)\delta^{d-2}} + \frac{(-d^2+3d-4)R^{d-3}}{2(d-2)(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right], \quad (5.10)$$

where in the second line, we have expanded the integrand for small z to identify the divergent terms arising from the integration near the asymptotic boundary. Hence the divergences appearing in the bulk action (5.6) become

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \frac{\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \left[\frac{R^{d-1}}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)\delta^{d-2}} + \frac{(-d^2+3d-4)R^{d-3}}{2(d-2)(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right]. \quad (5.11)$$

Note that there are both even and odd power law divergences in this expression and also that the overall sign is negative.

Now we move on to compute the contributions of the null joint in eq. (5.5). The region $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$ has four null joints coming from the intersections of the various null boundaries: $S^+ \cap S^-$, $C^+ \cap C^-$, $C^+ \cap S^+$ and $C^- \cap S^-$ — see figure (3)a. Hence we divide the null joint term into the four corresponding contributions

$$I_{\text{jnt}} = I^{(1)}(S^+ \cap S^-) + I^{(2)}(C^+ \cap C^-) + I^{(3)}(C^+ \cap S^+) + I^{(4)}(C^- \cap S^-) \quad (5.12)$$

and evaluate each in turn using the prescription given in appendix A. Note that the latter requires writing the (outward directed) null normals for each of the corresponding surfaces, which we find using eqs. (5.3) and (5.4):

$$\begin{aligned} S^+ : \mathbf{k}_1 &= \alpha (dt - dz), & S^- : \mathbf{k}_2 &= \alpha (-dt - dz), \\ C^+ : \mathbf{k}_3 &= \beta \left(dt + \frac{r dr + z dz}{\sqrt{r^2 + z^2}} \right), & C^- : \mathbf{k}_4 &= \beta \left(-dt + \frac{r dr + z dz}{\sqrt{r^2 + z^2}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (5.13)$$

where α and β are arbitrary (dimensionless) normalization constants for the null normals. For simplicity, we have chosen the same normalization constant on S^+ and S^- , and on C^+ and C^- .

Beginning with $I^{(1)}(S^+ \cap S^-)$, we find $a = -2 \log(\alpha \delta/L)$ using eq. (A.8). Hence the joint contribution becomes

$$\begin{aligned} I^{(1)} &= -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \frac{\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \log\left(\frac{\alpha \delta}{L}\right) \frac{(R^2 - \delta^2)^{\frac{d-1}{2}}}{\delta^{d-1}} \\ &= -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \frac{\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \log\left(\frac{\alpha \delta}{L}\right) \left[\frac{R^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{2} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \frac{(d-1)(d-3)}{8} \frac{R^{d-5}}{\delta^{d-5}} + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.14)$$

Hence the divergence structure here involves a logarithmic divergence multiplying power law divergences, with only odd (even) powers for even (odd) d . Note that the overall sign of this null joint contribution is positive.

Next for $C^+ \cap C^-$, we have $a = -2 \log(\beta z/L)$ and so the joint contribution becomes

$$\begin{aligned} I^{(2)} &= -\frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{4\pi G_N} \int_{\delta}^R dz \frac{(R^2 - z^2)^{\frac{d-3}{2}}}{z^{d-1}} \log\left(\frac{\beta z}{L}\right) \\ &= -\frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{4\pi G_N} \log\left(\frac{\beta \delta}{L}\right) \left[\frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)\delta^{d-2}} - \frac{(d-3)}{2(d-4)} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \frac{(d-3)(d-5)}{8(d-6)} \frac{R^{d-6}}{\delta^{d-6}} + \dots \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)^2\delta^{d-2}} - \frac{(d-3)}{2(d-4)^2} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \frac{(d-3)(d-5)}{8(d-6)^2} \frac{R^{d-6}}{\delta^{d-6}} + \dots \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

Again, we find that there are only even or odd powers, but not both. There are also terms involving both power law divergences multiplied by a logarithmic divergence.

For $C^+ \cap S^+$, we have $a = \log\left(\frac{\alpha\beta}{2} \frac{z^2}{L^2} \frac{R+\delta}{R+\delta-z}\right)$ and the joint contribution is given by

$$\begin{aligned} I^{(3)} &= \frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{8\pi G_N} (R+\delta)^{d-2} \int_{\delta}^{\frac{R-\delta}{2}} dz \frac{\left(1 - \frac{2z}{R+\delta}\right)^{\frac{d-3}{2}}}{z^{d-1}} \log\left(\frac{\alpha\beta}{2} \frac{z^2}{L^2} \frac{R+\delta}{R+\delta-z}\right) \\ &= \frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{4\pi G_N} \log\left(\sqrt{\frac{\alpha\beta}{2}} \frac{\delta}{L}\right) \left[\frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)\delta^{d-2}} - \frac{(d-3)}{2(d-4)} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \frac{(d-3)(d-5)}{8(d-6)} \frac{R^{d-6}}{\delta^{d-6}} + \dots \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{L^{d-1}\Omega_{d-2}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\frac{R^{d-2}}{(d-2)^2\delta^{d-2}} + \frac{d-5}{2(d-3)(d-2)} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} - \frac{3d^2 - 20d + 36}{4(d-4)^2(d-2)} \frac{R^{d-4}}{\delta^{d-4}} + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.16)$$

Note that this joint contributions has both even and odd power divergences, as well as a logarithmic factor in some of the contributions. Further, we note in passing that both here and in eq. (5.15), the

integrals can generate additional logarithms and so we may find divergences of the form $\log^2 \delta$. For example, such terms would appear in both eqs. (5.15) and (5.16) for $d = 2$. Next, we must evaluate the joint contribution coming from $C^- \cap S^-$ but by the symmetry of the present geometry under $t \rightarrow -t$, we have $I^{(4)}(C^- \cap S^-) = I^{(3)}(C^+ \cap S^+)$.

Up to this point, it seems that we have taken into account all of the contributions to the gravitational action, however, we need to point out that our discussion has overlooked one geometric structure in the boundary of $\widetilde{\mathcal{W}}$. In particular, there is a codimension-three ‘corner’ where all four null surfaces simultaneously intersect, *i.e.*, $S^+ \cap S^- \cap C^+ \cap C^-$ which is the spherical surface given by $(z, t, r) = (\delta, 0, \sqrt{R^2 - \delta^2})$. As discussed in [14], the boundary terms that might be required in the gravitational action for such higher codimension corners requires further analysis and remain unknown at the present time. While our intuition is that the contribution from this corner vanishes in our example,¹² this provides further motivation for a detailed study of such higher order intersections of boundary surfaces. In any event, in our example, it seems that all possible divergences are already appearing in our final result, and hence even if this extra corner were to make a contribution to the action, it would not add anything conceptually new.

Finally, the total action $I(\widetilde{\mathcal{W}})$ combining the results in eqs. (5.11) and (5.14–5.16) and then eq. (5.1) yields the leading divergence structure for the subregion complexity as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_A(B) &= \frac{1}{\pi} \left(I_{\text{bulk}} + I^{(1)} + I^{(2)} + 2I^{(3)} \right) \\ &= -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \frac{\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \left[\frac{R^{d-1}}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \left(\frac{2d-3}{(d-2)^2} - \frac{(d-1)}{d-2} \log 2 \right) \frac{R^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} - \frac{3d^2 - 13d + 12}{2(d-2)(d-3)} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \frac{\Omega_{d-2}}{d-1} \log \left(\frac{L}{\alpha \delta} \right) \left[\frac{R^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{d-2} \frac{R^{d-2}}{\delta^{d-2}} - \frac{d-1}{2} \frac{R^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (5.17)$$

Note that we can recognize the leading divergences ($\propto 1/\delta^{d-1}$) as being proportional to the volume of the ball-shaped region, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{V}(B) = \Omega_{d-2} R^{d-1}/(d-1)$. Now we expect the coefficients of the subleading divergences are also proportional to various geometric factors. However, in this example, both the background curvature and the extrinsic curvature of the time slice vanish. Hence, the next pair of divergences ($\propto 1/\delta^{d-2}$) must be proportional to the volume of the boundary, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{V}(\partial B) = \Omega_{d-2} R^{d-2}$. Similarly the coefficients of the terms proportional to $1/\delta^{d-3}$ involve an integral of $\mathbf{s}_i \tilde{K}^i = (d-2)/R$ over ∂B , as in eq. (4.11), while the higher order terms will involve higher powers of the boundary extrinsic curvature. One notable feature of eq. (5.17) is that the coefficient β has canceled out in the total action. In fact, it is straightforward to show that this cancellation extends to include the R^{d-6}/δ^{d-6} terms and higher. We return to discuss this feature in section 6.

Now given the results of the above calculation and our previous experience, we expect the the CA duality produces the following general form for the divergences in subregion complexity:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_A(A) &= \frac{1}{\delta^{d-1}} \int_A d^{d-1} \sigma \sqrt{h} \left[v_1(\mathcal{R}, K) + \log \left(\frac{L}{\alpha \delta} \right) v_2(\mathcal{R}, K) \right] \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{\delta^{d-2}} \int_{\partial A} d^{d-2} \tilde{\sigma} \sqrt{\tilde{h}} \left[b_1(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) + \log \left(\frac{L}{\tilde{\alpha} \delta} \right) b_2(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5.18)$$

¹²In part, this intuition is informed by the vanishing contribution of similar singularities in the examples in [39].

$$\text{with} \quad v_k(\mathcal{R}, K) = \sum_{n=0}^{\lfloor \frac{d-1}{2} \rfloor} \sum_i c_{i,n}^{[k]}(d) \delta^{2n} [\mathcal{R}, K]_i^{2n}, \quad (5.19)$$

$$b_k(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{n}, \mathbf{t}) = \sum_{n=0}^{d-1} \sum_i \tilde{c}_{i,n}^{[k]}(d) \delta^n [\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}]_i^n. \quad (5.20)$$

with d boundary dimensions. The expressions in eq. (5.19) would be identical to those found in eq. (3.18) and the only difference here is that the corresponding integral in eq. (5.18) is now restricted to the subregion A . As in the previous section, we also find additional divergences that are associated with the entangling surface ∂A . The corresponding integrands $b_{1,2}$ involve: \mathcal{R} , the background curvatures of the AdS boundary; \tilde{K}_{ab}^i , the extrinsic curvatures of the codimension-two entangling surface; and also \mathbf{s}^i and \mathbf{t}^i , a preferred basis in the space transverse to ∂A — see the description under eq. (4.2). The appearance of the coefficients α and $\tilde{\alpha}$ in the logarithmic factors introduces some additional ambiguity in the above expressions and we will return to discuss this point in section 6. We note that the contribution associated with the entangling surface may involve divergences proportional to $\log^2 \delta$ coming from the b_2 term, as discussed for the example above.

We note that invariance under time reversal results in only even powers of δ appearing in the integrands $v_{1,2}$, but this is not the case for $b_{1,2}$. There it only imposes the weaker constraint: $b_k(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}) = b_k(\mathcal{R}, \tilde{K}; \mathbf{s}, -\mathbf{t})$ — see discussion around eq. (4.4). Further, with CV duality, we were able to find further restrictions by considering the case of time symmetry, *e.g.*, in eq. (4.3), $\tilde{c}_{1,0}$ vanishes. However, the same considerations cannot be made here because

$$\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) \neq \mathcal{C}_A(A) + \mathcal{C}_A(\bar{A}), \quad (5.21)$$

even in the special case of time symmetry and in fact, we saw contributions proportional to $\mathcal{V}(\partial A)$, the volume of the entangling surface, explicitly appear the example above in eq. (5.17).

6. Discussion

In this paper, we studied the two conjectures for holographic complexity: the complexity=action (CA) conjecture and the complexity=volume (CV) conjecture. In particular, we examined the structure of UV divergences in the complexity following from these two conjectures. We found that both \mathcal{C}_A and \mathcal{C}_V contain a series of power law divergences and the coefficients of these divergences are determined by local integrals of various geometric invariants over the corresponding time slice Σ , as shown in eqs. (2.15) and (3.17). These coefficients also contain dimensionless parameters characterizing the underlying CFT, *e.g.*, $C_T \sim L^{d-1}/G_N$ in the present case where the bulk is described by Einstein gravity.¹³ The leading divergence appearing with the CV duality is proportional to the volume of the boundary time slice, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma) \sim \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$. A similar divergence appears with the CA duality, however, an extra factor

¹³If the boundary CFT is deformed by a relevant operator, it is straightforward to show that the corresponding (dimensionful) coupling will also appear in these coefficients [40]. In this case, the structure of the UV divergent terms is analogous to the results found for holographic entanglement entropy in [18].

proportional to $\log \delta$ arises from the asymptotic joint contributions in the WDW action, *e.g.*, see eq. (3.15). Hence the leading divergence appearing with the CA duality takes the form

$$\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) \sim \log[L/(\alpha \delta)] \frac{\mathcal{V}(\Sigma)}{\delta^{d-1}}, \quad (6.1)$$

where L is the AdS curvature scale and α is a (dimensionless) normalization constant — see further discussion below.

We note that the asymptotic joint contribution, which produces this divergence (6.1), is essential for the consistency of our CA calculations in sections 3 and 5. The bulk integral of the Einstein-Hilbert action (3.6) contributes a divergence proportional to the boundary volume but the coefficient is negative, which follows from Einstein’s equations and the negative cosmological constant. That is, we have $I_{\text{bulk}} \sim -\mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$ but if this was the leading divergence, the resulting WDW action would be negative. Since by definition the complexity is positive, this would produce an inconsistency for CA duality.¹⁴ However, the joint contribution is positive and contains an even stronger divergence with the extra $\log \delta$ factor, *e.g.*, see eqs. (3.15) and (3.16). Hence it is responsible for making the holographic complexity positive and ensuring the consistency of the CA duality.

As noted in the introduction, the locality of the coefficients in the holographic complexity suggests that these divergences should be associated with establishing local correlations down to the cutoff scale in the boundary CFT. On the gravity side, since the calculations in CV duality resemble those in holographic entanglement entropy so closely, it is not surprising that the coefficients of the power law divergences are determined by local integrals. Essentially, the initial terms in the FG expansion (2.2) are expressed in terms of the boundary geometry and the equations determining the asymptotic shape of the extremal surface have a similar geometric interpretation [18]. On the other hand, it is not immediately clear that the CA duality should produce coefficients with a similar locality. Of course, our explicit calculations in section 3 demonstrate that this is the case, at least for the first few divergences. It would be interesting to thoroughly investigate if this locality extends to all of the UV divergences appearing in the holographic complexity, as assumed in the discussion at the end of section 3. It is clear that locality continues to hold for all of the divergences in the joint contribution, since these only rely on evaluating the asymptotic expansion of the metric at $z = \delta$. On the other hand, one needs a better understanding of the general geometry of the null boundaries of the WDW patch to determine if the bulk integral also produces coefficients which are always local.

In passing, we note that in the context of holographic entanglement entropy, ref. [41] shows that this behaviour may fail in certain situations. Although the coefficients are still determined by local integrals, the integrand involves state dependent data in these cases. It would also be interesting to see if these results extend to holographic calculations of complexity.

We now turn to the factor of α appearing in the argument of the logarithm in eq. (6.1), or more generally in eq. (3.17) for the CA duality. As noted previously, this (dimensionless) coefficient is an arbitrary normalization constant for the null normals, *e.g.*, see eq. (3.13) or (5.13),¹⁵ which arises because

¹⁴Note that with regularization scheme illustrated in figure 2a, there is an additional GHY surface term which is positive and which will dominate over the bulk term, *e.g.*, compare eqs. (C.5) and (C.7) for the example examined in appendix C.

¹⁵In general, we have two independent normalization constants for the normals on the future and past null boundaries, as in eq. (3.13), in which case the factor of α is replaced by $\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2}$, as in eq. (6.1).

of the freedom to rescale the affine parameter along the future and past null boundaries of the WDW patch [14]. In order to make a meaningful comparison of the gravitational action for different WDW patches, *e.g.*, in different spacetimes as in [39], one must first fix this normalization constant in a consistent way. The suggestion of [14] was to impose a normalization condition on the null normals near the asymptotic AdS boundary. In particular, one can choose

$$\mathbf{k} \cdot \hat{t} = \pm\alpha \tag{6.2}$$

at the AdS boundary. Here, \mathbf{k} is the normal to the future (+) or past (-) null boundary (written as an outward pointing one-form — see appendix A); $\hat{t} = \partial_t$ is the timelike vector in the asymptotic AdS geometry which is normalized to describe the time flow in the boundary theory; and α is an arbitrary positive constant.

One simple choice that was suggested in [14] is $\alpha = 1$. However there is a puzzle here as follows: With $\alpha = 1$, the result, *e.g.*, in eq. (6.1) takes the form $\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) \sim \log(L/\delta) \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$ and so the complexity explicitly depends on the AdS curvature scale L , which has no interpretation in the boundary theory. Hence it seems another choice is required to eliminate this dependence. Let us instead set $\alpha = L/\ell$ where ℓ is some scale in the boundary theory which is common to all states and geometries for which we might want to evaluate the complexity. One candidate would be $\ell = \delta$, the short-distance cutoff, however, with this choice, the argument of the log reduces to one and the contribution in eq. (6.1) vanishes. Unfortunately, as noted in the discussion above, this would leave us with a negative complexity¹⁶ and so this choice of ℓ appears inconsistent. Another choice would be the size of the boundary time slice, *i.e.*, $\ell = \ell_{\mathcal{V}} \sim \mathcal{V}^{1/(d-1)}$. However, with this choice, the complexity becomes superextensive, *i.e.*, the leading contribution grows faster than the volume of the time slice. As this contribution to the complexity seems most naturally related to the establishing very short-distance correlations in the boundary CFT, it seems that this contribution should only be proportional to $\mathcal{V}(\Sigma)$ and should not be superextensive. Unfortunately, these two choices seem to be the only scales in the boundary theory that will naturally arise in any geometry and for any state, and they both yield undesirable results. However, it may then be that ℓ is a new scale defined by the precise microscopic rules used to define the complexity. For example, if we set $\ell = e^\sigma \delta$ (*i.e.*, $\alpha = e^{-\sigma} L/\delta$) where σ is some numerical factor,¹⁷ then eq. (6.1) becomes $\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) \sim \sigma \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$ and one can imagine that different choices of σ correspond to different choices for the set of universal gates which are used to prepare states and define the complexity, *e.g.*, ℓ might be related to the maximum range over which the universal gates act in the CFT. Note that with this prescription, there is no real distinction between the two families of divergent terms appearing in eq. (3.17) since δ is eliminated from the argument of the logarithm. However, generically the null boundaries for the WDW patch will end on joints deep in the interior of the bulk geometry, and the corresponding null joint terms will introduce new contributions where $\log \delta$ is mixed with IR features, *e.g.*, if one considers complexity of the thermofield double state dual to a black hole. Further, this $\log \delta$ may also ‘infect’ quantities which might otherwise be expected to be finite, such as the rate of growth of the complexity in certain situations [10, 42].¹⁸

One of the key features which was observed here was the geometric nature of the coefficients in the various power law divergences appearing in the holographic complexity. While this feature is entirely

¹⁶As emphasized in footnote 14, we re-iterate that this is a feature of the regularization illustrated in figure 2b. With the alternate regularization in figure 2a, the GHY contribution on the regulator surface dominates over the bulk term to

Figure 4: We consider the ground state $|\psi_0\rangle$ of the boundary theory but evaluate the complexity on three different time slices, Σ_1 , Σ_2 and Σ_3 . Comparing the first two time slices, the complexity sees a large reduction of Σ_2 because the proper volume of this time slice is reduced by $\Delta\mathcal{V} = (\sqrt{\Delta\ell^2 - \Delta t^2} - \Delta\ell) \mathcal{V}_{\text{trans}}$ where $\mathcal{V}_{\text{trans}}$ is the volume in the transverse directions. The third time slice Σ_3 is composed of null segments and so the leading divergence in the complexity vanishes.

expected given our experiences from holographic entanglement entropy [17, 18, 36], it means that the complexity has some unusual features. To illustrate this point, recall again that the leading term for both CA and CV duality is proportional to the volume of the time slice, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma) \sim \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$. Now consider the ground state of the boundary theory in flat space but let us evaluate the complexity on two different time slices, Σ_1 and Σ_2 , as illustrated in figure 4. In the second case, we have pushed Σ_2 forward in time over a portion of the time slice and hence, because of the Lorentzian signature of the boundary theory, the proper volume is reduced. Comparing these two time slices illustrated in the figure, $\Delta\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}(\Sigma_2) - \mathcal{V}(\Sigma_1) = (\sqrt{\Delta\ell^2 - \Delta t^2} - \Delta\ell) \mathcal{V}_{\text{trans}} < 0$ where $\mathcal{V}_{\text{trans}}$ is the volume in the directions transverse to the page. Hence there is an enormous reduction in the corresponding complexity: $\Delta\mathcal{C} \sim \Delta\mathcal{V}/\delta^{d-1} < 0$. In fact, the leading divergence can be completely removed by evaluating the complexity on a time slice composed of a series of null segments, as illustrated by Σ_3 in figure 4. In this case, we expect that the complexity will still contain otherwise subleading divergences associated with the ‘folds’ between the null

produce a positive action, without the joint contribution — see appendix C.

¹⁷Of course, given the previous discussion, there must be a lower bound on σ . Examining eq. (3.16), we find $\sigma > 1/(d-1)$.

¹⁸Recently, ref. [43] divergences in the WDW action using a additional boundary term introduced in [14], which renders the action invariant under reparameterizations of the null boundary coordinates. In particular, it was found that this boundary term also removes the $\log(L/\delta) \mathcal{V}(\Sigma)/\delta^{d-1}$ divergence.

segments in this case,¹⁹ *i.e.*, $\mathcal{C}(\Sigma_3) \sim \mathcal{V}_{\text{trans}}/\delta^{d-2}$.

However, it seems challenging to understand this behaviour from the usual perspective of circuit complexity. The latter involves using discrete gates to prepare a lattice approximation of the state in the boundary field theory. While this provides an intuitive picture for the complexity of states on a constant time slice, it seems ill-suited to discuss states (even ground states) that are defined on Cauchy surfaces which vary in time. Given a state defined on a discrete lattice for a constant time slice, one might consider evolving it to a time-varying slice with a differential application of the (local) Hamiltonian across the lattice. However, it is not at all clear why this process should significantly reduce the complexity of the state. Of course, similar issues arise if one considers entanglement entropy for discrete lattice models. However, in this case, we have a field theoretic approach where the entanglement entropy can be defined in terms of a path integral approach. Hence we naturally anticipate that the divergences in the entanglement entropy are defined in terms of covariant geometric quantities in a curved background or with a time-varying Cauchy surface. Of course, this discussion highlights the challenge of developing an analogous field theoretic approach to define complexity in a covariant manner. Perhaps, the techniques developed in [46, 47, 48] or in [49] can provide better insight towards developing such a covariant approach.

Subregion Complexity

In sections 4 and 5, we also considered generalizing the CV and CA conjectures to the complexity of the mixed state produced by reducing the boundary state to a specific subregion of the boundary time slice. Our proposals were motivated by the idea that this mixed state should be encoded in the corresponding entanglement wedge in the bulk [23, 24]. While our suggestion for CV duality applies for general time-dependent situations, it reduces in a time-independent case to the proposal first studied in [21] — see also [22].

The original notion of circuit complexity that was introduced in holography, *e.g.*, [4, 8, 9, 10], referred to pure states in the boundary theory. For a subregion complexity, we are instead considering the preparation of a mixed state, described by the density matrix ρ_A which comes from reducing the global pure state to the region A . Since a pure reference state will never become mixed by the application of a unitary circuit, we should instead think in terms of preparing ρ_A with a completely positive trace-preserving (CPTP) map acting on the reference state. From this perspective, the set of allowed universal gates would be extended to include ‘ancillary’ and ‘erasure’ gates, which add and remove additional degrees of freedom [1, 50]. However, the dilation theorems [51] imply that the most general CPTP maps acting on a system of qubits can be realized as unitary evolution of the system coupled to ancillary qubits [1]. That is, we may also think of subregion complexity as first extending the Hilbert space of A with new ancillary degrees of freedom to purify the state ρ_A and then determining the minimum number of universal gates needed to prepare the resulting pure state from a reference state in the extended Hilbert space. However, we expect in the present holographic context (or in quantum field theory, more generally) that the specific rules defining subregion complexity must restrict the allowed ancilla and how they are permitted to interact with the QFT degrees of freedom in the subregion. For example, locality of the

¹⁹A logarithmic divergence appears with $d = 2$ and in this case, the holographic calculations for the CV duality would be closely related to those evaluating the cusp anomaly in holographic gauge theories [44, 45].

QFT may suggest that the ancilla only interact with the degrees of freedom near the boundary of the subregion. Better insight into these restrictions may come from further studies of holographic subregion complexity.

Turning to the structure of the UV divergences revealed by our calculations in sections 4 and 5, we found that these were more or less the same as found for the pure states. In particular, for a given region A , both $\mathcal{C}_A(A)$ and $\mathcal{C}_V(A)$ contained power law divergences and the coefficients of these divergences are again determined by local integrals of various geometric invariants, as in eqs. (4.2) and (5.18). However, there are now two types of integrals: The first were $(d-1)$ -dimensional integrals over the entire region A and the integrands were identical to those found in the previous calculations for a pure state on an entire time slice. The second were $(d-2)$ -dimensional integrals over the boundary ∂A and the integrands involved geometric invariants constructed on this geometry, as described schematically in eqs. (4.3) and (5.20). In the discussion of complexity for pure states, we observed that it seems natural that the UV divergences multiplying ‘bulk’ integrals over A should be associated with the necessity of establishing correlations between the CFT degrees of freedom down to the arbitrarily short distance scales. Similarly then, the divergences multiplying the ‘boundary’ integrals must be related to the UV structure of the portion of ρ_A describing the degrees of freedom near the boundary ∂A . In particular, we note that these degrees of freedom behave as though they are nearly maximally mixed or strongly entangled with ancilla, *i.e.*, the near-boundary degrees of freedom appear as though they are in the Rindler vacuum with a local temperature that diverges at ∂A — see discussions in [52, 53].

We note that there were no essential differences between the CV and CA duality for the divergences associated with the integrals over A . On the other hand, those associated with the boundary integrals seemed to show some more interesting differences. For example, the CA duality generally produces a divergence proportional to $\mathcal{V}(\partial A)/\delta^{d-2}$, while the analogous divergence never arises in the CV duality. Similarly, for a configuration which is time-symmetric about a time slice $\Sigma = A \cup \bar{A}$, we argued that $\mathcal{C}_V(\Sigma) = \mathcal{C}_V(A) + \mathcal{C}_V(\bar{A})$ in eq. (4.5), while it is clear that $\mathcal{C}_A(\Sigma) \neq \mathcal{C}_A(A) + \mathcal{C}_A(\bar{A})$ even in the time-symmetric case. These differences must be related to differences in the implicit microscopic rules defining the subregion complexity for these two dualities. In particular, as discussed above, the different dualities may introduce different types of ancilla and allow for different types of interactions between the ancilla and the CFT degrees of freedom in the subregion.

We close here with a technical observation about our proposal for subregion complexity with the CA duality. One notable feature of eq. (5.17) is that the coefficient β does not appear in the final complexity. That is, while this coefficient which appears in the two joint contributions individually in eqs. (5.15) and (5.16), it cancels out in the total action. In fact, we will now argue that this cancellation is complete, rather than only holding to some high order in the expansion near the asymptotic boundary. The first observation is that β dependence in eqs. (5.15) and (5.16) is proportional to the volume of the corresponding surface, *i.e.*,

$$I^{(2)} \sim -\frac{\log \beta}{4\pi G_N} \mathcal{V}(C^+ \cap C^-), \quad I^{(3)} \sim +\frac{\log \beta}{8\pi G_N} \mathcal{V}(C^+ \cap S^+), \quad I^{(4)} \sim +\frac{\log \beta}{8\pi G_N} \mathcal{V}(C^- \cap S^-). \quad (6.3)$$

Next, the key observation is that for the particular geometry which we are considering in the example in section 5 (*i.e.*, the bulk geometry is empty AdS and the boundary region is a ball on a constant time

slice), the boundary (5.3) of the entanglement wedge is actually a Killing horizon and the corresponding normals (5.13) are null Killing vectors, *e.g.*, [54, 55]. Hence, $C^+ \cap C^-$, which corresponds to a portion of the bifurcation surface, is mapped to either $C^+ \cap S^+$ or $C^- \cap S^-$ by the Killing flow along the horizon – see figure 3. Hence the ‘area’ of these three cross-sections of the Killing horizon are identical, *i.e.*, $\mathcal{V}(C^+ \cap C^-) = \mathcal{V}(C^+ \cap S^+) = \mathcal{V}(C^- \cap S^-)$, and hence the sum of the three expressions in eq. (6.3) exactly cancel, ensuring that the total action contains no β dependence.

It was a fortunate coincidence that β did not appear in the subregion complexity for the simple example considered in section 5. For more generic situations, we would expect the subregion complexity to depend on the analogous normalization constant for the null generators of the boundary of entanglement wedge. Essentially, the same issues which were discussed above for α , the normalization constant for the null generators on the boundaries of the WDW patch, will arise again here for β . It may seem natural to normalize the corresponding null normals near the asymptotic AdS boundary, in a manner similar to eq. (6.2). However, we point out that in the generic situation, the generators of the boundary of the entanglement wedge intersect the AdS boundary outside of the domain of dependence of the particular subregion of interest [24]. As a result, we have the somewhat unsettling possibility that the subregion complexity may depend on features of the background geometry or of the global state which are causally disconnected from the subregion. Certainly, our holographic proposals for evaluating subregion complexity should be studied further to make sure that they are consistent with the expectations which come from a quantum information perspective.

To conclude the discussion, we make a few comments on other possible future directions: It would be interesting to study the rate of growth or time-dependence of subregion complexity. For example, if one considers the thermofield double state and a subregion that includes portions on both boundaries of the dual black hole, then we know that at some late time, there will be a transition to the RT surface which is disconnected and the holographic entanglement entropy saturates at some constant value [56]. Similarly, we expect that the subregion complexity defined using either eq. (4.1) or eq. (5.1) will also saturate at the same time. Another possibility would be to extend the present considerations to holographic complexity in other bulk geometries, such as Lifshitz black holes and Dp-branes.

Recently, ref. [57] introduced the concept of ‘bit threads’, which are flow lines emanating from a boundary region A and threading the extremal RT surface, to define holographic entanglement in terms of the max flow-min cut principle. It would be interesting to understand if some property of the bit threads or the corresponding flows can be related to holographic complexity. It might also be of interest to consider other covariantly defined geometric features of the bulk, *e.g.*, the spacetime volume of the entire entanglement wedge or the gravitational action evaluated on this region [22]. It might also be interesting to extend the holographic complexity calculations to connect to the constructions appearing in [58, 59, 60, 61], where other fields are integrated over surfaces and regions in the bulk.

Acknowledgements

We thank Dorit Aharonov, Amin Faraji Astaneh, Omer Ben-Ami, Horacio Casini, Shira Chapman, Patrick Hayden, Michal Heller, Luis Lehner, Aitor Lewkowycz, Hugo Marrochio, Eric Poisson, Sergey

Solodukhin, Sotaro Sugishita, Brian Swingle, Guifre Vidal, Andrew Waldron, Run-Qiu Yang and Ying Zhao for useful comments and discussions. Research at Perimeter Institute is supported by the Government of Canada through the Department of Innovation, Science and Economic Development and by the Province of Ontario through the Ministry. The work of DC is partially supported by the Israel Science Foundation (grant 1989/14), the US-Israel Binational Science Foundation (grant 2012383) and the German-Israeli Foundation for Scientific Research and Development (grant I-244-303.7-2013). DC is also grateful for support from the Visiting Graduate Fellows program at the Perimeter Institute. PR is grateful to the Perimeter Scholars International program at Perimeter Institute. RCM is supported by funding from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, from the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research and from the Simons Foundation through the “It from Qubit” collaboration.

A. Action User’s Manual

The CA duality [9, 10] requires evaluating the gravitational action for a bulk spacetime region with null boundaries. It is only very recently that a careful analysis was made of the boundary terms which must be added to the gravitational action for null boundary surfaces and for joints where such null boundaries intersect with other boundary surfaces [14] — see also [62]. We review these results here but present them with a slightly different set of conventions. In particular, as discussed below, the normals to the boundary surfaces are always directed outward from the region of interest, and we do not make any special account for their orientation in time.

To begin, we write the gravitational action as

$$I = \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} \int_{\mathcal{M}} d^{d+1}x \sqrt{-g} (R - 2\Lambda) + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\mathcal{B}} d^d x \sqrt{|h|} K - \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\mathcal{B}'} d\lambda d^{d-1}\theta \sqrt{\gamma} \kappa + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\Sigma} d^{d-1}x \sqrt{\sigma} \eta + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\Sigma'} d^{d-1}x \sqrt{\sigma} a. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

In the first line, we have the standard Hilbert action, with a cosmological constant, and the Gibbons-Hawking boundary term [63, 64]. We have normalized the *negative* cosmological constant here such that L is the curvature scale of the anti-de Sitter vacuum.

Note that the Gibbons-Hawking boundary term is written in a way that it can be evaluated on either spacelike or timelike boundaries. However, to do so, we have a convention where the normal one-form is directed away from or out of the region of interest. That is, if a certain point of the boundary is determined by an equation $f(x) = 0$, then the function $f(x)$ increases as we move out of the region of interest and hence, the form df is directed outward. This may seem somewhat unconventional [14] since for a spacelike boundary, the (timelike) normal form $\mathbf{t} = t_\mu dx^\mu$ is outward directed but the normal vector $\vec{t} = t^\mu \partial_\mu$ is then inward directed.

The first term in the second line of eq. (A.1) is the corresponding surface term for null boundaries. The constant κ is defined by the equation

$$k^\rho \nabla_\rho k_\mu = \kappa k_\mu \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $\mathbf{k} = k_\mu dx^\mu$ is the outward directed null normal. We can think that κ measures the failure of λ to be an affine parameter on the null generators of the null boundary. Of course, by choosing the normalization \mathbf{k} appropriately then, we can always set $\kappa = 0$.

For nonsmooth boundaries, we have the two joint terms appearing as the second and third terms in the second line of eq. (A.1). Here we are only considering the contributions required for spacelike joints. In particular, the first term is required for spacelike joints of spacelike and timelike boundary regions [65], as illustrated in figure 5 — see also [66]. The integrand η is given by:

$$(a) \ \& \ (c) : \quad \cosh \eta \equiv |\mathbf{t}_1 \cdot \mathbf{t}_2| \quad \text{with} \quad \text{sign}(\eta) = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{t}_1 \cdot \mathbf{t}_2) \text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{t}_2) \quad (\text{A.3})$$

$$(b) \ \& \ (d) : \quad \cosh \eta \equiv |\mathbf{n}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_2| \quad \text{with} \quad \text{sign}(\eta) = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{n}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_2) \text{sign}(\mathbf{n}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_2) \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$(e) : \quad \sinh \eta \equiv \epsilon \mathbf{t}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_2 \quad \text{with} \quad \epsilon = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{n}_2 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{n}}_1) \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Our notation here distinguishes timelike and spacelike normals. In particular, timelike normals are denoted \mathbf{t}_i with $\mathbf{t}_i \cdot \mathbf{t}_i = -1$, and spacelike normals are denoted \mathbf{n}_i with $\mathbf{n}_i \cdot \mathbf{n}_i = +1$. Implicitly again we are referring to the outward directed normal one forms. We have also introduced auxiliary unit vectors, $\hat{\mathbf{n}}_i$ and $\hat{\mathbf{t}}_i$ — *vectors*, not one-forms. These are defined as the unit vector that is in the tangent space of the appropriate boundary region, orthogonal to the joint and pointing outward from the boundary region.

Figure 5: Various joints or junctions considered by Hayward [65]. Class I junctions are shown in (a) and (b) while Class II junctions are given in (c), (d) and (e).

Figure 6: Various different joints involving null boundaries. The null boundaries are indicated in blue.

We have chosen to normalize these auxiliary vectors as unit vectors but the signs in eqs. (A.3–A.5) are independent of the normalization of these vectors. Further note that although the expression for the sign of η is not symmetric in 1 and 2 (in the first two expressions), the result does not depend on which surfaces are labeled 1 or 2 since, *e.g.*, we have $\text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{t}_2) = \text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{t}_1)$ in eq. A.5.

The last term in eq. (A.1) is the appropriate boundary term for a spacelike joint involving one or two null boundary surfaces, as illustrated in figure 6. Here, the integrand a is given by:

$$(a) \ \& \ (e) : \quad a \equiv \epsilon \log |\mathbf{t}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2| \quad \text{with } \epsilon = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{t}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2) \text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{n}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$(b) \ \& \ (f) : \quad a \equiv \epsilon \log |\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_2| \quad \text{with } \epsilon = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{n}_2) \text{sign}(\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \hat{\mathbf{t}}_2), \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$(c) \ \& \ (d) : \quad a \equiv \epsilon \log |\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2/2| \quad \text{with } \epsilon = -\text{sign}(\mathbf{k}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2) \text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

Implicitly again we are referring to outward directed normal null one forms with \mathbf{k}_1 or \mathbf{k}_2 . Again, we also introduce auxiliary null vectors $\hat{\mathbf{k}}_i$ — *vectors*, not one-forms. These are defined as the null vector that is in the tangent space of the appropriate boundary region, orthogonal to the joint and pointing outward from the boundary region. Again, although the expression for the sign of a is not symmetric in 1 and 2 (in the last expression), the result does not depend on which surfaces are labeled 1 or 2 since, *e.g.*, we have $\text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_1 \cdot \mathbf{k}_2) = \text{sign}(\hat{\mathbf{k}}_2 \cdot \mathbf{k}_1)$ in eq. (A.8).

Further, we should recall from the discussion in [14], the boundary terms in eq. (A.1) associated with the null boundary surfaces and null joints are somewhat ambiguous. By construction, the variation of these boundary terms is well-defined and cancels the corresponding total derivative terms coming from the variation of the bulk action. However, when the gravitational action is evaluated on a particular

spacetime geometry, it will generally yield different numerical values depending on different choices that can be made in constructing these boundary terms. In particular, κ depends on an arbitrary choice for the parameterization for the null generators. Further, for the null joints, a depends on the arbitrary normalization of the null tangent k^α and in principle, we could add an additional function a_0 to a in eqs. (A.6–A.8), which remains fixed when the action is varied.

Now as discussed [14], there is a natural prescription to these ambiguities in the gravitational action. As mentioned above, the κ ambiguity is easily resolved by choosing the generators of the null boundary surfaces to be affinely parametrized, and then the corresponding boundary terms simply vanish. Further, eqs. (A.6–A.8) make a particular choice for the functions a_0 at the null joints which guaranteed additivity for the gravitational action. These choices leave only the freedom to rescale the affine parameter along any of the null boundaries by a constant factor. However, this final ambiguity can be removed by imposing a normalization condition on the null normals near the asymptotic AdS boundary. One particularly appealing aspect of these choices is that they allow us to make a meaningful comparison of the action for different WDW patches, including in different bulk spacetimes. For the most part, we simply adopt these choices formulated in [14] for our calculations of I_{WDW} . However, we will not choose a fixed normalization condition for the null normals at the AdS boundary in sections 3 and 5 — see discussion in section 6.

B. Example: Extremal volume for a spherical boundary

Let us consider an explicit example of a codimension-one slice of the boundary where both the intrinsic and extrinsic curvatures are non-vanishing. For simplicity, we will consider Euclidean AdS_{d+1} in a foliation where the full boundary metric is simply S^d , with standard coordinates $\{\theta, \phi_1, \dots, \phi_{d-1}\}$ — see figure 7. Then we can consider a codimension-one slice with the geometry S^{d-1} given by $\theta = \theta_0$, for which the extrinsic curvature is nonvanishing as long as $\theta_0 \neq \frac{\pi}{2}$. To obtain the corresponding extremal surface in the bulk, we could write the volume functional (2.6) and attempt to solve the Euler-Lagrange equations (2.7). From spherical symmetry, we know that $\theta = \theta(\rho)$ where ρ is the bulk radial direction which certainly simplifies the latter task.

Figure 7: Extremal surface with $\theta_0 \neq \frac{\pi}{2}$ obtained by boosting the symmetric extremal surface at $\theta_0 = \frac{\pi}{2}$.

However, we proceed with a useful trick following the discussion in [54]. That is, we use the fact that AdS can be embedded in flat space in one higher dimension

$$ds^2 = -dy_{-1}^2 + \sum_{i=0}^d dy_i^2. \quad (\text{B.1})$$

Now AdS_{d+1} is basically a hyperbolic slice of this, such that

$$y_{-1}^2 - \sum_{i=0}^d y_i^2 = L^2 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

Consider the foliation

$$\begin{aligned} y_{-1} &= L \cosh u, & y_0 &= L \sinh u \cos \theta \\ y_1 &= L \sinh u \sin \theta \cos \phi_1, & \dots, & y_d = L \sinh u \sin \theta \cdots \sin \phi_{d-1} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

which then yields the induced metric for the AdS geometry

$$ds^2 = L^2 [du^2 + \sinh^2 u d\Omega_d^2] \quad (\text{B.4})$$

where $d\Omega_d^2$ is the usual line element on a unit S^d . Let us look at the plane $y_0 = 0 \implies \theta = \frac{\pi}{2}$. By symmetry, this must be an extremal surface and its intersection with the boundary which lies at $u \rightarrow \infty$, is the equator of the boundary S^d . Hence we can see the bulk surface described by $y_0 = 0$ is a codimension-one extremal surface with an S^{d-1} boundary. Now we simply perform a boost with boost parameter β in the embedding space (B.1), which shifts the plane and hence its intersection surface (B.2),

$$\begin{aligned} y_{-1} &= (\cosh \beta)L \cosh u + (\sinh \beta)L \sinh u \cos \theta', \\ y_0 &= (\sinh \beta)L \cosh u + (\cosh \beta)L \sinh u \cos \theta'. \end{aligned}$$

where θ' is the angular coordinate for the symmetric extremal surface. Setting $\theta' = \frac{\pi}{2}$, we get an equation for $\theta(u)$

$$\cos \theta = \coth u \sinh \beta \quad (\text{B.5})$$

where, as $u \rightarrow \infty$, $\theta \rightarrow \cos^{-1}(\sinh \beta) = \theta_0 \neq \frac{\pi}{2}$. We can check that this bulk surface (B.5) satisfies the required Euler-Lagrange equation. Transforming the radial coordinate with $u = \log(2L/z)$, the AdS metric (B.4) is put in FG form (2.1)

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{z^2} \left[dz^2 + \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{4L^2} \right)^2 L^2 d\Omega_d^2 \right] \quad (\text{B.6})$$

with the extremal surface becoming $\theta(\rho) = \cos^{-1} \left(\left(\frac{1+\rho/4}{1-\rho/4} \right) \cos \theta_0 \right)$. From this result, we can obtain the induced metric which, when substituted into the volume functional, yields the complexity

$$\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N} \frac{\sin^{d-1} \theta_0 \Omega_{d-1}}{d-1} \left(\frac{L^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{(d-1)^2 L^{d-3}}{4(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} - \frac{(d-1)(d-2) \cot^2 \theta_0 L^{d-3}}{2(d-3)\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right), \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where as in the main text, we have set the regulator surface at $z = \delta$.

Now the boundary metric is $ds_{\text{bdy}}^2 = L^2 d\Omega_d^2$. Hence we recognize $L^{d-1} \sin^{d-1} \theta_0 \Omega_{d-1}$ as the volume of the S^{d-1} boundary slice. Further we can evaluate

$$\mathcal{R} = \frac{d(d-1)}{L^2}, \quad \mathcal{R}_a^a = \frac{(d-1)^2}{L^2}, \quad K = \frac{(d-1) \cot \theta_0}{L} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

Then we can explicitly confirm that the expansion of the complexity in eq. (B.7) matches eq. (2.13), with integrals of boundary curvature invariants. There is one minor discrepancy in this comparison, namely, the $\cot^2 \theta_0$ term above appears with a positive sign while the sign of the K^2 term in eq. (2.13) is negative. This difference occurs because implicitly this sign is set by a factor of $\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ and while the calculations in the section 2 use a Lorentzian signature, in this appendix, we work with a Euclidean signature.

C. Example: Wheeler-DeWitt action for global AdS

Using the rules prescribed in appendix A, here we study the divergence structure of the WDW action in the simple example of a constant time slice on the boundary of global AdS_{d+1} . We will also compare the results found using the two different regularization procedures illustrated in figure 2. In either case, we introduce a standard (timelike) regulator surface at a distance δ from the boundary of AdS. Then in figure 2a, we discard the portion of the WDW patch extending beyond this surface, *i.e.*, we only integrate the bulk action out to this maximum radius. However, the regulated WDW region then has a new timelike boundary segment and two null joints at this surface, which contribute to I_{WDW} . In figure 2b, we instead regulate the calculation by simply shifting the edge of the WDW patch inwards to the regulator surface. We will show that the structure of the UV divergences in the corresponding complexity \mathcal{C}_A is the same for both procedures.

The AdS_{d+1} metric with boundary geometry $R \times S^{d-1}$ can be written in the following form:

$$ds^2 = \frac{L^2}{\cos^2 \theta} (-d\tau^2 + d\theta^2 + \sin^2 \theta d\Omega_{d-1}^2), \quad (\text{C.1})$$

where L is the AdS radius, and the boundary is at $\theta = \pi/2$. From the previous discussion of the geometries in figure 2, we see that the WDW action may receive contributions from the Einstein-Hilbert bulk term, the Gibbons-Hawking-York boundary term, and the null joint terms in eq. (A.1):

$$I_{\text{WDW}} = I_{\text{bulk}} + I_{\text{GHY}} + I_{\text{jnt}}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

As discussed in appendix A, we are assuming that the generators on null boundaries are affinely parametrized so that we may ignore the null boundary terms, *i.e.*, $\kappa = 0$. One may also examine the contributions to the gravitational action coming from the caustics at the tips of the WDW patch where all of the null generators meet. However, these contributions were examined in detail in [39] and were shown to vanish there.

Using the regularization of Figure 2a, the boundaries of the WDW patch are

$$S^+ : \quad \theta = \frac{\pi}{2} - \tau \quad \text{for} \quad \frac{\pi}{2} \geq \tau \geq \delta',$$

$$\begin{aligned}
S^- : \quad \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} + \tau \quad \text{for} \quad -\frac{\pi}{2} \leq \tau \leq -\delta', \\
R : \quad \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} - \delta' \quad \text{for} \quad -\delta' \leq \tau \leq \delta',
\end{aligned} \tag{C.3}$$

where S^+ and S^- are the future and past null boundaries, while R is the UV regulator surface. Of course, implicitly we have chosen the boundary time slice to be $\tau = 0$. The bulk contribution to the WDW action then becomes

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{d L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \int_{\delta'}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} d\theta' \theta' \cot^{d-1} \theta' \csc^2 \theta' \tag{C.4}$$

where $\theta' = \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta$ and Ω_{d-1} is the area of a unit $(d-1)$ -sphere. The integral above can be evaluated in terms of hypergeometric functions, but here we are only looking for the leading behavior as $\delta' \rightarrow 0$, which can be extracted using a series expansion for small θ' ,

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{d L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\frac{1}{(d-1)\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{d-2}{30(d-3)\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \tag{C.5}$$

To evaluate the GHY and null joint terms, we must consider the normals to the boundary surfaces (C.3),

$$S^+ : \mathbf{k}_1 = \alpha_1 L (d\theta + d\tau), \quad S^- : \mathbf{k}_2 = \alpha_2 L (d\theta - d\tau), \quad R : \mathbf{n} = \frac{L}{\sin \delta'} d\theta, \tag{C.6}$$

where $\alpha_{1,2}$ are (dimensionless) normalization constants. For the regulator surface R , we have $K = \frac{1}{L} \left(\frac{d-1}{\cos \delta'} + \cos \delta' \right)$ and hence the corresponding boundary term becomes

$$I_{\text{GHY}} = \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \delta' \frac{\cos^d \delta'}{\sin^d \delta'} \left(\frac{d-1}{\cos^2 \delta'} + 1 \right) = \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left(\frac{d}{\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{d^2 - 3d + 3}{3\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right), \tag{C.7}$$

where we are considering the limit $\delta' \rightarrow 0$ in the final expression. For the null joint at $S^+ \cap R$, eq. (A.7) yields $a_1 = -\log(\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k}_1) = -\log(\alpha_1 \sin \delta')$. Similarly for $S^- \cap R$, $a_2 = -\log(\alpha_2 \sin \delta')$. Hence combining the two joint contributions yields

$$\begin{aligned}
I_{\text{int}} &= -\frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \frac{\cos^{d-1} \delta'}{\sin^{d-1} \delta'} \log(\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \sin \delta') \\
&= \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\log\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta'}\right) \left(\frac{1}{\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{3\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right) + \left(\frac{1}{6\delta'^{d-3}} - \frac{10d-11}{180\delta'^{d-5}} \right) \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{C.8}$$

Combining all of the above results, we see the divergence structure of the corresponding complexity (1.2) emerges as

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathcal{C}_A &= \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \left[\frac{d(d-2)}{(d-1)\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{10d^3 - 61d^2 + 117d - 75}{30(d-3)\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \\
&\quad + \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \log\left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta'}\right) \left[\frac{1}{\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{3\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right]
\end{aligned} \tag{C.9}$$

Note that the leading divergence coming from the joint term is positive. Likewise, the leading power divergence is positive in this regularization.

This result is expressed in terms of the (dimensionless) boundary regulator δ' , which was convenient in the present coordinates (C.1). To relate δ' to the short-distance cutoff δ appearing in the main text, we introduce the coordinate transformation

$$z = \frac{2L \cos \theta}{1 + \sin \theta}. \quad (\text{C.10})$$

Thus, the two regulators are related by

$$\delta = \frac{2L \sin \delta'}{1 + \cos \delta'} \longrightarrow \delta' = \frac{\delta}{L} - \frac{\delta^3}{12 L^3} + \dots. \quad (\text{C.11})$$

Then, in terms of δ , the complexity (C.9) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{C}_A = & \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \left[\frac{d(d-2)}{d-1} \frac{L^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{15d^3 - 97d^2 + 199d - 135}{60(d-3)} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \\ & + \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \log \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta} \right) \left[\frac{L^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{4} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.12})$$

Alternatively, we could have used the second regularization illustrated Figure 2b. For this case there is no time-like boundary, and the null normals \mathbf{k}_1 and \mathbf{k}_2 are the same as in eq. (C.6). The boundaries of the WDW patch are:

$$\begin{aligned} S^+ : \quad \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} - \tau - \delta' \quad \text{for} \quad \frac{\pi}{2} - \delta' \geq \tau \geq 0, \\ S^- : \quad \theta &= \frac{\pi}{2} + \tau - \delta' \quad \text{for} \quad -\frac{\pi}{2} + \delta' \leq \tau \leq 0, \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.13})$$

For this case there is no space-like boundary. The joint terms turn out to be the same in the two regularizations. Expressed in terms of the cutoff δ , eq. (C.8) becomes

$$I_{\text{int}} = \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\log \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta} \right) \left(\frac{L^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{4} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right) + \left(\frac{L^{d-3}}{4\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right) \right]. \quad (\text{C.14})$$

However, the bulk term is slightly modified:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{bulk}} &= \frac{2}{16\pi G_N} \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - \delta'} d\theta \int_0^{\frac{\pi}{2} - \theta - \delta'} d\tau \int d\Omega_{d-1} \frac{L^{d+1} \sin^{d-1} \theta}{\cos^{d+1} \theta} \left(\frac{-2d}{L^2} \right) \\ &= -\frac{d L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \int_{\delta'}^{\frac{\pi}{2}} dx (x - \delta') \cot^{d-1} x \csc^2 x \\ &= -\frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\frac{1}{(d-1)\delta'^{d-1}} - \frac{d}{3(d-3)} \frac{1}{\delta'^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \\ &= -\frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left[\frac{L^{d-1}}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{(d+1)}{4(d-3)} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.15})$$

Combining these two contributions for the action, we find

$$\mathcal{C}_A = -\frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \left[\frac{L^{d-1}}{(d-1)\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{2(d-3)} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right] \quad (\text{C.16})$$

$$+ \frac{L^{d-1} \Omega_{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \log \left(\frac{L}{\sqrt{\alpha_1 \alpha_2} \delta} \right) \left[\frac{L^{d-1}}{\delta^{d-1}} - \frac{d-1}{4} \frac{L^{d-3}}{\delta^{d-3}} + \dots \right]$$

This result can also be compared with the general geometric expression in eq. (3.16). The required curvature invariants for the present example are

$$\mathcal{R} = \mathcal{R}_a^a = \frac{(d-1)(d-2)}{L^2}, \quad K^2 = K_{ab}K^{ab} = 0. \quad (\text{C.17})$$

Now substituting these expressions into eq. (3.16) reproduces precisely the divergences given above in eq. (C.16).

Comparing eqs. (C.12) and (C.16), we see that the form of divergences remains the same between the two regularizations, however, the coefficients are typically different. Generally, these coefficients are not universal and so these differences are not at all surprising. However, it is of interest to compare the logarithmic contribution appearing with the two regulators since the coefficient of this term is usually regarded as universal. However, unfortunately a careful analysis shows that in general the two regularizations produce different coefficients for this term as well. We expect that this difference is related to the ambiguity in the choice of the normalization constants, α_1 and α_2 , discussed in section 6.

D. Geometric details for CA duality calculation

Two coefficients, $q_0^{(2)}$ and $q_2^{(0)}$, appear in eq. (3.11) and here we will derive eq. (3.12) which provides a geometric translation for these factors. Recall that these coefficients were defined by the double expansion of the measure $\sqrt{\gamma} = \sqrt{\det[g_{ab}(x, z)]}$ in eq. (3.8), which we reproduce here for the reader's convenience:

$$\sqrt{\gamma} = \sqrt{h(\sigma)} \left([1 + q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + \dots] + [q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a) + q_1^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + \dots]t + [q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a) + q_2^{(2)}(\sigma^a)z^2 + \dots]t^2 + \dots \right) \quad (\text{D.1})$$

Expanding the determinant using FG expansion (2.2), as well as eq. (2.3), then yields

$$\sqrt{\gamma} = \sqrt{h} \left(1 + \frac{z^2}{2} g^{ab(0)} g_{ab(1)} + \dots \right) = \sqrt{h} \left(1 - \frac{z^2}{2(d-2)} \left(\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{R} \right) + \dots \right) \quad (\text{D.2})$$

where $\mathcal{R}_a^a = h^{ab} \mathcal{R}_{ab}$ — recall that the boundary metric takes the form given in eq. (3.1) and we are considering the time slice $t = 0$. Hence comparing eqs. (D.1) and (D.2), we see

$$q_0^{(2)}(\sigma^a) = -\frac{1}{2(d-2)} \left(\mathcal{R}_a^a - \frac{1}{2} \mathcal{R} \right) \Big|_{t=0}. \quad (\text{D.3})$$

To evaluate $q_1^{(0)}$ and $q_2^{(0)}$, we first set $z = 0$ to reduce eq. (D.1) to

$$\sqrt{\gamma}|_{z=0} = \sqrt{h} \left(1 + q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a)t + q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a)t^2 + \dots \right). \quad (\text{D.4})$$

Now differentiating with respect to time, we find

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{h}} \partial_t \sqrt{\gamma}|_{t=0} = q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a), \quad \frac{1}{\sqrt{h}} \partial_t^2 \sqrt{\gamma}|_{t=0} = 2q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a). \quad (\text{D.5})$$

Now we may write the trace of the extrinsic curvature as

$$K(t, \sigma) = \nabla_\mu n^\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_\mu (n^\mu \sqrt{-g}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_t (n^t \sqrt{-g}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g}} \partial_t \left(\frac{\sqrt{-g}}{\sqrt{-g_{tt}}} \right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\gamma}} \partial_t \sqrt{\gamma}, \quad (\text{D.6})$$

since we have fixed the boundary metric as in eq. (3.1). Hence comparing the last two equations, we see

$$q_1^{(0)}(\sigma^a) = K(t, \sigma)|_{t=0}. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

Now turning on to $q_2^{(0)}$, eq. D.6 gives

$$\sqrt{\gamma} K(t, \sigma) = \partial_t \sqrt{\gamma}. \quad (\text{D.8})$$

By differentiating this result, we can rewrite the expression for $q_2^{(0)}$ in eq. (D.5) as

$$q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a) = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{h}} \partial_t^2 \sqrt{\gamma}|_{t=0} = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{h}} \partial_t [\sqrt{\gamma} K(t, \sigma)]|_{t=0} = \frac{1}{2} [K^2 + \partial_t K]|_{t=0}, \quad (\text{D.9})$$

where the final result uses eq. (D.8) again. To find a covariant replacement for $\partial_t K$, we can use the following identity (*e.g.*, see [67])

$$\frac{1}{N} [\mathcal{L}_m K + D_a D^a N] = K_{ab} K^{ab} + n^i n^j \mathcal{R}_{ij} \quad (\text{D.10})$$

where N is the lapse function. In our case, $\mathcal{L}_m = \partial_t$ and $N = 1$, and hence we may write

$$\partial_t K = K_{ab} K^{ab} + n^i n^j \mathcal{R}_{ij} = K_{ab} K^{ab} + \mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R} \quad (\text{D.11})$$

where we used $n^i n^j \mathcal{R}_{ij} = \mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R}$. Thus from eq.(D.9), we have

$$q_2^{(0)}(\sigma^a) = \frac{1}{2} \left(K^2 + K_{ab} K^{ab} + \mathcal{R}_a^a - \mathcal{R} \right) \Big|_{t=0}. \quad (\text{D.12})$$

References

- [1] J. Watrous, ‘‘Quantum computational complexity,’’ in *Encyclopedia of Complexity and Systems Science*, ed., R. A. Meyers (2009) 7174–7201, [arXiv:0804.3401 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [2] S. Gharibian, Y. Huang, Z. Landau, and S. W. Shin, ‘‘Quantum hamiltonian complexity,’’ *Foundations and Trends in Theoretical Computer Science* **10** (2015) 159–282, [arXiv:1401.3916 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [3] T. J. Osborne, ‘‘Hamiltonian complexity,’’ *Reports on Progress in Physics* **75** (2012) 022001, [arXiv:1106.5875 \[quant-ph\]](#).
- [4] L. Susskind, ‘‘Computational Complexity and Black Hole Horizons,’’ *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 24–43, [arXiv:1402.5674 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [5] L. Susskind, ‘‘Addendum to: Computational Complexity and Black Hole Horizons,’’ *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 44, [arXiv:1403.5695 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [6] D. Stanford and L. Susskind, ‘‘Complexity and Shock Wave Geometries,’’ *Phys. Rev.* **D90** (2014) 126007, [arXiv:1406.2678 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [7] L. Susskind and Y. Zhao, “Switchbacks and the Bridge to Nowhere,” [arXiv:1408.2823 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [8] L. Susskind, “Entanglement is not enough,” *Fortsch. Phys.* **64** (2016) 49–71, [arXiv:1411.0690 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [9] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, “Holographic Complexity Equals Bulk Action?,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116** (2016) 191301, [arXiv:1509.07876 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [10] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle, and Y. Zhao, “Complexity, action, and black holes,” *Phys. Rev.* **D93** (2016) 086006, [arXiv:1512.04993 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [11] J. Couch, W. Fischler, and P. H. Nguyen, “Noether charge, black hole volume and complexity,” [arXiv:1610.02038 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [12] M. Christodoulou and C. Rovelli, “How big is a black hole?,” *Phys. Rev.* **D91** (2015) 064046, [arXiv:1411.2854 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [13] M. Christodoulou and T. De Lorenzo, “Volume inside old black holes,” *Phys. Rev.* **D94** (2016) 104002, [arXiv:1604.07222 \[gr-qc\]](#).
- [14] L. Lehner, R. C. Myers, E. Poisson, and R. D. Sorkin, “Gravitational action with null boundaries,” *Phys. Rev.* **D94** (2016) 084046, [arXiv:1609.00207 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [15] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **96** (2006) 181602, [arXiv:hep-th/0603001 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [16] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, “Aspects of Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2006) 045, [arXiv:hep-th/0605073 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [17] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “On Holographic Entanglement Entropy and Higher Curvature Gravity,” *JHEP* **04** (2011) 025, [arXiv:1101.5813 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [18] L.-Y. Hung, R. C. Myers, and M. Smolkin, “Some Calculable Contributions to Holographic Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2011) 039, [arXiv:1105.6055 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [19] L. Bombelli, R. K. Koul, J. Lee, and R. D. Sorkin, “A Quantum Source of Entropy for Black Holes,” *Phys. Rev.* **D34** (1986) 373–383.
- [20] M. Srednicki, “Entropy and area,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **71** (1993) 666–669, [arXiv:hep-th/9303048 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [21] M. Alishahiha, “Holographic Complexity,” *Phys. Rev.* **D92** (2015) 126009, [arXiv:1509.06614 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [22] O. Ben-Ami and D. Carmi, “On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity,” *JHEP* **11** (2016) 129, [arXiv:1609.02514 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [23] B. Czech, J. L. Karczmarek, F. Nogueira, and M. Van Raamsdonk, “The Gravity Dual of a Density Matrix,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **29** (2012) 155009, [arXiv:1204.1330 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [24] M. Headrick, V. E. Hubeny, A. Lawrence, and M. Rangamani, “Causality & holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **12** (2014) 162, [arXiv:1408.6300 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [25] R. Emparan, C. V. Johnson, and R. C. Myers, “Surface terms as counterterms in the AdS/CFT correspondence,” *Phys. Rev.* **D60** (1999) 104001, [arXiv:hep-th/9903238 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [26] S. de Haro, S. N. Solodukhin, and K. Skenderis, “Holographic reconstruction of space-time and renormalization in the AdS/CFT correspondence,” *Commun. Math. Phys.* **217** (2001) 595–622, [arXiv:hep-th/0002230 \[hep-th\]](#).

- [27] K. Skenderis, “Lecture notes on holographic renormalization,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **19** (2002) 5849–5876, [arXiv:hep-th/0209067 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [28] A. Schwimmer and S. Theisen, “Entanglement Entropy, Trace Anomalies and Holography,” *Nucl. Phys.* **B801** (2008) 1–24, [arXiv:0802.1017 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [29] C. Fefferman and C. R. Graham, “The ambient metric,” [arXiv:0710.0919 \[math.DG\]](#).
- [30] C. R. Graham and E. Witten, “Conformal anomaly of submanifold observables in AdS/CFT correspondence,” *Nucl. Phys.* **B546** (1999) 52–64, [arXiv:hep-th/9901021 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [31] C. R. Graham and E. Witten, “Conformal anomaly of submanifold observables in AdS / CFT correspondence,” *Nucl. Phys.* **B546** (1999) 52–64, [arXiv:hep-th/9901021 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [32] A. Buchel, J. Escobedo, R. C. Myers, M. F. Paulos, A. Sinha, and M. Smolkin, “Holographic GB gravity in arbitrary dimensions,” *JHEP* **03** (2010) 111, [arXiv:0911.4257 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [33] R. C. Myers, M. F. Paulos, and A. Sinha, “Holographic studies of quasi-topological gravity,” *JHEP* **08** (2010) 035, [arXiv:1004.2055 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [34] P. Bueno and R. C. Myers, “Corner contributions to holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **08** (2015) 068, [arXiv:1505.07842 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [35] S. N. Solodukhin, “Entanglement entropy, conformal invariance and extrinsic geometry,” *Phys. Lett.* **B665** (2008) 305–309, [arXiv:0802.3117 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [36] R. C. Myers and A. Singh, “Entanglement Entropy for Singular Surfaces,” *JHEP* **09** (2012) 013, [arXiv:1206.5225 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [37] V. E. Hubeny, M. Rangamani, and T. Takayanagi, “A Covariant holographic entanglement entropy proposal,” *JHEP* **07** (2007) 062, [arXiv:0705.0016 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [38] X. Dong, A. Lewkowycz, and M. Rangamani, “Deriving covariant holographic entanglement,” *JHEP* **11** (2016) 028, [arXiv:1607.07506 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [39] S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, and R. C. Myers, “Complexity of Formation in Holography,” [arXiv:1610.08063 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [40] D. Carmi, “More on Holographic Volumes.” In preparation.
- [41] D. Marolf and A. C. Wall, “State-Dependent Divergences in the Entanglement Entropy,” *JHEP* **10** (2016) 109, [arXiv:1607.01246 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [42] D. Carmi, S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, R. C. Myers, and S. Sugishita, “On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity.” In preparation.
- [43] A. Reynolds and S. F. Ross, “Divergences in Holographic Complexity,” [arXiv:1612.05439 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [44] M. Kruczenski, “A Note on twist two operators in N=4 SYM and Wilson loops in Minkowski signature,” *JHEP* **12** (2002) 024, [arXiv:hep-th/0210115 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [45] L. F. Alday and J. M. Maldacena, “Gluon scattering amplitudes at strong coupling,” *JHEP* **06** (2007) 064, [arXiv:0705.0303 \[hep-th\]](#).
- [46] M. A. Nielsen, “A geometric approach to quantum circuit lower bounds,” *Quantum Info. Comput.* **6** no. 3, (May, 2006) 213–262, [arXiv:quant-ph/0502070 \[quant-ph\]](#).

- [47] M. A. Nielsen, M. R. Dowling, M. Gu, and A. C. Doherty, “Quantum computation as geometry,” *Science* **311** no. 5764, (2006) 1133–1135, [arXiv:quant-ph/0603161](#) [quant-ph].
- [48] M. R. Dowling and M. A. Nielsen, “The geometry of quantum computation,” *Quantum Info. Comput.* **8** no. 10, (Nov., 2008) 861–899, [arXiv:quant-ph/0701004](#) [quant-ph].
- [49] D. A. Roberts and B. Yoshida, “Chaos and complexity by design,” [arXiv:1610.04903](#) [quant-ph].
- [50] D. Aharonov, A. Kitaev, and N. Nisan, “Quantum circuits with mixed states,” in *Proceedings of the Thirtieth Annual ACM Symposium on Theory of Computing* (1998) 20–30, [arXiv:quant-ph/9806029](#) [quant-ph].
- [51] W. F. Stinespring, “Positive functions on c^* -algebras,” *Proceedings of the American Mathematical Society* **6** no. 2, (1955) 211–216.
- [52] R. Arias, D. Blanco, H. Casini, and M. Huerta, “Local temperatures and local terms in modular Hamiltonians,” [arXiv:1611.08517](#) [hep-th].
- [53] E. Bianchi and R. C. Myers, “On the Architecture of Spacetime Geometry,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **31** (2014) 214002, [arXiv:1212.5183](#) [hep-th].
- [54] H. Casini, M. Huerta, and R. C. Myers, “Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,” *JHEP* **05** (2011) 036, [arXiv:1102.0440](#) [hep-th].
- [55] T. Faulkner, M. Guica, T. Hartman, R. C. Myers, and M. Van Raamsdonk, “Gravitation from Entanglement in Holographic CFTs,” *JHEP* **03** (2014) 051, [arXiv:1312.7856](#) [hep-th].
- [56] T. Hartman and J. Maldacena, “Time Evolution of Entanglement Entropy from Black Hole Interiors,” *JHEP* **05** (2013) 014, [arXiv:1303.1080](#) [hep-th].
- [57] M. Freedman and M. Headrick, “Bit threads and holographic entanglement,” [arXiv:1604.00354](#) [hep-th].
- [58] N. Lashkari and M. Van Raamsdonk, “Canonical Energy is Quantum Fisher Information,” *JHEP* **04** (2016) 153, [arXiv:1508.00897](#) [hep-th].
- [59] J. de Boer, M. P. Heller, R. C. Myers, and Y. Neiman, “Holographic de Sitter Geometry from Entanglement in Conformal Field Theory,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **116** (2016) 061602, [arXiv:1509.00113](#) [hep-th].
- [60] J. de Boer, F. M. Haehl, M. P. Heller, and R. C. Myers, “Entanglement, holography and causal diamonds,” *JHEP* **08** (2016) 162, [arXiv:1606.03307](#) [hep-th].
- [61] B. Czech, L. Lamprou, S. McCandlish, B. Mosk, and J. Sully, “A Stereoscopic Look into the Bulk,” *JHEP* **07** (2016) 129, [arXiv:1604.03110](#) [hep-th].
- [62] K. Parattu, S. Chakraborty, B. R. Majhi, and T. Padmanabhan, “A Boundary Term for the Gravitational Action with Null Boundaries,” *Gen. Rel. Grav.* **48** (2016) 94, [arXiv:1501.01053](#) [gr-qc].
- [63] J. W. York, Jr., “Role of conformal three geometry in the dynamics of gravitation,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **28** (1972) 1082–1085.
- [64] G. W. Gibbons and S. W. Hawking, “Cosmological Event Horizons, Thermodynamics, and Particle Creation,” *Phys. Rev.* **D15** (1977) 2738–2751.
- [65] G. Hayward, “Gravitational action for space-times with nonsmooth boundaries,” *Phys. Rev.* **D47** (1993) 3275–3280.
- [66] D. Brill and G. Hayward, “Is the gravitational action additive?,” *Phys. Rev.* **D50** (1994) 4914–4919, [arXiv:gr-qc/9403018](#) [gr-qc].
- [67] E.ourgoulhon, “3+1 formalism and bases of numerical relativity,” [arXiv:gr-qc/0703035](#) [gr-qc].

Chapter 8

On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity

On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity

Dean Carmi,^{a,b} Shira Chapman,^a Hugo Marrochio,^{a,c} Robert C. Myers^a and Sotaro Sugishita^{a,d}

^a*Perimeter Institute for Theoretical Physics, Waterloo, ON N2L 2Y5, Canada*

^b*Raymond and Beverly Sackler Faculty of Exact Sciences*

School of Physics and Astronomy, Tel-Aviv University, Ramat-Aviv 69978, Israel

^c*Department of Physics & Astronomy*

University of Waterloo, Waterloo, ON N2L 3G1, Canada

^d*Department of Physics, Osaka University, Toyonaka, Osaka, 560-0043, Japan*

E-mail: schapman@perimeterinstitute.ca,

hmarrochio@perimeterinstitute.ca, rmyers@perimeterinstitute.ca,

sugishita@het.phys.sci.osaka-u.ac.jp

ABSTRACT: We evaluate the full time dependence of holographic complexity in various eternal black hole backgrounds using both the complexity=action (CA) and the complexity=volume (CV) conjectures. We conclude using the CV conjecture that the rate of change of complexity is a monotonically increasing function of time, which saturates from below to a positive constant in the late time limit. Using the CA conjecture for uncharged black holes, the holographic complexity remains constant for an initial period, then briefly decreases but quickly begins to increase. As observed previously, at late times, the rate of growth of the complexity approaches a constant, which may be associated with Lloyd's bound on the rate of computation. However, we find that this late time limit is approached from above, thus violating the bound. Adding a charge to the eternal black holes washes out the early time behaviour, *i.e.*, complexity immediately begins increasing with sufficient charge, but the late time behaviour is essentially the same as in the neutral case. We also evaluate the complexity of formation for charged black holes and find that it is divergent for extremal black holes, implying that the states at finite chemical potential and zero temperature are infinitely more complex than their finite temperature counterparts.

Contents

1	Introduction	2
2	Complexity=Action	5
2.1	Evaluating the Action	6
2.2	Time Dependence of Complexity	13
2.3	Examples	19
3	Complexity=Volume	23
3.1	Late Time Behaviour	27
3.2	General Time Dependence	31
4	Charged Black Holes	31
4.1	Complexity=Action	38
4.2	Complexity=Volume	44
5	Discussion	45
A	Details of Complexity=Action for BTZ Black Holes	52
A.1	General Boundary Times	52
A.2	Boundary Counterterm	56
B	Additional Examples of Time Dependence of Complexity	59
B.1	CA Results in $d = 3$	59
B.2	CV Results for Other Geometries	62
C	Late Time Behaviour for the CV Proposal	63
D	Complexity of Formation for Charged Black Holes	66
D.1	Complexity=Action	67
D.2	Complexity=Volume	72
D.3	Small Hyperbolic Black Holes	74
E	Ambiguities in the Action Calculations	76
E.1	Influence of a Constant a_0	76
E.2	Boundary Counterterm	77

1 Introduction

In recent years, surprising new connections have been developing between quantum information and quantum gravity. The AdS/CFT correspondence allows us to quantitatively study these connections in a holographic framework where certain geometric quantities in the bulk spacetime can be related to the entanglement properties of the boundary field theory. The Ryu-Takayanagi construction, which provides a geometrical realization of the entanglement entropy of the boundary CFT, is the prime example of such a relation [1–4]. However, a new concept that has recently entered this discussion is quantum computational complexity. In fact, two holographic proposals have been developed to describe the quantum complexity of states in the boundary theory, namely, the complexity=volume (CV) conjecture [5, 6] and the complexity=action (CA) conjecture [7, 8].

In the holographic context, quantum complexity quantifies how hard it is to prepare a particular state of interest, by applying a series of (simple) elementary gates to a (simple) reference state, *e.g.*, see [9, 10] for reviews. However, despite being relatively well understood for spin-chains, only recently complexity models have been developed for quantum field theories [11–13]. While only considering free scalars [11, 12], these calculations yield striking similarities to the results produced with holographic complexity. In [13], the time dependence of complexity in Abelian gauge theories was studied. Related investigations attempting to better understand complexity from the perspective of the boundary theory have also appeared in [14–19].

A prime arena for discussions of holographic complexity has been the eternal two-sided black hole and this will also be the case in the present paper. This bulk geometry is dual to the thermofield double state in the boundary theory [20],

$$|\text{TFD}(t_L, t_R)\rangle = Z^{-1/2} \sum_{\alpha} e^{-E_{\alpha}/(2T)} e^{-iE_{\alpha}(t_L+t_R)} |E_{\alpha}\rangle_L |E_{\alpha}\rangle_R, \quad (1.1)$$

where L and R label the quantum states (and times) associated with the left and right boundaries. Hence, we have an entangled state of two copies of the boundary CFT and this entanglement is responsible for the geometric connection in the bulk, *i.e.*, the Einstein-Rosen bridge [21, 22]. A puzzle was to understand the growth of the black hole interior in terms of the boundary degrees of freedom. The conjectured holographic complexity appears to provide an explanation [5], since a characteristic property of quantum complexity is that it continues to grow for very long times after the system has thermalized. In fact, the complexity is conjectured to continue growing until a time scale which is exponential in the number of degrees of freedom in the system [23].

Turning to the bulk definitions proposed for holographic complexity, we have the following: The complexity=volume conjecture equates the complexity to the volume¹ of the extremal/maximal time slice anchored at boundary times t_L and t_R [5, 6],

$$\mathcal{C}_V = \max \left[\frac{\mathcal{V}(\mathcal{B})}{G_N \ell} \right], \quad (1.2)$$

where ℓ is a certain length scale associated with the geometry (see figure 5). The complexity=action conjecture instead equates the boundary complexity with the gravitational action evaluated on a region of spacetime known as the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) patch, *i.e.*, the region bounded by the null surfaces anchored at the relevant times on the left and right boundaries (see, *e.g.*, figure 1)

$$\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{I_{WDW}}{\pi \hbar}. \quad (1.3)$$

One might also regard the WDW patch as the domain of dependence of the maximal time slice appearing in the CV conjecture. However, one should keep in mind that there are also certain ambiguities in defining the contributions of the null boundaries to the gravitational action I_{WDW} [25]. Various features of these two holographic quantities have been studied — *e.g.*, see [5–8, 26–29]. While eqs. (1.2) and (1.3) do not yield the same results quantitatively for the complexity, they still agree at a qualitative level. Therefore it may be that the differences of these bulk quantities are related to differences in the microscopic definition of complexity in the boundary theory, *e.g.*, in the choice of elementary gates [26].

One striking result found with the CA proposal is that the late time growth rate is proportional to $2M/\pi$, independent of the boundary curvature and the spacetime dimension [7, 8]. Further it was suggested that this saturation of the growth rate is related to Lloyd’s bound on the rate of computation by a system with energy M [30]. Using the CV conjecture, the late time growth rate of the complexity also saturates, but this final rate is only proportional to the mass at high temperatures and with a coefficient that depends on the spacetime dimension [6, 26]. Despite extensive discussions of this late time limit for the time dependence of the holographic complexity, the question of its full time evolution and in particular the rate of change at early times has not been thoroughly investigated.² Therefore, in the present paper, we study the full time evolution of holographic complexity, for both the CV and the CA proposals, in static two-sided eternal black holes. We consider black holes in various dimensions

¹This extremal volume was also argued to be dual to the quantum information metric, when comparing two vacuum states of boundary theories which differ by a marginal deformation [24].

²However, see [24] and section 8 of [8]

and with spherical, planar and hyperbolic horizon geometries. We also investigate the properties of complexity for charged black holes (for $d \geq 3$, where d is the spacetime dimension of the boundary theory). The full time profile in all cases except $d = 2$ requires some numerical treatment. We are, however, able to identify certain general features.

For the CA proposal (and in $d \geq 3$), we find that the complexity remains unchanged for some critical time, which is of the order of the thermal scale. Immediately after this time, the rate of change of the complexity is negatively divergent and we observe a short transient period during which the complexity is decreasing. At late times, the rate of change in complexity approaches a constant, previously understood to be associated with Lloyd's bound on the rate of computation. However we observe a violation of this late time bound since the rate approaches the late time limit from above. We also comment on the role of the arbitrary length scale in the boundary theory associated with the holographic normalization of null-normals and its influence on the rate of change of complexity. For the CV proposal, the rate of change of complexity is a monotonically increasing function of time, and it saturates to a constant at late times. While at high temperatures this late time rate is proportional to the mass, the precise value depends on the boundary curvature for spherical and hyperbolic horizons at finite temperatures. For both conjectures (and in $d \geq 3$), we also examined the rate of change of complexity for charged black holes, as well as their complexity of formation. In either case, we find that the holographic complexity smoothly approaches to that of the neutral black holes in the limit of zero charge. With the CA approach, adding a charge washes out the curious early time behaviour, *i.e.*, complexity immediately begins increasing with sufficient charge, but the late time violation is essentially the same as in the neutral case. Further, the complexity of formation for charged extremal black holes is divergent in either case, implying that the holographic states at finite chemical potential and zero temperature are infinitely more complex than their finite temperature counterparts.

The remainder of our paper is organized as follows: In section 2, we investigate the full time evolution of complexity for the thermofield double state (1.1), dual to an eternal AdS black hole, using the CA conjecture. We consider different boundary geometries and different dimensions, and investigate how the holographic complexity approaches the late time limit. In section 3, we study the time evolution of complexity using the CV conjecture. We consider various geometries and dimensions, and prove that it approaches its late time limit from below. In section 4, we analyze Reissner-Nordstrom AdS charged black holes, their complexity of formation and how they violate a proposed generalization of Lloyd's bound. Finally, we discuss some implications of our results, as well as possible future directions, in section 5. We relegate certain details of the calculations to the appendices. In appendix A, we present additional details for

the action calculation for BTZ black holes. Extra examples of the time dependence of complexity for uncharged black holes in $d = 3$ using the CA conjecture and for spherical and hyperbolic geometries in $d = 3$ and $d = 4$ using the CV conjecture are presented in appendix B. We present a late time expansion of the uncharged CV results in appendix C. In appendix D, we show the details of the calculation of the complexity of formation for charged black holes, both using the CA and CV proposals. In appendix E, we discuss the influence of ambiguities associated with the presence of null boundaries on the CA proposal results.

2 Complexity=Action

In this section, we study the time evolution of holographic complexity using the complexity=action (CA) conjecture [7, 8] for (neutral) eternal AdS black holes in $d + 1$ dimensions. The proposed translation between the boundary and the bulk theories states that the quantum complexity of the boundary state is given by the gravitational action evaluated on a bulk region known as the Wheeler-DeWitt (WDW) patch, as in eq. (1.3). Our conventions and notation here follow those established in [26]. The (neutral) black hole metric for different horizon geometries reads

$$ds^2 = -f(r) dt^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2, \quad (2.1)$$

with the blackening factor

$$f(r) = \frac{r^2}{L^2} + k - \frac{\omega^{d-2}}{r^{d-2}}. \quad (2.2)$$

Here L denotes the AdS curvature scale while k indicates the curvature of the $(d-1)$ -dimensional line element $d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2$. The parameter k assumes three different values, $\{+1, 0, -1\}$, which correspond to spherical, planar, and hyperbolic horizon geometries, respectively. In the expressions below, we will use $\Omega_{k,d-1}$ to denote the dimensionless volume of the relevant spatial geometry. For $k = 1$, this is just the volume of a $(d-1)$ -dimensional unit sphere, *i.e.*, $\Omega_{1,d-1} = 2\pi^{d/2}/\Gamma(d/2)$, while for hyperbolic and planar geometries, we must introduce an infrared regulator to produce a finite volume (*e.g.*, see eq. (2.3) in [26]).

The relation between the position of the horizon r_h and the ‘mass’ parameter ω is [31, 32]

$$\omega^{d-2} = r_h^{d-2} \left(\frac{r_h^2}{L^2} + k \right), \quad (2.3)$$

which is then related to the mass of the black hole with

$$M = \frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}}{16\pi G_N} \omega^{d-2}. \quad (2.4)$$

We will also use the temperature and entropy of the black hole given by

$$S = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4G_N} r_h^{d-1}, \quad T = \frac{1}{4\pi} \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_h} = \frac{1}{4\pi r_h} \left(d \frac{r_h^2}{L^2} + (d-2)k \right). \quad (2.5)$$

To describe the null sheets bounding the WDW patch, it is convenient to define the tortoise coordinate, and its asymptotic value:

$$r^*(r) = \int \frac{dr}{f(r)}, \quad r_\infty^* = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} r^*(r). \quad (2.6)$$

We then define the Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates, u and v , describing out- and in-going null rays, respectively,

$$v = t + r^*(r), \quad u = t - r^*(r). \quad (2.7)$$

2.1 Evaluating the Action

The causal structure of the black holes described by the metric (2.1) is illustrated by the Penrose diagram in figure 1.³ We are considering the holographic complexity of the boundary state on the constant time slices, denoted by t_L and t_R , on the two asymptotic boundaries. The corresponding WDW patch (also depicted in figure 1) is then bounded by the light sheets sent from these two asymptotic time slices. We will be interested in the time dependence of the complexity and therefore in the time dependence of the gravitational action evaluated on this patch as the boundary time increases.⁴ The result depends only on $t = t_L + t_R$ and not on each of the boundary times separately due to the invariance of the system under boosts in Kruskal coordinates, *i.e.*, under shifts $t_L \rightarrow t_L + \Delta t$ and $t_R \rightarrow t_R - \Delta t$. In terms of the boundary theory, this corresponds to the invariance of the thermofield double state (1.1) under an evolution with the Hamiltonian $H = H_L - H_R$. In any event, we can therefore deduce the rate of change of the holographic complexity for a general choice of time slices from the result for the symmetric configuration with times $t_L = t_R \equiv t/2$.

For our calculations, there are two different regimes to be considered with respect to the position of the WDW patch. The first, illustrated in the left panel of figure 1, is when the WDW patch is in contact with the past singularity. In the second regime, shown in the right panel, the past light sheets from the left and right boundaries

³Small hyperbolic black holes are an exception since their causal structure resembles that of charged black holes. We will comment on this case at the end of appendix D, where we discuss further properties of charged black holes.

⁴The geometry is symmetric under $t \rightarrow -t$ and we only consider the behaviour of the complexity for $t > 0$. We briefly comment on the decrease of the complexity found for $t < 0$ in section 2.2.1.

Figure 1: Penrose diagram of the WDW patch of an eternal AdS black hole, moving forward in time in a symmetric way ($t_L = t_R$).

intersect before hitting the past singularity. The critical time t_c separating the two regimes is easily found to be

$$t_c = 2(r_\infty^* - r^*(0)), \quad (2.8)$$

for the symmetric scenario (*i.e.*, $t_L = t_R = t/2$). Generally, we can only find closed form expression for t_c in specific dimensions. However, for planar black holes (*i.e.*, $k = 0$ in eq. (2.2)), the solution can be written in a closed form for any d as:

$$t_c = \frac{2\pi L^2}{d r_h} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{d}\right) = \frac{1}{2T} \cot\left(\frac{\pi}{d}\right), \quad (2.9)$$

where $T = dr_h/(4\pi L^2)$ is the boundary temperature (2.5) in this case.

In the following, we evaluate the various contributions to the gravitational action for both the $0 < t < t_c$ and $t > t_c$ regimes. We use these results to compute the rate of change of the holographic complexity using eq. (1.3). In fact, we will find that the action does not change in the initial time period, $0 \leq t \leq t_c$, while it does change as t changes for $t > t_c$. The gravitational action can be written as follows [25]:

$$\begin{aligned}
I = & \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} \int_{\mathcal{M}} d^{d+1}x \sqrt{-g} \left(\mathcal{R} + \frac{d(d-1)}{L^2} \right) \\
& + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_B d^d x \sqrt{|h|} K + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_\Sigma d^{d-1}x \sqrt{\sigma} \eta \\
& - \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{B'} d\lambda d^{d-1}\theta \sqrt{\gamma} \kappa + \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_{\Sigma'} d^{d-1}x \sqrt{\sigma} a.
\end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

The first line contains the standard Einstein-Hilbert action including the Ricci scalar \mathcal{R} and the cosmological constant $\Lambda = -d(d-1)/(2L^2)$. The second line begins with

the Gibbons-Hawking-York (GHY) surface term [33, 34] for smooth timelike and space-like segments of the boundary, which is defined in terms of the trace of the extrinsic curvature K . In the second contribution there are the Hayward joint terms [35, 36], which appear at the intersection of two such boundary segments and which are defined in terms of the “boost angle” η between the corresponding normal vectors. The last line contains the additional terms which are required when the boundary includes null segments [25].⁵ First of these is the surface term for the null segments defined in terms of the κ , which measures the failure of the null generators to be affinely parametrized. Secondly, there are the joint terms at the intersection of these null boundary segments with any other boundary segment, where a relates the normals on the intersecting segments. We follow the conventions of appendix A of [27] and the precise definition of all of the boundary terms can be found there.

Let us recall that there are certain ambiguities associated with the null surface and joint contributions [25]. In the following, we adopt the natural conventions presented in the discussion of [25]. In particular, we choose the normals to the null boundary segments to be affinely parameterized. This sets $\kappa = 0$ and hence we do not have to consider the corresponding boundary terms for the null segments in eq. (2.10). We also fix the conventions for a so that the action is additive — see [25] or appendix A of [27]. Finally, we are left with a freedom to rescale each of the null normals \mathbf{k}_i by an overall constant. We fix this ambiguity by setting $\mathbf{k}_i \cdot \hat{t} = \pm\alpha$ at the asymptotic boundary, where $\hat{t} = \partial_t$ is the time-like vector describing the time flow in the boundary theory and α is some positive constant. If we assume that \hat{t} is future directed on all boundaries, then the $+$ and $-$ sign is chosen here for the future and past null boundaries of the WDW patch, respectively. We will see that different choices of the normalization constant α will modify subleading contributions to $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt$ in a late time expansion in the following. More generally, we also comment on how making different choices to fix these ambiguities might effect our results for the time rate of change of the holographic complexity in appendix E.

Finally, we observe that the action of the WDW patch is divergent because this spacetime region extends all the way to the asymptotic AdS boundary and so we regulate the calculation of the complexity in the standard way (*e.g.*, see [32, 41, 42]) by introducing a cutoff surface at $r = r_{\max}$. In general, a potential subtlety is choosing the cutoff surface in a consistent way to allow for the comparison of WDW actions evaluated in different spacetimes. However, as described in [26], one can describe the different geometries in a canonical way using the Fefferman-Graham expansion and then we set the radial cutoff surface at $z = \delta$. As usual, δ plays the role of a short-distance cutoff

⁵See also [37–40] for other developments on the action with null boundaries and corners.

in the dual boundary theory. This highlights the fact that the divergence in the action is a UV divergence in the holographic complexity related to establishing correlations in the boundary CFT down to the cutoff scale [26, 27]. Further, we note that in the present calculations, this UV divergence will be independent of time and so it does not influence the time rate of change of the holographic complexity. We will also need to introduce a regulator surface at $r = \epsilon_0$ near the past and future singularities.

2.1.1 Initial times: $t < t_c$

For times before t_c , the action (2.10) contains three nonvanishing contributions: the bulk contribution; the GHY surface contributions from the regulator surfaces at the past and future singularities, as well as from the UV cutoff surfaces; and the null joint terms where the null boundaries of the WDW patches intersect the regulator surfaces at the past and future singularities, as well as the intersections with the UV cutoff surface. We will evaluate all these contributions in turn and demonstrate that the total action is independent of time in the interval $t_c \geq t (\geq -t_c)$.⁶ Due to the symmetry of the configuration that we have chosen, we can evaluate the contributions for the right side of the Penrose diagram (in the left panel of figure 1) and then simply multiply the result by a factor of two.

Bulk contribution: We divide the WDW patch into three regions: I, the region behind the future horizon; II, the region outside both horizons; and III, the regions behind the past horizon — see figure 1. The corresponding bulk contributions to the action read:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{I}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int_{\epsilon_0}^{r_h} r^{d-1} \left(\frac{t}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{II}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N L^2} \int_{r_h}^{r_{\text{max}}} r^{d-1} \left(r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{III}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int_{\epsilon_0}^{r_h} r^{d-1} \left(-\frac{t}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \end{aligned} \quad (2.11)$$

where r_{max} is a UV cutoff. Summing these three contributions, we are left with:

$$I_{\text{bulk}}^0 = -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{2\pi G_N L^2} \int_{\epsilon_0}^{r_{\text{max}}} r^{d-1} (r_\infty^* - r^*(r)) dr, \quad (2.12)$$

where an extra factor of two was included to account for the two sides of the Penrose diagram in figure 1. We see that the time dependences in $I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{I}}$ and $I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{III}}$ precisely cancel and hence the total bulk contribution is time independent.

⁶See comment about negative times around eq. (2.44).

GHY surface contributions: There are three different GHY surface contributions to be considered: those coming from the regulator surfaces at the future and past singularities, and the surface contribution at the UV cutoff surface.⁷ We use the following (outward-directed unit) normal vectors to evaluate the corresponding extrinsic curvatures

$$\begin{aligned} r = r_{\max} : \quad \mathbf{s} &= s_{\mu} dx^{\mu} = \frac{dr}{\sqrt{f(r_{\max})}} \\ r = \epsilon_0 : \quad \mathbf{t} &= t_{\mu} dx^{\mu} = -\frac{dr}{\sqrt{-f(\epsilon_0)}} \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

where the second normal applies for both regulator surfaces next to the past and future singularities. For a constant r surface in the metric (2.1), the trace of the extrinsic curvature is given by

$$K = \frac{n_r}{2} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right), \quad (2.14)$$

and as a result, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{surf}}^{\text{future}} &= -\frac{r^{d-1} \Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) \left(\frac{t}{2} + r_{\infty}^* - r^*(r) \right) \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}, \\ I_{\text{surf}}^{\text{past}} &= -\frac{r^{d-1} \Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) \left(-\frac{t}{2} + r_{\infty}^* - r^*(r) \right) \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}, \\ I_{\text{surf}}^{\text{cutoff}} &= \frac{r^{d-1} \Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) (r_{\infty}^* - r^*(r)) \Big|_{r=r_{\max}}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.15)$$

We see that the surface contribution $I_{\text{surf}}^{\text{cutoff}}$ at the UV cutoff surface is independent of time. Further we note that this contribution is identical in the regime $t > t_c$. Therefore, the UV surface terms do not contribute to the time dependence of holographic complexity and we will ignore them both here and in the next section. For $t < t_c$, we see that the time dependence of the GHY surface contributions from the past and future singularities precisely cancels leaving:

$$I_{\text{surf, sing}}^0 = -\frac{r^{d-1} \Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) (r_{\infty}^* - r^*(r)) \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}. \quad (2.16)$$

We note again that this contribution is independent of time for all $t < t_c$.

⁷Recall that we chose the null normals to be affinely parametrized and hence the null surface contributions vanish, *i.e.*, $\kappa = 0$.

Null joint contributions: There are a number of null joint contributions to be considered. In particular, we have the joint contributions at the intersections of the null boundaries of the WDW patch with the regulator surfaces at the past and future singularities and those at their intersections with the UV cutoff surface. These contributions were carefully evaluated in [26] — see eqs. (2.34) and (2.35) of the reference — and they are not modified in the present case. However, two key observations are that the null joint contributions at the singularities vanish, while those at the UV cutoff surface have no time dependence. Hence neither of these terms contribute to the time rate of change of holographic complexity.

Total Action: Hence as our calculations above demonstrate, the total gravitational action of the WDW patch is independent of time for the initial time period $t < t_c$. If we denote its value by I_0 ,⁸ then in this early time interval, we have

$$0 \leq t \leq t_c : \quad \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{dI_0}{dt} = 0. \quad (2.17)$$

2.1.2 Later times: $t > t_c$

For times $t > t_c$, the same three sets of terms make nonvanishing contributions to the action of the WDW patch, *i.e.*, the bulk term, the GHY surface terms and the null joint terms, and so we again evaluate each of these contributions in turn. We again use the symmetry of the configuration to only explicitly evaluate the contributions for the right side of the Penrose diagram (in the right panel of figure 1) and then simply multiply the result by a factor of two.

Bulk contribution: As before, we split the WDW patch into three regions which we denote as I, II and III — see figure 1. The corresponding bulk contributions to the gravitational action become:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{I}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int_0^{r_h} r^{d-1} \left(\frac{t}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{II}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int_{r_h}^{r_{\text{max}}} r^{d-1} 2 \left(r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{III}} &= -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} \int_{r_m}^{r_h} r^{d-1} \left(-\frac{t}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) dr \end{aligned} \quad (2.18)$$

where r_m is the radius behind the past horizon where the null boundary sheets from the left and right boundaries intersect. This position is determined by the following

⁸Note that $I_0 = I_{\text{WDW}}(t_L = t_R = 0)$ and so this result is identical to the action evaluated in [26]. In particular, the complexity of formation of the thermofield double state in the boundary is given by I_0 minus twice the corresponding action of the WDW patch in vacuum AdS.

equation:

$$\frac{t}{2} - r_\infty^* + r^*(r_m) = 0. \quad (2.19)$$

Generally, this is a transcendental equation and we can only determine r_m numerically. Combining the above results, we obtain the total bulk contribution

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = I_{\text{bulk}}^0 - \frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N L^2} \int_0^{r_m} r^{d-1} \left(\frac{t}{2} - r_\infty^* + r^*(r) \right) dr, \quad (2.20)$$

where we have again included a factor of two to account for the equal contributions coming from the two sides of the WDW patch shown in figure 1. We have also introduced I_{bulk}^0 , which was defined in eq. (2.12) and which is time independent.

GHY surface contributions: For $t > t_c$, the WDW patch does not reach the past singularity and so only the regulator surface at the future singularity contributes here. The expression takes the same form as in eq. (2.15) and as a result we obtain

$$I_{\text{surf}}^{\text{future}} = -\frac{f(r)r^{d-1}\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\frac{\partial_r f(r)}{f(r)} + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} \right) \left(\frac{t}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r) \right) \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}. \quad (2.21)$$

We also have the GHY contribution from the UV cutoff surface as in eq. (2.15). However, this contribution is time independent and so we ignore it here.

Using eq. (2.16), the above expression can be rewritten as follows

$$I_{\text{surf}} = I_{\text{surf},\text{sing}}^0 - \frac{r^{d-1}\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) \left(\frac{t}{2} - r_\infty^* + r^*(r) \right) \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}. \quad (2.22)$$

The difference $I_{\text{surf}} - I_{\text{surf},\text{sing}}^0$ encodes the change in the GHY contribution to the holographic complexity after $t = t_c$.

Null Joint Contribution: There are null joint contributions from the intersection of the null boundaries with the regulator surface at the future singularity and with the UV cutoff surface. However, as in the previous section, the former vanish while the latter are independent of time. Therefore neither of these contribute to $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt$. The last joint contribution to consider when $t > t_c$ is that from the intersection of the two past null boundaries at $r = r_m$. To evaluate this term, we use the following outward-directed null normal vectors:

$$\text{Right : } \mathbf{k}_R = -\alpha dt + \alpha \frac{dr}{f(r)}; \quad \text{Left : } \mathbf{k}_L = \alpha dt + \alpha \frac{dr}{f(r)}. \quad (2.23)$$

Here we have assumed that the Killing vector ∂_t describes a flow from right to left for the region behind the past horizon in figure 1. The joint term can then be evaluated as

$$I_{\text{jnt}} = -\frac{\Omega_{d-1} r_m^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \log \frac{|f(r_m)|}{\alpha^2}, \quad (2.24)$$

This term depends on t through the implicit time dependence of r_m , as determined by eq. (2.19). We would like to stress that this contribution is sensitive to the ambiguities discussed in [25], *i.e.*, through its dependence on the normalization constant α . We discuss this issue further in appendix E.

Total Action: The total action for $t > t_c$ is given by the sum of eqs. (2.20), (2.22) and (2.24) plus some time independent contributions from the UV cutoff surfaces and the null junctions. It is sometimes convenient to express our various contributions in terms of $\delta t = t - t_c$. As a consequence, the equation for the position r_m of the past null junction becomes

$$\frac{\delta t}{2} + r^*(r_m) - r^*(0) = 0. \quad (2.25)$$

The total gravitational action can then be expressed as

$$I = I_0 + \delta I \quad \text{with} \quad \delta I = \delta I_{\text{bulk}} + \delta I_{\text{surf}} + I_{\text{jnt}}. \quad (2.26)$$

where

$$\delta I_{\text{bulk}} \equiv I_{\text{bulk}} - I_{\text{bulk}}^0 = -\frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N L^2} \int_0^{r_m} dr r^{d-1} \left(\frac{\delta t}{2} + r^*(r) - r^*(0) \right), \quad (2.27)$$

$$\delta I_{\text{surf}} \equiv I_{\text{surf}} - I_{\text{surf}}^0 = -\frac{r^{d-1}\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left(\partial_r f(r) + \frac{2(d-1)}{r} f(r) \right) \frac{\delta t}{2} \Big|_{r=\epsilon_0}, \quad (2.28)$$

$$I_{\text{jnt}} = -\frac{\Omega_{d-1} r_m^{d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \log \frac{|f(r_m)|}{\alpha^2}. \quad (2.29)$$

We note that δI is finite, *i.e.*, independent of the UV cutoff δ . Further it vanishes in the limit $\delta t \rightarrow 0$, which can be seen by explicitly substituting the blackening factor (2.2) into eqs. (2.27)-(2.29). However, we will show below that the rate of change of the holographic complexity is discontinuous at $t = t_c$.

2.2 Time Dependence of Complexity

Here we examine the time dependence of the holographic complexity. As we already noted above in eq. (2.17), initially, we have

$$0 \leq t \leq t_c : \quad \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{1}{\pi} \frac{dI_0}{dt} = 0, \quad (2.30)$$

where t_c was defined in eq. (2.8).

For later times $t > t_c$, we obtain the time derivative of complexity by differentiating eqs. (2.25)-(2.29) with respect to time. From eq. (2.25), we find the time dependence of the meeting point r_m to be

$$\frac{dr_m}{dt} = -\frac{f(r_m)}{2}. \quad (2.31)$$

Differentiating eq. (2.27) yields

$$\frac{dI_{\text{bulk}}}{dt} = \frac{d\delta I_{\text{bulk}}}{dt} = -\frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N L^2} r_m^d, \quad (2.32)$$

where in obtaining this result, we used eq. (2.25) to demonstrate that the contribution coming from differentiating the upper limit of integration vanishes. Evaluating the GHY surface term (2.28) at $r = \epsilon_0$ and then taking the $\epsilon_0 \rightarrow 0$ limit yields

$$\frac{dI_{\text{surf}}}{dt} = \frac{d\delta I_{\text{surf}}}{dt} = \frac{\omega^{d-2} d \Omega_{k,d-1}}{16\pi G_N}. \quad (2.33)$$

Finally, differentiating the null joint term (2.29) gives

$$\frac{dI_{\text{jnt}}}{dt} = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1} r_m^{d-2}}{16\pi G_N} \left[(d-1) f(r_m) \log \frac{|f(r_m)|}{\alpha^2} + r_m \partial_r f(r_m) \right]. \quad (2.34)$$

where we have used eq. (2.31). Using the explicit form of the blackening factor (2.2) and summing the three terms above, eq. (1.3) yields the rate of growth of holographic complexity as

$$t > t_c : \quad \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(2M + \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1} (d-1) r_m^{d-2}}{16\pi G_N} f(r_m) \log \frac{|f(r_m)|}{\alpha^2} \right). \quad (2.35)$$

Of course, this result reproduces the expected rate of growth at late times [7, 8], *i.e.*, $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt = 2M/\pi$, since in this limit r_m approaches r_h and so the second term on the right vanishes with $f(r_m \rightarrow r_h) \rightarrow 0^-$. We provide further comments on the properties of our result (2.35) below.

2.2.1 Comments

As already noted above, this result (2.35) reproduces the expected rate of growth at late times since in this limit r_m approaches r_h and so $f(r_m \rightarrow r_h) \rightarrow 0^-$. We also note that at late times with r_m approaching r_h from below, $f(r_m)$ is small and negative and therefore the correction to $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt = 2M/\pi$ in eq. (2.35) is positive! That is, $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt$ approaches the late time limit from above. Recall that [7, 8] suggested that the late time limit of $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt$ may be related to Lloyd's bound $2M/\pi$ for the rate of computation for a system of energy M [30]. Therefore we see here a (small) violation of Lloyd's bound in the eternal black hole.

Late time expansion: To get a better understanding of the late time behaviour, it is possible to solve the equation for r_m in a late time expansion. We do this by defining the regular part of the blackening factor $F(r)$:

$$f(r) \equiv F(r)(r - r_h) \quad (2.36)$$

and decomposing the inverse blackening factor as

$$\frac{1}{f(r)} = \frac{1}{F(r_h)(r-r_h)} + \frac{F(r_h) - F(r)}{F(r_h)F(r)(r-r_h)}. \quad (2.37)$$

This leads to the following form of the tortoise coordinate

$$r^*(r) = \frac{1}{F(r_h)} \log \frac{|r-r_h|}{\tilde{\ell}} + \int^r \frac{F(r_h) - F(r)}{F(r_h)F(r)(r-r_h)} dr \quad (2.38)$$

where $\tilde{\ell}$ is an unspecified integration constant. Using eqs. (2.5) and (2.25), we can solve for r_m at late times as

$$r_m = r_h (1 - c_1 e^{-2\pi T(t-t_c)}) + \dots \quad (2.39)$$

with

$$c_1 = \exp \left[- \int_0^{r_h} dr \frac{F(r_h) - F(r)}{F(r)(r-r_h)} \right] > 0, \quad (2.40)$$

and where the ellipsis stands for corrections which are higher order in $(r_h - r_m)$, *i.e.*, which would decay at least as fast as $e^{-4\pi T t}$. Substituting this expression (2.39) into eq. (2.35), we obtain at the first corrections to the rate of change in complexity in the $t \rightarrow \infty$ limit

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{2M}{\pi} + 2(d-1)c_1 S T^2 e^{-2\pi T(t-t_c)} \left(t - t_c - \frac{1}{2\pi T} \log \left[\frac{4\pi c_1 T r_h}{\alpha^2} \right] \right) + \dots \quad (2.41)$$

We see that the final factor will always become positive for sufficiently late times and hence the bound conjectured by [7, 8] will be violated.

Early times: It is also interesting to look at an early time expansion of the expression (2.35). At very early times after t_c , r_m is very close to the past singularity, *i.e.*, as $\delta t = t - t_c \rightarrow 0$, $r_m \rightarrow 0$. As a consequence, $f(r_m) \sim -\omega^{d-2}/r_m^{d-2}$ and the second term in eq. (2.35) diverges to minus infinity (as long as $d \geq 3$). More explicitly, one can show that this leading divergence as $\delta t \rightarrow 0$ is logarithmic with

$$\left. \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \right|_{\delta t \rightarrow 0} \longrightarrow - \frac{(d-2)M}{(d-1)\pi} \log \left(\frac{2\omega}{\alpha^{2(d-1)/(d-2)}(d-1)\delta t} \right) \quad \text{for } d \geq 3. \quad (2.42)$$

Despite this divergence, we note again that the complexity itself remains finite as $\delta t \rightarrow 0$ and it is only its derivative which is divergent. We would also like to stress again, that these results are influenced by the ambiguities in the corner term mentioned in [25]. We explore this issue further in appendix E. We also examine the case $d = 2$, *i.e.*, BTZ black holes, in detail in the following section.

Averaging: The discussion above indicates that the action changes very rapidly in the vicinity of $\delta t = 0$ — see also the examples in section 2.3. However, one might argue

that the holographic complexity does not have a good definition on time scales smaller than $\beta = 1/T$ in the context of the eternal black hole.⁹ Hence we might average the rate of change in complexity over time scales which are longer than the thermal time scale. We can define a simple averaged rate of change in complexity as follows:

$$\left[\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \right]_{\gamma; \text{avg}} = \frac{1}{\gamma\beta} \int_{t-\gamma\beta/2}^{t+\gamma\beta/2} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt'} dt' = \frac{\mathcal{C}_A(t+\gamma\beta/2) - \mathcal{C}_A(t-\gamma\beta/2)}{\gamma\beta}, \quad (2.43)$$

where γ is some numerical factor of order one. In the second expression, we see that we have essentially constructed a discrete time derivative on a time step $\Delta t = \gamma/T$.

Let us comment on the properties of this averaged rate: First, we note that $\left[\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \right]_{\gamma; \text{avg}}$ remains continuous at all times. However, its time derivative will be discontinuous at $|t \pm \frac{\gamma\beta}{2}| = t_c$ because of the discontinuity in $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt$ noted above. When $\gamma\beta/2 < t_c$ there will generically be a short period of time right after $t = t_c - \gamma\beta/2$ for which this averaged rate will be negative. After this period, the rate will rise quickly to positive values. Note that this averaging does not remove the (small) violation of Lloyd's bound, discussed above. We will return to discuss this time averaging in more detail in section 5.

Negative Times: In our setup, the complexity is a symmetric function of time $\mathcal{C}_A(t) = \mathcal{C}_A(-t)$. Of course, this implies that the time derivative is anti-symmetric

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt}(t) = -\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt}(-t). \quad (2.44)$$

Our system therefore admits a regime of decreasing complexity, at least for large negative times. This situation is unstable — an arbitrary small perturbation would cause the complexity to start increasing again. A discussion of this issue can be found in subsection [2.1] of [43].

Dependence on the boundary curvature: Given the black hole metric in eqs. (2.1) and (2.2), it is clear that L is the AdS curvature scale. However, implicitly, L also plays the role of the curvature of the boundary metric in the cases $k = \pm 1$. Hence when we express our results in terms of quantities of the boundary theory, it is perfectly consistent for the final answer to depend on L . However, if we introduce a separate curvature scale R for the boundary metric, it becomes a consistency test to demonstrate that we can eliminate the AdS scale from our expressions.

Hence let us consider the AdS black hole metric

$$ds^2 = -f(r) \frac{L^2}{R^2} d\tau^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2, \quad (2.45)$$

⁹We thank Lenny Susskind, Dan Roberts and Brian Swingle for correspondence on this point.

where $f(r)$ is still given by eq. (2.2). Now scaling the metric in the asymptotic region $r \rightarrow \infty$ by R^2/r^2 yields the boundary metric

$$ds_{bdy}^2 = -d\tau^2 + R^2 d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2, \quad (2.46)$$

where the curvature of the spatial geometry is now set by R .¹⁰ Of course, the only real change between eqs. (2.1) and (2.45) is that we have rescaled the time variable, *i.e.*, $\tau = (R/L)t$. So essentially all of our computations follow identically for the ‘new’ geometry to those that were performed above. However, the scaling of the time coordinate appears in various places, such as the definition of the null coordinates in eq. (2.7) or of the null normals in eq. (2.23). Another important difference is in the definition of various quantities which characterize the boundary state in terms of the geometric parameters appearing in the bulk. In particular, eqs. (2.4) and (2.5) are replaced with the following

$$\begin{aligned} M &= \frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}}{16\pi G_N} \frac{L}{R} \omega^{d-2}, & S &= \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4G_N} r_h^{d-1}, \\ T &= \frac{L}{4\pi R} \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_h} = \frac{L}{4\pi R r_h} \left(d \frac{r_h^2}{L^2} + (d-2)k \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.47)$$

and the spatial volume of boundary becomes $V = \Omega_{k,d-1} R^{d-1}$. Given these changes, the critical time is given by

$$\tau_c = \frac{2R}{L} (r_\infty^* - r^*(0)) \quad (2.48)$$

and our result (2.35) for the rate of change of the complexity becomes

$$\tau > \tau_c : \quad \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(2M + \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}(d-1)r_m^{d-2}}{16\pi G_N} \frac{L}{R} f(r_m) \log \frac{L^2 |f(r_m)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} \right), \quad (2.49)$$

where the equation for the meeting point can be written as

$$\delta\tau = -\frac{2R}{L} (r^*(r_m) - r^*(0)). \quad (2.50)$$

Now we would like to recast this result (2.49) in terms of boundary quantities. We do so by first defining a dimensionless radial coordinate $x = r/r_h$. Next we note that

¹⁰Notice that for the planar geometry, *i.e.*, $k = 0$, there is no curvature scale and hence R becomes some arbitrary length scale in the boundary theory. Further, for $k = 0$ in eq. (2.1), we implicitly had chosen the boundary metric $d\Sigma_{0,d-1}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{d-1} dx_i^2/L^2$, following [26]. Normalizing with the AdS curvature scale L was required to ensure that the line element was dimensionless. Here, it is more natural to set $d\Sigma_{0,d-1}^2 = \sum_{i=1}^{d-1} d\tilde{x}_i^2/R^2$, so that the boundary metric (2.46) is independent of R (and L). Of course, this is equivalent to rescaling the (spatial) boundary coordinates as $\tilde{x}_i = (R/L)x_i$.

from eq. (2.47), we see that the dimensionless ratio of geometric scales r_h/L in the bulk is determined by the dimensionless product of boundary quantities RT . In particular, we find

$$\frac{r_h}{L} = \frac{2\pi RT}{d} \left(1 + \sqrt{1 - \frac{d(d-2)k}{(2\pi RT)^2}} \right) \equiv 2\pi RT \tilde{g}(RT). \quad (2.51)$$

Now examining the blackening factor, we can write:

$$\begin{aligned} f(r) &= \frac{r^2}{L^2} + k + \frac{r_h^{d-2}}{r^{d-2}} \left(\frac{r_h^2}{L^2} + k \right) \\ &= \frac{r_h^2}{L^2} \left(x^2 + \frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} - \frac{1}{x^{d-2}} \left(1 + \frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} \right) \right) \equiv \frac{r_h^2}{L^2} \tilde{f}(x, RT). \end{aligned} \quad (2.52)$$

Further, combining the above expressions in eq. (2.50), we have

$$\pi \tilde{g}(RT) T \delta\tau = - \int_0^{x_m} \frac{dx}{\tilde{f}(x, RT)}, \quad (2.53)$$

which demonstrates that x_m is implicitly a function of the (dimensionless) boundary quantities, $T\delta\tau$ and RT . Further, these results allow us to translate the rate of change in complexity (2.49) for $\tau > \tau_c$ to the form¹¹

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(2M + ST(d-1) \tilde{g}(RT) x_m^{d-2} \tilde{f}(x_m, RT) \log \left[\frac{2\pi LT}{\alpha} \tilde{g}(RT) |\tilde{f}(x_m, RT)|^{1/2} \right] \right). \quad (2.54)$$

Here we see that the right-hand side is expressed in terms of boundary quantities, except for a single factor of L appearing in the argument of the logarithm. Of course, this argument also contains a factor of the (dimensionless) normalization constant α , which is arbitrary. Precisely, the same situation arose in [27] in investigating the structure of the UV divergences in holographic complexity. Following [27], it is natural to choose $\alpha = L/\ell$ which eliminates the errant factor of L but introduces some new scale ℓ in the boundary theory. Hence this choice raises the question of what the most appropriate choice for ℓ would be. For simplicity in the following, we will set $\ell = R$, the curvature scale in the $k = \pm 1$ boundary geometries (2.46). As noted in the planar case (see footnote 10), R remains an arbitrary length scale in the boundary theory. We return to discuss this point in section 5.

¹¹Let us note that for planar horizons, *i.e.*, for $k = 0$, eq. (2.51) yields $\tilde{g} = 2/d$ while eq. (2.52) simply gives $\tilde{f}(x_m, RT) = (x^d - 1)/x^{d-2}$. Hence $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ does not actually depend on RT for $k = 0$.

2.3 Examples

In this subsection, we present two specific examples in which we solve explicitly for the meeting point and evaluate the rate of change in complexity for all times $t > t_c$. First, we will consider BTZ black holes ($d = 2$) for which analytic results can be obtained. Further details of the results for this special case are given in appendix A. Next, we consider numerical solutions for $d = 4$ with various horizon geometries. As a further example we consider the case $d = 3$ in appendix B.

2.3.1 BTZ Black Holes

For BTZ black holes, most of the expressions can be evaluated analytically. The evaluation of the action given in section 2.1 strictly applies only to $d > 2$ and so we must derive the results separately here for the BTZ case. While we review the salient calculations below, further details are also given for this special case in appendix A. Following eq. (2.45), we write the BTZ metric as

$$ds^2 = -f(r) \frac{L^2}{R^2} d\tau^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2 d\phi^2, \quad (2.55)$$

where the blackening factor, mass, temperature and entropy are then given by

$$f(r) = \frac{r^2 - r_h^2}{L^2}, \quad M = \frac{r_h^2}{8G_N L R}, \quad T = \frac{r_h}{2\pi L R}, \quad S = \frac{\pi r_h}{2G_N}. \quad (2.56)$$

As described in section 2.2.1, with the coordinates in eq. (2.55), the boundary geometry is fixed by a new independent scale R . In particular, the boundary metric is given by

$$ds^2 = -d\tau^2 + R^2 d\phi^2, \quad (2.57)$$

and hence a constant τ slice is a circle with the circumference $2\pi R$.¹²

We can evaluate the tortoise coordinate (2.6) analytically as

$$r^*(r) = \frac{L^2}{2r_h} \log \frac{|r - r_h|}{r + r_h}, \quad \implies \quad r_\infty^* = r_0^* = \tau_c = 0. \quad (2.58)$$

The latter, *i.e.*, $\tau_c = 0$, means that the action of the BTZ black hole starts changing right away for $\tau > 0$. This is due to the fact that for the boundary time slice at $\tau = 0$, *i.e.*, $\tau_R = \tau_L = 0$, the null rays coming from the left and right boundaries to define the past and future boundaries of the WDW patch meet at the singularity at $r = 0$.

¹²Note that $\beta = 1/T$ should satisfy $\beta < 2\pi R$ so that the BTZ black hole solution is the dominant saddle point in the gravitational path integral. Further note that, R is associated with the spatial size of the boundary here, rather than a curvature scale as in eq. (2.46).

Given eq. (2.58), the meeting point relation in eq. (2.25) can be solved analytically for general times,

$$r_m = r_h \tanh\left(\frac{r_h \tau}{2LR}\right). \quad (2.59)$$

Now in evaluating the action, eqs. (2.27)–(2.29) are not modified up to some factors of L/R coming from rescaling the time coordinate — see the details in appendix A — and their sum still reflects the change in complexity from what it was at $\tau = 0$. The growth rate (2.49) is then not modified for $d = 2$ and substituting in the BTZ blackening factor (2.56) and the meeting point (2.59) then yields

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{r_h^2}{4\pi G_N LR} \left(1 + \operatorname{sech}^2\left(\frac{r_h \tau}{2LR}\right) \log\left[\frac{R\alpha}{r_h} \cosh\left(\frac{r_h \tau}{2LR}\right)\right] \right), \quad (2.60)$$

where we have also used $\Omega_{+1,1} = 2\pi$ above. Further using the expressions for the mass and temperature in eq. (2.56), this result can be expressed in terms of boundary quantities as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(1 + \operatorname{sech}^2(\pi T \tau) \log\left[\frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \cosh(\pi T \tau)\right] \right). \quad (2.61)$$

Of course, the above expression is evaluated for $\tau > 0$. One simple consistency check on our result is that in the limit $\tau \rightarrow \infty$, we recover the expected late time result of [7, 8], *i.e.*, $d\mathcal{C}_A/dt = 2M/\pi$. As in eq. (2.54), we see the appearance of both L and α in the argument of the logarithm. Hence there is some ambiguity about the interpretation of this result in the boundary theory.

Now we can also rewrite eq. (2.61) in the following form

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(\tanh^2(\pi\tau/\beta) + \frac{\log \cosh(\pi\tau/\beta)}{\cosh^2(\pi\tau/\beta)} + \frac{\log\left[\frac{\beta e}{2\pi L} \alpha\right]}{\cosh^2(\pi\tau/\beta)} \right) \quad (2.62)$$

where we have introduced $\beta = 1/T$ and e is simply Euler's number, *i.e.*, $\log(e) = 1$. This form facilitates a comparison to the analogous result in [8] evaluated with a regulator based on timelike radial geodesics in the bulk, which is

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(\tanh^2(\pi\tau/\beta) + \frac{\log \cosh(\pi\tau/\beta)}{\cosh^2(\pi\tau/\beta)} - \frac{\log \epsilon}{\cosh^2(\pi\tau/\beta)} \right) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon). \quad (2.63)$$

where ϵ is a dimensionless UV regulator, *i.e.*, $\epsilon \sim \delta/\beta$ and δ is the short-distance cut-off in the boundary theory.¹³ Interestingly, we see that eqs. (2.62) and (2.63) will be in complete agreement if we choose $\alpha \sim L/\delta$. We return to a discussion of this point in section 5.

¹³We thank Ying Zhao for explaining this point.

Figure 2: Left panel: time derivative of the complexity for the BTZ black hole ($d = 2$) from eq. (2.61) with $\alpha = L/R$. Right panel: ‘total’ complexity found by integrating $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$. Results are shown for several values of the horizon radius — $r_h/L = 1$ (blue), $r_h/L = 1.5$ (dashed red) and $r_h/L = 3.5$ (dot-dashed green).

To close this section, we plot both the rate of change of the complexity (2.61) and the total complexity in figure 2 for several values of r_h/L . In the figure, we have chosen $\alpha = L/R$ and then in the argument of the logarithmic factor, we have $2\pi RT = r_h/L$ using eq. (2.56). Note that all of the curves for $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ in the left panel exceed the Lloyd bound and further the violation increases for smaller black holes, *i.e.*, smaller r_h/L , or equivalently smaller temperatures. The right panel shows the complexity itself, found by integrating $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$. The integration constant is chosen there so that the result of $\mathcal{C}_A(\tau = 0)$ corresponds to the complexity of formation [26]. In particular, we choose $\mathcal{C}_A(\tau = 0) = \mathcal{C}_{\text{form}} = -\frac{L}{2G_N}$ — see eq. (4.8) in ref. [26].¹⁴ After dividing by βM , all of these become functions of r_h/L . We provide further details of the calculations and a more extensive discussion of the special case of BTZ black holes in appendix A.

2.3.2 $d = 4$

To study the case where the boundary theory lives in $d = 4$, in principle, we simply substitute this value into eqs. (2.49) or (2.54) for $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$, with the blackening factor given by eq. (2.2). Of course, we must evaluate the meeting point r_m , or alternatively the dimensionless x_m , numerically. For the latter, we introduce the dimensionless radius $x = r/r_h$, as well as $\tilde{f}(x, RT) = L^2/r_h^2 f(r)$ from eq. (2.52). Then following eq. (2.53),

¹⁴This corresponds to comparing the complexity of the thermofield double state to that of (two copies of) the Neveu-Schwarz vacuum in the boundary theory [44]. Comparing to the Ramond vacuum would instead yield $\mathcal{C}_{\text{form}} = 0$ [26].

we can then define a dimensionless tortoise coordinate

$$\begin{aligned} x^*(x, RT) &\equiv \int \frac{dx}{\tilde{f}(x, RT)} = \frac{r_h}{L^2} r^*(r) \\ &= \frac{r_h^2}{2r_h^2 + kL^2} \left(\frac{1}{2} \log \frac{|1-x|}{1+x} + \frac{\sqrt{r_h^2 + kL^2}}{r_h} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{r_h x}{\sqrt{r_h^2 + kL^2}} \right] \right), \end{aligned} \quad (2.64)$$

which yields

$$x_\infty^* \equiv x^*(\infty, RT) = \frac{\pi}{2} r_h \frac{\sqrt{r_h^2 + kL^2}}{2r_h^2 + kL^2} \quad \text{and} \quad x^*(0, RT) = 0. \quad (2.65)$$

It is clear from eq. (2.64) that x^* is a function of the ratio r_h/L , however, as our notation indicates the latter is implicitly fixed in eq. (2.51) by RT in the boundary theory. Combining these results with eq. (2.48) yields the critical time, at which the complexity begins to change,

$$\tau_c = \frac{2LR}{r_h} (x_\infty^* - x^*(0)) = \pi LR \frac{\sqrt{r_h^2 + kL^2}}{2r_h^2 + kL^2} = \frac{1}{2T} \left(1 + k \left(\frac{L}{r_h} \right)^2 \right). \quad (2.66)$$

Note that for $k = 0$, we have $\tau_c = 1/(2T)$, *i.e.*, the critical time does not depend on R for the planar geometry. Figure 3 shows a plot of τ_c as a function of r_h/L for the various horizon geometries.

Figure 3: Critical time t_c as a function of the horizon radius for $d = 4$ for the various horizon geometries, *i.e.*, spherical $k = 1$ (blue), planar $k = 0$ (dashed-red) and large hyperbolic $k = -1$ (dot-dashed green). Note that we only consider $r_h > L$.

Now solving numerically for the meeting point x_m using eq. (2.53), we can evaluate $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ in eq. (2.54), as shown in figure 4 for spherical ($k = 1$) and planar ($k = 0$)

horizons. As commented above, we have set $\alpha = L/R$ for simplicity in these plots. Note that for a fixed r_h/L , the planar geometries seem to violate the $2M/\pi$ bound more strongly. We also note that the violation of the bound is stronger for smaller black holes, *i.e.*, smaller values of r_h/L . A more careful examination shows that generally $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is larger for $k = 0$ than for $k = +1$ and that this difference between the rate of growth for these two cases grows as the size of the black hole shrinks. Similar results apply for hyperbolic horizon geometries and for other boundary dimensions. We describe our results for the case of $d = 3$ for all three horizon geometries in appendix B.

Figure 4: Time derivative of complexity as a function of time for spherical ($k = +1$, left) and planar ($k = 0$, right) horizons with $d = 4$ boundary dimensions for various values of the horizon radius, *i.e.*, $r_h/L = 1$ (blue), $r_h/L = 1.5$ (dashed red) and $r_h/L = 3.5$ (dot-dashed green). We present the plots as a function of $\delta\tau = \tau - \tau_c$ to allow for a meaningful comparison between the different cases. We stress again that each of the curves has a different value of τ_c — see figure 3.

3 Complexity=Volume

In this section, we study the time dependence of the complexity for eternal AdS black holes using the complexity=volume conjecture [5, 6]. Applying eq. (1.2), we must evaluate the volume of the extremal codimension-one bulk surface, whose boundaries correspond to the desired time slices in the two asymptotic boundaries, as shown in figure 5.¹⁵ As in the previous section, the symmetry of our setup implies that the volume depends only on the total boundary time $t = t_L + t_R$. Thus, it is enough to

¹⁵For a proposed generalization for the complexity of subsystems in terms of the co-dimension one volume enclosed by the Ryu-Takayanagi surface, see [27, 45, 46].

consider the symmetric case $t_L = t_R$, as we assume from now on. Further, in eq. (1.2), we will simply set $\ell = L$, the AdS radius, to eliminate the ambiguity associated with the choice of the scale ℓ .

Figure 5: A representation of the maximal wormhole connecting the two boundaries anchored at times t_L and t_R (depicted at symmetric times in the figure). The bridge reaches the minimum distance inside the future horizon at r_{min} , and approaches each boundary tangent to constant time slices.

First, we review the computation of the maximal volume following [6] and then evaluate its time derivative. We will see that the time derivative of the extremal volume is determined by a conserved quantity E . With the infalling Eddington-Finkelstein coordinates (2.7), the metric (2.1) becomes

$$v = t + r^*(r); \quad ds^2 = -f(r) dv^2 + 2 dv dr + r^2 d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2. \quad (3.1)$$

Now, assuming that the extremal surface is ‘spherically’ symmetric,¹⁶ its profile will be determined by an embedding $r(\lambda)$ and $v(\lambda)$, where λ is some radial coordinate intrinsic to the surface. The maximal volume is then obtained by extremizing

$$\mathcal{V} = \Omega_{k,d-1} \int d\lambda r^{d-1} \sqrt{-f(r)\dot{v}^2 + 2\dot{v}\dot{r}} \equiv \Omega_{k,d-1} \int d\lambda \mathcal{L}(\dot{v}, r, \dot{r}), \quad (3.2)$$

¹⁶That is, the extremal surface has the same symmetry as the spatial slices described by $d\Sigma_{k,d-1}^2$, e.g., it is spherically symmetric for $k = +1$.

where the dots indicate derivatives with respect to λ . Since the integrand \mathcal{L} does not depend explicitly on v , we have a conserved quantity E defined as

$$E = -\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \dot{v}} = \frac{r^{d-1}(f\dot{v} - \dot{r})}{\sqrt{-f\dot{v}^2 + 2\dot{v}\dot{r}}}. \quad (3.3)$$

We will refer to this quantity as the energy. Since the expression in eq. (3.2) is reparametrization invariant, we are free to choose λ to keep the radial volume element fixed, *i.e.*,

$$r^{d-1}\sqrt{-f\dot{v}^2 + 2\dot{v}\dot{r}} = 1. \quad (3.4)$$

The equations determining $r(\lambda)$ and $v(\lambda)$ then simplify to

$$E = r^{2(d-1)}(f(r)\dot{v} - \dot{r}), \quad (3.5)$$

$$r^{2(d-1)}\dot{r}^2 = f(r) + r^{-2(d-1)}E^2, \quad (3.6)$$

and further, the maximal volume can be written as

$$\mathcal{V} = 2\Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} \frac{dr}{\dot{r}} = 2\Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} dr \frac{r^{2(d-1)}}{\sqrt{f(r)r^{2(d-1)} + E^2}}. \quad (3.7)$$

Here, we are assuming a symmetric configuration where $t_L = t_R$, as described above, and so the integral only runs from a minimum radius r_{min} to the cutoff surface at $r = r_{max}$. The minimal radius is determined by setting $\dot{r} = 0$ in eq. (3.6), *i.e.*,

$$f(r_{min})r_{min}^{2(d-1)} + E^2 = 0. \quad (3.8)$$

Further we note that this turning point is inside the horizon (see figure 5) and hence we have $f(r_{min}) < 0$, $\dot{r}|_{r=r_{min}} = 0$ and $\dot{v}|_{r=r_{min}} > 0$. Therefore we may conclude that $E < 0$ by evaluating eq. (3.5) at this point. Now using eqs. (3.5) and (3.6), we have

$$t_R + r_\infty^* - r^*(r_{min}) = \int_{v_{min}}^{v_\infty} dv = \int_{r_{min}}^{r=\infty} dr \left[\frac{E}{f(r)\sqrt{f(r)r^{2(d-1)} + E^2}} + \frac{1}{f(r)} \right], \quad (3.9)$$

where the symmetry of our configuration determines $t = 0$ at the turning point, *i.e.*, $v_{min} = r^*(r_{min})$. One may verify that the integrand in the final expression is well-behaved at the horizon, using the fact that the energy is negative. The integrand also decays as L^2/r^2 with $r \rightarrow \infty$ and so in the following, we will replace the upper limit of the integral by $r = r_{max}$ because the difference produced by this replacement vanishes as the short-distance cutoff is taken to zero. We will make use of this several times in the derivation below.

Using eq. (3.9), we can rewrite eq. (3.7) as follows:

$$\frac{\mathcal{V}}{2\Omega_{k,d-1}} = \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} dr \left[\frac{\sqrt{f(r)r^{2(d-1)} + E^2}}{f(r)} + \frac{E}{f(r)} \right] - E(t_R + r_\infty^* - r^*(r_{min})). \quad (3.10)$$

Next, we would like to take the time derivative of this equation, however, we would like to use the time coordinate introduced in eq. (2.45), *i.e.*, $\tau = Rt/L$. We use eq. (3.8) to simplify the contribution from the derivative acting on r_{min} in the lower limit of the integral to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{2\Omega_{k,d-1}} \frac{d\mathcal{V}}{d\tau_R} &= \frac{dE}{d\tau_R} \int_{r_{min}}^{r_{max}} dr \left[\frac{E}{f(r)\sqrt{f(r)r^{2(d-1)} + E^2}} + \frac{1}{f(r)} \right] \\ &\quad - \frac{dE}{d\tau_R} \left(\frac{L}{R} \tau_R + r_\infty^* - r^*(r_{min}) \right) - \frac{L}{R} E. \end{aligned} \quad (3.11)$$

Note that $dE/d\tau_R$ is a constant that characterizes the entire surface and so it was brought outside of the integral in the first term. However, the remaining integral is identical to that appearing in eq. (3.9) and so we may further simplify the result to

$$\frac{d\mathcal{V}}{d\tau_R} = -2\Omega_{k,d-1} \frac{L}{R} E. \quad (3.12)$$

Since we set $\tau_R = \tau_L$, the derivative with respect to $\tau = \tau_R + \tau_L$ is given by simply multiplying the result by a factor of 1/2. Hence our final result for the rate of growth of the complexity becomes

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{1}{G_N L} \frac{d\mathcal{V}}{d\tau} = -\frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{G_N R} E = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{G_N R} \sqrt{-f(r_{min})} r_{min}^{d-1}. \quad (3.13)$$

Therefore, the time derivative of complexity is completely determined by computing either E or r_{min} , with eq. (3.8).

However, as in eq. (2.54), we would like to show that eq. (3.13) can be expressed entirely in terms of boundary quantities. After some work, the final result takes the form

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{8\pi M}{(d-1)} \frac{8\pi^2 R^2 T^2 \tilde{g}^2(RT)}{4\pi^2 R^2 T^2 \tilde{g}^2(RT) + k} \sqrt{-\tilde{f}(x_{min}, RT)} x_{min}^{d-1}, \quad (3.14)$$

where the functions $\tilde{g}(RT)$ and $\tilde{f}(x, RT)$ were defined in eqs. (2.51) and (2.52), respectively. Further, as above, we have introduced the dimensionless radial coordinate $x = r/r_h$. Then defining the corresponding tortoise coordinate $x^*(x) \equiv \int dx/\tilde{f}(x, RT)$ and also $x_E \equiv E/r_h^{d-1}$, x_{min} is determined by the boundary versions of eqs. (3.8) and

(3.9):

$$0 = 4\pi^2 R^2 T^2 \tilde{g}^2(RT) \tilde{f}(x_{min}, RT) x_{min}^{2(d-1)} + x_E^2, \quad (3.15)$$

$$\frac{\tau_R}{\beta} + \frac{x_\infty^* - x^*(x_{min})}{2\pi} = \int_{x_{min}}^{x=\infty} \frac{dx \left[x_E + \sqrt{4\pi^2 R^2 T^2 \tilde{g}^2(RT) \tilde{f}(x, RT) x^{2(d-1)} + x_E^2} \right]}{2\pi \tilde{f}(x, RT) \sqrt{4\pi^2 R^2 T^2 \tilde{g}^2(RT) \tilde{f}(x, RT) x^{2(d-1)} + x_E^2}}.$$

3.1 Late Time Behaviour

Before examining the full time-dependence of $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$, we would like to study its late time behaviour. At late times, the maximal surface is (almost) tangent to a special slice of constant $r = \tilde{r}_{min}$ inside the black hole [6].¹⁷ To evaluate \tilde{r}_{min} , we first define the function $W(r)$ as appeared in eq. (3.13),

$$W(r) \equiv \sqrt{-f(r)} r^{d-1}, \quad (3.16)$$

and observe that eq. (3.8) can be rewritten as $-W(r_{min})^2 + E^2 = 0$. The latter generally has two positive roots, with the larger root corresponding to r_{min} . However, in the late time limit, $|E|$ increases until the two roots meet at the extremum of $-W(r)^2$, which also corresponds to the extremum of $W(r)$. Hence \tilde{r}_{min} is both a root of eq. (3.8) and the extremum of $W(r)$. Then \tilde{r}_{min} can be computed as

$$0 = W'(\tilde{r}_{min}) = (d-1)\tilde{r}_{min}^{d-2} \sqrt{-f(\tilde{r}_{min})} - \frac{\tilde{r}_{min}^{d-1} f'(\tilde{r}_{min})}{2\sqrt{-f(\tilde{r}_{min})}}. \quad (3.17)$$

Since $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ in eq. (3.13) only depends on the time τ through r_{min} , at late times, we have

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{G_N R} \left[W(\tilde{r}_{min}) + \frac{1}{2} W''(\tilde{r}_{min}) (r_{min} - \tilde{r}_{min})^2 + \mathcal{O}((r_{min} - \tilde{r}_{min})^3) \right]. \quad (3.18)$$

Hence asymptotically, $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ approaches the constant value

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{G_N R} W(\tilde{r}_{min}) = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{G_N R} \sqrt{-f(\tilde{r}_{min})} \tilde{r}_{min}^{d-1}. \quad (3.19)$$

Further, we observe that $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ approaches this limit from below because $W''(\tilde{r}_{min})$ is negative. The latter conclusion is easily produced by noting from eq. (3.16), that $W(r)$ vanishes at both $r = r_h$ and 0 and that $W(r) > 0$ inside the horizon. Hence

¹⁷Similar behaviour appears in computing the time dependence of holographic entanglement entropy for regions with components in both asymptotic boundaries [21]. However, the special (codimension-two) surface appearing there extremizes the area rather than the volume.

the extremum (3.17) must be a maximum, *i.e.*, $W''(\tilde{r}_{min}) < 0$.¹⁸ In appendix C, we examine the leading correction to the late time limit (3.19) and show that $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ approaches this asymptotic value with an exponential decay in τ . Next we turn to computing the asymptotic value (3.19).

Planar horizons: With $k = 0$, eq. (3.17) can be solved analytically for \tilde{r}_{min} and we find

$$\tilde{r}_{min} = \left(\frac{\omega^{d-2} L^2}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{d}} = \frac{r_h}{2^{\frac{1}{d}}}, \quad (3.20)$$

which then leads to

$$\sqrt{-f(\tilde{r}_{min})} \tilde{r}_{min}^{d-1} = \frac{\omega^{d-2} L}{2}. \quad (3.21)$$

Thus, using eq. (2.47), the asymptotic value (3.19) becomes

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{8\pi M}{d-1}, \quad (3.22)$$

for any planar black hole. Of course, this reproduces the result first found in [6].

Curved horizons: Figure 6a shows a plot of the late time limit (3.19) for spherical black holes (with $k = 1$) for $d = 3$ and 4 . We can see that $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ approaches the value $8\pi M/(d-1)$ in the limit $r_h \gg L$, *i.e.*, $RT \gg 1$.

Since the mass of hyperbolic black holes (*i.e.*, $k = -1$) can take negative values, $\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} \lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} d\mathcal{C}_V/dt$ would diverge at $M = 0$ before reaching the minimal mass. Hence, we instead present numerical plots of

$$\frac{d-1}{8\pi(M - M_{min})} \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau}, \quad (3.23)$$

where M_{min} is the minimal value of mass

$$M_{min} = -\frac{(d-1)\Omega_{-1,d-1}}{8\pi G_N d} \left(\frac{d-2}{d} \right)^{\frac{d-2}{2}} \frac{L^{d-1}}{R}. \quad (3.24)$$

This corresponds to the mass of the extremal small hyperbolic black holes — see appendix D.3. Figure 6b presents the late time limit results for $d = 3$ and $d = 4$ as a function of r_h/L . Hence we can see that eq. (3.23) approaches to 1 from above, in the

¹⁸The case of small hyperbolic black holes, *i.e.*, $k = -1$ and $r_h < L$, is slightly more complicated since there is an inner horizon — see appendix D.3. However, implicitly r_{min} lies in between the two horizons and so one reaches the same conclusion.

limit $r_h/L \gg 1$. The divergence in these curves where r_h/L approaches its minimal value, *i.e.*, $M \rightarrow M_{min}$, is interesting because $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ actually vanishes in the extremal limit. The horizon radius of the extremal black hole can be written as $r_h^{ext} = \frac{\sqrt{d-2}L}{\sqrt{d}}$. Then we would readily find in the extremal limit that $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau \sim (r - r_h^{ext})$ while $M - M_{min} \sim (r - r_h^{ext})^2$. As a consequence, while both the numerator and denominator vanish in this limit, we still obtain a divergent result.

Figure 6: (a) Late time rate of change in complexity $\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ as a function of r_h/L for spherical black holes ($k = 1$) in $d = 3$ (green) and $d = 4$ (dashed purple) dimensions. The vertical dashed line at $r_h/L = 1$ indicates the Hawking-Page phase transition below which the dominant saddle point in the bulk partition function is vacuum AdS rather than a (small) spherical black hole. (b) Plots of $\frac{(d-1)}{8\pi(M-M_{min})} \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ as a function of r_h/L for hyperbolic black holes ($k = -1$) in $d = 3$ (green) and $d = 4$ (dashed purple) dimensions. The vertical lines indicate the minimal values of r_h/L corresponding to extremal small hyperbolic black holes. The gray dashed horizontal line indicates 1, which is approached in the large black hole limit ($r_h \gg L$).

Now we proceed to examine the late time behaviour analytically in the limit of large temperatures, *i.e.*, for large black holes. First, we expand eq. (3.17) in the limit $r_h \gg L$ to find the leading corrections to \tilde{r}_{min} compared to its planar value (3.20),

$$\tilde{r}_{min} = \frac{r_h}{2^{\frac{1}{d}}} \left[1 - \frac{(2^{2/d}(d-1) - d)}{d^2} \frac{L^2}{r_h^2} k + \frac{(d-1) \left(-d^2 + 2^{\frac{2}{d}+1}d + 2^{4/d}(d-3)(d-1) \right)}{2d^4} \frac{L^4}{r_h^4} k^2 + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{L^6}{r_h^6}\right) \right]. \quad (3.25)$$

Using this expression, the asymptotic value of $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ can be written in terms of the

following expansion¹⁹

$$\begin{aligned}
\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(d-1)}{8\pi M} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} &= \left(1 - \frac{M_{min}}{M} \delta_{k,-1}\right) \left(1 - 2^{\frac{2}{d}-1} k \frac{L^2}{r_h^2} + \frac{2^{\frac{2}{d}} (\gamma + d) k^2 L^4}{d^2 r_h^4} + \dots\right) \\
&= \left(1 + \frac{2d(d(d-2))^{\frac{d-2}{2}}}{(4\pi)^d (RT)^d} \delta_{k,-1} + \dots\right) \\
&\quad \times \left(1 - \frac{2^{\frac{2}{d}-1} d^2 k}{(4\pi)^2 (RT)^2} + \frac{2^{\frac{2}{d}} (\gamma - d(d-3)) d^2 k^2}{(4\pi)^4 (RT)^4} + \dots\right)
\end{aligned} \tag{3.26}$$

where to reduce the clutter in the above expressions, we have defined the coefficient:

$$\gamma = 2^{\frac{2}{d}-3} (3d-2)(d-2). \tag{3.27}$$

Let us first focus our attention on the second factor on the right-hand side of eq. (3.26). Here the corrections involve (integer) powers of k/R^2 and hence we expect that these terms can be expressed as simple powers of the boundary curvature. Of course, these curvature corrections become important when the temperature is comparable to the curvature scale, *i.e.*, $RT \sim 1$. However, for high temperatures where the characteristic thermal wavelength is much shorter than the curvature scale, these terms become vanishingly small and the asymptotic growth rate approaches the flat space limit $8\pi M/(d-1)$, as in eq. (3.22).

The above discussion overlooks the first factor on the right-hand side of eq. (3.26). This factor only appears for the case of the hyperbolic horizons (*i.e.*, $k = -1$) and is related to the fact that the minimal mass is actually negative (rather than zero) for these black holes. Further, we observe that when the boundary dimension d is odd, the first correction in this factor involves an odd power of $1/R$. Therefore while the corrections in this factor are appearing because of the negative curvature in the boundary metric (2.46), they will not generally be expressed in terms of geometric factors involving powers of the curvature tensor.

We also note that the expression in eq. (3.26) only holds for $d \geq 3$ and so the leading correction for $RT \gg 1$ always comes from the second factor, *i.e.*, the term proportional to $k/(RT)^2$. Therefore we can conclude that for spherical black holes, the asymptotic value (3.19) approaches the planar value (3.22) from below as $RT \rightarrow 0$. Of course, this is in agreement with the results shown in figure 6a, where we see that for all values of RT ,

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} \leq \frac{8\pi M}{d-1} \quad \text{for } k = +1. \tag{3.28}$$

¹⁹This expansion can also be expressed in terms of central charge over the entropy — see [26].

Similarly for hyperbolic black holes, the asymptotic value (3.19) approaches the planar value (3.22) from above in the limit $RT \rightarrow 0$. Again, this agrees with the results shown in figure 6b, where we see that for all values of RT ,

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} \geq \frac{8\pi}{d-1} (M - M_{min}) \quad \text{for } k = -1. \quad (3.29)$$

3.2 General Time Dependence

To close this section, we present plots of $d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ for planar black holes in various dimensions for general values of the time. We explore further examples with spherical and hyperbolic horizon geometries in appendix B.

In the case that $k = 0$ (and $d \geq 3$), if we define $a \equiv \frac{d-1}{8\pi M} d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$, eq. (3.13) can be recast in the form

$$a = 2s_{min}^{d/2} \sqrt{1 - s_{min}^d}, \quad (s_{min} \equiv r_{min}/r_h). \quad (3.30)$$

Inverting this equation, we can represent s_{min} as a function of a ,

$$s_{min} = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - a^2}}{2} \right)^{\frac{1}{d}}. \quad (3.31)$$

Then rewriting eq. (3.9) in terms of dimensionless quantities, one can find the relation between $a = \frac{d-1}{8\pi M} d\mathcal{C}_V/d\tau$ and τ/β

$$\tau/\beta = \frac{da}{4\pi} \int_{s_{min}}^{\infty} ds \frac{s^{d-2}}{(1-s^d) \sqrt{s_{min}^d (1-s_{min}^d) - s^d (1-s^d)}}. \quad (3.32)$$

Since this relation and eq. (3.31) do not depend on r_h/L , the plot of a as a function of τ/β has the same form for all values r_h/L . Figure 7 shows the plot and we see that at late times, it approaches to one from below, as discussed above in section 3.1.

Figure 7 shows $\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} d\mathcal{C}_V/dt$ for the case of $d = 2$, *i.e.*, BTZ black holes. A similar derivation to the one presented for planar black holes holds in this case. Again, the result does not depend on the value of r_h/L and approaches to one at late times.

4 Charged Black Holes

In this section, we study the growth rate of the complexity for charged black holes with $d \geq 3$ using both the CA and CV conjectures. Charged black holes are solutions to Einstein gravity coupled to a Maxwell field with the following action:

$$I = I_{\text{grav}} - \frac{1}{4g^2} \int d^{d+1}x \sqrt{-g} F_{ab} F^{ab} \quad (4.1)$$

Figure 7: Plot of $\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} \frac{dC_V}{d\tau}$ for planar $d = 4$ (blue), planar $d = 3$ (dashed-red) and $d = 2$ (dot-dashed green) black holes. All three curves are independent of r_h/L and approach to one at late times.

where I_{grav} is the gravitational action given in eq. (2.10). Note that the gauge coupling g has dimensions of length $\frac{d-3}{2}$.

The black hole metric takes the form (2.45) with blackening factor given by, *e.g.*, [47, 48]:²⁰

$$f(r) = \frac{r^2}{L^2} + k - \frac{\omega^{d-2}}{r^{d-2}} + \frac{q^2}{r^{2(d-2)}}, \quad (4.2)$$

and the Maxwell potential can be written as:²¹

$$A_\tau = \frac{g}{2\sqrt{2\pi G_N}} \frac{L}{R} \sqrt{\frac{d-1}{d-2}} \left(\frac{q}{r_+^{d-2}} - \frac{q}{r_-^{d-2}} \right). \quad (4.3)$$

The new blackening factor (4.2) has two real roots, r_+ and r_- (where $r_+ \geq r_-$) corresponding to the outer and inner horizons, respectively. Figure 8 shows the Penrose diagrams for these charged black holes. We note that the integration constant in A_τ was chosen such that it vanishes at the outer horizon, which ensures that it is a well behaved differential form at the corresponding bifurcation surface [47]. It will typically be convenient to write our results in terms of r_+ and r_- by expressing ω^{d-2} and q^2 in terms of r_+ and r_- using the equations $f(r_+) = f(r_-) = 0$ — see below.

²⁰We work with the rescaled time $\tau = Rt/L$ throughout the following.

²¹Our conventions compare to those of [47] (denoted with tildes) as follows: $A_t = \tilde{A}_t \frac{g}{2\sqrt{\pi G}}$, $Q = \tilde{Q} \frac{2\sqrt{\pi G}}{g}$, $\mu = \tilde{\mu} \frac{g}{2\sqrt{\pi G}}$; and to those of [48] by the identification $1/g^2 = \ell^2/G_N$ where ℓ is an extra length scale introduced there to distinguish the coupling of the Maxwell field.

Of course, the Maxwell field in the bulk is dual to a conserved current corresponding to a global $U(1)$ symmetry in the boundary theory *e.g.*, [48]. Hence the charged black hole geometry extends the thermofield double state (1.1) to the entangled state where, as well as a temperature T , we have a chemical potential μ which distinguishes the boundary states by their $U(1)$ charges. We will refer to this as the charged thermofield double state,

$$|\text{cTFD}(t_L, t_R)\rangle = Z^{-1/2} \sum_{\alpha, \sigma} e^{-(E_\alpha - \mu Q_\sigma)/(2T)} e^{-iE_\alpha(t_L + t_R)} |E_\alpha, -Q_\sigma\rangle_L |E_\alpha, Q_\sigma\rangle_R, \quad (4.4)$$

where L and R label the quantum states (and times) at the left and right boundaries. Notice that tracing out the states in either boundary produces the density matrix corresponding to the grand canonical ensemble characterized by T and μ — see further discussion below.

The thermodynamic quantities describing the black hole are the same as those given in eq. (2.47) with the replacement $r_h \rightarrow r_+$ *i.e.*,

$$M = \frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}}{16\pi G_N} \frac{L}{R} \omega^{d-2}, \quad S = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4G_N} r_+^{d-1}, \quad T = \frac{L}{R} \frac{1}{4\pi} \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial r} \right|_{r=r_+}. \quad (4.5)$$

The charge is naturally defined in terms of Gauss' law, *i.e.*,

$$Q = \oint *F = \frac{q\Omega_{k,d-1}\sqrt{(d-1)(d-2)}}{2g\sqrt{2\pi G_N}} \quad (4.6)$$

where the $(d-1)$ -form $*F$ is the Hodge dual of the field strength $F_{ab} = \partial_a A_b - \partial_b A_a$. Of course, the Maxwell field in the bulk is dual to a global symmetry current in the boundary theory.²² In this holographic context, the charge (4.6) also corresponds to the integral of the zeroth component of the boundary current over a constant τ slice. The chemical potential can be determined using the thermodynamic relation $dM = TdS + \mu dQ$,

$$\mu = \frac{g}{2\sqrt{2\pi G_N}} \frac{L}{R} \sqrt{\frac{d-1}{d-2}} \frac{q}{r_+^{d-2}}. \quad (4.7)$$

Comparing to eq. (4.3), this also corresponds to the ‘non-normalizable’ mode of the gauge potential, *i.e.*, $\mu = \lim_{r \rightarrow \infty} A_\tau$.

We note that the action (4.1) provides a well defined variational principle where we keep the gauge potential fixed at the boundary. Hence if we were examining the thermodynamics of these black holes, *e.g.*, with the corresponding Euclidean action, then

²²The current can be defined by varying the boundary action with respect to the gauge field, *e.g.*, [48].

we would be working with the grand canonical ensemble where the chemical potential μ is fixed. That is, implicitly, our control parameters are the temperature T and the chemical potential μ [47, 48]. Hence the full geometry of the eternal charged black hole is dual to the charged thermofield double state, given in eq. (4.4). Alternatively, we could consider a fixed charge ensemble, but this would require adding a boundary term of the form $1/g^2 \int_{\partial\mathcal{M}} d^d x \sqrt{\gamma} n^a F_{ab} A^b$ to the action. It would be interesting to pursue this possibility in the context of the complexity=action proposal, where it seems that we would need to include this boundary term on all of the boundaries of the WDW patch.

In order to express our results for the complexity in terms of boundary quantities, it will be useful to also have holographic expressions for the central charges associated with the two-point functions of the boundary stress tensor (*e.g.*, [49–51]) and currents (*e.g.*, [52, 53]). That is, for a d -dimensional CFT, the leading singularities in the vacuum correlators take the form:

$$\langle T_{\mu\nu}(x) T_{\rho\sigma}(0) \rangle = \frac{C_T}{x^{2d}} \mathcal{I}_{ab,cd}, \quad \langle J_\mu(x) J_\nu(0) \rangle = \frac{C_J}{x^{2(d-1)}} I_{\mu\nu}(x) \quad (4.8)$$

where

$$\mathcal{I}_{ab,cd} \equiv \frac{1}{2} (I_{\mu\nu}(x) I_{\rho\sigma}(x) + I_{\mu\sigma}(x) I_{\nu\rho}(x)) - \frac{1}{d} \eta_{\mu\nu} \eta_{\rho\sigma}, \quad I_{\mu\nu} \equiv \eta_{\mu\nu} - 2 \frac{x_\mu x_\nu}{x^2}. \quad (4.9)$$

For our holographic framework, the two central charges can then be expressed in terms of bulk parameters as

$$C_T = \frac{d+1}{d-1} \frac{\Gamma(d+1)}{8\pi^{(d+2)/2} \Gamma(d/2)} \frac{L^{d-1}}{G_N}, \quad C_J = \frac{(d-2)\Gamma(d)}{2\pi^{d/2} \Gamma(d/2)} \frac{L^{d-3}}{g^2}. \quad (4.10)$$

It will be convenient to work in terms of the following dimensionless quantities:

$$x \equiv \frac{r}{r_+}, \quad y \equiv \frac{r_-}{r_+}, \quad z \equiv \frac{L}{r_+}. \quad (4.11)$$

Here, x is a dimensionless radial coordinate, while y and z can be expressed in terms of dimensionless boundary quantities. In particular, combining the expressions above yields

$$\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}} \frac{\mu}{T} = h(y, z), \quad RT = \tilde{h}(y, z). \quad (4.12)$$

Of course, these equations can be inverted and so one can think directly of y and z as boundary quantities. As we will see, all our result can be expressed as functions of ν

and RT , or alternatively of y and z . Explicit expressions for $h(y, z)$ and $\tilde{h}(y, z)$ for the different dimensions and geometries read

$$h(y, z) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}\pi(d-1) \left(y^{\frac{d}{2}-1} \sqrt{1-y^{d-2}} \sqrt{(kz^2+1)-y^{d-2}(kz^2+y^2)} \right)}{\sqrt{d(d+1)} \left((d-2)kz^2 + d - 2y^{d-2} \left((d-2)kz^2 + d - 1 \right) + (d-2)y^{2(d-2)}(kz^2+y^2) \right)},$$

$$\tilde{h}(y, z) = \frac{(d-2)kz^2 + d - 2y^{d-2} \left((d-2)kz^2 + d - 1 \right) + (d-2)y^{2(d-2)}(kz^2+y^2)}{4\pi z (1-y^{d-2})}. \quad (4.13)$$

It is instructive to expand these functions in the small charge limit (*i.e.*, small y) where one obtains

$$h(y, z) = \frac{2\sqrt{2}\pi(d-1)\sqrt{1+kz^2}}{\sqrt{d(d+1)}(d+(d-2)kz^2)} y^{\frac{d}{2}-1} \times \left[1 + \left(1 + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1}{(1+kz^2)} - \frac{2}{d+(d-2)kz^2} \right) y^{d-2} + \mathcal{O}(y^d) \right] \quad (4.14)$$

$$\tilde{h}(y, z) = \frac{d+(d-2)kz^2}{4\pi z} - \frac{(1+kz^2)}{4\pi z} (d-2)y^{d-2} + \mathcal{O}(y^{2(d-2)}).$$

As expected, the dimensionless quantity ν goes to zero and TR to the uncharged limit as in eq. (2.47). From the expansions in eq. (4.14), we can also conclude that the chemical potential, $\sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}} \mu R = \tilde{h}(y, z)h(y, z)$ scales as $\propto y^{\frac{d-2}{2}}$ for small charges. Similarly, the blackening factor can be expressed as $f(x, y, z)$ where x was defined in eq. (4.11).

Complexity of Formation: The complexity of formation for uncharged black holes was examined in detail in [26]. Hence for completeness, we also examine the ‘complexity of formation’ of charged black holes here and the corresponding calculations are described in detail in appendix D. The question of interest is what is the additional complexity involved in preparing the two copies of the boundary CFT in the charged entangled thermofield double state (4.4) compared to preparing each of the CFTs separately in their vacuum state. Using the CA proposal,²³ the bulk calculation consists of evaluating the gravitational action for the WDW patch (anchored at $t_L = t_R = 0$) in the charged AdS black hole background and subtracting twice the action for the WDW patch in empty AdS space (*i.e.*, $\omega = q = 0$). A key feature of this subtraction is that all of the UV (large r) divergences cancel leaving a UV-finite result.

We discuss here the charged complexity of formation using the CA conjecture for the planar case, *i.e.*, $k = 0$, for $d = 4$. For small chemical potential, the charged

²³Of course, an analogous calculation can also be performed using the CV proposal, see appendix D.

Figure 8: Penrose diagrams for a charged black hole. On the left figure we break-down the action calculation for the Wheeler-DeWitt patch. The future (past) corner approaches the inner (outer) horizon in the late time limit. On the right, we identify the maximal volume that is evaluated in the CV proposal. As in section 2 we have for the case of a general boundary size $t = \frac{L}{R}\tau$.

complexity of formation can be written as a series expansion for small y ,

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{S}{2\pi} \left(1 + \left(\frac{20}{3\pi} + \frac{4}{\pi} \log \left[\frac{yz \alpha R}{2L} \right] \right) y^3 + \dots \right), \quad (4.15)$$

where S is the thermal entropy. Of course, we recover the $d = 4$ planar result found in [26] in the limit of vanishing chemical potential, *i.e.*, $y \rightarrow 0$. We can rewrite the above expression without the explicit zR dependence, using the $k = 0$ and $d = 4$ instances of eq. (4.13), which reads

$$\nu = \frac{3\pi}{\sqrt{10}} \frac{y\sqrt{1+y^2}}{(2-y^2-y^4)}, \quad TR = \frac{(1-y^2)(2+y^2)}{2\pi z}. \quad (4.16)$$

Figure 9: Complexity of formation divided by the entropy for the planar charged black hole in $d = 4$. Here we are subtracting the complexity of two copies of the vacuum spacetime (*i.e.*, the zero mass and zero charge limit of the planar black hole). In this plot, we keep the chemical potential fixed as $\sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}} \mu R = \frac{1}{2}$. For a fixed chemical potential in the limit of zero temperature (dual to extremal black hole) the complexity of formation is divergent.

The expansion of the complexity of formation then becomes

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{S}{2\pi} \left(1 + \frac{10^{3/2}}{(3\pi)^4} \left(20 + 12 \log \left[\frac{10^{1/2}}{3\pi^2} \frac{\alpha \nu}{LT} \right] \right) \nu^3 + \dots \right). \quad (4.17)$$

As in section 2, we might simplify the above expression by choosing the normalization of the null normals at infinity to be $\alpha = L/R$, where R is to be interpreted not as the curvature scale, but instead as an arbitrary reference length scale in the boundary theory (for $k = 0$).

We also use the boundary quantities from eq. (4.16) to evaluate numerically the complexity of formation fixing the chemical potential and varying the temperature in figure 9. There is an unexpected behaviour when the temperature is very small, as the complexity of formation grows unbounded. The fact that the complexity of formation for extremal black holes of finite chemical potential is divergent suggests that the proposed ground state for large charged black holes in [8] should be revisited. It is also interesting to notice that in this limit of zero temperature with a fixed chemical potential, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ goes to zero [8], as we will show in the following subsection. We will explore further some features of the charged complexity of formation in appendix D.

4.1 Complexity=Action

Next, we examine the time evolution of holographic complexity using the CA proposal for the eternal charged AdS black holes. The integrand of the bulk action is given by²⁴

$$I(r) \equiv \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} (\mathcal{R} - 2\Lambda) - \frac{1}{4g^2} F_{ab} F^{ab} = \frac{1}{16\pi G_N} \left(-\frac{2d}{L^2} + \frac{2(d-2)q^2}{r^{2(d-1)}} \right). \quad (4.18)$$

We then write the bulk action as

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = \frac{L}{R} \Omega_{k,d-1} \int dr r^{d-1} I(r) \int d\tau \quad (4.19)$$

where we still have to specify the limits of integration. In particular, we need to find the future (r_m^1) and past (r_m^2) meeting points of the null sheets bounding the WDW patch — see figure 8. These satisfy the following relations

$$\frac{L}{R} \frac{\tau}{2} + r_\infty^* - r^*(r_m^1) = 0, \quad \frac{L}{R} \frac{\tau}{2} - r_\infty^* + r^*(r_m^2) = 0. \quad (4.20)$$

Note that taking the time derivative of these relations yields:

$$\frac{R}{L} \frac{dr_m^1}{d\tau} = \frac{f(r_m^1)}{2}, \quad \frac{R}{L} \frac{dr_m^2}{d\tau} = -\frac{f(r_m^2)}{2}. \quad (4.21)$$

We again divide the bulk contribution into three separate regions

$$\begin{aligned} I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{I}} &= 2\Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_m^1}^{r_+} I(r) r^{d-1} \left(\frac{\tau}{2} + \frac{R}{L} (r_\infty^* - r^*(r)) \right) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{II}} &= 4\Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_+}^{r_{\text{max}}} I(r) r^{d-1} \frac{R}{L} (r_\infty^* - r^*(r)) dr \\ I_{\text{bulk}}^{\text{III}} &= 2\Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_m^2}^{r_+} I(r) r^{d-1} \left(-\frac{\tau}{2} + \frac{R}{L} (r_\infty^* - r^*(r)) \right) dr. \end{aligned} \quad (4.22)$$

Differentiating with respect to τ we see once again (as in the neutral case) that the contributions due to differentiating the limits of integration vanish using eq. (4.20). The contribution outside the black hole (region II) is independent of time.²⁵ Hence the only nonvanishing contribution comes from differentiating inside the integrals and we obtain

$$\frac{dI_{\text{bulk}}}{d\tau} = \frac{L}{R} \Omega_{k,d-1} \int_{r_m^1}^{r_m^2} r^{d-1} I(r) dr = \frac{L}{R} \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left[\frac{r^d}{L^2} + \frac{q^2}{r^{d-2}} \right] \Bigg|_{r_m^2}^{r_m^1}. \quad (4.23)$$

²⁴To simplify this expression, we have used the trace of Einstein equations, which yields $\mathcal{R} = -\frac{d(d+1)}{L^2} + \frac{d-3}{d-1} \frac{4\pi G_N}{g^2} F_{ab} F^{ab}$.

²⁵This results from the boost invariance of the exterior geometry, as noted in [7, 8].

There are no contributions to $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ from the surface terms or from the asymptotic boundaries here, but we do expect the two joints (at $r = r_m^1$ and r_m^2) to contribute:

$$I_{\text{corner}} = -\frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} \left[(r_m^1)^{d-1} \log \left[\frac{L^2 |f(r_m^1)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} \right] + (r_m^2)^{d-1} \log \left[\frac{L^2 |f(r_m^2)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} \right] \right]. \quad (4.24)$$

Differentiating the corner contribution with respect to τ then gives

$$\frac{dI_{\text{corner}}}{d\tau} = -\frac{L}{R} \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{16\pi G_N} \left[(d-1) r^{d-2} f(r) \log \frac{L^2 |f(r)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} + r^{d-1} \partial_r f(r) \right] \Bigg|_{r_m^2}^{r_m^1}, \quad (4.25)$$

where we used eq. (4.20). Combining the nonvanishing contributions together leads to

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{L}{R} \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1} (d-1)}{8\pi^2 G_N} \frac{q^2}{r^{d-2}} \Bigg|_{r_m^2}^{r_m^1} - \frac{L}{R} \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1} (d-1)}{16\pi^2 G_N} r^{d-2} f(r) \log \frac{L^2 |f(r)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} \Bigg|_{r_m^2}^{r_m^1}. \quad (4.26)$$

As a consistency check, we note that in the late time limit, we recover eq. (3.39) of [25]:

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1} (d-1) q^2}{8\pi^2 G_N} \frac{L}{R} \frac{1}{r^{d-2}} \Bigg|_{r_+}^{r_-}, \quad (4.27)$$

where we have used that $r_m^1 \rightarrow r_-$ and $r_m^2 \rightarrow r_+$ in this limit. It is also possible to express this late time rate of change using the black hole mass and the dimensionless quantities from eq. (4.11) as

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(\frac{(1-y^{d-2})((1-y^d) + kz^2(1-y^{d-2}))}{(1-y^{2(d-1)}) + kz^2(1-y^{2(d-2)})} \right). \quad (4.28)$$

In these variables, the late time limit of the uncharged case is easily obtained with $y \rightarrow 0$.

Now it is straightforward to solve for the two meeting points numerically using eq. (4.20) and then to evaluate the rate of change in complexity (4.26). To illustrate these results, we show $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ for $d = 4$ in figures 10 and 11.²⁶ For these black holes, the boundary quantities ν and RT in eq. (4.12) can be obtained from the ratios y and z as

$$\nu = \sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T} \frac{\mu}{T}} = \frac{3\pi}{\sqrt{10}} \frac{y \sqrt{1+y^2+kz^2}}{(1-y^2)(2+y^2+kz^2)}, \quad RT = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{(1-y^2)(2+y^2+kz^2)}{z}. \quad (4.29)$$

In the figures, the rate of change in complexity is presented for fixed values of these boundary quantities.

²⁶As before, we set $\alpha = L/R$ for simplicity.

Figure 10: The time derivative of complexity with $d = 4$, $k = 1$ and non-zero chemical potential, obtained by fixing the parameters in eq. (4.29). The various curves correspond to: $\nu = 0.1$ in blue (solid) , $\nu = 1$ in orange (dashed) and $\nu = 5$ in green (dot-dashed) for $TR = 1$ (Left) and $TR = \frac{1}{2}$ (Right). In order to illustrate the violation of the bound, we explicitly show the late time limit from eq. (4.28) in the right figure.

Figure 11: The time derivative of complexity with $d = 4$, $k = 0$ and non-zero chemical potential, obtained by fixing the parameters in eq. (4.29). The various curves correspond to: $\nu = 0.1$ in blue (solid) , $\nu = 1$ in orange (dashed) and $\nu = 5$ in green (dot-dashed). We varied the chemical potential while fixing the temperature as $TR = \frac{1}{2}$, where as before the scale R in the planar geometry is related to an arbitrary scale in the boundary theory.

4.1.1 Comments

Let us make a number of observations about these results for the charged black holes. First, we note that in both figures, for very small charge (or small chemical potential), the rate of change in complexity develops a minimum at some finite time. This minimum becomes deeper and sharper for smaller charges, and so the behaviour smoothly approaches that of the neutral black holes ($\nu = 0$), shown in figure 4. In particular,

the pronounced minimum in $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is centered around the neutral τ_c , and its shape resembles closely the negative divergent rate of change observed right after τ_c in the neutral case, and as noted above, the late time limit approaches $2M/\pi$, as expected for neutral AdS black holes.²⁷

Next, we might consider the extremal limit of the charged black holes where $T \rightarrow 0$. It is straightforward to show $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau \simeq 0$ in this limit. For example, from eq. (4.29), we see that this limit corresponds to $y \rightarrow 1$ and this certainly produces a vanishing rate of change for the late time limit in eq. (4.28). More generally, this limit corresponds to $r_- \rightarrow r_+$ and we find $r_m^1 \sim r_m^2$. The latter then produces a cancellation and vanishing $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau \simeq 0$ in eq. (4.26).

Late time expansion: In a very similar manner to the analysis of the late time limit in section 2.2.1, we can obtain the late time limit of the growth rate of the holographic complexity for charged black holes. First, we decompose the inverse blackening factor as

$$\frac{1}{f(r)} = \frac{1}{r_+ - r_-} \left(\frac{r_+}{F(r_+)r(r - r_+)} - \frac{r_-}{F(r_-)r(r - r_-)} + H(r) \right) \quad (4.30)$$

where we have defined:

$$f(r) \equiv F(r)(r - r_+)(r - r_-) \quad (4.31)$$

and $F(r)$ is a strictly positive function. Further, we have defined

$$H(r) = \frac{F(r_+)r - F(r)r_+}{F(r_+)F(r)r(r - r_+)} - \frac{F(r_-)r - F(r)r_-}{F(r_-)F(r)r(r - r_-)}, \quad (4.32)$$

which is regular both at r_+ and at r_- and decays at least as fast as $1/r^2$ when r approaches infinity. This leads to the tortoise coordinate:

$$r^*(r) = \frac{\log(|r - r_+|/r)}{F(r_+)(r_+ - r_-)} - \frac{\log(|r - r_-|/r)}{F(r_-)(r_+ - r_-)} + \frac{1}{r_+ - r_-} \int^r H(\tilde{r})d\tilde{r}. \quad (4.33)$$

We have left the lower limit in the last integral implicit, as this choice does not influence the subtractions involved in the equations determining the meeting points. Solving for the first subleading order in the late time limit of eq. (4.20), we obtain

$$r_m^1 = r_- \left(1 + c_- e^{-\frac{F(r_-)(r_+ - r_-)}{2} \frac{L}{R} \tau} \right), \quad r_m^2 = r_+ \left(1 - c_+ e^{-\frac{F(r_+)(r_+ - r_-)}{2} \frac{L}{R} \tau} \right) \quad (4.34)$$

²⁷In fact, one can easily show that eq. (2.49) is recovered in the zero charge limit analytically. The key observation is that r_- vanishes as $r_-^{d-2} = q^2/\omega^{d-2}$ in this limit. Along with $r_m^1 \sim r_-$ and $r_m^2 \simeq r_m^{(neutral)}$, eq. (4.26) reduces to the neutral growth rate (2.49) for $\tau > \tau_c$. We consider the early time behaviour in the zero charge limit below.

where c_+ and c_- are positive constants given by

$$c_- = \left(\frac{r_+ - r_-}{r_-} \right)^{\frac{F(r_-)}{F(r_+)}} e^{-F(r_-) \int_{r_-}^{\infty} H(\tilde{r}) d\tilde{r}}, \quad c_+ = \left(\frac{r_+ - r_-}{r_+} \right)^{\frac{F(r_+)}{F(r_-)}} e^{F(r_+) \int_{r_+}^{\infty} H(\tilde{r}) d\tilde{r}}. \quad (4.35)$$

From eq. (4.26), we can now demonstrate that

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} + \frac{(r_+ - r_-)^2 L^2 \Omega_{d-1} (d-1)}{2 R^2 16\pi^2 G_N} \tau \\ \times \left(c_+ r_+^{d-1} F(r_+)^2 e^{-\frac{F(r_+)(r_+ - r_-)}{2} \frac{L}{R} \tau} - c_- r_-^{d-1} F(r_-)^2 e^{-\frac{F(r_-)(r_+ - r_-)}{2} \frac{L}{R} \tau} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (4.36)$$

where we have neglected terms that decay exponentially compared to those that decay as τ times an exponential above. At very late times the exponent with smaller coefficient will dominate and will determine whether the limit is reached from above or from below. We have checked the ratio $F(r_+)/F(r_-) = -f'(r_+)/f'(r_-)$ for a variety of dimensions and geometries and found that it is in general positive and smaller than one. As a consequence, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ generally approaches the late time limit from above.

Early time behaviour: We note that for the charged black holes, there is not a critical time before which the time derivative of the complexity is equal to zero. In the charged black hole, the past and future oriented joint terms (see the left panel in figure 8) start moving right away. However, we will show that for a small chemical potential, the time derivative of the complexity is exponentially suppressed at early times. In order to investigate this behaviour, we investigate the early time regime of the rate of change of complexity in an analytic expansion for small charges. To complete the picture, we also consider in this section the early time behaviour of the rate of change of complexity for near extremal black holes.

As we have already mentioned at the beginning of this subsection, in the limit in which the charge is small, the action does not change much for a certain period of time after $\tau = 0$. In this situation, the future and past corner points (*i.e.*, r_m^1 and r_m^2 respectively, or x_m^1 and x_m^2 in terms of the dimensionless coordinate $x = r/r_+$) are exponentially close to the inner horizon r_- at early times. For instance in $d = 4$, we can derive the following expressions in a small charge expansion, *i.e.*, $y \rightarrow 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} x_m^1 = y \left(1 + \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\pi(1 + kz^2)}{2 + kz^2} \frac{2\tau T + \sqrt{1 + kz^2}}{y^3} \right) + \mathcal{O} \left(\frac{1}{y} \right) \right] \right), \\ x_m^2 = y \left(1 + \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\pi(1 + kz^2)}{2 + kz^2} \frac{-2\tau T + \sqrt{1 + kz^2}}{y^3} \right) + \mathcal{O} \left(\frac{1}{y} \right) \right] \right). \end{aligned} \quad (4.37)$$

This expansion demonstrates that the two corners remain exponentially close to r_- at early times. Given the above expression, it is clear that r_m^1 never leaves this regime and keeps approaching r_- . However, in the second expression for r_m^2 , the leading term in the exponent flips its sign at some $\tau = \tau_c = \frac{1}{2T}\sqrt{1+kz^2}$, which is precisely the uncharged critical time given in eq. (2.66). Hence the rate of change of complexity given by eq. (4.26) is exponentially suppressed as long as $\tau \lesssim \tau_c$.

Another case for which the early time behaviour can be studied in an analytic expansion is the near-extremal black holes. In this case, the inner and outer horizons are very close to each other as $y \rightarrow 1$. If we define $y = 1 - \epsilon$ where $\epsilon \ll 1$, eq. (4.20) yields at early times

$$\begin{aligned} x_m^1 &= 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2} (1 + \pi\tau T) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon\tau^3 T^3, \epsilon^2\tau T, \epsilon^2 \log \epsilon), \\ x_m^2 &= 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2} (1 - \pi\tau T) + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon\tau^3 T^3, \epsilon^2\tau T, \epsilon^2 \log \epsilon). \end{aligned} \quad (4.38)$$

In general, the geometry and hence, the complexity are symmetric under $\tau \rightarrow -\tau$. Therefore only even derivatives of \mathcal{C}_A are nonvanishing at $\tau = 0$, *e.g.*, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau|_{\tau=0} = 0$. We can evaluate the second derivative of \mathcal{C}_A at $\tau = 0$ using eqs. (4.26) and (4.21), and the expansion for $x_m \equiv x_m^1 = x_m^2$ at $\tau = 0$ which reads

$$\begin{aligned} x_m &= 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{(3kz^2 + 7)\epsilon^2 \log(\epsilon)}{4(kz^2 + 3)} - \frac{\epsilon^2}{8(kz^2 + 3)} \times \left(16\pi\sqrt{\frac{1}{kz^2 + 2}} + 3 + 28 \log(2) \right) \\ &\quad + kz^2 \left(4\pi(kz^2 + 4)\sqrt{\frac{1}{kz^2 + 2}} + 1 + 6 \log(4) \right) - 8(kz^2 + 2)^{3/2} \cot^{-1}(\sqrt{kz^2 + 2}). \end{aligned} \quad (4.39)$$

Hence using the above results, the first nonvanishing derivative becomes

$$\left. \frac{d^2\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau^2} \right|_{\tau=0} = \frac{4(kz^2 + 2)}{2kz^2 + 3} \epsilon MT + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3). \quad (4.40)$$

Note that the temperature here is of order ϵ and as a consequence the leading term in an ϵ expansion is in fact of order ϵ^2 . Despite being suppressed by the parameter ϵ , the complexity grows quadratically (and the rate of change grows linearly) with τ at early times.

Lloyd's bound: A generalization of Lloyd's bound for the case of charged black holes has been proposed in [8] (see also [54]). According to this suggestion, the natural bound for states at a finite chemical potential becomes

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \leq \frac{2}{\pi} \left[(M - \mu Q) - (M - \mu Q)|_{gs} \right]. \quad (4.41)$$

Figure 12: The time derivative of complexity with $d = 4$, $k = 1$ with non-zero chemical potential, by fixing the parameters in eq. (4.29). The various curves correspond to: $\nu = 0.1$ in blue (solid), $\nu = 1$ in orange (dashed) and $\nu = 5$ in green (dot-dashed) for $TR = 1$ (left) and $TR = \frac{1}{2}$ (right). Late time limits are obtained from eqs. (3.17), (3.19) and are indicated by horizontal lines of the appropriate color.

This bound was inspired by the late time growth rate of holographic complexity for the charged black holes. One important element of this proposed bound is that it involves the subtraction of certain thermodynamic quantities associated with the ground state (gs) of the system in question, which according to the proposal of [8] is the state minimizing $(M - \mu Q)$ for a given value of the chemical potential. For instance, for spherical black holes with $\mu < \frac{gL}{2R\sqrt{2\pi G}} \sqrt{\frac{d-1}{d-2}}$, the ground state is simply the vacuum solution ($M = Q = 0$) with a constant gauge field, while for larger chemical potentials, the ground state is the extremal black hole with same chemical potential μ as the state of interest. However, it was also found in [8] that the proposed bound (4.41) is violated for black holes which are intermediate or large compared to the AdS radius ($r_+ \gtrsim L$), while for small black holes the bound is exactly saturated. On the other hand, we showed earlier that the complexity calculated from the action always approaches its late time limit from above, and as a consequence we conclude that the bound in eq. (4.41) is always violated.

4.2 Complexity=Volume

We can also extend the analysis of section 3 to evaluate the rate of change of complexity for the charged case using the CV proposal (1.2). A maximal volume connecting the two boundaries anchored at t_L and t_R is depicted on the right side of figure 8. The analysis and the results are very similar to the uncharged case. For example, one still calculates the rate of change by computing r_{min} (or the associated E) in eq. (3.8), but now with the blackening factor for charged solutions in eq. (4.2). The growth rate can be evaluated as detailed in section 3.2.

Figure 13: The time derivative of complexity with $d = 4$, $k = 0$ with non-zero chemical potential, by fixing the parameters in eq. (4.29). The various curves correspond to: $\nu = 0.1$ in blue (solid), $\nu = 1$ in orange (dashed) and $\nu = 5$ in green (dot-dashed). Curves are independent of TR in eq. (4.12) as expected for the planar geometry. Late time limits are obtained from eqs. (3.17), (3.19) and are indicated by horizontal lines of the appropriate color.

We present some of the results in figures 12 and 13. The growth rate depends on the charge parameter as expected, and it also approaches zero near the extremal limit, analogous to the previous results from CA. It smoothly approaches the neutral behaviour (*e.g.*, shown in figures 7 and 24b) in the limit $q \rightarrow 0$.

5 Discussion

In this paper, we computed the general time dependence of holographic complexity in various AdS black hole geometries.²⁸ Further we examined the time dependence using both the complexity=action (CA) and the complexity=volume (CV) conjectures. Using the CV conjecture, the rate of change of complexity is a positive monotonically increasing function of time, and it saturates to a positive constant as $t \rightarrow \infty$. In particular, for planar black holes, the limiting rate is given by eq. (3.22),

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{d\tau} = \frac{8\pi M}{d-1}, \quad (3.22)$$

as was first found in [6]. When the boundary geometry is curved, this result is modified by various curvature corrections which become important when the temperature is of the same order as the curvature scale, *i.e.*, $RT \lesssim 1$.

²⁸Here, we have focused on eternal two-sided black holes and in a companion paper, we will also study one-sided black holes [55].

Using the CA conjecture, the rate of change of the complexity shows some curious features. Of course, there is a universal late time rate of growth

$$\lim_{\tau \rightarrow \infty} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi}, \quad (5.1)$$

as shown in eq. (2.41). This universal rate, discovered in [7, 8], holds in any number of dimensions and is not affected by the boundary curvature. However, as also shown in eq. (2.41), $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ overshoots this late time limit at early times and approaches the final limit from above. Further $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is initially zero and the complexity only begins to change after some critical time τ_c (for $d \geq 3$). This initial phase of constant complexity was also observed in [7, 8]. In the bulk, the vanishing of $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ results because of the ‘boost’ symmetry of the eternal black hole geometry and the fact that in this initial period of time the WDW patch touches both the past and future singularities, *e.g.*, see the left panel in figure 1. A third curious feature that we found is that immediately after $\tau = \tau_c$, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is divergent and negative, as shown in eq. (2.42)²⁹ — see also figure 4.

We reiterate that the three features above only appear for the time rate of change evaluated with the CA proposal. None of these features appeared in the results found using the CV proposal in section 3. Further, when a chemical potential was introduced in section 4, this washed out the unusual behaviour at early times, at least when the chemical potential was comparable to the temperature, as shown in figures 10 and 11. Of course, as we discussed, the limit $q \rightarrow 0$ was a smooth one and the curious behaviour found for the neutral black holes was recovered. So when the chemical potential was small but nonvanishing, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ varied very little for an initial period and then quickly dipped to negative values before rising again. We can also add that with a chemical potential, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ would still overshoot the late time limit but that the amount by which the limit was exceeded was much less pronounced when the chemical potential became large.

At this point, let us add that the curious behaviour found with the CA proposal also seems to be particular to the eternal black hole, *i.e.*, to the thermofield double state (1.1). Analogous computations of the action for a one-sided black hole yield results more similar to those found here with the CV proposal [55]. That is, in this context, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is a positive monotonically increasing function of time, which saturates to some positive constant in the late time limit.

²⁹This negative spike (as well as the overshoot of the late time limit) in $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ also appears in different holographic settings, such as the holographic dual of non-commutative SYM theories [56]. We thank Josiah Couch for discussing this upcoming work with us.

In the above discussion, we commented that for higher dimensions (*i.e.*, $d \geq 3$), the action (for neutral black holes) does not change at all for some period $-\tau_c \leq \tau \leq \tau_c$ and then changes very rapidly just after $\tau = \tau_c$. We observe that the time scale τ_c is of the order of the thermal time scale $\beta = 1/T$, *e.g.*, see eq. (2.66) for $d = 4$. In particular, the latter equation demonstrates that the critical time is a physical quantity independent of the ambiguity introduced by the normalization constant α of null normals. In contrast, the period of time over which $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is negative, depends both on β and on α . For very small black holes, it is possible to obtain an estimate of this period by equating the RHS of eq. (2.42) with the constant term in the complexity $2M/\pi$ and we see that this period depends explicitly on the reference scale ℓ (as in $\alpha = L/\ell$) (*i.e.*, the spike lasts for $\delta t_0 \sim \beta (\ell/\beta)^{2(d-1)/(d-2)}$). However, we might add that this negative spike can grow arbitrarily wide³⁰ for extremely large values of ℓ , or alternatively, for extremely small values of the parameter α . While the latter remains a logical possibility, it also seems very unnatural for our complexity calculations, *e.g.*, see [11, 27].

However, one might argue that the holographic definition of circuit complexity is not robust enough to consider time scales smaller than β in the context of the eternal black hole.³¹ That is, we might only want to consider the behaviour of complexity over time scales which are longer than the thermal time scale. Therefore we defined an averaged version of $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ in eq. (2.43), which is essentially a symmetric discrete time derivative with a time step $\Delta t = \gamma/T$. With a large enough γ , the complexity begins changing right away and the sharp negative spike in $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is washed out by the averaging procedure.³² However, we note that this averaging does not remove the behaviour where the rate of change overshoots its late time limit. This feature should not be associated with short times since in fact, the late time limit is being approached from above, as shown in eq. (2.41). Some examples of these averaged growth rates are shown in figure 14.

Recall that [7, 8] suggested that the late time limit of $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ may be related to Lloyd's bound $2M/\pi$ for the rate of computation for a system of energy M [30]. These authors also proposed a generalization of Lloyd's bound that should apply for charged black holes — see eq. (4.41). However, they also pointed out apparent violations of the latter bound for intermediate or large charge black holes (*i.e.*, $r_+ \gtrsim L$). However, our calculations of the rate of change of holographic complexity for general times showed that $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ always overshoots the late time limit. As a consequence, for every situation that we examined in sections 2.2.1 and 4.1.1, the corresponding bound on $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ was violated. This certainly calls into question these proposals or at least their

³⁰The growth rate is exceptionally slow with $\delta t_0 \sim \beta \log[\log(\ell/\beta)]$ for very large values of ℓ .

³¹We thank Lenny Susskind, Dan Roberts and Brian Swingle for correspondence on this point.

³²This simply requires that $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau > 0$ at $\tau = \gamma\beta/2$.

Figure 14: The averaged rate of growth of complexity from eq. (2.43) (with $\gamma = 1$) as a function of time for the $d = 3$ planar black hole (left) and $d = 4$ planar (right). Results are shown for several values of the horizon radius — $r_h/L = 1$ (blue), $r_h/L = 1.5$ (dashed red) and $r_h/L = 3.5$ (dot-dashed green). Note that, as in figures 2 and 4, smaller black holes violate the Lloyd bound more strongly. Note also, that the averaged derivative is discontinuous at $|\tau/\beta \pm \frac{1}{2}| = \tau_c/\beta$, where for $d = 3$, $\tau_c/\beta = \frac{1}{2\sqrt{3}}$ and for $d = 4$, $\tau_c/\beta = \frac{1}{2}$.

interpretation (as we describe next).

Let us comment that similar violations are observed for the proposed bounds for the maximal rate of entanglement growth in relativistic systems [57, 58].³³ In this case, the proposal is that following a quantum quench, the rate of growth of the entanglement entropy for a large region will be bounded by

$$\frac{1}{s_{eq} A} \frac{dS_{EE}}{dt} \leq v_E \quad (5.2)$$

where s_{eq} is the equilibrium entropy density, A is the area of the entangling surface, and $v_E (\leq 1)$ is a universal velocity that depends on the dimension of the spacetime. In certain contexts, this bound can be proven but it requires considering a certain scaling regime where $\beta \ll t, R$ where R is the characteristic size of the entangling region [59]. In contrast, in numerical studies, one may find that the rate of growth actually overshoots the expected bound, *e.g.*, [58, 60]. By analogy, it may be that one should only interpret the bounds on the growth of complexity in a particular scaling regime. For example, if we demand that $\beta \ll t$, then the corrections in eq. (2.41) to the late time limit would be vanishingly small. We might also point out that one needs to test carefully the validity of the assumptions entering in the derivation of Lloyd’s bound in

³³We thank Mark Mezei for explaining this point to us.

a holographic setup, in particular the use of orthogonalizing gates.³⁴

We must also comment that the precise details of the manner in which $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ overshoots the late time limit depend on the normalization constant α , which fixes the normal vectors on the null boundaries of the WDW patch. In our various plots, *e.g.*, figures 2 and 4, we chose $\alpha = L/R$ for simplicity and as a result, the late time limit was only exceeded by a relatively small amount. However, by choosing α to be very large, the amount by which $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ overshoots this limit can be made very large. This is easily demonstrated by examining eq. (2.49) evaluated for two different values of the normalization constant, *i.e.*, α_1 and α_2 , but for the same time τ where $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ exceeds the late time limit for α_1 . Now we see in eq. (2.49) shows that with α_2 , $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is the previous value plus a positive quantity multiplying $\log(\alpha_2/\alpha_1)$ and so by choosing α_2 large enough, we can make the excess as large as we want.

We can also study the maximal rate of complexity growth analytically when α is very large. The simplest case to consider here is $d = 2$ for which the maximum was calculated in appendix A. For example, if we choose $\alpha = L/\delta$, then eq. (A.23) yields

$$\left. \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} \right|_{max} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(1 + \log \left[\frac{1}{2\pi\delta T} \right] \right). \quad (5.3)$$

However, we should also remark that in this instance, the violation is an early time feature, *i.e.*, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ peaks at precisely $\tau = 0$ and the width of the peak is of order β . Hence the averaging discussed above will reduce the excess but it will still remain significant with this extreme choice of α . A similar result holds in higher dimensions. For instance, if we consider the planar uncharged black holes in section 2 with $\alpha = L/\delta$, then the limit $\delta \rightarrow 0$ yields

$$\left. \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} \right|_{max} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \log \left(\frac{d}{4\pi\delta T} \right) + \mathcal{O} \left(\log \left(\log \frac{1}{\delta T} \right) \right), \quad (5.4)$$

for the leading behaviour of the peak of the growth rate. Note that this result reproduces the leading behaviour in eq. (5.3) with $d = 2$.

Having noted that the amount by which $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ exceeds that late time limit is controlled by α , we might add that this produces a finite shift in the complexity. That is comparing the complexity at late times for different choices of α has a rather simple expression

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A(\alpha_1) - \Delta\mathcal{C}_A(\alpha_2) = \frac{S}{2\pi^2} \log(\alpha_1^2/\alpha_2^2). \quad (5.5)$$

That is, the total shift in the complexity caused by the overshoot scales with S , the entanglement entropy between the two CFTs in the thermofield double state (1.1).

³⁴We thank William Cottrell and Miguel Montero for sharing their upcoming work [61] on this subject with us.

The Δ for the complexities in this difference indicates that we are subtracting two copies of the vacuum complexity. This subtraction removes the α dependence of the UV divergent contributions, which is not captured in the time derivative $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$.³⁵ Of course, we should also recall that the total holographic complexity diverges in this late time limit, since it is growing linearly with time.

As we first noted in eq. (2.54), we should choose $\alpha = L/\ell$ in order that our general results for $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ can be fully expressed in terms of boundary quantities. That is, the argument of the logarithm in eq. (2.54) contains an errant factor of the AdS scale, which is not a quantity that the boundary CFT should know about, but this can be eliminated using our freedom in choosing α . However, this choice for α also introduces some new scale ℓ in the boundary theory. It is reassuring that precisely the same situation arises in the UV divergences of holographic complexity [27]. That is, the contributions to the gravitational action coming from the joints where the null boundaries intersect the asymptotic cutoff surface also introduce logarithms where the argument contains the combination L/α , as in eq. (2.54). Of course, choosing $\alpha = L/\ell$ leaves us with the question of what the most appropriate choice for ℓ would be. While the ambiguity left in choosing ℓ may have originally seemed problematic, it was recently found that precisely the same ambiguity appears in complexity models for quantum field theory [11, 12] where the complexity of ground states of free scalar field theories were examined.³⁶ Further let us add that setting $\ell = e^\sigma \delta$, where σ is some numerical factor and δ is the short-distance cutoff in the boundary theory, was a convenient choice because it removed an extra logarithmic factor in the leading UV divergence. However, our results show that with this choice, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ would depend on the short-distance cutoff, *i.e.*, an apparently IR contribution to the complexity would now depend on the UV cutoff.

To close our discussion, we would like to return to our calculations of the complexity of charged AdS black holes. In particular, in section 4 (and appendix D), we found that the complexity of formation diverged for extremal charged black holes. Both these results appeared using either the CA or CV conjectures. We stress that in the complexity of formation, there was still a cancellation of the UV divergences associated with the asymptotic boundary. Instead this divergence was a new IR divergence, associated with the infinitely long throat of the extremal black holes. Further, the results in section 4 indicate that the rate of change of the complexity vanishes for extremal black holes. If one considers the CA predictions, we find that extremal black holes with finite chemical potential has these IR divergences, while systems with zero chemical potential

³⁵From [27], the leading UV behaviour is $[\mathcal{C}_A]_{\text{UV}}(\alpha_1) - [\mathcal{C}_A]_{\text{UV}}(\alpha_2) \simeq -\frac{L^{d-1}}{4\pi^2 G_N} \frac{V}{\delta^{d-1}} \log(\alpha_1^2/\alpha_2^2)$.

³⁶The complexity for a free scalar quantum field theory in the time-dependent thermofield double state, and the similarities and differences with the holographic results presented in this work, will be discussed in [63].

and zero temperature (*i.e.*, extremal hyperbolic black holes without any charge) have finite contributions to the complexity from the IR.³⁷ In order to illustrate these results, figure 15 shows a schematic phase diagram for the hyperbolic black holes for $d = 4$, in terms of the y and z variables introduced in eq. (4.11). There is a line of states at $y = 1$ with finite chemical potential and zero temperature with infinite complexity, while the states with zero chemical potential ends in a point $y = 1, z = \sqrt{2}$ with finite complexity.

Figure 15: Lines of constant μR (dashed blue) and constant TR (dot-dashed red) for the hyperbolic black hole in $d = 4$, with $y = \frac{r_-}{r_+}$ and $z = \frac{L}{r_+}$. The temperature and chemical potential increase as one moves towards the left, as indicated by the arrows. The line of extremal black holes at $y = 1$ with finite chemical potential has states with infinite complexity. However, the extremal black hole represented by the blue dot with coordinates $y = 1, z = \sqrt{2}$ is the small uncharged extremal hyperbolic black hole, with zero chemical potential and finite complexity (using the CA proposal).

Combining these results suggests a ‘Third Law of Complexity’.³⁸ That is, the corresponding ‘extremal’ thermofield double states (4.4) at zero temperature and finite chemical potential are infinitely complex compared to the finite temperature states.

³⁷We might add that using the CV proposal actually yields a similar IR divergence for these black holes [26].

³⁸We thank Henry Maxfield and Robie Hennigar for independently suggesting this connection.

Hence no physical process should be able to produce the extremal states in a finite amount of time. It would be interesting to further test this idea by examining the complexity of extremal spinning black holes [62, 64].

Acknowledgments

We would like to thank Alice Bernamonti, Adam Brown, William Cottrell, Josiah Couch, Bartek Czech, Lorenzo Di-Pietro, Federico Galli, Robie Hennigar, Javier Martinez, Henry Maxfield, Mark Mezei, Miguel Montero, Djordje Radicevic, Dan Roberts, Jamie Sully, Lenny Susskind, Todd Sierens, Brian Swingle, Tadashi Takayanagi and Ying Zhao for useful comments and discussions. We also would like to thank Ipsita Mandal for collaboration on the initial stages of this project. Research at Perimeter Institute is supported by the Government of Canada through Industry Canada and by the Province of Ontario through the Ministry of Research & Innovation. This research was supported in part by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. NSF PHY11-25915. SC acknowledges support from an Israeli Women in Science Fellowship from the Israeli Council of Higher Education. RCM is supported by funding from the Natural Sciences and Engineering Research Council of Canada, from the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research and from the Simons Foundation through the “It from Qubit” collaboration. SS thanks Perimeter Institute for their hospitality during this project. The work of SS is supported in part by the Grant-in-Aid for JSPS Research Fellow, Grant Number JP16J01004.

A Details of Complexity=Action for BTZ Black Holes

In this appendix, we add some more details of the holographic complexity for the BTZ holes, using the complexity=action proposal. Much of these results are already summarized in section 2.3.1. The new results here include the derivation of our results for non-symmetric boundary times $\tau_L \neq \tau_R$ and their generalization for negative times.

A.1 General Boundary Times

We consider the BTZ metric, given in eq. (2.55):

$$ds^2 = -f(r)\frac{L^2}{R^2}d\tau^2 + \frac{dr^2}{f(r)} + r^2d\phi^2, \quad \text{with } f(r) = \frac{r^2 - r_h^2}{L^2}. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

The boundary metric takes the form given in eq. (2.57) and so a constant time slice is simply a circle with circumference $2\pi R$. For general boundary times (τ_L, τ_R) ,³⁹ the

³⁹Here, we do not assume $\tau_L = \tau_R$, but, of course, the result depends only on the total time $\tau = \tau_L + \tau_R$ due to the symmetry of the background.

WDW patch takes the form depicted in figure 16. When the total time $\tau = \tau_L + \tau_R$ is positive $\tau > 0$ (or negative $\tau < 0$), the WDW patch does not reach the past (future) singularity and there is a past (future) corner represented by the dot in figure 16. The radial coordinate r_m of this joint is given by

$$r_m(\tau_L, \tau_R) = r_h \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau_L + \tau_R|}{2LR} = r_h \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR}. \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Figure 16: The WDW patches in the BTZ black hole background. The dashed lines represent the cutoff surfaces. The left (right) panel illustrates the case in which $\tau = \tau_L + \tau_R > 0$ ($\tau = \tau_L + \tau_R < 0$).

The action for the WDW patch consists of a bulk term, surface terms and joint terms, as described in the main text:

$$I_{BTZ} = I_{\text{bulk}} + I_{\text{surf}} + I_{\text{jnt}}. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The bulk term I_{bulk} is given by

$$I_{\text{bulk}} = -\frac{2LR}{G_N \delta} - \frac{r_h^2 |\tau|}{4G_N LR} + \frac{r_m}{2G_N}, \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where we used the cutoff $r = r_{\text{max}} = LR/\delta + r_h^2 \delta/(4LR)$ corresponding to the UV regulator $z = \delta$ in a Fefferman-Graham expansion (see [26]).

As in the text, we choose here an affine parametrization for the null generators. For this reason, the null surface terms vanish. Therefore the only nonvanishing surface

contributions come from the surface at the future singularity and the UV cutoff surfaces. The contribution from the singularity is given by

$$I_{\text{surf},\text{sing}} = \frac{r_h^2 |\tau|}{4G_N LR}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The contribution from the cutoff surfaces is UV-divergent:

$$I_{\text{surf},\text{cut}} = \frac{2LR}{G_N \delta}. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Thus, the total surface term is given by

$$I_{\text{surf}} = \frac{2LR}{G_N \delta} + \frac{r_h^2 |\tau|}{4G_N LR}. \quad (\text{A.7})$$

The normalization of null vectors \mathbf{k}_L and \mathbf{k}_R are set to be the same as in the main text:

$$\mathbf{k}_L \cdot \hat{\tau}_L = \mathbf{k}_R \cdot \hat{\tau}_R = \pm \alpha \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where $\hat{\tau}_L = \partial_{\tau_L}$ and $\hat{\tau}_R = \partial_{\tau_R}$, and the sign is chosen as $+$ ($-$) for future (past) null surfaces. The joint contributions come from joints at $r = r_m$ and at $r = r_{\text{max}}$ and are given by

$$I_{\text{jnt},\text{cut}} = -\frac{LR}{G_N \delta} \log \frac{\alpha \delta}{L}. \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$I_{\text{jnt},r_m} = -\frac{r_m}{4G_N} \log \left| \frac{L^2 f(r_m)}{\alpha^2 R^2} \right| = \frac{r_h}{2G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{r_h} \cosh \frac{r_h \tau}{2LR} \right). \quad (\text{A.10})$$

Therefore, the total action reads

$$\begin{aligned} I_{BTZ} &= I_{\text{bulk}} + I_{\text{surf}} + I_{\text{jnt}} \\ &= \frac{r_h}{2G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[1 + \log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{r_h} \cosh \frac{r_h \tau}{2LR} \right) \right] - \frac{LR}{G_N \delta} \log \frac{\alpha \delta}{L}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

We can regularize it by subtracting twice the action of the WDW patch in the vacuum AdS space, following [26]. If we consider the Neveu–Schwarz vacuum of the boundary theory [44], *i.e.*, with the metric $f_0(r) = r^2/L^2 + 1$, the action of vacuum AdS space is given by a sum of eq. (4.5) of [26] and eqs. (A.6) and (A.9) which remain the same for the empty AdS background (but need to be multiplied by a factor of a half if we consider a single copy of empty AdS). We therefore obtain:

$$I_{AdS} = \frac{\pi L}{4G_N} - \frac{LR}{2G_N \delta} \log \frac{\alpha \delta}{L}. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

The regularized action is then given after the subtraction by:

$$I_{reg}(\tau_L, \tau_R) = I_{BTZ}(\tau_L, \tau_R) - I_{AdS}(\tau_L) - I_{AdS}(\tau_R) \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$= -\frac{\pi L}{2G_N} + \frac{r_h}{2G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[1 + \log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{r_h} \cosh \frac{r_h \tau}{2LR} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{A.14})$$

The finite part of the holographic complexity from the CA conjecture is thus

$$\Delta \mathcal{C}_A(\tau_L, \tau_R) = \frac{I_{reg}}{\pi} = -\frac{L}{2G_N} + \frac{r_h}{2\pi G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[1 + \log \left(\frac{\alpha R}{r_h} \cosh \frac{r_h \tau}{2LR} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

This result can also be written as

$$\Delta \mathcal{C}_A(\tau_L, \tau_R) = -\frac{c}{3} + \frac{2M}{\pi^2 T} \tanh(\pi T |\tau|) \left(1 + \log \left[\frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \cosh(\pi T \tau) \right] \right), \quad (\text{A.16})$$

where c is the central charge of the boundary CFT, given by $c = 3L/(2G_N)$, M is the mass of the BTZ black hole $M = r_h^2/(8G_N LR)$, and T is the temperature $T = r_h/(2\pi LR)$. We can think of this result as the complexity of formation of the thermofield double state, with general times τ_L, τ_R . Note that the temperature should satisfy $T > 1/(2\pi R)$ so that the BTZ black hole is the dominant saddle point for the gravitational theory in the bulk. In order to express $\Delta \mathcal{C}_A$ solely in terms of boundary quantities, choose the normalization constant $\alpha = L/\ell$, where ℓ is a new length scale in the boundary theory, as discussed in section 2.2.1 — see also [27].

The holographic complexity of the AdS vacuum is independent of time and hence taking the derivative of eq. (A.16) with respect to time $\tau = \tau_L + \tau_R$, yields the rate of growth appearing in eq. (2.61)

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(1 + \text{sech}^2(\pi T \tau) \log \left[\frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \cosh(\pi T \tau) \right] \right). \quad (\text{A.17})$$

We are assuming $\tau > 0$ here.

Unlike the higher dimensional case, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is finite at $\tau = 0$.⁴⁰ In fact, we have

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}(\tau \rightarrow 0^+) = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(1 + \log \frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \right). \quad (\text{A.18})$$

At late times, we have

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}(\tau \rightarrow \infty) \sim \frac{2M}{\pi} \left[1 + 4 \left(\pi T \tau + \log \frac{\alpha}{4\pi LT} \right) e^{-2\pi T \tau} + \dots \right]. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

⁴⁰Recall the discussion for higher dimensional black holes around eq. (2.42).

Noting the coefficient of the exponential is positive, we find that it approaches $2M/\pi$ from above. In figure 2, we see that $\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}$ has a maximum at some time τ_{peak} . We can determine the latter by evaluating $\frac{d^2\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau^2}(\tau_{peak}) = 0$ and we find

$$\tau_{peak} = \frac{1}{\pi T} \cosh^{-1} \frac{\sqrt{e} 2\pi LT}{\alpha}. \quad (\text{A.20})$$

At that time, $\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}$ is greater than $2M/\pi$ with,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}(\tau_{peak}) = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2e} \left(\frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \right)^2 \right] > \frac{2M}{\pi}. \quad (\text{A.21})$$

Hence $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ always exceeds the Lloyd bound and further the violation increases for smaller black holes, *i.e.*, smaller temperatures. Substituting the minimum temperature, $T = 1/(2\pi R)$, into eq. (A.21) yields

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}(\tau_{peak}) \Big|_{T=\frac{1}{2\pi R}} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2e} \left(\frac{\alpha R}{L} \right)^2 \right]. \quad (\text{A.22})$$

Note that implicitly the above expressions require $2\pi LT \geq \alpha/\sqrt{e}$. Otherwise the maximum occurs at $\tau = 0$, *i.e.*,

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} \Big|_{max} = \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}(\tau = 0) = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left(1 + \log \left[\frac{\alpha}{2\pi LT} \right] \right) \quad \text{for } 2\pi LT < \alpha/\sqrt{e}. \quad (\text{A.23})$$

We observe, however, that the details of the violation of Lloyd's bound depend on the normalization constant α , *i.e.*, whether or not the violation is large depends crucially on the choice of α .

A.2 Boundary Counterterm

We will now add the boundary counterterm to the action, which was introduced in [25] to make the action invariant under the reparametrizations of null boundaries of the WDW patch. As we see in appendix E.2, the counterterm for the affine parametrization $\lambda = r/\alpha$, which corresponds to the normalization of \mathbf{k}_L and \mathbf{k}_R in the previous subsection A.1, is⁴¹

$$\Delta I_{\Sigma}^{BTZ} = -\frac{1}{G_N} r_{max} \left(\log \frac{r_{max}}{\alpha \tilde{L}} - 1 \right) + \frac{1}{2G_N} r_m \left(\log \frac{r_m}{\alpha \tilde{L}} - 1 \right), \quad (\text{A.24})$$

where \tilde{L} is an arbitrary constant. Similarly the counter term for pure AdS₃ is given by

$$\Delta I_{\Sigma}^{AdS} = -\frac{1}{2G_N} r_{max}^{AdS} \left(\log \frac{r_{max}^{AdS}}{\alpha \tilde{L}} - 1 \right), \quad (\text{A.25})$$

⁴¹This expression holds for the general boundary size $2\pi R$.

where we assume that the arbitrary constant \tilde{L} is the same as that in BTZ. Subtracting this from eq. (A.24), we obtain the regularized counter term

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta I^{reg} &= \Delta I_{\Sigma}^{BTZ} - 2\Delta I_{\Sigma}^{AdS} = \frac{1}{2G_N} r_m \left(\log \frac{r_m}{\alpha \tilde{L}} - 1 \right) \\ &= \frac{r_h}{2G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[\log \left(\frac{r_h}{\alpha \tilde{L}} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \right) - 1 \right].\end{aligned}\quad (\text{A.26})$$

Adding this result to eq. (A.14), the regularized BTZ action with the counter term is given by

$$I_{BTZ} = -\frac{\pi L}{2G_N} + \frac{r_h}{2G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[\log \left(\frac{R}{\tilde{L}} \sinh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \right) \right].\quad (\text{A.27})$$

Note that α -dependence cancels out. We thus obtain the holographic complexity

$$\Delta \mathcal{C}_A(\tau_L, \tau_R) = \frac{I_{BTZ}}{\pi} = -\frac{L}{2G_N} + \frac{r_h}{2\pi G_N} \tanh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \left[\log \left(\frac{R}{\tilde{L}} \sinh \frac{r_h |\tau|}{2LR} \right) \right]\quad (\text{A.28})$$

$$= -\frac{c}{3} + \frac{2M}{\pi^2 T} \tanh(\pi T |\tau|) \left(\log \left[\frac{R}{\tilde{L}} \sinh(\pi T |\tau|) \right] \right).\quad (\text{A.29})$$

Of course, the boundary counterterm introduces a new arbitrary length scale \tilde{L} . Hence we again encounter an ambiguity of the choice of the arbitrary length scale like in the choice of α without the counterterm or the ambiguous factor in the CV conjecture (1.2). The plots of eq. (A.29) for various R/\tilde{L} are shown in figure 17.

Figure 17: Plot of $[\pi/(2M\beta)]\mathcal{C}_A(\tau)$ with $TR = \frac{1}{2\pi}$ for $R/\tilde{L} = 0.5$ (solid blue), $R/\tilde{L} = 1.0$ (dashed red) and $R/\tilde{L} = 2.0$ (dot-dashed green).

The time derivative of the holographic complexity for $\tau > 0$ is

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} = \frac{2M}{\pi} \left[1 + \frac{\log\left(\frac{R}{\tilde{L}} \sinh(\pi T\tau)\right)}{\cosh^2(\pi T\tau)} \right]. \quad (\text{A.30})$$

We show the plots for various choices of \tilde{L} in Fig. 18. Unlike the case without the

Figure 18: Plot of $[\pi/(2M)]d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ for $R/\tilde{L} = 0.5$ (solid blue), $R/\tilde{L} = 1.0$ (dashed red) and $R/\tilde{L} = 2.0$ (dot-dashed green). The curves diverge at $\tau = 0$ and approach to 1 from above at late times.

counter term, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ is divergent at $\tau = 0$ with

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \sim \frac{2M}{\pi} \log[\pi T\tau] \quad \text{for } 0 < T\tau \ll 1. \quad (\text{A.31})$$

This divergence might be comparable to that found for higher dimensional black holes at $t = t_c$, *i.e.*, see eq. (2.42). However, the complexity of formation (A.29) still has a finite value at $\tau = 0$, as

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A(0) = -c/3. \quad (\text{A.32})$$

This matches the complexity of formation for Neveu-Schwarz vacuum found in [26]. At late times, $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ behaves as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} \sim \frac{2M}{\pi} \left[1 + 4 \left(\pi T\tau + \log \frac{R}{2\tilde{L}} \right) e^{-2\pi T\tau} \right]. \quad (\text{A.33})$$

Thus, the rate of growth still approaches the universal limit $2M/\pi$ from above, for any choices of \tilde{L} .

B Additional Examples of Time Dependence of Complexity

In eq. (2.35), we provided a general expression for the time rate of change of the holographic complexity of (neutral) AdS black holes using the CA conjecture. We examined some specific examples in section 2.3 for boundary CFTs with $d = 2$ and 4 — see also appendix A. Further, in eq. (3.13), together with eqs. (3.8) and (3.9), we provided an expression for the rate of change of complexity based on the CV conjecture, and examined numerically the cases of $d = 2$, and planar geometry with $d = 3, 4$ in subsection 3.2. In this appendix, we provide further examples of the time dependence of holographic complexity. We show that qualitatively the holographic complexity behaves in the same way in a different (odd) dimension, namely $d = 3$, using the CA conjecture. We also explore the influence of the choice of horizon geometry on the results of the CV conjecture in $d = 3$ and $d = 4$.

B.1 CA Results in $d = 3$

For the case of $d = 3$, we have the dimensionless tortoise coordinate $x^*(x, RT) = \frac{r_h}{L^2} r^*(r)$, where we have used the definition $x \equiv \frac{r}{r_h}$. This leads to

$$x^*(x, RT) = \frac{1}{\frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3} \left[\log \left[\frac{|x-1|}{\sqrt{\frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} + x^2 + x + 1}} \right] + \frac{\left(\frac{2kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3\right)}{\sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3}} \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{2x+1}{\sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3}} \right] \right], \quad (\text{B.1})$$

and

$$x_\infty^* = \frac{\pi \left(\frac{2kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3\right)}{2 \left(\frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3\right) \sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3}}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

We can evaluate the critical time τ_c using eq. (2.48). This leads to

$$\tau_c = \frac{1}{4\pi T \sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3}} \left[\sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3} \log \left(\frac{kL^2}{r_h^2} + 1 \right) + \left(\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 6 \right) \tan^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{4kL^2}{r_h^2} + 3} \right) \right]. \quad (\text{B.3})$$

We can apply these results to evaluate the rate of change of holographic complexity for spherical, planar and large hyperbolic black holes. By large hyperbolic black holes, we mean that $r_h/L \geq 1$ which implies that the mass is positive. Actually, we assumed here that $r_h > 2L/\sqrt{3}$ for the hyperbolic case with $k = -1$. In the regime $L \leq r_h \leq 2L/\sqrt{3}$, $f(r)$ has two additional negative real roots. While these do not indicate the existence of additional horizons, the tortoise coordinate is modified in this case and takes the

Figure 19: Critical time as a function of the horizon radius for $d = 3$ for the various geometries – spherical $k = 1$ (blue, solid), planar $k = 0$ (red, dashed) and large hyperbolic $k = -1$, $r_h > L$ (green, dot-dashed).

form

$$x^*(x, RT) = \frac{1}{3 - \frac{L^2}{r_h^2}} \log \left(\frac{|x-1|}{\sqrt{-\frac{L^2}{r_h^2} + x^2 + x + 1}} \right) - \frac{\left(3 - \frac{2L^2}{r_h^2}\right)}{\left(3 - \frac{L^2}{r_h^2}\right) \sqrt{\frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} - 3}} \coth^{-1} \left(\frac{2x+1}{\sqrt{\frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} - 3}} \right) \quad (\text{B.4})$$

and the critical time for the hyperbolic black holes in this mass range reads

$$\tau_c = \frac{1}{4\pi T \sqrt{\frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} - 3}} \left(\sqrt{\frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} - 3} \log \left(1 - \frac{L^2}{r_h^2} \right) + \left(6 - \frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} \right) \tanh^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{4L^2}{r_h^2} - 3} \right) \right). \quad (\text{B.5})$$

We present a plot of $\tau_c T$ as a function of the horizon radius in figure 19.

After solving numerically for x_m , the results are presented in figure 20 for $k = 0, 1$, and in figure 21 for $k = -1$. The overall behaviour of the rate of change of complexity is very similar to the results shown in figure 4 for spherical and planar black holes in $d = 4$. We also present the integrated complexity in figures 22 and 23 to demonstrate that there is no divergence near $\tau = \tau_c$. That is, these figures show $\mathcal{C}_A(\tau) - \mathcal{C}_A(\tau_c) = \int_{\tau_c}^{\tau} d\tau \frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau}$. Even though $d\mathcal{C}_A/d\tau$ diverges at the critical time (see eq. (2.42)), it is an integrable singularity and the complexity itself only shows a mild variation at this point. We have also included as the integration constant $\mathcal{C}_A(\tau_c)$ the complexity of formation, see [26]. Recall that the complexity of formation is given by the complexity of the thermofield double state minus twice that of the vacuum state of the CFT, and so presents a natural finite value for the complexity for $|\tau| < \tau_c$. Again we found similar results for $d = 4$, although we do not explicitly show the corresponding figures here.

Figure 20: Time derivative of complexity as a function of time for spherical (left) and planar (right) geometries in $d = 3$ boundary dimensions for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h = L$ (solid blue), $r_h = 1.5L$ (dashed red), $r_h = 3.5L$ (dot-dashed green). We present the plot as a function of the time coordinate in units of the thermal scale $\delta\tau T = (\tau - \tau_c)T$. We stress again that the complexity starts changing at τ_c and each of the curves presented has a different value of τ_c . For these parameters, the violation of the late time bound is clearly manifest.

Figure 21: Time derivative of complexity as a function of time for large hyperbolic black holes ($r_h > L$) in $d = 3$ boundary dimensions for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h = 1.1L$ (blue), $r_h = 1.5L$ (dashed red), $r_h = 3.5L$ (dot-dashed green). We present the plot as a function of the time coordinate in units of the thermal scale $\delta\tau T = (\tau - \tau_c)T$. We stress again that the complexity starts changing at τ_c and each of the curves presented has a different value of τ_c . For these parameters, the violation of the late time bound is clearly manifested.

Figure 22: Integrated complexity as a function of time for spherical (left) and planar (right) geometries in $d = 3$ boundary dimensions for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h = L$ (solid blue), $r_h = 1.5L$ (dashed red), $r_h = 3.5L$ (dot-dashed green). We see that it does not diverge at $\tau = \tau_c$ ($\delta\tau = 0$). The value at $\delta\tau = 0$ has been set according to the complexity of formation, see [26].

Figure 23: Integrated complexity as a function of time for large hyperbolic black holes in $d = 3$ boundary dimensions for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h = 1.1L$ (blue), $r_h = 1.5L$ (dashed red), $r_h = 3.5L$ (dot-dashed green). We see that it does not diverge at $\tau = \tau_c$ ($\delta\tau = 0$). The value at $\delta\tau = 0$ has been set according to the complexity of formation, see [26].

B.2 CV Results for Other Geometries

To complete the picture of the time dependence, we also give some examples of the results of the complexity=volume conjecture for the other geometries (*i.e.*, spherical and hyperbolic horizons) in $d = 3$ and $d = 4$ in figures 24 and 25.

Figure 24: Plots of $\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} d\mathcal{C}_V/dt$ for spherical black holes ($k = 1$) for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h/L = 1$ (blue), $r_h/L = 2$ (yellow), $r_h/L = 5$ (green). At late times, they approach to the asymptotic values indicated in figure 6a. The asymptotic value at late times is always smaller than 1 and approaches to 1 for large black holes. We can also see that the asymptotic value is always approached from below.

Figure 25: Plots of $\frac{d-1}{8\pi(M-M_{min})} d\mathcal{C}_V/dt$ for hyperbolic black holes ($k = -1$) for various values of the horizon radius – $r_h/L = 1$ (blue), $r_h/L = 2$ (yellow), $r_h/L = 5$ (green). Recall that M_{min} was introduced to avoid divergences as the mass takes both positive and negative values, see eq. (3.24) and the explanation above it. The asymptotic values at late times are greater than 1 for small black holes and approach to 1 for large black holes. The asymptotic value is always approached from below.

C Late Time Behaviour for the CV Proposal

In this appendix, we provide further details with regards to the late time growth of the holographic complexity, using the CV proposal. In particular, we will determine the leading correction of the late time behaviour of $d\mathcal{C}_V/dt$ given in eq. (3.22).

Eq. (3.9) determines r_{min} as a function of t . Using the function $W(r)$ in eq. (3.16), eq. (3.9) can be written as

$$\frac{t}{2} = - \int_{r_{min}}^{\infty} dr \frac{W(r_{min})}{f(r) \sqrt{-W(r)^2 + W(r_{min})^2}}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

Noting that $\frac{d}{dr}[W(r)^2 - W(r_{min})^2]_{r=r_{min}}$ vanishes at $r_{min} = \tilde{r}_{min}$, we introduce a function $Y(r; r_t, \tilde{r}_{min})$ defined as⁴²

$$W(r_{min}) - W(r) \equiv (r - r_{min})(r - 2\tilde{r}_{min} + r_{min})Y(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}). \quad (\text{C.2})$$

We then have

$$Y(r_{min}; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}) = -\frac{W'(r_{min})}{2(r_{min} - \tilde{r}_{min})}, \quad Y(\tilde{r}_{min}; \tilde{r}_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}) = -\frac{1}{2}W''(\tilde{r}_{min}). \quad (\text{C.3})$$

Separating the integrand in eq. (C.1) as follows

$$\begin{aligned} & -\frac{W(r_{min})}{f(r) \sqrt{-W(r)^2 + W(r_{min})^2}} \\ &= \frac{-\sqrt{W(r_{min})}r_{min}}{f(r_{min})r \sqrt{2(r - r_{min})(r - 2\tilde{r}_{min} + r_{min})}Y(r_{min}; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})} + j(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.4})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} j(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}) &\equiv -\sqrt{W(r_{min})} \\ &\times \left(\frac{f(r_{min})\sqrt{2W(r_{min})}Y(r_{min}; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})r - f(r)\sqrt{[W(r) + W(r_{min})]Y(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})r_{min}}}{f(r_{min})f(r)r\sqrt{2[W(r) + W(r_{min})]}(r - r_{min})(r - 2\tilde{r}_{min} + r_{min})Y(r_{min}; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})Y(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{C.5})$$

eq. (C.1) becomes⁴³

$$\frac{t}{2} = \frac{r_{min}^{2d-3/2} \log\left(\frac{\tilde{r}_{min} + \sqrt{r_{min}(2m-r_{min})}}{r_{min} - \tilde{r}_{min}}\right)}{W(r_{min})^{\frac{3}{2}} \sqrt{2(2\tilde{r}_{min} - r_{min})}Y(r_{min}; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})} + \int_{r_{min}}^{\infty} dr j(r; r_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}). \quad (\text{C.6})$$

We then set

$$\frac{r_{min}}{\tilde{r}_{min}} = 1 + e^{-\frac{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})} \frac{t}{2}}{\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-2}}} [c_1 + \epsilon(t)], \quad (\text{C.7})$$

⁴²This decomposition makes transparent the fact that the denominator of the integral (C.1) has generally an order one root, while for $r_{min} = \tilde{r}_{min}$, it has a root of order 2.

⁴³Again, we note that the second integral would have a pole at $r = r_h$ and what is actually meant by it is to subtract this pole as described in section 3.

where c_1 is a constant and $\epsilon(t)$ is a function which goes to zero as $t \rightarrow \infty$. Inserting this form into (C.6) and taking the limit $t \rightarrow \infty$, we obtain

$$0 = \frac{\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-3/2}}{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})}} \log \frac{2}{c_1} + J(\tilde{r}_{min}), \quad (\text{C.8})$$

where $J(\tilde{r}_{min})$ is a finite function

$$J(\tilde{r}_{min}) \equiv \int_{\tilde{r}_{min}}^{\infty} dr j(r; \tilde{r}_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}). \quad (\text{C.9})$$

In fact, the integrand $j(r; \tilde{r}_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min})$ is harmless around $r \sim \tilde{r}_{min}$ and $r \sim \infty$ because it behaves as

$$j(r; \tilde{r}_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}) \sim \tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-1} \frac{[-6(2d-1)W''(\tilde{r}_{min}) + W'''(\tilde{r}_{min})\tilde{r}_{min}]}{6[-W(\tilde{r}_{min})W''(\tilde{r}_{min})]^{\frac{3}{2}}} + \mathcal{O}(r - \tilde{r}_{min}), \quad (\text{C.10})$$

$$j(r; \tilde{r}_{min}, \tilde{r}_{min}) \sim -\frac{\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-1}}{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})}} \frac{1}{r^2} + \mathcal{O}(r^{-3}), \quad (\text{C.11})$$

and thus $J(\tilde{r}_{min})$ is finite.⁴⁴ Therefore, the late time behaviour of r_{min} is given by

$$r_{min} = \tilde{r}_{min} \left[1 + 2e^{-\frac{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})}}{2\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-2}}(t-2J(\tilde{r}_{min}))} + \epsilon(t) \right]. \quad (\text{C.12})$$

Using eq. (3.17) the coefficient of t is computed as

$$-\frac{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})}}{2\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-2}} = -\frac{\sqrt{-f(\tilde{r}_{min}) \left[(d-1)(d-2)k + d\frac{\tilde{r}_{min}^2}{L^2} \right]}}{2\tilde{r}_{min}}. \quad (\text{C.13})$$

In particular for planar black holes (*i.e.*, $k = 0$), inserting the analytical expression of \tilde{r}_{min} in eq. (3.20) the coefficient is given by

$$-\frac{\sqrt{-W(\tilde{r}_{min})^3 W''(\tilde{r}_{min})}}{2\tilde{r}_{min}^{2d-2}} = -\frac{d r_h}{2^{1+\frac{1}{d}} L^2} = -2^{-\frac{1}{d}} \frac{2\pi}{\beta}, \quad (\text{C.14})$$

and the rate of change in complexity follows from eq. (3.18) and eq. (C.12). One can find that the late time behaviour is given by

$$\frac{d-1}{8\pi M} \frac{d\mathcal{C}_V}{dt} = 1 - 2d^2 e^{-2^{1-\frac{1}{d}} \frac{2\pi}{\beta} (t-2J(\tilde{r}_{min}))} + \dots, \quad (\text{C.15})$$

where the dots stand for corrections which decay faster at late times than the leading exponential in eq. (C.15).

⁴⁴The integrand also has a pole at $r = r_h$ but it can be cured as discussed in section 3.

D Complexity of Formation for Charged Black Holes

In this appendix, we evaluate the complexity of formation for charged black holes. The complexity of formation for uncharged black holes was examined in detail in [26]. There, the complexity of formation is defined as the additional complexity involved in preparing two copies of the boundary CFT in the entangled thermofield double state (1.1) (evaluated at $t_L = t_R = 0$) compared to preparing each of the CFTs in their vacuum state. Using the CA proposal,⁴⁵ the bulk calculation consists of evaluating the gravitational action for the WDW patch (anchored at $t_L = t_R = 0$) in the (neutral) AdS black hole background and subtracting twice the action for the WDW in an appropriate vacuum of AdS space. A key aspect of this subtraction is that all of the UV (large r) divergences cancel, which as a consequence leaves a UV finite result.

Hence in the present charged case, the first question to settle is what is the appropriate reference state to compare to the charged thermofield double state (4.4). Here we recall that it was shown in [47] that at zero temperature and with a spherical boundary, the ground state for the fixed chemical potential ensemble is pure AdS for $\mu < \frac{gL}{2R\sqrt{2\pi G}}\sqrt{\frac{(d-1)}{(d-2)}}$ and an extremal black hole of the same chemical potential for $\mu > \frac{gL}{2R\sqrt{2\pi G}}\sqrt{\frac{(d-1)}{(d-2)}}$. It was also noted there that this extremal black hole may be unstable and decay by the emission of charged particles. For the planar boundary geometry (*i.e.*, $k = 0$) and the hyperbolic one (*i.e.*, $k = -1$), the ground state is always the extremal black hole.

Hence in evaluating the complexity of formation for the charged thermofield double state, one suggestion is to subtract the holographic complexity corresponding to an extremal black hole with the same chemical potential [8]. However, we find that the holographic complexity for an extremal black hole contains an additional infrared divergence and hence a meaningful comparison cannot be achieved by comparing a charged black hole to the corresponding extremal one. We will see that this IR divergence appears for both the CA and the CV conjectures. Therefore, we simply choose the uncharged vacuum ($\omega = q = 0$) as our reference state, *i.e.*, we subtract the holographic complexity of two copies of the corresponding AdS vacuum.

As in section 4, it is convenient to work with the dimensionless variables introduced in eq. (4.11). Recall

$$x \equiv \frac{r}{r_+}, \quad y \equiv \frac{r_-}{r_+}, \quad z \equiv \frac{L}{r_+}. \quad (4.11)$$

The first is a dimensionless radial coordinate, while the latter two can be defined in terms of boundary quantities, as in eq. (4.12). Further, in the following, we will focus

⁴⁵Of course, an analogous calculation can also be performed using the CV proposal — see below.

on the case of $d = 4$, where that latter expressions are explicitly given in eq. (4.29). In principle then, we can invert these formula to write our results in terms of the boundary quantities, $\nu = \sqrt{C_J/C_T} \mu/T$ and RT . In the planar geometry, *i.e.*, $k = 0$, for $d = 4$ eq. (4.29) reads

$$\nu = \sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}} \frac{\mu}{T} = \frac{3\pi}{\sqrt{10}} \frac{y\sqrt{y^2+1}}{(1-y^2)(2+y^2)}, \quad RT = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{(1-y^2)(2+y^2)}{z}. \quad (\text{D.1})$$

Then the first of these equations can be inverted to obtain

$$y^2 = \frac{\sqrt{3}\sqrt{15\nu^2 - \pi\sqrt{80\nu^2 + 9\pi^2} + 3\pi^2}}{2\sqrt{5}\nu} - \frac{1}{2} \quad (\text{D.2})$$

and for the second, we may write

$$z = \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{(1-y^2(\nu))(2+y^2(\nu))}{RT}. \quad (\text{D.3})$$

D.1 Complexity=Action

Using the CA proposal, the complexity of formation is given by:

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{1}{\pi} [\Delta I_{\text{bulk}} + I_{\text{jnt}}] \quad (\text{D.4})$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta I_{\text{bulk}} = & \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{2\pi G_N} \int_{r_m}^{r_{\text{max}}} \left(-\frac{d}{L^2} + \frac{q^2(d-2)}{r^{2(d-1)}} \right) r^{d-1} (r_{\infty}^* - r^*(r)) dr \\ & + \frac{d\Omega_{k,d-1}}{2\pi G_N L^2} \int_0^{r_{\text{max}}^{\text{vac}}} r^{d-1} (r_{\infty,\text{vac}}^* - r_{\text{vac}}^*(r)) dr \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.5})$$

and

$$I_{\text{jnt}} = -\frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N} r_m^{d-1} \log \frac{L^2 |f(r_m)|}{R^2 \alpha^2}. \quad (\text{D.6})$$

The meeting point r_m is obtained by numerically solving (4.20) for $\tau = 0$, *i.e.*,

$$r^*(r_m) = r_{\infty}^*. \quad (\text{D.7})$$

Note that here the future and past meeting points are at the same value of the radial coordinate, *i.e.*, $r_m^1 = r_m^2 = r_m$. Further, r_{max} corresponds to the UV cutoff $z = \delta$ in the Fefferman-Graham expansion of the respective metric.

D.1.1 Planar $d = 4$

We proceed by analyzing charged planar black holes. Recall that with $q = 0$, the planar black holes produced $\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = S/(2\pi)$ where S is the entanglement entropy of the thermofield double state (1.1) [26]. For the curved horizons, there were curvature corrections to this simple result, proportional to inverse powers of RT . Below, we will find that this expression receives corrections even with $k = 0$ in the charged case. Since the curvature vanishes, all of the nontrivial behaviour comes from the finite chemical potential.

As before, we redefine the tortoise coordinate (2.6) in terms of dimensionless variables

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{f}(x, y) &\equiv z^2 f(r) = \frac{(x^2 - 1)(x - y)(x + y)(x^2 + y^2 + 1)}{x^4} \\ x^*(x, y) &\equiv \frac{r^*(r)}{z^2 r_+} = \int^x \frac{dx}{\tilde{f}(x, y)} = \frac{y^3}{4y^4 - 2y^2 - 2} \log \frac{|x - y|}{x + y} \\ &\quad - \frac{1}{2(y^4 + y^2 - 2)} \log \frac{|x - 1|}{x + 1} + \frac{(y^2 + 1)^{3/2}}{2y^4 + 5y^2 + 2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{y^2 + 1}} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.8})$$

This allows us to rewrite eq. (D.7) for the meeting points as

$$x^*(x_m, y) = x_\infty^* = \frac{\pi (y^2 + 1)^{3/2}}{4y^4 + 10y^2 + 4} \quad (\text{D.9})$$

where $x_m \equiv r_m/r_+$. Given eq. (D.2), we see that x_m is a function of ν only.

There is a subtlety in numerically solving for the meeting point for small values of the charge. The reason is that r_- approaches zero as $r_-^{d-2} = q^2/\omega^{d-2}$ and the tortoise coordinate peaks very sharply around r_- . The meeting point equation $r_\infty^* = r^*(r_m)$ solves for the point in which the asymptotic value of the tortoise coordinate intersects back with the curve. As a consequence of the special form of the curve for small values of r_- , this happens very close to r_- . In fact, in the limit that r_- (or equivalently y) approaches zero, the meeting point can be approximated by (see eq. (4.37) with $\tau = 0$ and $k = 0$):

$$x_m = y \left(1 + \exp \left(-\frac{\pi}{2y^3} + \mathcal{O} \left(\frac{1}{y} \right) \right) \right). \quad (\text{D.10})$$

This means that the corner contribution is nonvanishing in the $r_- \rightarrow 0$ limit despite the fact that r_m approaches zero. In our plots, we have used similar approximations for the cases of small ν .

Motivated by the results of [26] for the neutral case, we will be interested in evaluating the ratio of complexity of formation over entropy. Using eq. (D.4) we find

$$\frac{\Delta\mathcal{C}_{\text{form}}}{S} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left[\frac{\Delta I_{\text{bulk}}}{S} + \frac{I_{\text{jnt}}}{S} \right] \quad (\text{D.11})$$

where

$$\frac{\Delta I_{\text{bulk}}}{S} = \frac{8}{\pi} \frac{x_{\text{max}}^3}{3} + \int_{x_m}^{x_{\text{max}}} \frac{4}{\pi x^3} (-2x^6 + y^4 + y^2) (x_{\infty}^* - x^*(x, y)) dx \quad (\text{D.12})$$

and

$$\frac{I_{\text{jnt}}}{S} = -\frac{x_m^{d-1}}{\pi} \log \frac{r_+^2 |\tilde{f}(x_m, y)|}{R^2 \alpha^2} = -\frac{x_m^{d-1}}{\pi} \log \left| \frac{g_2(x_m, y) L^2 T^2}{\alpha^2} \right|, \quad (\text{D.13})$$

where we have defined

$$g_2(x, y) = \frac{4\pi^2 (x^2 - 1) (x^2 - y^2) (x^2 + y^2 + 1)}{x^4 (y^2 - 1)^2 (y^2 + 2)^2} \quad (\text{D.14})$$

and the planar black hole complexity of formation is regularized at infinity by subtracting two copies of the vacuum [26]. A meaningful comparison between the two spacetimes is achieved by placing the cutoff at $x_{\text{max}} \equiv r_{\text{max}}/r_+$ corresponding to $z = \delta$ in the Fefferman-Graham expansion of the respective metric (see *e.g.*, appendix A of [26]). We see that the complexity of formation can be naturally split into a sum of two functions

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A \equiv \frac{S}{2\pi} \left(F(\nu) + G(\nu) \log \left(\frac{T^2 L^2}{\alpha^2} \right) \right), \quad (\text{D.15})$$

where S is the entropy of the charged AdS black hole, given in eq. (4.5); and $F(\nu)$ and $G(\nu)$ are universal functions that depend only on the ratio ν through their dependence on y as follows

$$\begin{aligned} G(\nu) = G(y) &= -\frac{2}{\pi} x_m^{d-1}, \\ F(\nu) = F(y) &= -\frac{2}{\pi} x_m^{d-1} \log |g_2(x_m, y)| + \frac{16}{\pi} \frac{x_{\text{max}}^3}{3} \\ &\quad - \int_{x_m}^{x_{\text{max}}} \frac{8}{\pi x^3} (2x^6 - y^4 - y^2) (x_{\infty}^* - x^*(x, y)) dx. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.16})$$

We note that our result for the complexity of formation depends on the arbitrary parameter α associated to the normalization of null normals. The two functions $G(\nu)$ and $F(\nu)$ are shown in figure 26 as a function of $\nu = \sqrt{\frac{C_I}{C_T} \frac{\mu}{T}}$. Note that in the limit $\nu \rightarrow 0$, the complexity of formation agrees with the uncharged result found in [26], *i.e.*, $F(\nu \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow 1$ and $G(\nu \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow 0$.

Figure 26: The functions $F(\nu)$ and $G(\nu)$ defined in eq. (D.16) which appear in the complexity of formation (D.15) for charged planar AdS₅ black holes as a function of $\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{C_J \mu}{C_T T}}$.

As we showed in section 4, we can write an expansion of the complexity of formation for small charge as an expansion in the parameter y , which reads

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{S}{2\pi} \left(1 + \left(\frac{20}{3\pi} + \frac{4}{\pi} \log \left[\frac{yz \alpha R}{2L} \right] \right) y^3 + \dots \right). \quad (4.15)$$

In order to probe the limit of extremal black holes, *i.e.*, $T \rightarrow 0$ with μ finite, we investigate eq. (D.15) in this limit. The result is divergent in the $T \rightarrow 0$ limit. To see this we use the expansion for x_m near extremality

$$x_m = 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{7}{12} \epsilon^2 \log \epsilon - \frac{8\sqrt{2}\pi + 3 + 28 \log(2) - 16\sqrt{2} \cot^{-1}\sqrt{2}}{24} \epsilon^2 + \dots, \quad (D.17)$$

where we have defined $y \equiv 1 - \epsilon$, and evaluate the complexity of formation

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_A = \frac{2S}{\pi^2} \left(\log \left(\frac{\alpha}{LT} \right) + \frac{1}{3} - \log \left(\frac{\pi}{\sqrt{3}} \right) + \mathcal{O}(RT \log RT) \right). \quad (D.18)$$

Note that the limit $RT \rightarrow 0$ corresponds to the limit $\nu \rightarrow \infty$, so the correction, where we have left implicit a function of z , is in fact a function of ν only. We find that the result diverges logarithmically at low temperatures and the coefficient of the logarithmic divergence is proportional to the entanglement entropy of the system. The result also depends on the arbitrary length scale $\ell \equiv L/\alpha$ associated to the normalization of null normals. We will see in the next subsection that a similar divergence at low temperatures appears using the CV conjecture.

D.1.2 Spherical $d = 4$

The calculation of the complexity of formation for spherical charged black holes follows closely the one of the planar case. However, the two contributions from eq. (D.4) need to be evaluated using the appropriate blackening factor (4.2) with $k = 1$. We show the results for $d = 4$ in figure 27 and note that again the complexity of formation diverges in the low temperature (near extremal) limit.

As in the planar case, we can find the leading behaviour when RT is small. The expansion for the meeting point reads

$$x_m = 1 - \frac{\epsilon}{2} + \frac{(3z^2 + 7) \epsilon^2 \log(\epsilon)}{4z^2 + 12} - \frac{\epsilon^2 \left(z^2(1 + 12 \log(2)) + 8(z^2 + 2)^{3/2} \tan^{-1}(\sqrt{z^2 + 2}) + 3 + 28 \log(2) \right)}{8(z^2 + 3)} + \mathcal{O}(\epsilon^3 \log \epsilon) \quad (\text{D.19})$$

and that of the complexity of formation

$$\Delta C_A = \frac{S}{3\pi^2(3 + z^2)} \left(-9(z^2 + 2) \log\left(\frac{\pi RT z}{z^2 + 3}\right) - 3(z^2 + 3) \log\left(\frac{L^2(z^2 + 3)}{\alpha^2 R^2 z^2}\right) + z^2 \log 64 \right. \\ \left. + (z^2 + 3) (3(\pi z - 2)z^2 + 2) - 6z^2 (z^2 + 2)^{3/2} \tan^{-1}(\sqrt{z^2 + 2}) + \mathcal{O}(RT \log RT) \right). \quad (\text{D.20})$$

Notice that as $z \rightarrow 0$, we recover the planar result in eq. (D.18). However, unlike in the planar case, now the overall coefficient that controls the divergence for small temperatures depends on z , which in turn depends on the product of the boundary size and the chemical potential. The exact relation is obtained from eq. (4.29), which leads to the relation

$$z = \frac{3\sqrt{2}}{\sqrt{40 \left(\sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}} \mu R \right)^2 - 9}}. \quad (\text{D.21})$$

where C_J and C_T are the coefficients in the two point function of stress tensors or currents, respectively, see eq. (4.10). The value of chemical potential for which z becomes imaginary in this expression exactly matches the value for which the extremal black holes cease to exist (see discussion at the beginning of this appendix). We stress once more that the conclusion that the complexity of formation diverges in the zero temperature limit holds also in the spherical geometry.

It is also interesting to write the first few terms in a small charge (small y) expansion. In fact, we will also expand our results for small z (large temperatures). In order to compare the results for charged black holes to those of neutral black holes found

Figure 27: Complexity of formation for spherical charged black holes in $d = 4$. In the left panel, we fix $RT = \frac{1}{2}$ and we show the dependence on the dimensionless boundary quantity ν . In the right panel, we fix the quantity $\sqrt{\frac{C_J}{C_T}}\mu R = \nu RT = 1$ and show the dependence on RT .

in [26], we express the result of [26] for spherical neutral black holes in $d = 4$, as an expansion in small z , (large horizon radius)

$$\left. \frac{\Delta\mathcal{C}_A}{S} \right|_{\mu=0} = \frac{1}{2\pi} + \frac{z^3}{\pi} - \frac{9z^4}{16\pi} + \mathcal{O}(z^6) = \frac{1}{2\pi} + \frac{1}{\pi^4} \frac{1}{(TR)^3} - \frac{9}{16\pi^5} \frac{1}{(TR)^4} + \mathcal{O}\left(\frac{1}{(TR)^6}\right). \quad (\text{D.22})$$

The dependence on z^3 in the expansion comes from the vacuum contribution to the complexity of formation for the spherical geometry, as can be seen from the $L^3 \delta_{k,1}$ dependence in equation (3.14) in [26]. For charged black holes, a double expansion in y and z reads

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\Delta\mathcal{C}_A}{S} &= \left(\frac{1}{2\pi} + \frac{z^3}{\pi} - \frac{9z^4}{16\pi} \right) - \left(\frac{9z^2}{8\pi} - \frac{3z^4}{16\pi} \right) y^2 \\ &+ \left(\frac{2}{3\pi^2} \left(5 + 3 \log \frac{R\alpha y z}{2L} \right) - \frac{z^2}{\pi^2} + \frac{z^4}{2\pi^2} \right) y^3 + \mathcal{O}(z^5, y^4). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.23})$$

We see by comparing this expression to (D.22) that the neutral limit is recovered in the zero charge limit $y \rightarrow 0$.

D.2 Complexity=Volume

In this subsection, we examine the complexity of formation evaluated using the CV conjecture. For simplicity, we will only consider planar (*i.e.*, $k = 0$) charged black holes in $d = 4$. The complexity of formation is then given by the following integrals:

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{2\Omega_{0,3}}{G_N L} \left[\int_{r_+}^{r_{\max}} \frac{r^3 dr}{\sqrt{f(r)}} - \int_0^{r_{\max}} \frac{r^3 dr}{\sqrt{f_0(r)}} \right], \quad (\text{D.24})$$

where $f(r)$ is the blackening factor (4.2) with $k = 0$, and $f_0(r) = r^2/L^2$ is the corresponding ‘blackening’ factor for empty AdS space. Using eqs. (4.11) and (D.8) we can perform a change of variables in (D.24) to the dimensionless coordinate x and then decompose the integration region for $x < 1$ and $x > 1$ which reads

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_V = 8S \left[\int_1^\infty \left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{\tilde{f}(x,y)}} - 1 \right) x^2 dx - \frac{1}{3} \right]. \quad (\text{D.25})$$

To evaluate the remaining integral, it is useful to perform the following change of variables:

$$x^2 = \frac{1}{u} + 1 \quad (\text{D.26})$$

and the integral can be evaluated explicitly yielding

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{8(y^4 + y^2 + 1)}{3\sqrt{y^2 + 2}} S K \left(\frac{2y^2 + 1}{y^2 + 2} \right) \quad (\text{D.27})$$

where K is the complete elliptic integral of the first kind and y can be expressed in terms of the boundary quantity ν using eq. (D.2).

There are two interesting limits to explore. The small charge limit $\nu \rightarrow 0$ and the near extremal limit $\nu \rightarrow \infty$. In the small charge limit, an expansion of eq. (D.27) reads:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\mathcal{C}_V = S \left(\frac{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(-\frac{3}{4})}{\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})} + \frac{5}{9\pi^{3/2}} \left(\frac{4\Gamma(\frac{1}{4})}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{4})} - \frac{\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})}{\Gamma(\frac{5}{4})} \right) \nu^2 \right. \\ \left. + \frac{100(7\sqrt{2}\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})\Gamma(\frac{3}{4})\Gamma(\frac{7}{4}) - 12\pi\Gamma(\frac{5}{4}))}{81\pi^{9/2}\Gamma(\frac{7}{4})} \nu^4 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.28})$$

Note that the leading term above matches the complexity of formation given in eq. (5.8) of [26] for a planar neutral black hole in $d = 4$. A near extremal (small temperature, or equivalently in the planar case, large $\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{C_I \mu}{C_T T}}$) expansion reads:

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_V = \frac{4S}{\sqrt{3}} \log \left(\frac{48\sqrt{5}\nu}{\pi} \right) - \frac{\pi S}{3\sqrt{15}\nu} \left(1 + 9 \log \left(\frac{48\sqrt{5}\nu}{\pi} \right) \right) + \dots, \quad (\text{D.29})$$

and we see that the complexity of formation is logarithmically divergent at extremality. This is similar to what we found using the action conjecture, see eq. (D.18). The reason for the divergence is easily understood looking back at the integral in eq. (D.25) and the definition of $\tilde{f}(x,y)$ in eq. (D.8). In the near extremal limit $\nu \rightarrow \infty$, the function $\tilde{f}(x,y)$ has two zeros in the neighborhood of $x = 1$ namely

$$x_1 = 1, \quad x_2 = y = 1 - \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{5}\nu} + \dots \quad (\text{D.30})$$

and so we are approximately integrating $1/(x-1)$ all the way to $x=1$.

The full ν dependence of the complexity of formation is presented in figures 28 and 29 with two possible normalizations. First, we define

$$\Delta\mathcal{C}_S = \frac{2\sqrt{\pi}\Gamma(-\frac{3}{4})}{\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})} S \quad (\text{D.31})$$

as a natural normalization to $\Delta\mathcal{C}_V$ where S in this expression denotes the entropy of the charged black hole. Another potential normalization is the corresponding complexity of formation of a neutral black hole with the same temperature. Expressing the latter in terms of ν , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\mathcal{C}_0 &= \frac{\Gamma(-\frac{3}{4})}{\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})} \frac{\pi^6 \sqrt{\pi}}{10} V C_T T^3 = -\frac{\sqrt{\pi} (y^4 + y^2 - 2)^3 \Gamma(-\frac{3}{4})}{4\Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})} S \\ &= \frac{27\pi^{7/2} (\sqrt{80\nu^2 + 9\pi^2} - 3\pi)^3 \Gamma(-\frac{3}{4})}{32000\nu^6 \Gamma(-\frac{1}{4})} S = \frac{27\pi^3 (\sqrt{80\nu^2 + 9\pi^2} - 3\pi)^3}{64000\nu^6} \Delta\mathcal{C}_S \end{aligned} \quad (\text{D.32})$$

where $V = \Omega_{k,d-1} R^3$ and again y was expressed in terms of ν using eq. (D.2).

The results are very similar to what we found with the CA conjecture, see *e.g.*, figure 9 and the expansions in eqs. (4.15) and (D.18). The logarithmic divergence for near extremal black holes is present using both the CA and the CV conjectures, however the additional scale in the logarithm governing the divergence is now μ rather than α/L the extra scale in the boundary theory introduced there by the choice of normalization of the null normals. Just like for the CA conjecture, here as well the neutral result is recovered in the limit of vanishing chemical potential.

D.3 Small Hyperbolic Black Holes

We briefly comment below on the time evolution of uncharged small hyperbolic black holes. For hyperbolic black holes with $r_h < L$, the mass parameter is negative, as can be seen from eqs. (2.3) and (2.4). In this case, the causal structure changes, with the appearance of an inner Cauchy horizon, and becomes similar to the one of charged black holes, as in figure 8. As was already pointed out in appendix [C.3] of [26], the CA calculation indicates that for small uncharged hyperbolic black holes the complexity does not change with time. In this subsection, we present an alternative argument for that statement using the neutral limit of charged black holes.

Consider the late time limit of the rate of change in complexity in eq. (4.28). In general, the zero charge limit is obtained by the requirement that the chemical potential vanishes. For small hyperbolic black holes, this limit does not coincide with the one in which the variable y vanishes. The expression for the chemical potential in general d

Figure 28: Complexity of formation from the CV conjecture normalized by $\Delta\mathcal{C}_S$ for planar ($k = 0$) charged black holes in $d = 4$ as a function of the dimensionless ratio of boundary quantities $\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{C_J \mu}{C_T T}}$ and its inverse. Extremal black holes ($T = 0$) have divergent complexity of formation also using the CV conjecture.

Figure 29: Complexity of formation from the CV conjecture normalized by $\Delta\mathcal{C}_0$ for planar ($k = 0$) charged black holes in $d = 4$ as a function of the dimensionless ratio of boundary quantities $\nu \equiv \sqrt{\frac{C_J \mu}{C_T T}}$ and its inverse. Extremal black holes ($T = 0$) have divergent complexity of formation also using the CV conjecture.

for $k = -1$ can be obtained from the multiplication of $h(y, z)$ and $\tilde{h}(y, z)$ in eq. (4.13), and it vanishes for

$$\mu = 0 \quad \rightarrow \quad z = \sqrt{\frac{1 - y^d}{1 - y^{d-2}}}. \quad (\text{D.33})$$

Evaluating eq. (4.28) for this value of z , namely, at zero chemical potential, results in a vanishing time derivative of \mathcal{C}_A for small uncharged hyperbolic black holes.

E Ambiguities in the Action Calculations

It was argued in [25] that the null boundary terms in eq. (2.10), associated with null boundary surfaces and null joints, introduce certain ambiguities in the numerical value of the gravitational action. In this appendix we consider the influence of these ambiguities on the time dependence of complexity of neutral black holes studied in this paper in section 2 using the CA conjecture. The influence of the various ambiguities on the complexity of formation was studied in appendix D of [26] and we will follow the discussion there closely. In particular it was demonstrated there that a large class of ambiguities are essentially equivalent to adding a constant to the null joint term a . This amounts to changing a in eq. (2.10) to

$$a_{\text{new}} = a + a_0. \quad (\text{E.1})$$

This is indeed the effect of multiplying the function $\Phi(x)$, which determines the position of the null surface according to $\Phi(x) = 0$, by a constant. A similar effect is achieved by a constant rescaling of the parameter λ , which runs along the null generators. Finally, this is also equivalent to changing the normalization constant α , which fixes the null normal normalization at the asymptotic boundary according to $\hat{k} \cdot \hat{\tau} = \pm\alpha$. We reiterate here, that these ambiguities do not affect the late time rate of growth of holographic complexity. In subsection E.1 we explore the influence of a constant a_0 on the action calculation. In appendix B of [25] it was argued that the reparametrization ambiguity can be avoided by including a certain boundary counterterm. We explore this possibility in subsection E.2.

E.1 Influence of a Constant a_0

When a_0 is a fixed constant, the joint term at $r = r_m$ in our calculations in section 2 is modified by

$$\Delta I_{\text{jnt}} = a_0 \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{8\pi G_N} r_m^{d-1}. \quad (\text{E.2})$$

Taking the time derivative and using eq. (2.31) yields

$$\Delta \left(\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{d\tau} \right) = -a_0 \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}(d-1)}{16\pi^2 G_N} \frac{L}{R} r_m^{d-2} f(r_m). \quad (\text{E.3})$$

This shift in the corner term is equivalent to changing the normalization constant α in eq. (2.49) to $\alpha_N = e^{a_0/2} \alpha$. Note that the term in eq. (E.3) also vanishes in the late time limit since r_m approaches the horizon radius r_h there and so $f(r_m)$ vanishes as $\tau \rightarrow \infty$. The modification does however contribute to the rate of change of complexity at earlier times. The influence of a constant a_0 on the rate of change of complexity and

Figure 30: The rate of change of the complexity (left) and its average value (right) as a function of time for spherical black holes ($k = 1$) in $d = 4$ with $r_h = 2L$ for different values of the constant a_0 – $a_0 = -4$ (blue, solid), $a_0 = -2$ (yellow, dashed), $a_0 = 0$ (green, dot-dashed), $a_0 = 2$ (red, dashed) and $a_0 = 4$ (purple, solid). We have set $\alpha = L/R$ for simplicity.

its average for a spherical black hole in $d = 4$ is studied numerically in figure 30. We note that the averaging procedure suggested in eq. (2.43) somewhat reduces the effect of changing a_0 , however the bound is still approached from above at late times.

E.2 Boundary Counterterm

In this subsection we discuss the effect of adding the boundary counterterm suggested in appendix B of [25] for eternal black hole backgrounds (2.1) on the rate of change of complexity. This counterterm makes the action invariant under the reparametrization of null surfaces. For simplicity we set in this subsection $R = L$. The counterterm for each null surface is given by

$$\Delta I_\Sigma = \frac{1}{8\pi G_N} \int_\Sigma d\lambda d^{d-1} \sqrt{\gamma} \Theta \log(\tilde{L}|\Theta|), \quad (\text{E.4})$$

where γ_{AB} is the cross-sectional metric of a bundle of null generators, Θ is the expansion parameter given by $\Theta = \partial_\lambda \log \sqrt{\gamma}$ and \tilde{L} is an arbitrary length scale.⁴⁶ We take for simplicity an affine parametrization

$$\lambda = \frac{r}{\alpha}. \quad (\text{E.5})$$

However, keep in mind that the total action with the counterterm does not depend on the parametrization of null surfaces. In this parametrization, the expansion takes the

⁴⁶The choice of the length scale corresponds to the ambiguous constant c in eq. (B4) of ref. [25].

form

$$\Theta = \frac{(d-1)\alpha}{r}. \quad (\text{E.6})$$

Taking into account that there are two future null boundaries and two past ones, the counterterm (E.4) at $t > t_c$ becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta I_\Sigma &= \frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \int_0^{r_{max}} dr r^{d-2} \log \frac{(d-1)\alpha\tilde{L}}{r} + \frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N} \int_{r_m}^{r_{max}} dr r^{d-2} \log \frac{(d-1)\alpha\tilde{L}}{r} \\ &= \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{2\pi G_N} r_{max}^{d-1} \left(\log \frac{(d-1)\alpha\tilde{L}}{r_{max}} + \frac{1}{d-1} \right) - \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}}{4\pi G_N} r_m^{d-1} \left(\log \frac{(d-1)\alpha\tilde{L}}{r_m} + \frac{1}{d-1} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (\text{E.7})$$

The time derivative of the counterterm is then readily evaluated using the relation (2.31) and found to be

$$\frac{d\Delta I_\Sigma}{dt} = -\frac{(d-1)\Omega_{k,d-1}r_m^{d-2}}{8\pi G_N} f(r_m) \log \left(\frac{r_m}{(d-1)\alpha\tilde{L}} \right). \quad (\text{E.8})$$

If we take another parametrization of null surfaces, the expression (E.8) changes. However, the total action is invariant under reparametrization. The rate of change of complexity with the counterterm is given by the following expression for any parametrization:

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} = \frac{1}{\pi} \left(2M + \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}(d-1)r_m^{d-2}f(r_m)}{16\pi G_N} \left[\log |f(r_m)| - 2 \log \left(\frac{r_m}{(d-1)\tilde{L}} \right) \right] \right). \quad (\text{E.9})$$

Note that the α -dependence which appeared in eq. (2.35) is totally canceled when including the boundary counterterm. We see from this expression that the counterterm does not resolve the divergence in $\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt}$ at times shortly after the critical time t_c which we observed in section 2.2 for $d > 2$. In fact, eq. (E.9) behaves shortly after t_c as

$$\frac{d\mathcal{C}_A}{dt} \sim \frac{\Omega_{k,d-1}d(d-1)\omega^{d-2}}{16\pi^2 G_N} \log r_m + \text{finite}, \quad (\text{E.10})$$

where r_m is very close to $r = 0$ at times right after t_c .

References

- [1] S. Ryu and T. Takayanagi, ‘‘Holographic derivation of entanglement entropy from AdS/CFT,’’ Phys. Rev. Lett. **96**, 181602 (2006) [hep-th/0603001](#).
- [2] H. Casini, M. Huerta and R. C. Myers, ‘‘Towards a derivation of holographic entanglement entropy,’’ JHEP **1105**, 036 (2011) [hep-th/1102.0440](#).

- [3] A. Lewkowycz and J. Maldacena, “Generalized gravitational entropy,” JHEP **1308**, 090 (2013), [hep-th/1304.4926](#).
- [4] X. Dong, A. Lewkowycz and M. Rangamani, “Deriving covariant holographic entanglement,” JHEP **1611** (2016) 028 [hep-th/1607.07506](#).
- [5] L. Susskind, “Computational Complexity and Black Hole Horizons,” Fortsch. Phys. **64**, 24 (2016) [hep-th/1402.5674](#).
- [6] D. Stanford and L. Susskind, “Complexity and Shock Wave Geometries,” Phys. Rev. D **90**, no. 12, 126007 (2014), [hep-th/1406.2678](#).
- [7] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle and Y. Zhao, “Holographic Complexity Equals Bulk Action?,” Phys. Rev. Lett. **116** (2016) no.19, 191301, [hep-th/1509.07876](#).
- [8] A. R. Brown, D. A. Roberts, L. Susskind, B. Swingle and Y. Zhao, “Complexity, action, and black holes,” Phys. Rev. D **93** (2016) no.8, 086006, [hep-th/1512.04993](#).
- [9] J. Watrous, “Quantum Computational Complexity,” pp 7174-7201 in *Encyclopedia of Complexity and Systems Science*, ed., R. A. Meyers (Springer, 2009) [quant-ph/0804.3401](#).
- [10] S. Aaronson, “The Complexity of Quantum States and Transformations: From Quantum Money to Black Holes,” [quant-ph/1607.05256](#).
- [11] R. A. Jefferson and R. C. Myers, “Circuit complexity in quantum field theory,” [hep-th/1707.08570](#).
- [12] S. Chapman, M. P. Heller, H. Marrochio and F. Pastawski, “Towards Complexity for Quantum Field Theory States,” [hep-th/1707.08582](#).
- [13] K. Hashimoto, N. Iizuka and S. Sugishita, “Time Evolution of Complexity in Abelian Gauge Theories - And Playing Quantum Othello Game -,” [hep-th/1707.03840](#).
- [14] W. Chemissany and T. J. Osborne, “Holographic fluctuations and the principle of minimal complexity,” JHEP **1612**, 055 (2016) [hep-th/11605.07768](#).
- [15] P. Caputa, N. Kundu, M. Miyaji, T. Takayanagi and K. Watanabe, “Anti-de Sitter Space from Optimization of Path Integrals in Conformal Field Theories,” Phys. Rev. Lett. **119**, no. 7, 071602 (2017) [hep-th/1703.00456](#).
- [16] P. Caputa, N. Kundu, M. Miyaji, T. Takayanagi and K. Watanabe, “Liouville Action as Path-Integral Complexity: From Continuous Tensor Networks to AdS/CFT,” [hep-th/1706.07056](#).
- [17] B. Czech, “Einstein’s Equations from Varying Complexity,” [hep-th/1706.00965](#).
- [18] D. A. Roberts and B. Yoshida, “Chaos and complexity by design,” JHEP **1704**, 121 (2017) [quant-ph/1610.04903](#).

- [19] R. Q. Yang, “A Complexity for Quantum Field Theory and Application in Thermofield Double States,” [hep-th/1709.00921](#)
- [20] J. M. Maldacena, “Eternal black holes in anti-de Sitter,” *JHEP* **0304**, 021 (2003) [hep-th/0106112](#).
- [21] T. Hartman and J. Maldacena, “Time Evolution of Entanglement Entropy from Black Hole Interiors,” *JHEP* **1305**, 014 (2013), [hep-th/1303.1080](#).
- [22] J. Maldacena and L. Susskind, “Cool horizons for entangled black holes,” *Fortsch. Phys.* **61**, 781 (2013) [hep-th/1306.0533](#).
- [23] A. R. Brown and L. Susskind, “The Second Law of Quantum Complexity,” [hep-th/1701.01107](#).
- [24] M. Miyaji, T. Numasawa, N. Shiba, T. Takayanagi and K. Watanabe, “Distance between Quantum States and Gauge-Gravity Duality,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **115**, no. 26, 261602 (2015), [hep-th/1507.07555](#).
- [25] L. Lehner, R. C. Myers, E. Poisson and R. D. Sorkin, “Gravitational action with null boundaries,” *Phys. Rev. D* **94**, no. 8, 084046 (2016), [hep-th/1609.00207](#).
- [26] S. Chapman, H. Marrochio and R. C. Myers, “Complexity of Formation in Holography,” *JHEP* **1701** (2017) 062, [hep-th/1610.08063](#)
- [27] D. Carmi, R. C. Myers and P. Rath, “Comments on Holographic Complexity,” *JHEP* **1703** (2017) 118, [hep-th/1612.00433](#).
- [28] A. Reynolds and S. F. Ross, “Divergences in Holographic Complexity,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **34**, no. 10, 105004 (2017) [hep-th/1612.05439](#).
- [29] Y. Zhao, “Complexity, boost symmetry, and firewalls,” [hep-th/1702.03957](#).
- [30] S. Lloyd, “Ultimate physical limits to computation,” *Nature* 406 (2000), no. 6799 10471054 [quant-ph/9908043](#).
- [31] R. C. Myers, “Stress tensors and Casimir energies in the AdS/CFT correspondence,” *Phys. Rev. D* **60** (1999) 046002, [hep-th/9903203](#).
- [32] R. Emparan, C. V. Johnson and R. C. Myers, “Surface terms as counterterms in the AdS/CFT correspondence,” *Phys. Rev. D* **60** (1999) 104001, [hep-th/9903238](#).
- [33] J. W. York, Jr., “Role of conformal three geometry in the dynamics of gravitation,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **28** (1972) 1082, [PhysRevLett.28.1082](#).
- [34] G. W. Gibbons and S. W. Hawking, “Action Integrals and Partition Functions in Quantum Gravity,” *Phys. Rev. D* **15** (1977) 2752, [PhysRevD.15.2752](#).
- [35] G. Hayward, “Gravitational action for space-times with nonsmooth boundaries,” *Phys. Rev. D* **47** (1993) 3275, [PhysRevD.47.3275](#).

- [36] D. Brill and G. Hayward, “Is the gravitational action additive?,” *Phys. Rev. D* **50** (1994) 4914, [gr-qc/9403018](#).
- [37] K. Parattu, S. Chakraborty, B. R. Majhi and T. Padmanabhan, “A Boundary Term for the Gravitational Action with Null Boundaries”, *Gen. Rel. Grav.* **48**, no. 7, 94 (2016), [gr-qc/1501.01053](#).
- [38] F. Hopfmuller and L. Freidel, “Gravity Degrees of Freedom on a Null Surface,” *Phys. Rev. D* **95**, no. 10, 104006 (2017) [gr-qc/1611.03096](#).
- [39] I. Jubb, J. Samuel, R. Sorkin and S. Surya, “Boundary and Corner Terms in the Action for General Relativity,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **34**, no. 6, 065006 (2017) [gr-qc/1612.00149](#).
- [40] W. Wieland, “New boundary variables for classical and quantum gravity on a null surface,” [gr-qc/1704.07391](#)
- [41] S. de Haro, S. N. Solodukhin and K. Skenderis, “Holographic reconstruction of space-time and renormalization in the AdS / CFT correspondence,” *Commun. Math. Phys.* **217** (2001) 595, [hep-th/0002230](#).
- [42] K. Skenderis, “Lecture notes on holographic renormalization,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **19** (2002) 5849, [hep-th/0209067](#).
- [43] A. R. Brown, L. Susskind and Y. Zhao, “Quantum Complexity and Negative Curvature,” *Phys. Rev. D* **95**, no. 4, 045010 (2017) [hep-th/1608.02612](#).
- [44] O. Coussaert and M. Henneaux, “Supersymmetry of the (2+1) black holes,” *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **72** (1994) 183, [hep-th/9310194](#).
- [45] M. Alishahiha, “Holographic Complexity,” *Phys. Rev. D* **92**, no. 12, 126009 (2015) [hep-th/1509.06614](#).
- [46] O. Ben-Ami and D. Carmi, “On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity,” *JHEP* **1611**, 129 (2016) [hep-th/1609.02514](#).
- [47] A. Chamblin, R. Emparan, C. V. Johnson and R. C. Myers, “Charged AdS black holes and catastrophic holography”, *Phys. Rev. D* **60** (1999) 064018, [hep-th/9902170](#).
- [48] S. A. Hartnoll, “Lectures on holographic methods for condensed matter physics,” *Class. Quant. Grav.* **26**, 224002 (2009), [hep-th/0903.3246](#).
- [49] J. Erdmenger and H. Osborn, “Conserved currents and the energy momentum tensor in conformally invariant theories for general dimensions,” *Nucl. Phys. B* **483** (1997) 431 [hep-th/9605009](#).
- [50] H. Osborn and A. C. Petkou, “Implications of conformal invariance in field theories for general dimensions,” *Annals Phys.* **231** (1994) 311 [hep-th/9307010](#).
- [51] A. Buchel, J. Escobedo, R.C. Myers, M.F. Paulos, A. Sinha and M. Smolkin,

- “Holographic GB gravity in arbitrary dimensions,” JHEP **1003**, 111 (2010) [hep-th/0911.4257](#).
- [52] E. Barnes, E. Gorbatov, K. A. Intriligator and J. Wright, “Current correlators and AdS/CFT geometry,” Nucl. Phys. B **732**, 89 (2006) [hep-th/0507146](#).
- [53] D. Z. Freedman, S. D. Mathur, A. Matusis and L. Rastelli, “Correlation functions in the CFT(d) / AdS(d+1) correspondence,” Nucl. Phys. B **546**, 96 (1999) [hep-th/9804058](#).
- [54] R. G. Cai, S. M. Ruan, S. J. Wang, R. Q. Yang and R. H. Peng, “Action growth for AdS black holes,” JHEP **1609** (2016) 161, [gr-qc/1606.08307](#).
- [55] S. Chapman, H. Marrochio and R. C. Myers, in preparation.
- [56] J. Couch, S. Eccles, W. Fischler and M. Xiao, “Holographic Complexity of Non-Commutative SYM”, in preparation.
- [57] H. Liu and S. J. Suh, “Entanglement Tsunami: Universal Scaling in Holographic Thermalization,” Phys. Rev. Lett. **112** (2014) 011601 [hep-th/1305.7244](#).
- [58] H. Liu and S. J. Suh, “Entanglement growth during thermalization in holographic systems,” Phys. Rev. D **89** (2014) no.6, 066012 [hep-th/1311.1200](#).
- [59] M. Mezei, “On entanglement spreading from holography,” JHEP **1705** (2017) 064 [hep-th/1612.00082](#).
- [60] J. S. Cotler, M. P. Hertzberg, M. Mezei and M. T. Mueller, “Entanglement Growth after a Global Quench in Free Scalar Field Theory,” JHEP **1611** (2016) 166 [hep-th/1609.00872](#).
- [61] W. Cottrell, M. Montero, “Complexity Is Simple!”, in preparation.
- [62] S. W. Hawking, C. J. Hunter and M. Taylor, “Rotation and the AdS / CFT correspondence,” Phys. Rev. D **59** (1999) 064005 [hep-th/9811056](#).
- [63] S. Chapman, J. Eisert, M. P. Heller, R. A. Jefferson, H. Marrochio, R. C. Myers, F. Pastawski, in preparation.
- [64] G. W. Gibbons, H. Lu, D. N. Page and C. N. Pope, “Rotating black holes in higher dimensions with a cosmological constant,” Phys. Rev. Lett. **93** (2004) 171102 [hep-th/0409155](#).

תקציר

תיזה זו מורכבת ממאמרים שכתבתי במהלך הדוקטורט. בתיזה זו נחקר אספקטים של אנטרופיית שזירה וקומפלקסיטי קוונטית במסגרת תורות שדה ובהולוגרפיה. תורת השדות הקוונטית הינה המסגרת של המודל הסטנדרטי (התיאוריה הפיזיקלית הכי מדויקת לתיאור הטבע). תורת המיתרים הינה המועמדת המובילה לתורה גרביטציונית קוונטית, ולא יחוד של ארבעת הכוחות בטבע. מהדואליות ההולוגרפית (התגלתה ב 1997) אנו למדים שתורות שדה ותורות מיתר הינן דואליות זו לזו במקרים רבים.

שזירה הינה תופעה של מערכות קוונטיות, אשר אינה קיימת במערכות קלאסיות. שזירה מתארת קורלציות קוונטיות בין דרגות החופש של מערכת קוונטית. "אנטרופיית שזירה" הינה פונקציה אשר מודדת כמה שזירה יש למערכת קוונטית. ב-15 שנה האחרונות, אנטרופיית שזירה נהייתה אספקט חשוב בחקר תורות שדה. הולוגרפיה נותנת פרסקריפציה גיאומטרית פשוטה לחישוב אנטרופיית שזירה בתורות הולוגרפיות. יתר על כן, אנטרופיית שזירה היא כיום אחד הערכים הבולטים במילון ההולוגרפי. בשלוש השנים האחרונות, קומפלקסיטי קוונטית הוצגה במסגרת של תורות שדה. קומפלקסיטי קוונטית הינה גודל המודד כמה מערכת הינה קוונטית, אולם קומפלקסיטי היא מטבעה גודל מאוד שונה מאנטרופיית שזירה. קומפלקסיטי מתארת את המרחק של מצב קוונטי מסויים למצב קוונטי אחר.

בתיזה זו נדון בשני נושאים: הראשון הוא אנטרופיית שזירה בתורות שדה, עבור תורות הולוגרפיות ולא הולוגרפיות כאחד. הנושא השני הוא קומפלקסיטי קוונטית בתורות הולוגרפיות. הדואליות ההולוגרפית נותנת פרסקריפציה גיאומטרית לחישוב אנטרופיית שזירה וקומפלקסיטי. הפרסקריפציה ההולוגרפית עבור אנטרופיית שזירה הינה מוכחת מתמטית, ונחקרה רבות בעשר השנים האחרונות. לעומת זאת, הפרסקריפציה ההולוגרפית עבור קומפלקסיטי אינה מוכחת מתמטית. יתר על כן, קומפלקסיטי בתורות שדה הוא נושא שיש מעט מאוד ידע לגביו נכון להיום.

התיזה כוללת את המאמרים הרשומים למטה. כמו כן, התיזה תכלול הקדמה וסיכום של המאמרים.

1. "Holographic Entanglement Entropy of Multiple Strips"[7]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, J. Sonnenschein, JHEP 1411, 144 (2014)
2. "Renormalization group flow of entanglement entropy on spheres" [1]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, M. Smolkin, JHEP 1508, 048 (2015)
3. "On the Shape Dependence of Entanglement Entropy" [2]
D. Carmi, JHEP 1403, 045 (2014)
4. "On Volumes of Subregions in Holography and Complexity" [6]
O. Ben-Ami, D. Carmi, JHEP 1611, (2016) 129
5. "Comments on Holographic Complexity" [3]
D. Carmi, R.C. Myers, P. Rath, JHEP 1703, (2017) 118
6. "On the Time Dependence of Holographic Complexity" [5]
D. Carmi, S. Chapman, H. Marrochio, R.C. Myers, S. Sugishita, JHEP 1711, (2017) 188

במאמר הראשון נחקר את אנטרופיית השזירה הקונטית עבור מערכות עם משטח שזירה בעל סימטריית הזזה. בפרט, נחקר את דיאגרמות הפאזה, ומעברי הפאזה בין משטחי ה"ריו-טאקינאגי". נוכיח שעבור מערכת עם משטח שזירה המורכב מ-m רצועות מקבילות בעלות אורך שווה, ישנם רק שני משטחים מינימליים. עבור גיאומטריות שבהן ישנן גם משטחי "ריו-טאקינאגי" "מופרדים", נראה שישנן ארבעה משטחים מינימליים.

במאמר השני נחקר אנטרופיית שזירה בתורות שדה, והתנהגותה לאורך זרימת חבורת הרנומרליזציה. נראה את קיומה של נוסחה אשר מתארת את קצב השינוי של אנטרופיית השזירה לאורך זרימת הרנומרליזציה. נדון באפליקציות למשפטי מונוטוניות. נבצע חישובים מפורטים עבור שדה מאסיבי חופשי, ונשווה לתוצאות הקיימות בספרות.

במאמר השלישי נחקר את ההתנהגות של אנטרופיית שזירה לאחר שמשטח השזירה ישונה באופן פרטורבטיבי. אנו נרשום נוסחאות שמתארות את התיקונים לאנטרופיית השזירה במערכות הולוגרפיות ולא הולוגרפיות כאחד. נראה שמשטחי שזירה בעלי סימטריית סיבוב או הזזה הינן אקסטרמה של אנטרופיית השזירה.

במאמר הרביעי נחקר את השערת הנפח עבור קומפלקסיטי תת-מרחבית. נדון באפקט של מעברי פאזה של משטחי "ריו-טאקיאנאגי" על הנפח, ונבצע השוואה למעברי הפאזה של אנטרופיית השזירה ההולוגרפית. עבור חור שחור בגיאומטריית AdS, נראה שהנפח אינו מונטני כפונקציה של גודל משטח השזירה (בשונה מאנטרופיית השזירה ההולוגרפית, שהינה מונטנית במערכת זו).

במאמר החמישי נחקר את ההתבדרויות של קומפלקסיטי הולוגרפית. בפרט, נחקר את השערת הקומפלקסיטי=action ואת השערת הקומפלקסיטי=volume. נראה שההתבדרויות ניתנות לרישום כאינטגרלים לוקאליים של גדלים גיאומטריים של השפה. כמו כן, נראה שההתבדרות המובילות של הקומפלקסיטי בהשערת ה-action היא גדולה לוגריתמית מזו של ההתבדרויות בהשערת ה-volume.

במאמר השישי נחקר את הקומפלקסיטי ההולוגרפית כפונקציה של הזמן, בהשערת ה-volume ובהשערת ה-action. נראה שבשערת ה-action, "גבול הקומפלקסיטי" הינו מופר בזמנים מוקדמים. לעומת זאת, בשערת ה-'volume', "גבול הקומפלקסיטי" אינו מופר כלל. נחקר גם את הקומפלקסיטי בגיאומטריה של חור שחור טעון.

TEL AVIV UNIVERSITY

RAYMOND AND BEVERLY SACKLER
FACULTY OF EXACT SCIENCES
SCHOOL OF PHYSICS & ASTRONOMY

אוניברסיטת תל-אביב

הפקולטה למדעים מדוייקים
ע"ש ריימונד וברלי סאקלר
בית הספר לפיסיקה ואסטרונומיה

תזה לתואר "דוקטור לפילוסופיה"

**אנטרופיית שזירה וקומפלקסיטי קוונטית בתורות שדה קוונטיות
ובהולוגרפיה**

מוגשת על ידי

דין כרמי

המחקר נערך תחת הנחייתו של

פרופסור קובי זוננשיין

מאי 2018